

D2.2: Public Deliberative Workshops – Findings

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ABSTRACT:	This deliverable describes the main findings of the public deliberative workshops in the seven POIESIS partner countries. The impact of integrity and integration on public trust in science is discussed.
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Executive summary

Based on a series of public deliberative workshops (PDWs), the Report explores the attitudes of the public towards science. This includes public trust in science and whether and how it is affected by research integrity values and societal integration in science. Seven deliberative workshops were held between May to July 2023, with a total of 169 participants across seven different European countries including Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Spain, and the United Kingdom, thus representing different parts of Europe and different religious, cultural and science-in-society contexts. The deliberative workshops were conducted as part of WP2 of the POIESIS project (Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science), aiming to empirically examine how practices of integrity and integration affect public trust in science with a focus on the chains of mediation, i.e., the actors that connect research practices at the work floor with the interpretation and assessment of these by wider publics (e.g., journalists, science writers, science communicators).

Overall, participants expressed more positive attitudes than negative attitudes toward science as reported both during the group discussions and in the two questionnaires. However, they also showed some concerns about the instrumentalization of science by political power, for purposes of manipulating public opinion.

In general, it is evident from the PDWs that integrity was regarded as a determining factor for participants' trust in science. Conversely, lack of integrity such as data falsification is a generator of distrust in science. Promoting openness and transparency in science by making research protocols, data, and dissemination available to any member of society are considered key to scientific integrity. Moreover, it was also evident that a core component of scientific integrity was the presence of independent institutions (i.e., key actors and core processes) and self-control mechanisms to critically evaluate the quality of the scientific process. Scientific institutions where research is performed are perceived as also having a prominent role in promoting integrity in science, by regulating it and ensuring that good practices are followed.

Participants agreed overall that public integration can clearly bring society closer to science and scientists, creating a sense of belonging, encouraging public engagement in science and technology (S&T) issues, and facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of scientific knowledge (i.e., how science is done). This can contribute to a more scientifically literate society and awake people's interest in careers in science. In fact, participants in the PDW perceived public involvement in science as reflecting the democratic nature of science, by allowing scientific activities to be scrutinized and judged. Nevertheless, participants provided different ideas about the desirable extent of citizen involvement as well as the suitable topics that citizens can meaningfully contribute to. Participants agreed that the involvement of the general public can mainly be important for trusting science in the beginning of the implementation phase rather than the decision-making process, due to the lack of expertise of lay people.

Science communication appears to work as a crucial factor for trust in science, especially in the aspects of clarity and accessibility of the language, as well as availability of sources, and the reputation and credibility of the actors who communicate science (institutions or individuals) or the channels of communication. When discussing the role of the mediators, participants identified that actors' credibility is a crucial criterion for assessing trustworthiness of the communication channel. Also, rigour in the communication style of scientists is decisive for trust in science.

One interesting finding of the PDWs relates to the publics of science. Participants seemed to categorize themselves, those who attended the PDWs, as one distinct group of people that is more interested in S&T issues and aware of the scientific process. This ingroup contrasts with the outgroup, made up of laypeople and probably less involved and interested in science. Considering the assumptions of Social Identity Approach (Abrams & Hogg, 1990), group membership can shape people's attitudes towards science and, particularly, how certain factors affect trust in science. Thus, participants who consider themselves as part of the ingroup still trusted science when reading about cases of lack of integrity but postulated that the outgroup could be more sensitive to cases of bad science and show lower levels of trust.

This report provides an overview of the main findings on the impact of integrity and integration on society trust in science research. Several similarities and some differences were found between the countries. Although interesting answers emerged, explanations and comparisons between countries should be read with caution due to characteristics of the samples and the events.

The structure of the report is as follows. The first section presents an introduction about the POIESIS project and the PDWs. This is followed by the methodology section that describes the participants' recruitment process, the guidelines and materials developed for the discussions, the set-up of the event, participants' characteristics, and the data analysis of the deliberative workshops. The third section describes the findings from the workshops including the small group discussions and the plenary session. The fourth section presents the main findings of the questionnaires.

1 Introduction

This section briefly outlines the POIESIS project and the set-up of the PDWs.

1.1 About the project

POIESIS is a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe that strives to tackle societal mistrust in science by understanding how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle.

Moreover, the project aims to understand how institutions, particularly research performing organisations (RPOs) and research funding organisations (RFOs), can foster research practices that are, in turn, conducive to enhancing public trust in science. Consistent with the expected outcome of the research and innovation actions supported under the HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44 topic, the goal of POIESIS is to develop evidence-based recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research, ultimately contributing to the long-term perspective of increased public trust in science and increased alignment of research with societal needs, expectations, and values.

The ‘HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44’ call for proposals on ‘Societal trust in science, research and innovation’ provided the opportunity for addressing systematically the relatedness of research integrity and integration on the one hand and prevalence and patterns of trust on the other. In particular, POIESIS tests a set of three intuitively appealing assumptions:

- First, that “... trust depends on scientists and engineers’ capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity” and that breaches to research integrity, i.e., research misconduct or questionable research practices, will lead to mistrust.
- Second, that “... citizen and civil society’s involvement in co-creating R&I agendas and contents makes research more relevant and responsive to society and strengthens co-ownership and trust”.
- Third, the call assumes that these markers of responsible research practices – integrity and societal integration – are “fostered by conducive institutional governance arrangements and policy environments”. The assumption is that institutions matter by enabling and supporting researchers to act responsibly.

POIESIS will address these assumptions drawing on and collaborating with previous and ongoing EU funded projects, and by engaging actively with seven types of stakeholders including: 1) mediating actors, 2) researchers, 3) research leaders and managers in RPOs, 4) research integrity officers, 5) R&I policy makers, 6) RFOs, and 7) the general public, in the empirical studies proposed. The focus will be on co-creating, with these stakeholders’, concrete recommendations for tackling societal mistrust in science and for strengthening the co-creation of R&I contents by society, using stakeholder networks also to catalyse dissemination and uptake of project results.

The key output from POIESIS will be policy recommendations for tackling societal mistrust in science and for strengthening the co-creation of R&I contents by society. A core set of general recommendations, relevant for all end-users, will be extended by sets of user-specific recommendations tailored to their needs. All POIESIS recommendations will be packaged together in an accessible and attractive format, tailored to the specific needs of diverse actors, thereby promoting mutual understanding among R&I stakeholders.

1.2 Public Deliberative Workshops

Public Deliberative Workshops (PDWs), sometimes referred to as dialogue events/workshops or deliberative policy workshops (Rowe & Frewer, 2000), aim to provide the opportunity for citizens to discuss and evaluate alternatives, as well as judge and contribute to discussions of science that affect their lives. It is expected that dialogue can lead to better science and policy, and it helps to support social relevance of funded research. As such, public deliberation is a method that allows for citizens to deliberate about an issue that matters to them, to have a better understanding of their most important points and concerns, and to determine which issues they associate with what they consider most important. Many research developments are potentially disruptive technologies and bring into question research integrity issues, which might affect opinions and trust in science and scientists' work. See for example the race for COVID-19 vaccines and people's hesitation to receive the vaccine (e. g., Tram et al., 2022) or the 'net zero' and carbon removal (lack of) discussion about what the narrative actually means and what is or is not encapsulated in it (Frankhauser et al., 2022).

For the purposes of the POIESIS project, 'public deliberative workshops' are used as the generic term encompassing democratic practices sharing these features. It is distinguished from other forms of deliberation events by the fact that we are not collecting opinions for policy-making processes or decisions, but rather the key feature is to allow for equal and inclusive participation (Weeks, 2000). Participants were provided with a kit with some information on the topic before the discussions took place, to be better informed about what the discussions would focus on. The primary aim of the deliberative workshops is then to elicit a diverse set of attitudes and perspectives where citizens can simply share their opinions and not to reach a consensus or fixed decisions.

The PDWs aimed to explore public trust in science and how it is affected by research integrity values and societal integration in science. These goals can be translated into the following questions that guided the workshops:

- What are participants' attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices?
- What are participants' main concerns, hopes and expectations concerning research integrity?
- Do these affect public trust in science?
- What communication channels do people use and trust to get scientific information?
- What manifestations of integrity and integration in research affect public trust in science, and how?

Specifically, the data from the workshops will allow us to investigate:

- public attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices;
- public concerns, hopes and expectations towards research integrity practices;
- whether attitudes and concerns about a lack of scientific integrity and societal integration affect public trust;
- how people choose media and messages concerning aspects related to science and technology;
- how people use and see traditional and new media as means of scientific authority; and
- desirable ways to integrate citizens and other stakeholders in the research process.

2 Methodology

The study protocol for the PDWs was submitted and approved by the Ethics Council of ISCTE-IUL (Protocol 45/2023), and a Joint Controller Data Agreement (JDA) was developed and signed by all partners. Deliverable 2.2 presents the outcomes of a wide range of PDWs. This section outlines the methodological issues related to recruitment, guidelines, materials, set-up of the event, participants, and the data coding and analysis of the deliberative workshops conducted in all the consortium partner countries.

2.1 Recruitment

2.1.1 Selection criteria and sampling strategy

According to the protocol in Deliverable 2.1 developed by ISCTE, the focus was on representatives of different groups of the “general public” as the relevant actors from citizen science associations, civil society organisations, NGOs, minority groups, and different user communities for the deliberation. Therefore, during the recruitment, all POIESIS consortium partners followed a purposeful sample design, and socio-demographic variation was a main criterion in the sample strategy to try and ensure variation in characteristics including age, gender, and educational background. However, the balance between some socio-demographic criteria and representation of voices from different social groups was also considered.

2.1.2 Recruiting strategy

Various strategies were combined to reach participants during the recruitment process. These included the promotion of the workshops on the POIESIS official website, sharing posters/flyers on different platforms, offline and online, phone calls and email campaigns, social media channels like Facebook and Twitter (recently renamed X), WhatsApp and other online platforms, attending other research workshops to attract potential interested participants, and personal contacts including collaborators and colleagues at universities.

In addition, some countries adopted other strategies to recruit participants. In Spain, the national team had the help of the consultancy Empodera. In the UK, participants were recruited with the help of a professional recruitment service (Apogee London). In France, the event was organized with the support of the sociological studies company n-clique, a professional group led by former students of the sociology department at Sorbonne University. Regardless the fact that this strategy might have something to do with cultural background and local situations, it could offer a general insight into further recruitment for such research events.

Detailed information about the recruitment process of each partner can be found in each National Report in the Appendix (Annexes A to G).

2.2 Procedure/Guidelines for conducting the deliberative workshops

ISCTE-IUL developed a set of guidelines to support partners in running the events in their countries. The complete description is in Annex H and includes the information about the preparation of the event, the agenda for the day, how to use the stimuli materials, and other practicalities.

According to the protocol (D2.1 Protocol for the empirical case studies) in WP2, a three-phase event was envisaged with an initial debate/Q&A session, small group discussions, and a plenary session to explore opinions and attitudes toward research integrity and dimensions of trust (e.g., scientists vs institutions vs media vs disciplines, etc), and to understand how these relate to public trust.

The events took place as a four-hour event, including a coffee break half-way through the event. Participants were asked to arrive half an hour before the event to allow time for setting in. A professional facilitator assisted with conducting the workshops. Table 1 presents the structure and content of the PDWs.

Upon arrival of participants, those were asked to complete a short questionnaire exploring public attitudes and trust. Then, there was a brief introduction by the facilitator about the purpose, domestic issues, and timetable of the event, followed by the expert talk. More information on the expert talks can be found in the national reports attached to this Report.

During the expert talk, participants were presented with information concerning one (or the two) thematic areas of the project – COVID-19 and the science of climate change and issues of trust in science. This was followed by a Q&A session with the same topical researcher, to help participants with concepts on research integrity and social integration needed to inform the discussions that would follow. Meanwhile, in each workshop, professional moderators and national project partners helped facilitate the focus-group discussions by guiding the discussions, offering clarification whenever needed and keeping track of time. Most consortium partners directly invited experts from their networks to give the talk. In the UK there were no specific experts invited to talk to the groups, one among the moderators acted as ‘expert’ to provide input and clarification when required.

After the initial debate, the focus group discussions took place based on the stimuli materials prepared for the purpose. In this session, participants read the specific cases presented to them and discussed among themselves, providing their main impressions about the cases they were confronted with. The new questions/issues emerging from these small discussions were written up on flip chart paper and/or post-it notes. All discussions were audio recorded.

The second part of the focus groups’ session was for collective deliberation on the cases that would inspire greater trust in participants, whose results were then brought into the plenary discussion that followed. In the plenary session, participants reviewed the main issues discussed, and whether their most important questions and/or concerns had been discussed. It was also assessed whether there have been changes in the way they saw and thought about research integrity and societal integration and about the role of the chains of mediation as sources of communication of scientific information. This helped participants recognising and prioritising which issues were most important to them about the topics at stake – in a card sorting exercise. Each group was asked to nominate a spokesperson to make a summary of the main discussions

to the whole group and the priority questions identified. At the end, the facilitator summarized the main points brought up by participants, before concluding with some reflective remarks. Last but not least, participants filled in a second short questionnaire to ascertain whether changes in attitudes towards research integrity and societal integration had occurred following participation in the event.

Table 1. Structure and content of the PDWs

Phase	Deliberative elements	Specifications for group deliberations
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the event (professional moderator) • Short pre-workshop questionnaire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public attitudes and trust in science • Concepts on research integrity and societal integration needed in the discussion
Expert talk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation by topical expert(s) • Q&A session with expert(s) 	
Small group discussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants read and discussed the specific cases (stimuli materials) • Small group deliberation 	<p>Deliberation based on two moments of discussion (research integrity and public integration in science), each moment based on two cases; each case with two versions except for case 4, which was presented in one version.</p> <p>The goal of case 1 was to explore how lack of research integrity affects public trust in science, and to examine how the chains of mediation influence this relation.</p> <p>The goal of case 2 was to explore how claims of research misconduct affect public trust in science, and to examine how the chains of mediation influence this relation.</p> <p>The goal of case 3 was to explore how societal integration in science (through public consultation events) affects public trust in science, as well as to examine how the chains of mediation influence this relation.</p> <p>The goal of case 4 was to explore how people think about integration of society in research; what levels of participation do people think are appropriate; how societal integration in science (through citizen science) affects public trust in science.</p> <p>Guiding questions for the cases:</p> <p>1) What are participants' attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices?</p>

		<p>2) What are participants' main concerns, hopes and expectations concerning research integrity?</p> <p>3) Do these affect public trust in science?</p> <p>4) What communication channels do people use and trust to get scientific information?</p> <p>5) What manifestations of integrity and integration in research affect public trust in science, and how?</p>
Plenary session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapporteurs from each group relay a summary of the group discussion • Plenum deliberation • Short after-workshop questionnaire 	<p>1) A reflecting period where participants reviewed the main issues discussed.</p> <p>2) Card sorting exercise. All groups ranked the importance of the cases they discussed.</p>

2.3 Materials

2.3.1 Materials for partners

In order to support partners in running the event efficiently and ensure the alignment of the methodology among countries, the ISCTE-IUL team co-designed the necessary materials with all partners.

- The Information Kit included information about the project and the event (Annex I).
- The Participant Information Sheet was sent by email one week before the event (Annex J).
- The Informed Consent form was presented to and signed by participants at the beginning of the PDW (Annex K).
- The Debriefing was delivered to participants at the end of the event (Annex L).
- The Case Package, which included the description of the cases, their versions and the guiding questions, were adapted to the national context. There were four cases, and each case had two versions (traditional media vs. social media), except for the last case. Case 1 was about an alleged medicine (ivermectin) that prevents COVID-19; case 2 was about the “Climategate” scandal; case 3 referred to a public consultation on the provision of the Pfizer vaccine for the immunization of young children against Covid-19; case 4 presented a participatory science programme open to the public. The complete cases and the guiding questions for each case can be found in Annex M.
- The two questionnaires were completed by participants before and after the PDW (Annex N).

To allow the comparison of results across countries, we designed and provided a codebook for qualitative analysis and a template for the national reports. The codebook for the qualitative analysis is attached at Annex O.

2.4 Set up of the event

The PDWs across seven countries were conducted by each consortium partner in their own country. The date and venue were chosen according to local convenience. Most countries chose a weekday, but Portugal and Greece chose Saturday due to the concern with participants' need to request leave or absence from their employment. Unlike the single day event in the majority of countries, the UK organised three weekdays instead because of various concerns about public availability, including talk of a looming industrial strike in public transportation. This strategy may have been the main reason why the number of attendees (42) in UK was the highest among all partners.

Regarding the venues selected for the events, these were in convenient central locations with easy access to various public transportation services. Furthermore, to ensure a stimulating environment, fostering meaningful discussions and encouraging diverse perspectives on the matters under exploration, most events were held in universities or research-related spaces such as community venues and a Research Council. The exception was Greece, where the workshop was conducted at a hotel.

Table 2 presents the dates, venues and experts names and position for each PDW. More details about the set-up of each event and the reasons for these decisions can be found in each national report.

Table 2. Events date, venue and topical expert name and position

Country	Date(s)	Venue	Expert
Denmark	Friday, June 2 nd , 2023	Aarhus Institute for Advanced Studies (AIAS) on the campus of Aarhus University	Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen, associate professor and leader of Centre for Science Studies at the Department of Mathematics at Aarhus University
France	Friday, July 7 th , 2023	Maison de la Recherche at Sorbonne University	Michel Dubois, CNRS sociologist and national partner for the POIESIS project
Germany	Friday, June 9 th , 2023	Berlin, bUm (community space for nonprofit organizations and activists)	Philipp Schrögel, expert in science communication
Greece	Saturday, May 13 th , 2023	Titania Hotel (center of Athens)	Iris-Theodora Vlachantoni, medical doctor specializing in Pulmonology, Elisavet Feloni, adjunct lecturer at the Department of Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, University of West Attica, also a post-doctoral researcher.
Portugal	Saturday, June 3 rd , 2023	Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Avenida das Forças Armadas, Lisbon)	Carla Gomes, PhD, research fellow at the University of Lisbon - Institute of Social Sciences

Spain	Thursday, June 22 nd , 2023	"Casa de la Ciencia", the headquarters of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) in the Valencian region	Luís Zurano, science journalist at the University Polytechnic of Valencia (UPV) Isidoro García Cano, responsible for scientific communication and dissemination of the CSIC delegation in the Comunitat Valenciana
United Kingdom	Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, July 4 th , 5 th , 6 th , 2023	The Marchmont Community Centre in Central London	No specific experts invited to talk to the group, one among the moderators acted as 'expert' if such input was required

Note: The UK had no specific experts invited to talk to the group because the team wanted "the deliberations to be largely unprompted on the 'circumstances and factors of trust in science'." (See national report in Annex G). This was slightly different from other countries.

2.5 Information on participants

The events were planned to involve up to 40 participants in each POIESIS consortium member country (described in D2.1). This number was difficult to approach in most countries, with the exception being the UK. This was despite sustained efforts put into recruitment strategies by all partners. Still, the study included a total of 169 participants.

Participations who attended the events were not paid, except in UK where attendees received a cash incentive of £45 + £15 travel expenses. This likely partly explains why the number of attendees in the UK compared to other partner countries was relatively high. There was a discrepancy between the number of people who registered and who attended the event on the day (see table 3), with 74% of the registered participants attending the event. This discrepancy was higher in France, where 21 participants had registered but nine attended the event.

Table 3 shows the numbers of attendees in each country and the number of groups formed for the small group discussions. In the UK, attendees formed five groups; in Denmark, Germany, Greece, and Portugal, four groups were formed; in Spain three; and in France two. Table 4 shows the characteristics of participants.

Table 3. Number of registered participants and attendees in the events in the seven POIESIS countries, and number of groups formed

Country	Number of registered participants	Number of attendees	Number of groups for small discussions
Denmark	40	27	4
France	21	9	2
Germany	20	15	4
Greece	43	32	4
Portugal	32	24	4

Spain	27	20	3
United Kingdom	45	42	5
Total	228	169	26

Table 4. Participants' information on gender, age and level of education

	Denmark	France	Germany	Greece	Portugal	Spain	United Kingdom
Gender							
Female	10	5	11	20	19	11	23
Male	17	4	5	12	5	6	19
Total	27	9	16	32	24	17	42

Age							
18-24	0	1	0	1	2	0	0
25-29	0	0	2	5	5	2	3
30-34	2	0	0	6	5	3	13
35-39	0	1	1	5	1	1	6
40-44	0	2	1	6	4	5	7
45-49	1	0	2	0	3	2	5
50-54	5	2	0	1	1	0	3
55-59	2	1	2	6	1	1	5
60-64	2	1	2	1	0	2	0
65+	15	1	2	1	2	1	0
Total	27	9	12	32	24	17	42

Education							
Low secondary education	5	0	0	0	0	0	0
Upper secondary education	7	1	3	5	4	0	15
Bachelor's or equivalent level	7	0	1	11	2	6	13
Master's or equivalent level	7	4	6	9	9	7	10
Doctor or equivalent level	0	4	2	7	9	4	4
NA	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	27	9	12	32	24	17	42

Note: As the information on gender and age is based on the observation from the completed questionnaires, there might be some slight differences in the numbers when compared to the number of general attendees.

2.6 Data analysis

The data from the PDWs was collected through audio recordings of the events (small group discussions and plenary session), questionnaires filled out by the participants before and after the event, flip charts, and post-it notes.

The audio recordings were transcribed verbatim by research assistants and reviewed by the principal investigators/team researchers in each country. Transcriptions have been coded in national languages for the national reports. Some transcripts (e.g., quotes) were translated by the local teams from the local language to English with the assistance of a translation software and then checked by the local research team.

The data from the transcripts was coded by each partner using a common coding scheme provided by the coordinator of the deliberative events (ISCTE-IUL). The coding was performed in a deductive and inductive way, organised by topics and subtopics chosen according to the topics of interest (defined in the research questions). The list of codes was provided to partners and used for the analysis of the national discussions. Topics and/or subtopics that were not listed in the coding list, were added under a section 'other topics' to guarantee that all aspects of the deliberative events were recorded in the national reports. The national qualitative analysis allowed for understanding what aspects of integrity and integration participants talked about more frequently, and in depth, in the national contexts.

A cross-country analysis was then performed by the coordinating team of the PDWs (ISCTE-IUL) using the data from the national reports, which was combined and analysed in a comparative way. This allowed for exploring comparatively the opinions and attitudes towards research integrity, the diversity of factors that affect trust in science, and specifically, the relevance of communication channels, across countries.

The cross-country analysis also allowed for the comparison of data from the individual deliberations, while looking for similarities/differences across national contexts using the same coding list used in the national contexts. Quantitative data from the questionnaires were also analysed using a cross-country strategy, using the SPSS software package, and described using descriptive analyses (means, standard deviations, and percentages).

3 Findings from the deliberative workshops

3.1 General attitudes towards science

In general, most participants across the seven PDWs showed more positive than negative attitudes towards science. **Gratefulness** for scientific achievements, especially in contexts of great uncertainty like the COVID-19 pandemic, was one of the most mentioned ideas. Science and technology were seen as synonymous with **progress and innovation**, as it can improve people's lives (health, education, environment, quality of living) and serve the "**common good**". In the Danish PDW, one of the participants shared the story of her mother suffering from breast cancer who due to an experimental drug has been doing well:

"She is just as you and me. That would not have been possible ten or fifteen years ago. So, cheers for science!" (DK participant)

Another example comes from the UK: "[Science] is just like trying to make the world a better place and just make it all easier". (UK participant)

The principles of **logic, rationality**, objectivity and **rigour** were also used to describe the scientific process. These characteristics seemed particularly important in PDWs where a great number of participants had a link to science such as in France, Portugal, and one of the groups in the UK.

"You need to follow a method up and then replicate and yeah, like, be consistent. (...) You need to prove or not... associations". (UK participant)

On the negative side, several participants in Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, and Portugal shared concerns with the **instrumentalization of science by political power**, which they believed was for the purpose of manipulating public opinion. This topic became particularly salient when cases about COVID-19 were being discussed. In the German and Greek PDWs, participants revealed dissatisfaction with the way politicians supposedly based their decisions about vaccination on science, limiting individual freedom, on science, but ended up imposing these decisions without proper explanations or enough transparency (about vaccination being needed to travel and to enter public spaces, the closing of public playgrounds, etc.). In the French and in the Greek PDWs, this concern was extended to industry, especially major corporations (private interests) for the purpose of profit.

"This subject is particularly close to my heart because, as a Brazilian, I've experienced this manipulation of science by political actors in Brazil, particularly to avoid confinement and to avoid an economic crisis. It was a subject that was very much involved in Brazilian life and politics. And a number of people fell into the traps." (FR participant)

The **ambiguity of science** was also occasionally identified as a negative aspect by some participants in the German and Greek workshops. Participants stated that scientists are often telling different stories about the same topic and therefore contradicting each other. In the Spanish PDW, this idea was seen from a different perspective: Science follows a rationale, hypotheses are put forward, data is obtained and sometimes there are doubts. In their words:

"I said it does not affect the way I see science because it is science. It is questioning hypotheses, data and, therefore, doubt. It is rational." (ES participant)

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

A great variety of issues emerged in the group discussions that could have both positive and negative effects on the way people trust science, from untoward personal experiences and unmet expectations, to the perceived benefits and problems of science. The topics most frequently covered in the various PDWs are presented below and include: i) integrity practices, ii) public involvement, iii) science communication (these three topics will be briefly addressed in this section since there will be sections fully dedicated to exploring them below), iv) scientists and their context, v) institutions, and the vi) impact of science on society.

i) Integrity practices

Ideas related to **integrity practices** were mentioned as a determining factor for participants' trust in science. Principles such as **transparency**, scientific **rigour**, **replicability**, **responsibility**, and **accountability**, operationalised through integrity practices such as data accessibility (i.e., open access data) and academic community validation (i.e., peer-review process), assumed particular importance in the Danish, French, Greek and Portuguese PDWs.

“What I find reassuring is that these reviews are also transparent, meaning that they can be accessed and reported on, and that we don't just hear about the results. We also hear about everything that goes into evaluating the study and saying, «Wait a minute, there's a problem with this study.»” (FR participant)

“What we expect from science, to be transparent in terms of open access, data quantification, these things.” (PT participant)

On the contrary, **lack of integrity** such as data falsification was mentioned as a generator of distrust in science, but mainly as a factor that leads to a bad image of the scientists involved in the specific cases discussed in the groups. Aspects such as **lack of objectivity and transparency** raised suspicions towards the experts. In the UK, some participants in the PDW pushed ahead with this line of thinking and concentrated their discussion on documented cases of secret and improper experiments by scientists.

“Secretive scientific experiments, that includes splitting up twins or infecting a whole community with syphilis... that we found out 60 years later... that continues, particularly in poor communities.” (UK participant)

Taken together, these results suggest that integrity practices, based on principles such as transparency, rigour, and responsibility contribute to public trust in science in general, whereas the lack of integrity practices was perceived as the responsibility of the scientist (i.e., individual behaviour), thus affecting trust in science in general to a lesser extent.

Possible **conflicts of interest** were mentioned as a factor of mistrust in the Danish, Greek, Spanish and Portuguese PDWs. A suspicion of researchers not being independent, having undisclosed stakes or hidden agendas, was repeatedly flagged as a potential source of distrust. The concern with the real motivations and personal interests of researchers to perform, report, and communicate research was reinforced by the involvement of funding from actors with economic interests.

“What was the background for them to come up with something like that. Is there, as we’ve talked about, something hidden behind it? Are there personal interests? Are there financial interests?” (DK participant)

“Did this scientist have an economic interest in the sales of the medication?” (PT participant)

In the Greek PDW, some participants revealed they believed there are scientists manipulating data and/or producing specific results to serve their own interests or those of their funders. For example, one participant referred to how scientists extracted scientific results that favoured tobacco companies and mobile phone companies:

“With a very quick Google search you will find many, many instances of data cooking by perfectly respectable scientists on a number of key issues.” (GR participant)

ii) *Public involvement*

Public integration in science was discussed as a factor for trusting science in PDWs in France and Greece. It was perceived as a form of democratization of the scientific process and an opportunity for people to compare scientific findings with their own experiences, which could boost confidence in science. Nevertheless, some participants in the French PDW identified the risk of trust being only a concern among the most aware part of the population, in particular those more attentive to science.

“[Public involvement in science] personally, I think it can increase confidence, because for example if I took part in something at the Natural History Museum, I’d have more confidence in that institution, I know it, I’ve taken part, I’ve talked to people from there, etc.” (FR participant)

iii) *Science communication*

Science communication was brought up as a crucial factor for trust in science in all countries. **Clarity and accessibility of the language** were considered particularly important aspects to decide whether the content being communicated is trustworthy. Participants in Spain and in the UK also stated that **rigour in the communication style** of scientists is also decisive for public trust in science.

“There is this kind of missing link between what we do, what we research, and how to spell it to a public, which doesn’t have the same sort of knowledge... like, for example, if I would talk to my parents about machine learning, they wouldn’t understand anything. So, you need to change the sort of language.” (UK participant)

In all countries, most participants highlighted that the **availability of sources** is very important for a more profound understanding of scientific findings and its trustworthiness. Contrasting a variety of sources and the opportunity for cross-checking information from various sources were identified as strategies that allow people to evaluate the veracity of information. This idea was salient in the Spanish and Portuguese PDWs, with most participants in the Portuguese PDW declaring that to feel completely informed about the situation, they need to have access to the original sources of information.

The **reputation and credibility** of the actors who communicate science (institutions or individuals), and the channels they use to communicate, were also identified as reasons for trusting science in the workshops in Denmark, Greece, Germany, and Portugal. In this sense, some participants in the Spanish and Portuguese PDWs mentioned that social media channels are not adequate for disseminating scientific information due to the superficiality and biased arguments that can be found in these media. In this line of reasoning, some participants in the Danish PDW also showed negative attitudes towards the use of Twitter/X, but Facebook posts were still considered to be at least somewhat useful for science communication.

iv) Scientists and the context of research

In the voices of participants, scientists assumed an interesting role as a source of trust (or lack of it) in science in all countries. A recurring idea in the various discussions was the existence of **conflicting scientific opinions**, meaning that researchers have different opinions on the same topics. It was a particularly important topic in the Greek PDW, interpreted by some participants as a source of mistrust because “science can’t afford difference of opinions among the experts”, as voiced by one participant. This idea is believed by some participants to make people feel insecure about who and what drives science. However, others interpreted this as ignorance, attributed even to the acclaimed experts in their field.

Scientists’ nationality and/or place of work were also factors mentioned by participants as capable of affecting people’s trust in science. This topic emerged in Denmark and Germany, and it was particularly salient for case 1, which took place in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Participants in the German PDW showed some doubts about the political system in Argentina and were convinced that in countries with political tensions, scientific results may be influenced by political interests.

“When I read China, I’m already suspicious. I know that this is an authoritarian system and that there, economy comes first and the environment last. So, I wouldn’t necessarily believe that.” (DE participant)

In the Danish PDW, some participants favoured the Danish researchers over other nationalities, while others made no distinction.

“Moderator: I heard several of you mention that there are some Danish researchers who look into it and stuff like that. Do you think there’s a difference in the quality of the research, for example?”

Participant 1: Yes. Well, you do get a bit nationalistic, I think that there are some countries that we trust more than others. And I apologise for being - or I’m like that.

Participant 2: I just wanted to say: not really, I almost said. Because if the researchers, well, then they should - basically, they’ll find the truth. And if the researchers do their work properly and follow the method that you say should be followed, and it’s documented in the right way, and the data is valid and representative and all that stuff that needs to be in order before you can say: ‘check!, it’s true’, then it doesn’t really matter who’s doing the research, it might be a waste of money if we all have to sit around reinventing the wheel.” (DK participants)

Apart from nationality, participants in the Danish PDW discussed the more general **academic performance** of researchers and of their institutions and how they affect their credibility. This included issues like track record and reputation, indicating that participants are highly sensitive to the historical context of research and its trustworthiness:

“[It matters] how credible it is, how big and how recognized it is, how much they are known for doing good research.” (DK participant)

Regarding the track record of the researchers, a few participants in the Portuguese PDW raised suspicions about the past of those researchers who are accused – even if the facts have not been proven – of lack of integrity and doubt their credibility.

“[It makes me doubt] the scientist’s behaviour in the past.” (PT participant)

v) *Scientific institutions*

Science-related institutions were acknowledged as important guardians of the scientific process, which could enhance trust in science. Independent institutes and research networks should monitor and certify scientific processes, taking a regulatory role in maintaining trust in science. This idea was particularly salient in the French and Greek PDWs.

“On the preprints, we saw how networks of researchers had organised themselves, because it was so huge to check out a discipline, a thing, to say “OK, we’ll do the studies, because people in hospitals don’t have the time”. There are projects that have been set up like that and that have worked. Personally, I find that it restores confidence because things are re-examined, because things are pointed out, because we ask for more answers about certain troublesome results and all that, we can have access to.” (FR participant)

The **influence of political power** on institutions and the way politicians manage crises related to scientific issues (e.g., the COVID-19 pandemic) were also perceived as factors promoting distrust, particularly in Germany and Greece.

Commercialisation of research by private institutions, mainly for profit, was addressed in the Greek PDW as a reason for distrusting science. Participants demonstrated concern with the involvement of the industry in research and scepticism about such scientific actors’ influence on science, especially pharmaceutical companies. Thus, many participants expressed the opinion that research should receive public funding under an adequate regulatory framework.

“That’s why it’s important that the funding be public in that sense (...) public access to the research results.” (GR participant)

vi) *Impact of science on society*

One of the factors negatively affecting people’s trust in science is the **impact of science on society**. Despite recognising that scientific advancements contribute to the improvement of people’s lives, participants in the Greek PDW showed some concerns about the real impact of science, that is, the social use of scientific findings. **Poor living conditions** and the lack of access to basic needs (such as security, healthcare, and adequate wages) can lead citizens to be suspicious of the actors in science.

In Spain and the UK, participants also raised concerns about the impact of science on people but focused their discussion on the unknown and **uncertain consequences of science**. The lack of information about the long-term consequences of science and the uncertainty regarding the use of scientific results were identified as factors impacting on public trust. In the UK, participants went further in their concerns about identifying catastrophic consequences for society.

“The use of [the] atomic bomb ended the Second World War, but you know, it’s become a dangerous thing in the world, I think that could potentially end life on this planet.” (UK participant)

Thus, not knowing all the consequences of science, not being sure of how scientific results can be used, and not watching the improvement of people’s daily lives were perceived as factors leading to mistrust in science.

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

Views on integrity and lack of integrity

The theme of research integrity practices took on different levels of relevance in the discussion in the various groups across the seven countries: it was a hot point of discussion in some PDWs (e.g., France) and only superficially addressed in others (e.g., Denmark, Germany, Portugal, Spain). Although a negative perspective on integrity is conveyed in the two cases presented in the first part of the discussion to participants, participants considered them an exception and circumscribed to a specific person (the scientist). Furthermore, some participants revealed a broad understanding of research integrity and misconduct practices, by discussing traditional ‘FFP’ (fabrication, falsification and plagiarism) elements, but also by identifying problems such as conflicts of interest or unwillingness to share data. Overall, participants stated that improving research quality and transparency requires a transparent and open science, relying on mechanisms such as open access data and journals, and peer-review.

Integrity was conceived as both a governing **principle and standard** of scientific activities, as established in a Code of Ethics, but also as an **individual characteristic** that should guide researchers’ behaviour. In the French PDW, participants disagreed with the simplistic idea that researchers are inherently truthful and immune to any form of influence or pressure, but rather emphasized – as did participants in the German PDW – the significance of scientists’ capacity for introspective scrutiny of their work (i.e., self-reflection), keeping in mind their scientific and social duties. Yet, in the Greek PDW participants conceded that research misconduct might be **unintentional** in the case of questionable research and some understanding is needed. But the participants were clear that if research misconduct is proven to be purpose-driven, then there is no excuse and there should be repercussions. This idea is an acknowledgement that scientists may purposefully commit fraud for various reasons, including: undisclosed conflicts of interest, unwarranted political affiliations, over-promised expectations, and institutional pressure (“publish or perish”).

“But he doesn’t want to publish these research results. And then you just wonder what, is it not done well enough, or does he just not want to come forward? Is there someone there, does he have another agenda? Is there someone he’s trying to - is there a

pharmaceutical company behind it that he needs to benefit in some way?” (DK participant)

“My trust in science, if I may emphasise, is not unlimited anyway. Because science always takes place under certain framework conditions, is made by people, and functions on certain data bases. It is also linked to many interests, so you always have to look very carefully...” (DE participant)

Relationship between researchers and stakeholders

Despite all the motives pointed out to justify scientists’ misconduct, the relationship between researchers and those actors who fund research (i.e., with economic interests) was particularly important for participants in Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, and Spain. Participants also discussed whether stakeholders could affect or impede scientists from presenting things in a specific way, which can happen in some cases. In the UK, participants further emphasised that different parties can hold different interpretations of the same data set and the controversial situations where debate may have been hijacked by vested interests.

“They just looked at the data, and they interpret it in a certain way. And then when somebody else looked at it, and went, oh, well, that’s not how I interpret it... the media gets hold of that... oh, well, this proves that climate change isn’t happening, it’s all vested interest.” (UK participant)

Independent assessment, openness and transparency

Across all PDWs, a core component of scientific integrity was the presence of independent **institutions and self-control mechanisms** to critically evaluate the quality of the scientific process. Promoting **openness and transparency in science** by making research protocols, data, and dissemination available to any member of society is key to scientific integrity as proposed by several participants. It allows everyone (and anyone), especially those who have higher levels of scientific literacy and interest, to monitor how science is done. For cases 1 and 2, this meant describing and explaining the methodology of the study, showing the data and making the data accessible to everyone. At the same time, there are already successful mechanisms in place such as **peer review** in general and double-blinded peer review, which was featured by participants who are linked to science (e.g., France, Portugal, Spain). Thus, peers seemed to assume a major role in this process of quality assurance.

“It would be good if those who have done the study and the critics had a kind of confrontation, a discussion to clarify these doubts. That is to say, if there is a well-defined group of people who are against it, a debate can be held if the issue is very important.” (ES participant)

“What’s important is that the opening up of data, the publication of data, should provide an opportunity for dialogue between researchers and other colleagues who are in a position to understand what the researcher has done, in order to explain what we haven’t necessarily had the opportunity to explain.” (FR participant)

“What is missing is independent bodies that communicate with each other, make comments and come up with a proposal. In other words, there may be a data set, what

we call a scientific data set, an a, b, c data set, someone will evaluate it, someone will process it, and come to a conclusion. Somebody has to be involved, an independent body to see, let us say, whether the methodology was right, whether it came to the right result.” (GR participant)

Regulation by scientific institutions

Furthermore, **scientific institutions** where research is performed (e.g., universities, research centres) also have a prominent role in promoting integrity in science, by regulating it and ensuring that good practices are followed. As mentioned in several PDWs, if scientific institutions facilitate or hinder misconduct, they are equally important as the bare act of misconduct itself. In the Portuguese and Spanish PDWs, this was also related to **science communication** being in a crisis – a topic to be explored in the following section – since institutional actors have the responsibility to provide clear information on the behaviours in question rather than trying to excuse a researcher who has been accused or has committed misconduct.

“They tried to cover it up.” (UK participant)

Interestingly, in the Danish and Portuguese PDWs, some participants noted that misconduct itself is not the main issue, but rather the way in which it is dealt with in science and how it comes to affect decisions outside of science (e.g., political decisions on public policies). In participants’ views, lack of integrity happens in science as in other spheres of life, but its consequences can be much bigger and more comprehensive – including having far-reaching detrimental effects on the public perception of science.

Perceived lack of integrity and trust in science

In general, participants acknowledged that studies where there is suspicion of **lack of integrity** (even if it is a mere accusation) can **compromise the image of science** and **discredit it** to the general public. Misconduct such as data fabrication or manipulation, lack of ethical approval by competent authorities, lack of transparency, and conflicts of interest can lead to a trust deficit. On the contrary, open science and transparency, community-led review and regulatory mechanisms in science could inspire trust.

“If there is really some truth behind it, then I am willing to share. If it serves all of humanity, I would reveal that. I would do that if I knew I was really doing something for the common good, because then I wouldn’t have to hide anything. And that’s something that makes me doubt.” (DE participant)

In the different PDWs, the discussion about how lack of integrity can affect trust was more heated in case 1, on the Covid-19 medication, suggesting that there can be different “trusts”, depending on the field of science, and that trust in science might be more fragile in human health-related issues.

Different publics for science

In some discussions, participants stated that their trust was not affected by these specific cases, but they thought “others” might feel worried and see their trust in science decrease. Some

participants felt that there are two groups of people with different reactions to breaches of integrity in research: the ingroup, “us”, those who attended the PDW, and the outgroup, “others”, those who did not attend this event. In participants’ views, the **ingroup includes those who are well-educated, are more interested in S&T issues, or even professionally involved in science** and more likely aware of the research process. The **outgroup is** made up of the **general population** (i.e., laypeople), perhaps less scientifically literate and who can be particularly sensitive to these cases. This distinction proposed by participants can be explained by the **Social Identity Approach** (Abrams & Hogg, 1990), which includes social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979) and self-categorization theory (Turner et al., 1987). This approach suggests that individuals categorize themselves and others as members of social groups, and use these categories to infer about the attitudes and behaviours of the ingroup (us) and the outgroup (others). As people strive to have a positive self-image, the ingroup is positively distinctive from the outgroup (ingroup bias). Thus, for participants, the ingroup seemed to be able to make a clear distinction between the scientist who committed fraud and the class of scientists in general, and thus still trust in science. The outgroup, however, may overgeneralise the frequency of misconduct or cling to the idea that all science is bad science. Most of our participants identifying with the ingroup did not express a concern about science beyond the specific cases being discussed, considering them the exception to the norm. However, participants postulated that they were not certain that the outgroup (the general public) could make this distinction.

“M: When you read this, do you feel that it shakes your idea about science, in other words, do you see this is an isolated case and “it doesn’t shake my confidence at all...”

Participant 2: No, no. Not at all.

Participant 5: In science, in general, I think it’s a huge generalisation.” (PT participant)

“Someone who doesn’t know the [scientific] process and who isn’t so involved in these processes very quickly gets the picture that ok, there’s a lot of fraud here.” (PT participant)

Thus, the relationship between science and society is intricate: cases of misconduct say more about the scientist’s integrity (as an individual characteristic) than about their institution, the scientists’ class or science in general. However, the highlighting of bad research practices in the news has potential ramifications for the scientific community, research culture, and society at large. Ultimately, science can lose its reputation as a reliable source of knowledge and become damaged.

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

Discussions about public integration and trust in science considered how citizens access science and participate in the research process and in what way this affects people’s trust in science, whether they are participants or mere spectators. Regarding the perceptions of the appropriate level of involvement, discussions revolved around the tasks and stages in which the public can be included and the topics that can be debated by all. Cases 3 and 4 triggered discussions in different directions in most PDWs: while the project in case 4 was perceived as positive and interesting, leading to the identification of numerous benefits of public involvement in science, case 3 raised several problems with this involvement.

Personal involvement in science

In Denmark and Greece, several participants shared experiences of themselves being engaged in scientific projects, some of which were similar to case 4 (i.e., about nature and biodiversity).

“Yes, I have participated in such a project myself. (...) We had to drive around with a net on our car (...) and had to collect insects (...) and then send it to the National History Museum or something like that.” (DK participant)

In the Greek PDW, some participants mentioned that they participated alone in such projects and others take part with their children.

In Portugal and Spain, the majority of participants had never taken part in citizen science projects. In the Portuguese PDW, only few participants declared that they had already participated in biodiversity-related projects (e.g., BioBlitz), considering it a positive experience.

Other participants in the Danish PDW shared that they were subjects in medical research, as well as some participants in the Greek and Portuguese PDWs who answered questionnaires or were involved in focus groups or interviews.

Despite an overall positive experience in these forms of participation, one person in the Greek PDW shared that her involvement was trivialised as she never learned the results of the project she participated in.

The reasons for personal involvement were not much discussed, but **interest, knowledge** and **time** were keywords. In the German and Portuguese PDWs, participants underlined how important it was to be interested in the topic at stake in order to be willing to participate. Also, some participants doubted having enough knowledge (especially in case 3) and the capability to conduct data collection appropriately (in case 4). Finally, some participants identified lack of time as an obstacle to be involved in such projects.

“Whether we would participate, that would depend on our interests.” (PT participant)

“The type of knowledge required is not compatible with public participation.” (PT participant)

Desired level of public involvement in science and in policy-making

No participant, in any of the PDWs, suggested that the public should not be involved in science. In fact, public involvement in science was perceived as reflecting the democratic nature of science, by allowing scientific activities to be scrutinized and judged. However, the desired degree of participation varied greatly within each country’s discussion groups, from a **partial involvement** (i.e., in some of the activities) to a **full involvement** (i.e., from the beginning to the end of the scientific process). Also, public involvement was perceived as being **dependent on the topics** under discussion and should be carefully considered in areas such as health and medicine research where people might have less understanding of the issues. Furthermore, participation in **decision-making** – and its contribution to policy-making – is seen in a completely different way from participation in the research process. In most participants’ views, providing citizens with decision-making power in sensitive, controversial topics requiring great expertise, such as the vaccination of children, was considered inappropriate and even irresponsible.

Public involvement in data collection

Most participants expressed their favourable attitude towards partial involvement of the public in science. However, there was no consensus on the type of scientific activities that could include public participation. We can identify two types of activities: **data collection activities**, where people are invited to do observations, take pictures, or make videos, as proposed in case 4; and **data discussion/dissemination activities**, when scientific results are disseminated, and citizens can ask questions and clarify doubts. There was full agreement among participants that that society should be involved in the dissemination of results, for example by participating in public consultations. However, not all considered that the general public has the required skills to ensure the reliability of data collection. For example, in the Portuguese PDW some participants expressed their concern with the possible lack of skills of the general public to do observation of birds as asked in case 4. In this sense, some of the participants in the Danish and French PDWs proposed a clear division of labour between researchers and citizens when both are to collaborate on a single project.

“I think that the public should be much more involved in the communication, in the explanation, in the dissemination of this data, and perhaps more in the explanation, more for their reality, to know how this impacts them, than during the process itself, because there are methodological aspects and issues that are (...) complicated.” (PT participant)

“Participant 1: The role of the researcher is to set the framework for what should be counted, or for example, 15 minutes. That they set the framework for each individual. And then keeping track of all the individual participants, who gather the information and get it home. Isn't it?”

Participant 2: Yes. They're the ones who do the statistics.

Participant 3: We're the ones doing the work. They are the ones who finalize it.” (DK participants)

Public involvement in the dissemination process

For participants who considered that the public should be mainly invited to participate in the dissemination stage, events such as public consultations should have an **educational purpose**: specialists can inform society about the topic under discussion and explain the reasons for decisions already made – in a kind of science communication, but with the opportunity for the public to manifest their opinions, offer contextual knowledge and clarify their doubts.

“If I come to the meeting, I want to hear their opinion and several different opinions. So, I don't feel manipulated. On the contrary, I feel like I'm being informed about where they are.” (DK participant)

Full involvement in all stages of research

Participants advocating the **full involvement** of the public in science stated that people should participate in all stages of the scientific process, from definitions of goals and study design to dissemination of results, since citizens are stakeholders. One participant in the Portuguese PDW

stated that she also believed that citizens should decide how public funding for science should be assigned to different scientific fields. For these participants, asking the public to only participate in the data collection phase is “exploitative”, as voiced by one participant in the German PDW. The contribution of citizens needs to be valued.

“For me, this data collection is still (...) unpaid voluntary work. This is scientists putting citizens in charge of the only part that they, the scientists, think citizens can do.” (PT participant)

For the ‘common good’

One of the main reasons for this full involvement is the possibility of truly putting science at the service of the “common good”, responding to people’s needs and assessing the societal relevance of research – a clear benefit.

“I believe that participation should be from the origin, from the degree of decision on what research is carried out. Science aims to solve problems, and I think that research orientations are very much influenced by economic or academic interests, and research is not done on problems that can transform people’s lives. Do we want to go to Mars?” (ES participant)

To increase transparency

Participating in the research process from the beginning to the end can also increase the perception of transparency and, consequently, the understanding of findings and the acceptance of decisions. For example, one participant in the UK explained that some of the National Health Service (NHS) workers who participated in the trials volunteered to tell others about the vaccine.

Limited participation in certain topics and decision-making

One of the boundary conditions for considering the desired level of public involvement in science is the topic. Generally, in issues like **climate or medical research**, the majority of participants considered that public involvement should be partial since their technical knowledge and expertise is also limited and therefore their contribution would probably not be meaningful.

“I wouldn’t feel too confident about my ability to be very helpful... I mean, if someone were to present me their findings and asked me to look over them, I’d be very confused.” (UK participant)

Most participants across all countries considered that public consultations should not be binding. In fact, several participants were reluctant or negative towards participating in events requiring decision-making on a subject that requires great expertise, such as vaccination. Not only should citizens not be able to take such decisions in the name of others, but it is also unfair to lay that burden on them.

“It seems as if citizens are supposed to take a position on a scientific topic, which is not their task. As if responsibility is handed over.” (DE participant)

“I can't ask someone who has no idea about epidemics or viruses or whatever what they think about making a vaccine available to children aged five, six months, one year.” (PT participant)

“Let's say that participation in itself for me is not a disadvantage, it is a plus, an added value. The disadvantage I see is if the participants start to decide. (...) The dangerous thing is then to decide, that the participants have the possibility to decide because you need knowledge to do that. The disadvantage is that it is useful for people to think that they already know about vaccines, so it would be dangerous, it would be chaotic.” (ES participant)

Thus, most participants agreed that the public should not be involved in policy-making mainly due to the lack of technical knowledge, and that public consultations are important events for gathering opinions in favour or against a certain measure or public policy. For example, policy makers can use these events to understand whether amendments and adjustments are needed in the policies being proposed. However, some participants were suspicious about these events having a hidden agenda, especially if there are already recommendations from an expert group, which is evident in case 3. In Denmark, Germany and Portugal, participants suggested that political actors could be manipulating citizens' opinion under the argument of scientific involvement.

“There's one thing that makes me suspicious of consultation groups. To what extent are they not perversely created to get people to follow the line they really want?” (PT participant)

How people evaluate the main goals of public participation in science – its purpose – has several implications for deciding on the desired level of involvement. Considering the work of Stirling (2008), we could identify concerns among participants with public consultations being designed with an instrumental imperative, i.e., focusing on ensuring a particular outcome without a real social deliberation. This instrumental imperative contrasts with the normative (i.e., focusing on a transparent, open, representative, democratic process) and the substantive (i.e., achieving a better result using socially deliberated criteria for the outcomes) imperatives (Stirling, 2008), with the latter being the desired purpose of public consultations in participants' perspective.

Benefits of public involvement in science

Bring society closer to science

In general, participants in all PDWs identified and discussed many more benefits than problems that public involvement in science can bring. Public integration can clearly **bring society closer to science and scientists**, creating a sense of belonging, encouraging public engagement in S&T issues, and facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of scientific knowledge (i.e., how science is done). This can contribute to a more **scientifically literate society**, by raising awareness and educating people, as well as awake people's **interest in careers in science**, inspiring children to become researchers themselves.

“Just being a public awareness activity and giving a sense of being part of something.”
(GR participant)

“It’s fundamental, I think so, it’s involving people (...) it can help to reduce distances, so between the political power or the political decision-makers or the scientists and the population. So, this, this consultation helps to blur those differences” (PT participant)

Citizen science projects such as the one presented in case 4 are highly welcomed by participants because they might target **different audiences** (e.g., children and their families, schoolteachers) and require less specific knowledge.

Societal acceptance and relevance of research

Another benefit of participatory research identified by participants in Denmark and Spain was to establish the **societal acceptance** and **relevance of research**. Integrating the public in research projects could create the opportunity to reach out to people who might be interested in or affected by research. As also highlighted in the UK, it can contribute to **greater acceptance of policies** if these are aligned with the expectations of people. In France, several participants highlighted the importance of **citizens’ committees**, which would have a permanent presence in research organisations in order to reduce as far as possible the self-centredness of the scientific community. This proposal can simultaneously serve as a mechanism for the purpose of promoting integrity in science.

“Perhaps consultation should be replaced by observation with citizen groups there to verify the scientific debate under optimum conditions so that everyone has their say on all aspects. To make it clear to the public that they are not there to give their opinion, because unfortunately their opinion doesn’t hold water, but to form their own opinion. Perhaps their presence, as observers to check that the science is being done under their conditions, would already be enough to reduce mistrust.” (FR participant)

Getting more, and more diverse and socially relevant, data

Incorporating the public in research has also the advantages of getting **more and/or more diverse data** (Denmark, Germany and Greece) and using people’s inputs to build robust **context and socially-based knowledge** (Germany, Portugal and Spain). This means that, for some participants, knowledge can be produced by the community: new variables can be suggested by the public – even if researchers did not consider it in a first stage– and included in research because they are socially relevant in specific contexts.

“A question may arise that hasn’t been thought of. “It’s true. That gentleman or lady said this, this and this...” Why not? We can consider this variable in whatever study we’re doing” (PT participant)

“I think that’s really important, because I notice that those in science have their bubble, their scientific bubble, and we have our everyday bubble, and we need to find an overlap. And I think everyone can benefit from that.” (DE participant)

Problems of public involvement in science

Alongside the benefits of public involvement in science, potential problems were also emphasized in all the PDWs, especially when case 3 was discussed. In case 4, some problems became less relevant for most participants. Again, the topic was a boundary condition to assess the disadvantages of public involvement in science. Interestingly, in several PDWs participants not only pointed the problems but also presented some solutions, which we consider in this section as we acknowledge that they might be important for future recommendations.

Lack of expertise

One of the main problems discussed in all the PDWs was the **lack of expertise of the general public** in most topics, particularly in medical research, and it represented a great concern from participants' perspective. This problem seemed to be even more prominent in the discussion of recent phenomena such as COVID-19 and the vaccination of very young children. In this context, a majority of participants considered that the public should not make decisions at all. Public consultations should be the space to share fears and clarify doubts, rather than vote.

“Now I’m a mechanic, and what the hell do I know about that?” (DK participant)

“I really don’t want this to be a discussion outside the realm of science. The technical side. I don’t see any advantages.” (PT participant)

In order to solve the possible lack of knowledge to participate in the decisions, different strategies were proposed in the Spanish PDW, such as linking the level of involvement to the level of knowledge.

“I think you have to involve at different levels, the most informed as leaders of citizens, maybe they can get more involved. The public that has little information, that they are not necessarily part of the decision, but just participate to receive information.” (ES participant)

Intentions for public participation being unclear

Furthermore, not knowing the **true intention** and motivation for public integration in science could be a problem for successful public participation. Regarding case 3, the idea that a decision about children’s vaccination had already been made suggests that citizen participation is **fictitious**. The public would not have a real impact through the hearing because it was staged by other actors such as politicians or researchers, suggesting citizens could be manipulated, especially in relation to highly controversial political topics. This can backfire and have adverse consequences for actual citizen science projects.

“Well, I certainly believe that the population must be involved. And those who want to be at the hearing, they should be at the hearing. 100 percent. But it just seems a bit pointless because it seems like they’ve already made a decision. So, I can understand why some people might think, ‘Well, it doesn’t matter.’” (DK participant)

“Citizen participation as a fig leaf!” (DE participant)

The **devaluation** of public involvement, namely through the lack of feedback on the participation, was addressed in Germany, Greece, and Portugal. One participant in the Greek PDW shared that she never learned the results of the project in which she was involved. Some participants in the Portuguese PDW observed that they answered several surveys in the past but never had access to the findings of the study. If citizens perceive their contributions are not truly valued, they might feel frustrated, dismissive, and even contemptuous. Ultimately, these negative feelings can contribute to decreased trust in science.

Lack of rigour in data collection by the public

One of the concerns shared in almost all the groups was the possible **lack of rigour, reliability and validity** of the data collected by the public, as well as lack of standardisation. Lack of research skills for collecting data and personal biases (e.g., political, religious) amongst laypeople could be detrimental to scientific advancements. Also, because the public is volunteering in such projects, they can lack the time, the focus, or the discipline to complete this task.

“I’ve already seen cases [of citizen participation] that have drifted... Well, it depends on the protocols. And above all for the interpretation of the data that will follow the participatory collection with the citizens. Because there are cases where conclusions have been precipitated, which have sent out false information... Well, it was in the observation of insects in an area. So, we also have to be careful about all the criteria for selecting people to be able to use the data collected.” (FR participant)

“When there is bias, that in itself can create a problem in anything, whether we are talking about a simple discussion or we are talking about research.” (GR participant)

“The only thing you need to do in order to carry out an initiative of this calibre is to make sure you can check the veracity of what people send. Because otherwise, I could be saying that I took a photograph here in Entre Campos of an extraordinary species of beetle and then it was in Porto...” (PT participant)

Lack of representativeness of publics

One of the concerns identified in the German workshop was the **lack of representativeness** of publics. Without proper representativeness, certain opinions in a process such as a public consultation may be overrepresented and mostly this would be those of the ‘louder’ people, not necessarily representing a majority of citizens. In the German and Portuguese PDWs, some suggestions were made for reaching all people, including groups of society that are difficult to get involved in these projects: online recruitment by using social media and institutional websites, but mostly far-reaching communication channels (TV stations, radios) and local institutions like schools and health centres. Also, in Germany, participants suggested that there is the need to provide support for participants during the event such as babysitting facilities enabling young parents to participate.

“I’m talking about RTP, SIC, CNN, TVI, all of them. Firstly. Radios, not necessarily the ones I listen to, which are TSF and Antena 1, but the radios that reach the most people. Maybe Comercial. Local radio stations too.” (PT participant)

Further on the theme of who gets involved in science, in the UK and Portugal PDWs some participants expressed concerns about being labelled as **conspiracy theorists** or radicals when posing questions outside the dominant narrative. These labels might lead people to feel uncomfortable to participate in such events, and thus their dissenting voices are not heard. Also, even if these citizens attend a public consultation, others might attempt to suppress their ideas. Thus, labelling and repressing dissenting voices can lead to more mistrust in science.

“My issue is, if there’s any opposing view, you get labelled quite easily as a conspiracy theorist. The opposing voices get shut down quite easily.” (UK participant)

In the Portuguese PDW, participants shared that well-planned public consultations could indeed be the solution to prevent these opposing voices from totally rejecting science, namely antivaxxers groups.

“There is the benefit that in a public consultation when, for example, in this specific case, in the case of the anti-vaxxers, the moment we marginalise a group (...) the moment we give up trying to call out that group, that group gains more strength and gains more followers. However, if we waste a little time and try to explain and even debate with that group, so that other people can watch that debate...” (PT participant)

Finally, preparing programs or events that require public participation can also be a **time-consuming** activity for scientists, as mentioned by participants in the Spanish PDW. Despite not being debated in other groups, all partners had a similar experience in the preparation and implementation of their own PDW as described in this report.

Public involvement and trust in science

A non-linear relationship

Public involvement – as a symbol of democracy in science – was identified as a vital contributor to fostering trust in science. However, while acknowledging its positive impact, how public participation affects trust in science is dependent on many aspects mentioned above. These aspects include the topic, the goals of such events, and the characteristics of the publics who participate. Participants were far more critical about public involvement in public consultations (case 3) than in citizen science projects (case 4), mainly due to its implications for scientific advancement and for people’s lives.

Participants suggested that public involvement nurtures a **virtuous cycle** where society becomes fully invested in scientific activities: people learn about how science is done, perceive their contribution as valuable, become more interested and engaged, which, in turn, amplifies their trust in science. The more familiar science becomes, the more confidence society has in it.

By participating in such public meetings where scientific findings are presented, the public receives direct information about the topic, can discuss their doubts and, as a result, they will better understand the data. A better **understanding** of the arguments justifying decisions can contribute to **greater acceptance** of measures, initiatives, laws, or policies, which translates to higher trust in science and policy-making. However, **representativeness** is also a keystone for trust.

This indicates that public involvement – of all the groups in society – is perceived as being particularly important for drafting policies and immediately before the implementation of such

policies, when there is some flexibility to plan how these will be relevant for society and put in place.

“You’ll really find out what the people want, instead of the government just steering it their way.” (UK participant)

One of the concerns repeatedly voiced in all PDWs was that of a **lack of expertise** of the public to conduct a rigorous data collection, potentially leading to lower quality and validity of data. This was perceived as a factor that can negatively impact trust in science. This obstacle can, in the opinion of the participants in France, be overcome by offering training in scientific data collection to all of those who are interested in participating in such events.

“Is not reliable information, is it? I would always question whether this information is valid or not. It could bias the team’s results.” (PT participant)

The **lack of technical knowledge** on a specific topic also influences the capacity of the general public to truly contribute to highly specialised and sensitive discussions such as children’s vaccination, and was also perceived as a factor affecting trust in science. However, the real problem for trust was seen to arise only if, as a result of this discussion, there is a decision taken on the basis of a vote by a majority of citizen participants. Especially in medical research, PDWs participants considered that the public should not be involved in decisions, and their participation in public deliberations should be limited to exchanging ideas, becoming informed, and asking questions. According to most participants, involvement in the decision-making process can undermine public trust in policy-making that results from these consultations.

Moreover, participants posited that the impact of public involvement on trust could be influenced by the **potential manipulation** of participatory mechanisms. Therefore, the **goal** of these events is a cornerstone of trust-building, and it must be transparent to all citizens. If there is any suspicion of manipulation or use of these events to legitimise the measures taken by politicians, trust can be completely damaged.

“Imagine that the [working] group’s decision is contrary to what the majority in the public consultation said. Won’t that increase distrust in the institutions? (...) If people feel that their ideas are not valued, distrust in institutions increases, because what the beneficiary wants is never the same as what the technocrats want.” (PT participant)

As mentioned before, trying to **shut down** or remove the **dissenting voices** of the dominant narrative can also be interpreted as lack of transparency and generate decreased trust in science and scientific institutions.

“[Shutting down other voices] creates more mistrust and people are gravitated towards such opinions.” (UK participant)

In France, participants identified some strategies to maximize the benefits and minimize the problems of public involvement in science. These were aligned with the aspects previously discussed and included appropriate scientific oversight, effective training and education, and transparent communication about the public’s role in the scientific process.

To sum up, most participants advocated for a balance in the conceptualisation of **public integration in science as its relationship with trust is not linear**: while public involvement is valuable, science remains a domain for experts in some tasks and excessive public participation could restrain the pace of scientific advancements. Thus, a careful design and implementation of

strategies for citizen participation in science can transform public involvement into a powerful tool for promoting trust in science.

Involvement in this project and in this event

In the Greek PDW, most participants expressed their satisfaction for their participation in the event and with the role set for the public in this project – this is a partial involvement in science. Some participants also revealed that it would be important for them to be notified about the results of this research project. This will make them feel that they have contributed to something important. Most participants were satisfied with the structure of the workshop, with a few suggestions about the specificity of the questions presented.

In Germany, participants expressed that they would not necessarily prioritise their contribution to science in this regard but that it was interesting for them to discuss topics which one would normally not reflect on as much in a group with other citizens. This led to a self-reflection process. The event was also perceived as a dialogue, a way of communicating towards science – an important aspect for science communication, which should, according to one participant, always go into both directions. One participant shared the thoughts he had before the event:

“I came here with a very open mind, without prejudices, and wanted to get an idea of whether the whole thing makes sense and how it came into place. And whether there is perhaps some bias or whether there are perhaps some people who are pursuing particular goals or have certain ways of thinking that are all the same. Or whether there are actually citizens with different opinions.” (DE participant)

For most participants in the Portuguese PDW, this was their first time participating in a public deliberation. Participants said they enjoyed taking part in the event, found the cases interesting and were pleasantly surprised by how the discussions went. One of the participants shared that she would like to change groups in the second part of the discussion to have the opportunity to meet other people.

“My first time, I confess, and it’s super interesting, I like discussing ideas because sometimes (...) we come with a preconceived idea and then at the beginning of the debate new ideas come up and maybe the idea we came with changes. So, I think it’s important. And that feeling of belonging [to science]”. (PT participant)

“I’ve never attended an event like this before. (...) And I think it’s interesting, not only because we’re actually helping people to do research, but also because we get to know other people’s opinions and it’s really interesting to know how divergent opinions are and how those divergences can culminate in a common point.” (PT participant)

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

The trustworthiness of communication actors and channels to disseminate scientific information was undoubtedly among the most extensively discussed and debated topics in all the PDWs. In general, certain actors are expected to communicate through specific, professional channels. Traditional media were considered to generally constitute more trustworthy sources than social media. However, some participants recognised that the mainstream media is losing its voice to

social media, which causes some concerns. Several factors for trusting science communication were discussed, the most important being the credibility of the actors, the sources used and presented to the public, and the clarity, consistency and objectivity of language. Hidden interests of journalists or the media were perceived as factors for distrusting an actor or a channel.

Actors and channels: Who and what is trustworthy in science communication?

In all the PDWs, participants spend a great amount of time discussing the actors that are trustworthy in general and in their specific context (e.g., country), but also the channels used by these actors. Interestingly, in some groups, such as the French PDW, some participants argued that the **responsibility** for trust or distrust in scientific communication primarily falls upon **individual actors** (i.e., the communicator) rather than **the channel** they use (i.e., traditional media, social media platforms, etc.). For these participants, journalists shape how information is received. The content and the purpose defined by these actors in these communications can therefore be particularly important. In other groups, such as the Spanish PDW, the **channels chosen** were more important than the communicating actor and their role. In the PDWs in Denmark, Portugal and Spain a clear difference was perceived by participants between **traditional media** and **social media** in this regard.

Trustworthy actors and trustworthy channels

By interpreting these results together, it is possible to identify that trustworthy actors using trustworthy channels make the perfect combination of trustworthiness in science communication. For example, institutions using an official channel are highly trustworthy for participants in the French PDW, as they are often well-known for their role in disseminating scientific results to the general public. However, when a reliable actor uses other platforms or channels, such as social media (e.g., Facebook), **people's trustworthiness quickly declines raising doubts about the journalist's motive for doing so.**

“It is an informal, informal medium that is being used here. It is the private individual and what are his motives?” (DK participant)

“This thing about journalists not limiting themselves to using their means of work and having to go on Facebook... There's a lot to be said for that, isn't there?” (PT participant)

Trust in legacy media

When evaluating the trustworthiness of channels in **traditional media**, participants felt **more confident**, showing a clear idea of how much trust or distrust they could put in each channel of the traditional media. There was no consensus on which traditional channels are the most credible (TV stations vs. newspapers vs. radios), but there were several criteria people use in their evaluation, which will be further discussed in the following sections. For example, some participants considered important the level of detail and background information each channel can provide, while others focused on the prestige of the channel, considering its dependency on politics or private companies, or its tendency for sensationalism.

Critical to social media

Regarding **social media**, participants were **more critical** arguing that it can also be a source of disinformation. There is no particular monitoring of what is being shared in social media, meaning that anyone – even without being identified – could write anything – including lies – without identifying reliable sources, giving proper explanations or presenting proofs. Also, social media reinforce certain worldviews rather than maximising diversity of viewpoints: people have access to information that confirms their ideas and are not exposed to different perspectives.

“Anyone can go into Facebook and write things.” (DK participant)

“So, who we read the information from certainly plays a role, the language he uses, the references he uses, is something I totally agree with, the medium, which he uses, let’s say on Facebook there is no citation, anyone can upload what they want. It is not the same with the various science sites.” (GR participant)

“I don’t know how many of you were here around Brexit time, I was never presented anything on social media that was... (anti EU). My entire social media was just populated with pro EU stuff. And I think it’s similar if you’re like an anti-vaxxer. You don’t see the other side... because you click on the anti-vaccine things you get promoted more and more anti vaccine articles... It’s the same if you’re looking at the climate change argument. The algorithms work to maximise clicks rather than maximise viewpoints.” (UK participant)

Information shared in social media can reach a great number of people in no time, affecting people’s attitudes towards science. One participant in the UK narrated the experience of his mother who had become radicalised by YouTube and is now refusing vaccines:

“She got bored of seeing the BBC news cycle over and over... She found YouTube and now she is into all of the conspiracy (theories) because she won’t take any of the recommended vaccines...” (UK participant)

In the Danish and Portuguese context, Twitter/X is hardly used. Thus, the lack of familiarity with this channel put it in last place in the communication channels’ credibility. Also, in Germany Twitter/X was perceived as very confusing, overwhelming, and its content as being only small talk by most participants.

“This is not even in the media, it’s just Twitter...” (DK participant)

“I don’t think Twitter is a channel for publicising science.” (PT participant)

Therefore, when scientific information is disseminated through social media, knowing the high risk of information manipulation and the dissemination of fake news, people have to employ a set of strategies for the critical analysis of the information and for evaluating its reliability. Usually, the most important strategy is to cross-check sources and read the original articles.

In Greece and the UK, participants were generally suspicious about all communication channels, due the conflicts of interest these may hold, being influenced by their own agendas, politicians, scientists, and industries. The involvement of political power and industry in communication channels was particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic and now in the case of climate change.

“[The media] tells you a bag of lies every single time... It’s jargon, and I’m reading jargon now.” (UK participant)

In the UK, *BBC* was perceived as less trustworthy than before.

“I don’t believe that BBC is impartial anymore... It pushes the BBC’s agenda.” (UK participant)

In some PDWs, participants also discussed country-specific sources for a reliable communication of scientific findings. In Denmark, *DR* – the Danish national broadcast service – was considered in principle trustworthy assuming they are transparent about their sources. On the other hand, Fox News was perceived as not trustworthy.

“I didn’t doubt for a moment that when it says “DR journalist” here, it represents a very high degree of credibility, because I associate DR with a very high degree of credibility. Whereas if it had said “Fox News”, I might have thought “aah”, maybe it was someone they had found themselves.” (DK participant)

In Germany, *DIE ZEIT* – a renowned weekly German newspaper – was perceived as serious and one participant acknowledged that she generally trusts this newspaper and its articles.

In Portugal, *Jornal Público*, a Portuguese daily and generalist newspaper, was considered by all participants as a trusted source of information. Other references of trustworthiness were *Expresso* and *Diário de Notícias*. On the contrary, *Correio da Manhã*, another Portuguese generalist daily newspaper, is perceived to be a not trustworthy source.

“For me, Público is on par with Expresso and Diário de Notícias. (...) In fact, I, at Público, whenever something comes out that interests me, I go to see the link.” (PT participant)

Following the guidelines provided for partners to use the different case studies in their national context, each partner identified the media channels that were mostly considered as trustworthy by the general public in their countries and used it in their PDWs. This previous discussion indicates that participants perceived indeed these channels as trusted sources. Only the *BBC*, used in the UK cases, seems to be losing credibility, but participants did not identify trustworthy alternatives to it.

Finally, less discussed in all the PDWs was the role of experts (usually scientists) and scientific journals communicating scientific issues. These were identified as extremely trustworthy by some participants in Denmark and Greece.

The richness of this discussion indicates that participants can sometimes have difficulty to assess the credibility of sources (actors x channels) in science communication, especially when there is an overflow of information coming from different sources and the actors disagree (a topic previously discussed in this analysis).

The role of institutions in science communication

Overall, participants discussed mostly the roles of traditional media and journalists. The role of scientists and institutions was less debated and assumed particular relevance only in France and Portugal, where the participants had a closer link to science.

Being neutral, providing information

According to participants, the first role of mediators when communicating science-related issues is **giving information** using a **neutral**, impartial tone, without trying to persuade people. Participants expressed scepticism when mediating actors used language that was not considered neutral, hence suggesting that the mediating actor had other objectives – for example, a hidden agenda or personal interests – than merely informing. To ensure an impartial posture, communication actors must **present different views**, give space to opposing voices and opinions so that readers can paint their own picture.

“There were some vaccine-sceptics that never got broadcasting time.” (DK participant)

“I would like to be critical of the journalist’s way of describing. Because I think, I sit and think that - and I don’t attribute any motives to the journalist. But the journalist starts by saying that a new study from Argentina “claims”. You could also say “informs”. “Claims” is already an idea that this is something that may be on the edge of credibility. So, a kind of tone has already been set here.” (DK participant)

“The importance of communicating not only science and a scientific discovery, but the scientific process. If we want non-specialists to understand and trust science, etc., etc., we have to explain it to people.” (PT participant)

As mentioned in all groups in all countries, media also has the obligation to **verify and include their sources** of information. This contributes to the neutral posture that must be taken by the actors when communicating science-related information.

“We can say that whoever publishes this news item, or the newspaper itself, also has a duty to go and find the sources, on one side and on the other, regardless of what opinion we may or may not have about it.” (PT participant)

Seeking expert insight

Related to this, the **credibility of the sources** also plays a key role. The media has the responsibility of **seeking expert insight** and ensuring they possess a fundamental understanding of scientific processes before disseminating information. This means giving researchers the chance to clearly express themselves in the media.

“That’s where I think the media’s responsibility is not being properly assumed, since we know that the data has not been published and is not being communicated, why write about it in this way? In a way that leaves room for doubt, even though the media should say no? (...) Given the ethics of the profession of journalist, we are not going to write an article that says everything and its opposite at the same time!” (FR participant)

Communicate studies rigorously

Participants considered that mediators also have the important role of making readers **aware of the potential problems** with research, informing the public about what the characteristics of a rigorous scientific study are, and giving tips to help people identifying bad research practices. This can help people to better assess the trustworthiness of a specific study.

“But that’s where the media’s role is also to be, what do you call it, a watchdog and go out and say, listen, there’s something wrong here.” (DK participant)

In Portugal, participants mentioned that when using social media, journalists have to be very candid about their role in the publication. If they are authors of a piece of journalism and sharing it in their social media, they should state if it is a personal or a professional perspective. The reader should be able to identify if there are personal interests on the part of this person in publishing this information.

“It’s one thing to see a post made by Manuel Dias who I don’t know who he is. It’s another thing to be Manuel Dias whose profile says journalist for the Público newspaper. (...) I have to make this discussion very clear. We don’t know that for sure.” (PT participant)

Institutions should communicate bad practices

Finally, scientific **institutions**, namely universities and research centres, also have the duty to **communicate** about how scientific knowledge is produced and to **clarify or explain** their scientists’ behaviour, if necessary. This seems particularly important in cases of suspected lack of integrity.

“The Institution must explain what happened, separate itself from the scientist, explaining why and end up maintaining, trying to maintain trust. In other words, this person does not make the entire Institution that we are, we continue to be doing rigorous research.” (PT participant)

Thus, mediators have an impact on the formation of public opinion and have the means, through different channels, to critically affect social phenomena through science communication. We have witnessed this during the Covid-19 pandemic, as was mentioned by many participants. However, in participants’ views, mediators do not always fulfil these roles, which can affect the trustworthiness of the actors and channels that communicate scientific issues.

Motives for trusting and distrusting channels

Motives for trusting or distrusting communication actors and channels are closely related to the roles of these mediators. Participants revealed their expectations about these roles and used these as criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of the mediators. As these motives were more profoundly addressed above, only some of the motives will be briefly revisited in this section.

One of the main characteristics participants mentioned was that actors should be **independent** of the issue at stake. Personal relationships or close ties to the issue or people involved negatively affects trustworthiness.

“And you could say, as a colleague, you also have a stake, uh... representative role. (...) So, again, you can say whether it’s a company he works for or whether it’s his colleague; in that way, he has shares in it, and he’s also from that university, so in order to protect himself, he should also promote his colleague. So, that makes the credibility worse.” (DK participant)

Related to this, actors’ **credibility** was also a criterion for assessing trustworthiness of science communication in all the PDWs. Lack of credibility includes potential conflicts of interest related to the funding of research or other forms of support, as well as other specific interests of the

media such as attracting new readers resorting to sensationalism rather than concentrating on sharing scientific evidence or adequate explanations of the scientific process. Such characteristics can quickly lead to mistrust in these media.

When considering the channels, participants in the Greek and Spanish PDWs mentioned that credibility is related to the ownership of the media channel and the interests the journalists serve in this regard. In Portugal and Spain, publicly owned media were consistently referred to as being more rigorous in dealing with scientific stories or information.

Furthermore, in Germany and Spain participants categorised the channel's reputation and seriousness as crucial influencing factors for trust, which depends on its perceived legitimacy in communicating scientific issues and their experience (i.e., number of years) dedicated to this task.

Thus, **transparency** is required: the public should know who exactly the mediating actor is (e.g., name, professional category, institutional affiliation), and what are his/her motives and reasons for using that channel to communicate science-related issues.

“They talk about a coordinator who doesn't identify who she is either. She may be a well-known person, but she's not properly identified.” (PT participant)

In addition, related to what was noted before about **sources**, participants considered that trustworthy channels are those that present the original sources and direct access to them. Linking these references is crucial for allowing the reader to go into original sources or actively searching for additional information to dive deeper into the topic. The absence of these sources can jeopardise the credibility of the channel, so it becomes a factor of distrust.

“Then I Google it. If it catches my interest, I'll Google it in bits and pieces until I feel OK. [...] It's because, if, I would start googling, who is John Doe and who is this university and what was this scandal and what is the name of his colleague. I would google him too and then I would google climate and weather stations. It's just because if I get interested in something, I just google things. I think it's really exciting.” (DK participant)

“Not having the link [for the original article] is strange.” (PT participant)

“If it interests me, I'll go have a look-up and I would see what other things are out there to say, and I'll see what resonates with me.” (UK participant)

Thus, trustworthy communication channels are those that combine formats that cross-reference information with expert scientific opinions.

Across all PDWs, one of the motives pointed out by participants to trust channels was **language**. Language has to combine several characteristics to be considered trustworthy, one of which is **simplified and understandable** language, but **with tangible, consistent arguments**. People should be able to thoroughly follow the reasoning presented in the text (e.g., understanding what happened, what they are supposed to do). Therefore, purely scientific texts are not appropriate for laypeople, but oversimplification and platitudes can show condescension, which is not a good way to develop scientifically robust communication. Thus, **clarity** and **consistency** in a factual-based discourse are very important characteristics.

“And then there's the last one, uh, because it's written in good, down-to-earth language, to get us to include us and help, you could say, a small step on the way to making us a little interested in that.” (DK participant)

Referring to the neutrality of language, **objectivity** was also mentioned by most participants, above all in response to case 1. Here again one of the participants concerns is when only one side of the story is told to the public. If communication channels do not provide full information about the topic, including opposing views, they are not trustworthy. **Attractiveness** appeared to be particularly important when people are called to participatory actions and citizen science programs. Furthermore, in the German PDW, the **layout** of the communication was also perceived as an important factor for assessing the trustworthiness of channels as an excessive number of pictures is perceived as untrustworthy or challenging for processing the content.

“The moment he starts with this sentence, he’s already showing a tendency. He’s showing what his tendency is. And if we want to reach everyone, our interest is to reach everyone, not just those who want to hear us, it’s these phrases that need to be eliminated from communications.” (PT participant)

Finally, in most PDWs participants considered social media as not trustworthy to obtain scientific information since they include a wide variety of factors contributing to distrust. For example, people can quickly write whatever they want, without identify or verifying **sources**, as well as share information that supports their ideas, but **omit or discard contradicting information**.

Communication and trust in science

Communication, a key factor affecting trust in science

The way science is communicated clearly affects the public image of science and people’s trust in science. However, participants could distinguish between the trustworthiness of the communication channel and the credibility of science, stating that, in many cases, the negative effect of poor communication can be minimal.

“Because science is one thing and how it is communicated is another, and it complements it by saying I believe in science, in people and all the effort involved in the process, right?” (ES participant)

Several participants noted that **event-focused communication** tends to undermine public trust in science. For example, if communication channels over-publicise cases of bad scientific practices, such as the lack of integrity discussed in cases 1 and 2, the public can overestimate its frequency, which can in turn result in lower levels of public trust. In this case, media is doing a “disfavour to science” as mentioned by one participant in the Portuguese PDW. Thus, a more positive image of science needs to be conveyed by the media, showing how science can positively affect people’s lives.

Also, when communication of scientific findings is characterized by **lack of transparency** (e.g., only one side of the story), lack of **clarity and coherence** (e.g., unclear language, inconsistency in discourse), and poor **accessibility** (e.g., no sources available), people might feel more distrust than confidence. In such cases, the mediators seem to be attempting to “muddle the water”, which has a direct negative effect on trust in these channels.

In the French PDW, current media communication was deemed unsatisfactory and sometimes even detrimental for the public image of science. This was perceived as an opportunity for **research institutions** to modify their communication strategy in order to increase transparency, promote clear understanding of the scientific process, and subsequently, enhance public trust in

science. This idea appeared to be particularly important in the discussion of case 2A in the Portuguese PDW, where participants showed some mistrust towards the university's statement. The statement was considered a public relations manoeuvre, an attempt to demonstrate a good image, but without providing clear and strong arguments to defend the researcher.

In general, the dissemination of scientific knowledge via **social media** seems to contribute to a decrease in trust, regardless of the characteristics of the actor. It seems that there is a spillover effect from distrust in social media to distrust in science.

"I think it's us perpetuating messages that have a scientific weight behind them and can have this false connotation that is harmful to science, and how people trust science and how they approach it. However, on social media, this is more than what exists, which is using articles, but to compose a story in our own way." (PT participant)

The influence of communication on trust in science is hence multifaceted. The characteristics of the actor and the channel that communicate science, as well as the capacity of these mediators to meet the public expectations about their roles, are very relevant to trust. However, the complexity of these relationships lies in the interaction among these factors rather than their solo influence.

3.6 Card sorting exercise

The ranking exercise consisted in comparing the cases presented and discussed during the workshops and ranking them from the one that generated more trust among the participants to the one that generated less trust. The exercise started with the question: Do these cases make you trust science more or less? It had an individual phase, where participants answered alone, and a group phase, where the group discussed the main arguments for defining the final ranking. The rankings and their arguments were then presented in the plenary session.

The ranking exercise triggered a fruitful discussion on the factors that affect trust in science and which of those are more important for participants. For various reasons, not all the groups managed to reach a consensual ranking and had to vote to do so, while others were unable to define a real ranking, with some cases tied in the same position. Even so, this exercise was very important for synthesising the main ideas of each group, returning to some topics that might not have been explored in depth during the discussions due to time constraints.

In general, case 1 sparked many discussions on lack of trust in science and also created debate on mediator impacts, mainly the role of communication channels and actors when reporting situations of lack of integrity. The lack of transparency and data accessibility, such as lack of professional integrity, were important factors for distrusting science, as well as the biased, subjective, and inaccurate language used to communicate the case. This led to this case appearing several times in the penultimate or last place of the rankings.

The role of institutions as mediators in the relationship between the production of science and public trust became relevant in case 2. Especially in case 2A, institutions and an attempt to protect their images, sometimes motivated by private interests, were perceived as barriers to trust in science. Apart from Greece, this negative perspective on the institutional communication in a moment of crisis directed this case to the bottom of most rankings. Again, most participants showed a critical stance towards the chains of mediation involved in this case.

Case 3 generated ambivalent feelings towards science. Still, as it appears several times in the first two places of the ranking, the advantages identified in involving the public in deliberative consultations seem to outweigh the concerns of the participants with this participation. It seems that participants recognise the potential of public consultations for fostering trust in science as long as it requires the appropriate degree of participation, particularly no decisions being made by citizen participants and no manipulation of public participation. In this sense, when participants identify possible interferences from politicians or industries, public involvement is a factor contributing to distrust in science.

The citizen science project in case 4 represented a very positive example of public engagement, science communication and science education that participants generally agreed could positively affect the public's trust in science. By making science more accessible to the public and using understandable and positive language, case 4 created a good impression of science on most participants. Thus, case 4 was ranked first by many groups. However, despite the positive image of public involvement in science, some groups still identified challenges that can undermine trust in science, such as the lack of scientific robustness of citizen science projects and the risk of manipulation by political actors.

In Greece and Portugal, Cases 3 and 4 were consistently ranked as the most trustworthy, hence the participants seemed to give a priority to integration over integrity. In other PDWs, this preference was not so obvious.

In addition, social media was generally perceived as being untrustworthy. Thus, versions of the cases that used social media frequently led participants to consider that they did not have enough information about the situation. In general, negative attitudes associated with accessing confusing or partial information on social media was reiterated. Version B of each of the three cases also appeared at the bottom of the rankings a few times.

The combination between the topic of the case, how it is perceived by participants (more positive or negative) and the communication channel used (traditional vs social media) results in an intricate reality. This clearly demonstrates the complexity of factors affecting trust in science and participants' sensitivity to a multitude of factors.

4 Findings from the questionnaires

At the start and finish of each PDW, attendees were asked to fill out questionnaires. In these questionnaires, attendees were asked to indicate demographic information (as described in section 2.5 of this report) and their general attitudes towards science, which will be explored in this chapter. Participants also answered three open questions in each questionnaire, but these findings were not explored in this report.

Participants answered five items regarding science-related attitudes using a 5-point Likert scale from 1 – Totally agree to 5 – Totally disagree, with the option of choosing “Don’t know”. In Denmark, the answer scale was inverted, varying from Totally disagree (1) to Totally agree (5). For Denmark, answers to items 2 and 3 were inverted, whereas for the remaining countries items 1, 4 and 5 were inverted to facilitate the interpretation of the results. Thus, higher values represent more positive attitudes towards science.

Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) are reported in tables 5 and 6, with the first showing the results of the ‘before’ questionnaire and the latter revealing the results of the ‘after’ questionnaire.

Table 5. Attitudes towards S&T ‘before’: Descriptive statistics

Item	DK	FR	DE	GR	PT	ES	UK	Total
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.30 (0.72)	4.00 (1.41)	3.27 (1.27)	4.47 (0.57)	4.42 (0.50)	4.29 (1.05)	4.21 (0.75)	4.24 (0.84)
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	2.67 (1.21)	3.11 (1.17)	3.00 (1.25)	1.53 (0.62)	2.08 (1.06)	2.06 (0.75)	2.55 (1.11)	2.30 (1.11)
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	3.33 (1.44)	4.63 (0.74)	3.82 (1.66)	3.00 (1.44)	3.91 (1.10)	3.87 (1.20)	3.43 (1.23)	3.53 (1.35)
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	2.11 (1.25)	2.63 (1.19)	2.30 (1.16)	3.13 (1.24)	3.18 (0.85)	2.76 (1.03)	3.07 (1.00)	2.83 (1.15)
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	3.04 (1.29)	2.44 (0.88)	2.45 (1.21)	2.48 (1.50)	2.41 (0.80)	2.29 (1.36)	2.95 (1.15)	2.67 (1.23)
Notes. Mean and Standard Deviation (between parenthesis) are reported for each item and country. Total N/range = 157-161								
DK – Denmark, FR – France, DE – Germany, GR – Greece, PT – Portugal, ES – Spain, UK – United Kingdom								

Table 6. Attitudes towards S&T 'after': Descriptive statistics

Item	DK	FR	DE	GR	PT	ES	UK	Total
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.11 (0.80)	3.44 (1.67)	3.85 (0.55)	4.38 (0.61)	4.39 (0.50)	4.42 (0.67)	4.02 (0.87)	4.15 (0.82)
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	2.63 (1.21)	3.44 (1.24)	2.75 (1.22)	1.69 (0.69)	2.13 (1.01)	1.62 (0.65)	2.55 (1.11)	2.32 (1.12)
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	3.27 (1.28)	4.44 (1.13)	4.31 (1.11)	3.31 (1.38)	3.68 (1.25)	3.42 (1.38)	3.45 (1.23)	3.55 (1.30)
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	2.30 (1.14)	2.89 (1.05)	2.23 (0.73)	3.16 (1.37)	3.22 (1.00)	2.83 (1.27)	2.98 (0.95)	2.85 (1.14)
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2.63 (1.33)	2.33 (0.87)	2.39 (1.33)	2.63 (1.54)	2.65 (1.07)	2.50 (1.24)	3.10 (1.01)	2.71 (1.24)
Notes. Mean and Standard Deviation (between parenthesis) are reported for each item and country. Total <i>N</i> range = 156-158								
DK - Denmark, FR - France, DE - Germany, GR - Greece, PT - Portugal, ES - Spain, UK - United Kingdom								

In the first questionnaire, item 1 'Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable' presents the highest mean for all countries. Greece and Portugal showed the highest means and only in Germany was the mean below 4. In the second questionnaire, means are very similar, with France showing the greatest decrease and a mean below 4, as for Germany. The overall means are 4.24 ($SD = 0.84$) for 'before' and 4.15 ($SD = 0.82$) for 'after', meaning that most participants agree with the sentence. This result clearly shows a very favourable attitude towards S&T.

For item 2 'Science and technology make our lives change too fast', participants' perceptions are more heterogeneous with means ranging between 1.53 (Greece) and 3.33 (Denmark) in the 'before' questionnaire and between 1.62 (Spain) and 3.44 (France) in the 'after' questionnaire. Spain showed the greatest decrease (-0.44) between the two moments. The overall mean is around 2.3 for both questionnaires, which indicates that participants tend to disagree with the sentence.

Participants in France showed the highest level of disagreement to item 3 'We depend too much on science and not enough on faith' in both questionnaires, which is probably related to the characteristics of the sample. On the contrary, Greece and Denmark had the lowest means in the first and second questionnaire, respectively, and close to the medium point of the scale (3), suggesting that participants neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement. The overall means for the seven partners are around 3.5, and the standard deviations range from 1.11 to 1.38, which might be interpreted as a lack of agreement among participants in the same PDW.

Regarding item 4 'Scientists know best what is good for people', Denmark and Germany displayed the lowest means in the before and after questionnaires, respectively, indicating a less favourable attitude towards scientists, especially when compared to Portugal that showed the highest means in both moments. It is interesting to note that the overall means are almost the same, with 2.83 ($SD = 1.15$) for questionnaire 1 and 2.85 ($SD = 1.14$) for questionnaire 2. Among the seven partners,

France presented the greatest difference for item 4 between the questionnaires, but still a very small change (0.26).

Lastly, participants generally tended to disagree with item 5 ‘We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology’, with overall means of 2.67 ($SD = 1.23$) for questionnaire 1 and 2.71 ($SD = 1.24$) for questionnaire 2. Denmark and the UK presented the highest means for the before and after questionnaire, respectively, both around 3, which indicates that participants in these PDWs did not agree nor disagree with the sentence. The standard deviations were above 1 (except for France), suggesting again a lack of agreement among participants in the same PDW.

Together these results suggest that participants hold a favourable opinion about S&T in general, but are less positive about scientists and those governing science and technology. These ideas were also reflected in the group discussions, where participants highlighted the importance of conducting research that is relevant to society and the potential harm that conflicts of interest can bring to science.

To further explore the results, analyses of the level of agreement with each item were conducted. Answers of ‘tend to agree’ and ‘totally agree’ were aggregated to calculate the percentage of agreement per country. The following graphs (Figures 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) show the level of agreement to each item before and after the PDW by country, allowing for an easier visual comparison of results.

Figure 1. Percentage of agreement to item 1 ‘Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable’

Portugal revealed the highest percentage of agreement in both questionnaires, with 100% of the participants agreeing or tending to agree with the sentence. On the contrary, Germany, in the ‘before’ questionnaire, and France, in the ‘after’ questionnaire, showed the lowest percentages of agreement. These two countries also recorded bigger differences between the two measurements.

Figure 2. Percentage of agreement to item 2 ‘Science and technology make our lives change too fast’

Greece and Spain showed the highest percentages of agreement to item 2 in both questionnaires, above the value of 80%. Again, Germany and France displayed the lowest percentages of agreements in questionnaire 1 and 2, respectively. France also revealed the greatest decrease in the level of agreement from the ‘before’ to the ‘after’ questionnaire, while Spain and the UK were the only countries in which the agreement slightly increased.

Figure 3. Percentage of agreement to item 3 ‘We depend too much on science and not enough on faith’

Greece revealed the highest level of agreement with item 3, followed by the UK and Denmark. On the contrary, France showed the lowest percentage of agreement, with 0% in questionnaire 1 and 11% in questionnaire 2. Again, Spain displayed the highest increase in the agreement level between the two measurement moments.

Figure 4. Percentage of agreement to item 4 ‘Scientists know best what is good for people’

Greece revealed the highest percentage of agreement to item 4, around 40 percentage points, followed by Portugal. Greece and Portugal also presented the highest increase between the two measurements. Spain, in the ‘before’ questionnaire, and Germany, in the ‘after’ questionnaire, showed the lowest percentages of agreement. Interestingly, Denmark showed exactly the same percentage of agreement in both questionnaires.

In the ‘before’ questionnaire, Portugal showed the least agreement to item 5, below 10 percentage points, whereas Denmark revealed the highest percentage of agreement, with more than half of the participants agreeing to the sentence. In the ‘after’ questionnaire, the UK displayed the higher level of agreement and France the lowest level. Also, France had the exact same percentage of agreement in both questionnaires, and Greece presented a very small change between the two measurement moments.

Figure 5. Percentage of agreement to item 5 ‘We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology’

Table 7. Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Percentage of agreement in the seven PDWs

Item	Before (%)	After (%)
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	90.6	88.6
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	65.2	62.0
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	24.1	25.0
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	28.5	29.9
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	30.6	31.4

As summarised in Table 7, and previously discussed, the percentage of agreement with each item was very similar between the two questionnaires, suggesting that participants’ attitudes are difficult to change as social psychology literature showed in the last decades (Albarracín & Shavitt, 2018; Verplanken & Orbell, 2022). Item 1 received the greatest percentage of agreement among all partners with around 90%. On the contrary, item 3 received the lowest agreement from participants.

Still, it is interesting to note that for some countries agreement with some of the items increased after the PDW, whereas for others it decreased. These small changes may be due to the way the discussion took place and were guided in the different groups and countries, with the most prominent topics in each group or with primacy or recency effects (see Crano, 1977). It is possible that some participants retained better the information presented at the beginning of the PDW (primacy effect), giving more importance to cases of bad science (cases 1 and 2) and hence agreeing less with positive sentences about S&T in questionnaire 2. Other participants might tend to better remember information at the end of PDW, assigning more relevance to the citizen science program (case 4), and thus agreeing more with positive sentences about S&T in questionnaire 2.

For most participants (85.5%), it was the first time that they had participated in an event where the public was invited to discuss science. Reasons to attend the event included to have the chance to discuss S&T with others for about 45% of the participants, to find out more about S&T and research practices for around 29% of the participants, and to have their say on S&T issues for about 21%.

When asked about the possible impacts of the PDW in their lives, most participants (74.9%) considered that they would like to get involved in similar events in the future, meaning that this event could increase their awareness and curiosity about future public participation in science (Table 8). More than half of the participants (61.7%) also revealed that they would talk to friends and family about S&T issues and follow news on these issues (51.5%). Other potential impacts included, for example, replicating this PDW, conducting further research on these topics, and using some of the ideas discussed in their professional lives (e.g., to plan sessions of Responsible Research and Innovation).

Table 8. Impacts of this event on participants: Results (%)

Impacts...	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	74.9%
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	61.7%
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	51.5%
4. Other	4.8%

5 Concluding remarks

This section provides a brief summary of the main conclusions of the PDWs. The goal is to provide concise answers to the research questions posed at the beginning of this Report, considering the full analysis presented in the previous chapters.

Recruitment and participants for the event

The general difficulty in recruiting participants for this event resulted in smaller and more homogeneous samples than initially proposed and expected. Despite the considerable efforts employed by all partners, the samples consisted of many participants with a professional relationship to science who showed great interest in contributing to the discussion on trust in science. However, members of the ‘general public’ (rather than specific groups) did not seem as attracted to participate in this event, with the exception of the Danish PDW. With much of the target audience proving to be unreachable, to some extent this may have led to a situation that could be characterized as “preaching to the converted”.

A possible explanation for this includes the levels of knowledge of the general public about the topic and thus the confidence to participate in such discussions. Moreover, the topic may have seemed too distant from everyday concerns of the general public.

Also, several partners used institutional communication by their universities and research institutions to disseminate the event, which in some cases had a poor result. This might suggest that internal clients such as professors, students and other employees did not receive or pay attention to this type of information.

What are participants’ attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices? What are participants’ main concerns, hopes and expectations concerning research integrity?

In several PDWs, integrity was discussed superficially and cases of lack of integrity were considered an exception to the norm. Most participants are aware of the different forms of breaching integrity in research, mentioning aspects such as FFP (falsification, fabrication, plagiarism), but also referring to some questionable practices such as not disclosing conflicts of interest or not receiving ethical approval to conduct a study.

Participants’ main concerns were conflicts of interest, principally the influence of the political power or the private industry. In this sense, participants would expect scientific institutions, peers, and media to act as watchdogs to reveal cases of bad practices.

Do these affect public trust in science?

Integrity appears to be less relevant for developing trust in science than other aspects such as communication. However, lack of transparency in how the scientific process is conducted by researchers – mainly not sharing the data and not revealing personal interests – can lead to distrusting science. On the other hand, scientific self-control mechanisms, such as peer-review, and open science practices can contribute to more trust in science.

What communication channels do people use and trust to get scientific information?

Social media are generally perceived as an untrustworthy means to get scientific information. Traditional means such as television and radio stations seem to be the medium of choice when it comes to receiving information on science-related issues. However, this opinion did not constitute a broad consensus, as several groups showed concerns with the potential influence of media owners or political power in defining the ‘narrative’ in their countries.

There seems to be a halo effect associated with traditional media: if they are perceived as trustworthy for receiving information on a wide variety of topics, they are also considered trustworthy for learning about science, hence generating more trust in science. Besides the important role of the specific channel of communication, individual actors such as journalists or researchers also have an important role in perceptions of trust or distrust in scientific communication. To sum up, science communication was considering a factor for trusting science when recognised professionals who provide supporting evidence for their claims use trusted traditional channels.

What manifestations of integrity and integration in research affect public trust in science, and how?

Incidences of FFP were perceived as serious violations of researchers’ ethical code, with data fabrication being one of the problems most discussed by the groups. Questionable research practices were also perceived as serious problems in scientific production and a threat to trust in science. In participants’ view, there does not seem to be a hierarchy of bad practices and they all affect the credibility of science.

Public integration in research was identified as a key factor to fostering trust in science, by educating society about scientific activities and making people feel they can contribute to scientific advancement. At the same time, public integration also helps scientists to develop science that is socially relevant, meeting people’s needs of daily lives. On the contrary, a perceived lack of expertise of the general public and concealed agendas when involving the public were clearly seen as capable of hindering public trust in science.

Similarities and differences between the countries

In the previous sections, the similarities and differences between the countries were described. These results should, however, be interpreted with caution considering the small size of the samples. Several similarities were identified, suggesting that there are factors that contribute for trusting science that cut across different national contexts. There are also some differences that can possibly be a result of how each PDW was set-up (e.g., the topic presented by the expert), the characteristics of participants who showed up (e.g., their involvement with science) and how the discussions unfolded in each group (e.g., topics that received greater attention in each group).

There might also be national and cultural factors at play, such as the existence of recent cases in the country about lack of integrity in science (e.g., ethical scandals) or the protrusion of certain cultural values (e.g., high power distance, individualism). However, further research is required to explore the role of such factors in developing trust in science.

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APPENDIX

Annex A: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – Denmark

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *Denmark*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Iscte)*

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1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the event

The Workshop Setting

The Danish workshop was held on Friday June 2nd, 2023 at the Aarhus Institute for Advanced Studies (AIAS) on the campus of Aarhus University. The workshop took place over one full afternoon, from 14:00 to 18:00 followed by a drinks reception. The workshop program was designed and conducted in alignment with the across-country study protocol (D.3.1). The introductory ‘ice-breaker’ activity was, however, adapted to the national community singing tradition, and a well-known Danish folk song was sung accompanied by the moderator on violin and a self-made public trust-themed verse written by a team member. The ice-breaker helped with establishing a light, collective and casual atmosphere as a foundation for the following moderator introduction, survey completion, expert presentation and two-phase deliberation. Eskil Welan, professional facilitator and innovation, climate and technology expert, moderated the deliberation, which included an expert talk entitled ‘Trust and Mistrust in Science’, by dr. Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen, associate professor and leader of Centre for Science Studies at the Department of Mathematics at Aarhus University.

A total of 40 participants signed up for the event, with only 27 partakers present at the day as a result of last-minute cancellations (cf. section on recruitment). During the event, the participants were divided over four smaller groups with six or seven members, with each group individually moderated by a member of the POIESIS national project team. All participants stayed until the end of the event, with the majority remaining for the subsequent drinks-reception. Apart from voicing their opinions and thoughts during the small group discussions, plenum sessions and two questionnaires, participants were also given the opportunity to leave notes in a dedicated box. This option was particularly stressed by the moderator and allowed participants to contribute thoughts even when time for discussions ran out or if they felt more comfortable sharing it with the project team only, rather than with other participants. The comments received are addressed in the report, mainly indirectly through similar points raised in the different deliberations.

Sample and Recruitment

The sample design was guided by a purposeful maximum-variation strategy with the objective to secure diversity in representation and elicit a broad range of participant values and attitudes as a cross-section of relevant perspectives. This was aimed at providing in-depth information into the study research questions (Palinkas et al., 2015; Patton, 2015). The sample strategy in the study aimed to procure variation in the representation of the general population and include different participants from the general public and social groups interested and involved in the POIESIS topical areas such as representatives from citizen science associations, civil society organisations, NGOs, minority groups, and different user communities. In addition, socio-demographic variation was a main criterion in the sample strategy to ensure variation in characteristics including age, gender and educational background (see also Deliverable 2.1, section 3.1).

The main study sample strategy was adapted to the Danish national context, identifying relevant participants, social groups, organisations and gatekeepers within the different stakeholder categories mentioned above. For each, associated recruitment strategies were fashioned in terms of relevant contact points, media outlets and type of advertisement (through networks and event participation etc., organisation etc.). The materials provided by the study coordinator were adapted to the Danish national context and included social media flyers and posters with QR codes for additional information. In addition, two different and large roll-ups were designed for the workshop and for participation in The Festival of Research at Aarhus University, in which two project team members participated to bring attention to the workshop and recruit potential participants. For all materials, a national contact person was listed, as opposed to a registration link, to facilitate personal communication and an early sense of commitment.

In total, 50 organisations/gatekeepers were contacted to obtain permission for sharing of posters/ flyers or to ask gatekeepers to forward the information within their organisation. These organisations broadly covered different stakeholder categories, including patient and climate organisations; political, religious, LGBTI+, and science associations/groups; local libraries; topical interest Facebook groups concerning COVID-19 and climate; and different schools and student associations, among others. In addition, more than 500 personal invitations were sent out in the recruitment process, which resulted in the confirmed registration of the desired 40 invitations. The recruitment process was carefully tracked through a detailed excel sheet, ensuring transparency, coordination and proper feedback measures. The recruitment of 40 participants proved very challenging in terms of attracting especially young people. The deliberative workshop coincided with student exam periods and a large Aarhus music festival, which may explain some of the recruitment difficulties in this age category. In addition, the relative broadness of the topic of public trust in science, complicated the enquiries to some interest organisations such as patient organisations as these organisations mainly forward information to members related to events closely aligned with their own topical area. Personal invitations – often through some form of organisational membership – proved to be the most successful recruitment strategy.

Upon invitation acceptance, each participant received a detailed email with a three-page information sheet concerning the deliberative workshop (i.e. information about the topic, method and practicalities), an AU information sheet regarding data processing and -protection and an informed consent form that could be signed prior to the workshop or upon arrival at the day of the event. All participants will receive follow-up information upon report publication.

Despite the total of 40 accepted invitations, an unforeseen large amount of last-minute cancellations (mainly on the day and the two days leading up to the event) resulted in the participation of 27 members of the general public in the event.

The 27 participants allowed for the planned division of four groups in total, however, with 6-7 participants in each group rather than 10. It is the assessment that the reduced group size allowed for increased in-depth discussions and increased speaking time for each participant, and that the lower number of participants has not negatively influenced the deliberations and quality of the data.

For socio-demographic characteristics of the participants as indicated in the distributed survey, please see section 1.2. The questionnaire asks about professional science affiliation but not about organisational memberships and volunteer activities. The information available on such membership in terms of the different stakeholder categories is obtained through the recruitment process and mainly through the organisations/networks etc. through which people have been contacted. Consequently, such information provides an overview of stakeholder representation in terms of the selected criteria but does not offer a complete set of information regarding representation.

Across the 27 participants, five participants are involved in political associations representing four different political parties. Nine participants were recruited as members of two large patient organisations. One participant is involved in a religious Civil Society Organisation (CSO), and four other participants were recruited through different kinds of volunteer work, e.g. the DaneAge Association. Geographically, six participants reside in Aarhus, one in Copenhagen and the remaining participants live across the Central Denmark Region.

In the questionnaire, participants were asked to indicate their professional involvement in science. The findings displayed in figure 1 show that the participants are almost equally divided between participants not being professionally involved in science (n=14) and participants being involved in science through their profession to some degree (n=13). Of the latter group, however, only 4 participants – including one student – are involved full time with science-related topics, whereas the remaining (n=9) are involved indirectly or occasionally.

Figure 1: Professional Involvement in Science. Participant Distribution.

1.2 Participants in the Event

Figure 2 displays the characteristics of the participants of the Danish workshop. The group is skewed towards older participants with 15 (56%) participants being older than 65. The educational makeup has a larger spread, almost the same amount of participants per possible group, with a single participant not indicating their educational attainment. Primary education and lower secondary education are both mandatory in Denmark, and as such no participants have educational attainment below lower secondary. Regarding gender, males are overrepresented with 17 participants identifying as male (63%). Regarding occupation, the most common indication is being a pensioner, which 10 indicate (37%). All other job descriptions are singletons, but only one of the 17 other participants indicate working in manual labour and a single indicate being in between jobs.

Figure 2: Participant Demographics

Notes: Count of participant per demographic group. Total number of participants is 27. Due to all other occupations than “Pensioner” being singletons, all other occupations have been grouped as “Other”.

2 Discursive summary of cases

2.1 Phase 1 – Expert talk

In the expert talk, Associate Professor Kristian Hvidtfelt Nielsen gave an introduction to trust and mistrust in science. He discussed the importance of trust in order for science to function well and to properly inform other actors, particularly politicians or others depending on science in their decision making. He characterised trust as a culture, something which is built slowly in interactions and relationships between different people or communities. He then presented a brief overview of the state-of-the-art knowledge about trust in science, including variations between geographical and demographic backgrounds. This part concluded with the observation that trust in science is a multi-faceted notion, which, among possible others, consists of a few dimensions: (i) general trust in science, (ii) trust that researchers create correct knowledge, (iii) trust that researchers, either publicly or privately funded, have the right motivations to find and disseminate new knowledge, and (iv) trust that there are appropriate institutional frameworks in place to ensure trustworthy research, for example in terms of transparency and honesty. The talk concluded with a brief discussion about the importance of understanding issues related to trust in science in the appropriate context. A few recent examples in which trust in science was heavily debated in Danish society, e.g. climate change, vaccinations and nature conservation; demonstrated that levels of and reasons for trust in science can be rather context dependent.

Both during and directly following the expert talk, participants asked a few questions. These mainly centred on the relation between funding sources (e.g. public vs. private) and trustworthiness of research; on the tension between disinterested research and relevance of research; on the role of social media and other communication channels in affecting public trust in science; and on the purposes of doing research. All of these topics were discussed more intensively during the group discussions and we will revisit them later in this report.

2.2 Phase 2 – Focus groups

2.2.1 Group 1 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3B, 4

In the first group, comprising seven people, the discussions were rather well balanced, with all participants contributing more or less equally to the discussion. This was already set in motion at the very start of the afternoon, where participants took a round to have their first say on the first case. Discussions were very active, with lots of laughter, and participants often interrupting one another despite overall agreement. While participants expressed generally positive attitudes towards science, no very outspoken attitudes or characteristics became evident in this group.

The group engaged in the corona case study – in this version, the news piece was sent from the Danish Broadcasting Corporation (DR) – with great commitment, focusing their discussion on the origin and transparency of data and problematized the lack of sound documentation, sufficient

data and substantiated evidence. On this basis, the study was seen as a write-off, even though the researcher was noted to be affiliated with a reputable university. Relatedly, one participant brought up an old research misconduct case from England (i.e. the Wakefield case, see Godlee et al, 2011), pointing to the severity of such cases and that they might continue to have serious consequences despite being retracted.

The case gave rise to a broader discussion on some of the vaccines produced during COVID-19, discussing 'a scale of trust' (Male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 1) in terms of the country specific context in which the vaccines were produced, highlighting the US/German-produced Pfizer vaccine as more trustworthy than the ones produced in China and Russia, for instance. The group generally problematized the contextual impact on the perceptions of trustworthy and sound research, acknowledging that they themselves might have seen the case in a more positive light if it came from Sweden and not Argentina. As part of the discussion, the group also touched upon the advantages of Covid-19 being a global phenomenon in the sense that this accelerated the advancement of vaccine developments. In this regard, the group also engaged in a broader discussion concerning test of new therapeutics and resource prioritization in the Danish health care system.

As a mediator, they found DR to be trustworthy, stating that it increases trust to have the study addressed and questioned. Moreover, they believed that the media in general should act as a 'watchdog'. At the same time, not properly accounting for the experts included in the reporting decreased trust as it remained unclear in what way they constitute 'independent' experts.

In contrary to DR, they did not perceive Twitter to be a format that supports transparency and increases trust due to its particular construct. In addition, they also found the uncertainty in term of both sender and audiences in case 2 to reduce trust. Different from case 1, participants in the group felt that the study in case 2 was likely to be valid as claimed by the university, but that the lack of proper documentation in the Twitter communication made it more difficult to assess. Case 2 prompted a broader discussion in the group concerning trust and misconduct cases, as well as trust in research in relation to different research fields. For the former, the Danish Penkowa case (see Callaway, 2011) was mentioned plus examples from Germany concerning plagiarism of doctoral theses. The fact that such cases become known and that control mechanisms are in place are seen as fostering trust in research. Two participants explicitly mentioned that a single case such as the Penkowa case does not affect their general trust in researchers. Secondly, two participants brought forth the perspective that the natural sciences can be perceived as more trustworthy than the social sciences due to potential political and societal impacts of the latter. A third participant indirectly challenged this view by highlighting the strengths of interdisciplinary research, explicitly speaking to the benefits of combining research with insights from both health and social science.

In the group discussion on case 3, participants initially focused on the informal aspect of sharing an invitation to a public hearing on Facebook, questioning this type of media used and the reporter's intentions with the posting. The group also discussed the actual purpose of such a hearing, expecting that it would attract participants with polarized views on vaccination, primarily vaccine sceptics. Contrary to the public hearing, the participants were all much more positive towards the citizen science project in case four, emphasizing the benefits of creating engagement for nature and science topics among the public, including the value of involving pupils. The group also discussed the conditions under which public engagement is desirable, agreeing that the particular project makes for a good case and makes science fun. Consensus also existed that this may not be science as such in terms of the validity of the data. At the same time, two participants

also acknowledged that the opportunity to collect large sets of data, covering large areas too, might be of scientific interest.

2.2.2 Group 2 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3A, 4

The discussions in the group were active and engaging from the start, characterised by a pleasant and constructive atmosphere. The group came across as fairly balanced in terms of age and professional science involvement with two participants involved in science qua their professional work and study. Their familiarity with science issues and methods were merely applied in an indirect way in their argumentation and did not dominate the discussion. Contrary, the gender balance was rather skewed with five men and only two woman taking part. The female participants were a bit more hesitant to join the discussion in the first part of deliberation and spoke generally less than their male counterparts, although still expressing their doubts and perceptions. The group conveyed overall consensus in their identification of main issues and concerns regarding the discussed cases, and while no major polarized views were voiced, participants still emphasised different aspects and perceptions, also building on and occasionally questioning unanimous perceptions.

In relation to the first two cases concerning research integrity and lack thereof, a number of across-case topics emerged in the discussions, and it was evident that a number of factors influenced participants' views on trust in research and researcher credibility. In both the cases concerning a new preventive treatment for corona (case 1) and a potential research misconduct incidence related to climate data, contextual factors such as case location and university reputation fed into the discussion about credibility. In addition, conflicts of interests and matters of independence played a role, with participants generally perceiving established universities as trustworthy and with the intension of promoting sound research. However, while this was also true for the university in case two, participants questioned the nature of the independent investigation and the university's motives for sending out the official statement, which did not seem to be addressing the general public. As one of the participants stated: "They sit and write in their ivory tower but they mainly write for themselves" (female, 61+ years, group 2). Hence, both content and type of dissemination can increase/decrease source credibility. Failing to align the message with the intended target group, e.g. the general public, reduces relevance and trustworthiness and is perceived to be poor science communication.

Mediators are seen as crucial for the message validity, too. While the Danish Broadcasting Corporation (DR) is seen as a reliable source, the DR journalist's motives for posting the piece on Facebook (case 1) is questioned and suspected of being sensational press. In this regard, degree of source credibility and motive transparency are applied in the overall assessment, reciprocally up- and down scaling levels of credibility.

Case 1 also gave rise to a distinct discussion concerning the 'expertise' of experts and the degree to which single cases on detrimental research practices influence public trust in research. For the latter, agreement seemed to exist that a single case such as the corona research study – despite generating scepticism and concern – does not alter their general and mainly positive attitudes towards science nor reduce their trust in science at large. The mentioning of 'independent experts' in case 1 triggered a discussion on the diluted designation of 'experts' as almost everyone can be an expert and if a lack of transparency in type and use of expertise is not clearly stated, credibility is quickly reduced. Relatedly, several participants expressed that researcher dissensus within a

field might increase a lack of trust in science as it can be difficult to know what to believe is true. Conversely, another participant stated that disagreement among scientists not necessarily diminishes trust but rather requires the individual researcher to make their own position clear. The relation between consensus and truth reflects a larger academic debate as to whether greater researcher consensus might help fight misinformation while improving public debate and policy-making (Adam 2023).

In the case 3 deliberation, the main topic of discussion was to which degree the public should be involved in policy decision-making processes and the objectives for involving the public in such processes. While participants agreed on the general benefits of including citizens in policy decision-making processes through engagement formats such as public hearings, a majority felt that COVID-19 vaccination for children did not constitute the best case for public consultation due to its medical and rather sensitive nature. Participants feared that such a hearing would primarily attract people with polarized positions and not represent the population, in general. Relatedly, decisions concerning this particular topic should be made on a medically sound expert foundation. Participants were also sceptical towards the particular design of the hearing. Judging from the case, the decision on whether to offer vaccination seems to have been made in advance, leaving the rationale for public engagement to be merely instrumental (compared to substantive and normative imperatives, Stirling 2008) and an exercise of legitimization and a type of ‘tokenism’ at best (Arnstein 1969). One participant compared the public hearing in the case to the pro forma element inherent in ‘green washing’.

A general positive stance towards public engagement was also expressed in relation to case 4 concerning citizen science. The benefits of including a range of citizen perspectives, and potentially increasing citizens’ trust in research by bringing them closer to research processes were highlighted as positive, but as in the previous case, including citizens in scientific research was only regarded to be of use in some research projects. Hence, participants primarily focused the discussion on the potential challenges of having ordinary citizens collect and monitor data as they questioned how to properly secure data quality and study validity in terms of the scientific knowledge produced.

2.2.3 Group 3 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3A, 4

The discussions in this group started relatively cautious. None of the group members engaged in the questions/discussion after the expert talk and there was slight hesitation when trying to find a note taker. After some initial reticence, the discussions unfolded in a rather pleasant way, with none of the participants dominating the discussion and all participants engaging substantially. One of the participants demonstrated fairly strong opinions that could be classified as science sceptic, e.g. vocally declaring to be a vaccination sceptic and doubting some of the fundamentals of climate science. Another participant disclosed to be lowly educated and therefore sometimes faced challenges in understanding scientific communication. Nevertheless, this participant ‘always googled’ issues of interest or unclear and the participant regularly engaged in citizen science projects. The presence of these somewhat outspoken characters resulted in group members regularly disagreeing, but they themselves seemed to appreciate this: “I think it’s great that we don’t always agree. That creates a good discussion.” (female, 61+ years, group 3).

Based on the stimuli material of the various cases, diverse discussions unfolded. In relation to case 1, the participants quickly delved into conversations on the role of diverse actors - most notably

researchers, journalists, citizens and politicians - in doing and communicating science. In this discussion, the group conveyed a desire for an explicit division of labour between these actors, while all should be open to be properly informed by each other. Crossing the boundaries of these roles (e.g. politicians getting involved in research or researchers blending into the policymaking process) was considered undesirable.

Noteworthy was the fact that the discussions were only rather loosely related to the stimuli material. This was particularly true for the second case. As this case was presented as a Twitter thread, something most group members were rather unfamiliar with, the group quickly put the stimuli material aside, considering it as either inaccessible or not trustworthy. Instead, discussions centred on more general topics, including the trustworthiness of climate science more generally and the way in which different communication channels can or should be used. In relation to both cases presented before the break, the group also discussed the extent to which researchers should be externally constrained to certain questions or methods, or be liberated, allowing researchers to proceed as they see fit. This was one of the topics on which participants had clearly diverging thoughts.

After the break, when discussing the cases related to public engagement in science and science-related policymaking, the overall attitudes of the group seemed to be slightly more aligned. There was general consensus in the group that the engagement through a public hearing in case 3 was rather non-sensible, both because the public lacked the proper kind of expertise and because a decision already seemed to be in place. Some group members nevertheless expressed interest in joining the hearing, for example to be informed or to be able to express their own personal opinion (not necessarily with the aim to affect the final outcome of the process).

In contrast, the group was highly positive about the mode of participation suggested in the final case. They saw clear benefits of such a process for several stakeholders involved and agreed that, at least for some audiences, engaging with the research process in such a way could positively affect people's science attitudes. Also here, the group expressed a clear idea of division of labour, with citizen scientists only capable of performing certain roles, while requiring proper oversight and guidance from professional scientists.

2.2.4 Group 4 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3B, 4

In this final group, two participants (both women) dominated the discussion to some extent. At least one of them seemed to be fairly close to science, i.e. either having worked in science or having a relative working in it. Some other participants were slightly timid, with some only entering the discussion after the break. Generally, the participants seemed to be more at ease after the break. Nevertheless, all participants finally contributed to the discussions and especially case 4 seemed to be close to the heart of many participants. Participants also seemed comfortable to share personal experiences and to voice that they did not agree with general or majority opinions. For example, one of the participants explicitly mentioned to be 'among the 1% of people who has a different opinion on this'(male, 40-60 years), thereby going against the mainstream.

Discussions in this group focused among others on the importance of the messenger and medium used to communicate about science; the different intentions or stakes these actors might have; as well as some issues around meaningful integration of citizens in science and some ethical concerns.

In relation to the first case, some participants in this group expressed substantial concerns about the role and motives of various actors, in particular the journalists and financial sponsors of research, similar to some of the discussions in the other groups. Noteworthy in this group was that participants explicitly picked up on the notion of ‘research misconduct’ and even mentioned some other scandals involving misconduct, that were not mentioned in the stimuli material or the expert talk (e.g. the Penkowa case, see Callaway, 2011). The significance of the case being presented as a Facebook post was also hotly debated, with participants questioning why a journalist would use this communication channel and discussions about the ways in which these digital approaches could be used to include additional sources. Also, just as with some of the previous groups, the importance of scientific institutions like review mechanisms to combat misconduct was mentioned.

In relation to the second case, this group was noteworthy for their persistence in trying to fully understand the details of the case. Several members of the group expressed to have difficulties with grasping the case, but rather than putting it aside to have discussions about more general topics (like for example group 3 did), this group engaged in somewhat lengthy discussions to explain their understanding of the case’s content. When this was settled, the discussions once again revolved around actors’ intention; in this case, mainly questioning the motives of the university to communicate an official press release. Also the importance of reputation was extensively discussed, with the group agreeing on the fact that this has a significant impact on a source’s trustworthiness.

After the break, the questioning of actors’ motives and incentives continued. This was particularly the case in relation to case 3, where most group members considered the public hearing undesirable and would henceforth not participate in it. They even considered it “manipulative” (multiple participants), which, however, not all participants agreed with. Just as in other groups, the fact that a decision seemed to be made prior to the hearing, rendered the hearing meaningless according to most group members.

The conditions under which public engagement is meaningful and the way in which expert of professional researchers should guide such a process, were also the main topics discussed in relation to the last case. While being generally more positive about the engagement format suggested in this case, participants still casted doubt on whether this would affect the quality of the data and the subsequent conclusions. Hence, while being generally positive about the suggested involvement, the group also expressed some reservations, which will be discussed in more detail in the next section.

3 Integrity and Integration & Trust in Science

3.1 General Attitudes towards Science

Questionnaires

In the pre-workshop questionnaire, participants were asked to indicate their concerns about science. While these covered a variety of themes, few could be characterized within the themes of integrity and integration. However, a few themes of relevance did emerge prior to any influence from the workshop. Chief of these was concerns regarding the influence of special interest in science (mentioned by 5, 19%), the perceived distance of science to society (4, 15%), issues of ethics (non-specified, 3, 11%), and a single participant specifically mentioned misconduct (in Danish “uredelighed”).

In the post-workshop questionnaire, the participants were again asked to answer open questions. Regarding research integrity, framed as “bad practices in science”, the main theme was the influence of special interests, similar to the pre-questionnaire, and a series of concerns regarding potential negative consequences of bad scientific practices, e.g. that they cause harm or influence policy making for the worse. 5 participants (19%) specifically mentioned that bad science might be detrimental for trust in science. Regarding integration of the public, the sentiment of the participants was that integration is good but that there is too little of it. 3 participants (11%) explicitly connected integration to trust. A single participant indicated that “many citizens do not have the required competences” to allow for meaningful integration in research.

Workshop discussions

During the group discussions, participants only seldom explicitly referred to their general attitude towards science. Some of these references were made though, usually in a rather optimistic tone, i.e. conveying positive attitudes towards science, e.g. “But I also have a personal belief in science. So it’s because I’m characterised by this impression that science is something that is credible.” (female, 61+ years, group 4)

Interestingly, in some cases these attitudes were backed up with personal motivations. These typically involved personal experiences with successful health-related interventions. One of the participants in group 3, for example, shared the story of her mother suffering from breast cancer, but since she started taking an experimental drug she has been doing well: ‘She is just as you and me. That would not have been possible ten or fifteen years ago. So, cheers for science!’ (female, 40-60 years). Similarly, in group 4, a participant mentioned undergoing an experimental heart surgery: “I was only the 18th in the world to undergo this. The 18th! [...] It was a research project. So, it could have gone wrong.” (male, 61+ years). These stories concerning medical successes clearly boosted participants’ optimism towards and trust in science.

The participants which expressed negative attitudes towards science tended to back these up by anecdotes referring to the covid-19 pandemic, in which they felt that science was used to constrain people’s individual freedom while not taking into account people’s personal perspectives. These attitudes seemed to be solely concern science related to the pandemic, but were expressed in two groups.

3.2 Diversity of Factors that Affect Trust in Science

During the discussions across the various cases, many factors were mentioned that potentially could affect trust in research. Two of these were rather prominent and we will hence discuss these in more detail: independence and background/reputation.

First, participants discussed the issue of independence in many ways and at various occasions. Sometimes they mentioned it explicitly, but more commonly they referred to it in more implicit terms. When mentioned explicitly, a higher degree of independence was usually associated with a higher level of trust, for instance when referring to case 2: “We also read that there have been some independent people who have looked at this. There is no cheating.” (male, 40-60 years, group 1). However, some participants, referring to the same case, questioned what was meant by ‘independent experts’ as this was not clear from the text (group 2, cf. section 2.2.2). A suspicion of researchers not being independent, having undisclosed stakes or hidden agendas, was repeatedly flagged as a potential source of distrust. Participants in multiple groups asked themselves what the motivations were for actors to do research, report research, and communicate research in a certain way:

“So you could very well ask what the motives behind this are, I think. And here I think that the doctor probably has some motives, uh, he is himself involved in a development programme somewhere.” (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 1)

“But the research is still valid enough, but of course it’s targeted where the money is” (male, 61+ years, group 1, case 2) [responding to another participant questioning the validity of research if researchers have a financial stake in it]

“What was the background for them to come up with something like that. Is there, as we’ve talked about, something hidden behind it? Are there personal interests? Are there financial interests?” (male, 61+ years, group 4, case 2)

According to a majority of the participants, ways to strengthen a sense of independence in research is through following ‘objective’ procedures, apply quality checks or independent research validation measures. Participants across the groups heralded such scientific procedures as a way to assure credibility and trustworthiness:

“I am not a researcher but, as far as I know the peer review process, [gives a description of the review process, stressing that it involves independent people judging one’s work] it is very difficult to manipulate the process. [...] so, if that process is manipulated, ..., I just don’t think one could even do that.” (male, 39- years, group 2, case 2)

“[...] because you could say that any study has to follow a protocol, and then when you write an article, there must also be some kind of review, i.e. other independent people who are sent around and check the researchers. The head of research here, refuses to pass on data and things like that, and that means that all the lights must be on and you can’t take such a study seriously.” (male, 61+ years, group 4, case 2)

Also, not conforming to such procedures, for example by not being transparent about research data, is a source of suspicion among participants:

“I’m a little surprised that this Carvallo here is a professor and he’s at Buenos Aires university. [...], so you should trust that what he does is actually correct. But he doesn’t want to publish these research results. And then you just wonder what, is this, is it not done well enough, or does he just not want to come forward? Is there someone there, does he have another agenda? Is there someone he’s trying to - is there a pharmaceutical company behind it that he needs to benefit in some way?” (male, 40-60 years, group 2, case 1)

A second aspect that was hotly debated across the various groups and cases, was the impact of researchers’ and their institutions’ background and reputation on trust. Particularly, discussions in three groups revolved around the influence of nationality on trustworthiness, triggered by the cue that it was an Argentinian researcher that allegedly engaged in misconduct in case 1. Discussions unfolded differently across groups though. In some groups, Danish researchers were favoured over other nationalities, exemplified by the quotation: “I trust Danish researchers the most, until the opposite is proven” (male, 61+ years, group 4). By contrast, participants in other groups made no distinction. For instance one participant states: “but whether it’s an Argentinian or it’s a South African or a Korean or whatever, it won’t matter to me”. (male, 61+ years, group 3). In group 1, participants did not agree on this issue. The following conversation nicely exemplifies the kinds of issues at stake and the diverse perspectives of participants:

Moderator: “Um, among other things, I heard several of you mention that there are some DANISH researchers who look into it and stuff like that. Do you think there’s a difference in the quality of the research, for example?”

“Yes. Well, um, you do get a bit nationalistic, I think that there are some countries that we trust more than others. And I apologise for being - or I’m like that.” (female, 40-60 years)

“Yes but no no no, I just wanted to say: not really, I almost said. Because if the researchers, well, then they should - basically, they’ll find the truth. And if the researchers do their work properly and follow the method that you say should be followed, and it’s documented in the right way, and the data is valid and representative and all that stuff that needs to be in order before you can say: ‘check!, it’s true’, then it doesn’t really matter who’s doing the research, it might be a waste of money if we all have to sit around reinventing the wheel.” (male, 40-60 years)

“It must be terrible for the poor researcher who is sitting in Uganda and has really done his work thoroughly [several say yes] and is trying to get it out, you know, and then the general attitude is... “ (male, 40-60 years)

Apart from nationality, participants in group 4 discussed the more general background of researchers and their institutions and how they affect their credibility. This included issues like track record and reputation, indicating that participants are highly sensitive to the historical context of research and its trustworthiness:

“[It matters] how credible it is, how big and how recognized it is, how much they are known for doing good research” (female, 40-60 years, group 4, case 2)

“They [referring to well-known hospitals] have a lot of recognition. And of course they can take a few scratches, but they shouldn’t have too many of these, or they lose credibility.” (male, 61+ years, group 4, case 2)

“That’s right. The sender has a meaning, i.e. is it a place you trust and say that they are good at something, uh, whatever it is. It can also be so many other things. It can also be a company that really knows something about a certain field, or they’re the only one in the country that does something. Then you would think that it has credibility in its own field.” (female, 40-60 years, group 4, case 2)

“[...] then no one will recognize this researcher. He has not been affiliated with any institution, nor has he had any research funding or anything else. Then you start to question, well, did it happen?” (female, 40-60 years, group 4, case 1)

Not only the historical context and track record of the researchers involved in a case, but also the way in which results fit with the participants’ prior beliefs, were deemed important for trustworthiness. This was particularly voiced by one participant, but others in the same group seemed to agree: “Well, this one, the conclusion here is a bit similar to what I already think, so that’s why I have a different... We hit what I already think and that makes me, well, yes, I think it affects me.” (male, 61+ years, group 4, case 2)

Apart from these cross-cutting themes that reoccurred in all groups, several other factors affecting participants’ trust in research, either for better or worse, were mentioned. Participants in group 1 had discussions about the role of research disciplines or fields in determining whether research is to be trusted. In these discussions, participants did not come to a similar conclusion though:

“Yes, I think we maybe need to talk about the fact that there are different TYPES of research. I think that social science research is probably more up for discussion than the more natural science research” (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

“So if they’re going to inject me with some medicine, I’ll be more sceptical than if they say that people with red hair have more children than those with black hair. So, not very interesting, not very important. That’s how I feel. So if it’s medicine, then I think: hey hey!” (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

“I would say that if it is cross-sectional research, where we have both the humanities field and, for example, the clinical field together, now I myself am a representative of this. Then I start to have a little more trust in, okay, here you have the breadth, uh, so it’s not just about growth within a particular field, but we also have some other quality parameters.” (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

Another very interesting factor was mentioned in discussions in group 3. Here, participants discussed the need to being open to critique, including taking non-scientific voices seriously. This was mainly expressed in a negative tone, i.e. expressing that not taking concerns from outside academia seriously, negatively impacts participants’ attitudes towards science:

“I’m here because I want to talk about why trust in researchers can be difficult. It’s because it’s such a closed society. [...] I think they kind of belittle us.” (female, 61+ years, group 3, case 1)

[...] “What I think it is, again, is that the researchers become quite closed, because... Try to listen to common sense! Try to listen to what... How should I say it? Um... I think

it's so annoying that it's made so black and white, and I think it's actually the researchers who are doing it together with the politicians. I think the two groups, they make it very black and white" (female, 61+ years, group 3, case 2)

"I just think that scientists and the rest of us who are not scientists could come a long way if we could all learn, I think, if we could agree to disagree. Because if you agree to disagree, already there you've actually opened a little door, and then you can start talking." (female, 40-60 years, group 3, case 2)

Lastly, some participants explicitly voiced the idea of 'Needing to trust science, because we have no other option':

"Well, I have a foot in both camps, because I also want to believe the researchers, because I don't have the brains to figure these things out. And I absolutely have to believe in what you scientists are finding out. But my common sense also tells me something else, because, hello, are we suddenly going to be immortal?" (female, 61+ years, group 3, case 1)

Overall, we notice that a high diversity of factors affecting public trust in science were discussed, most prominently including the independence of research from their financial sponsors and the reputation or track record of those involved in research, either individuals or their institutions.

3.3 Attitudes towards Research Integrity Practices and Trust

Despite research integrity being explicitly mentioned in the preparatory material, the expert talk, and the case materials, the theme was hardly explicitly discussed in the group discussions. Several of the groups did not pick up on the theme of RI in relation to the cases (even in cases 1 and 2). Nonetheless, two groups did. In these groups, discussions about RI-related topics tended to be rather nuanced. For example, in group 4, in relation to case 1B, participants initially came to the conclusion that if research misconduct was involved in the work under discussion, then the results should be discarded as useless. However, one of the participants comments that this is not the 'real' point of the matter:

"We've been told, it's completely useless. I don't think that's so exciting. I think it's more exciting how it comes in and affects [the politicians' conclusion] and how it is treated, because there may be something to talk about." (male, 40-60 years, group 4)

In other words, the participant notes that misconduct in itself is not the main issue, but rather the way in which it is dealt with in science and how it comes to affect decisions outside of science. Later in the same group discussion, another participant reiterates a similar thought when noting:

"Because then it says lack of protocols and review, because that is the same as scientific misconduct. It's the same thing that applies there." (male, 61+ years, group 4)

Again, the participants argue that scientific institutions (like protocols or review mechanisms) that either facilitate or hinder misconduct are equally important as the bare act of misconduct itself. When the participants of this group sum up their discussions before moving to the next case, they even assert that these kinds of mechanisms are a "minimum condition for what can be called science." (male, 40-60 years, group 4)

While protocols and mechanisms to prevent misconduct are hence deemed to be important, participants of this group also see a dilemma, with too many resources being used on investigating misconduct, when there is no real reason for that:

“There is a dilemma there, because I would like it if a university comes along and says, ‘Such and such’, that it is right, and if it is not right, I would like someone to investigate it. But I don’t want, at the same time, I don’t want every single time there’s a tiny little reason, or no reason at all, that it’s questioned, because then it really takes resources to have to defend yourself or explain yourself.” (female, 61+ years, group 4, case 2)

Lastly, as mentioned in the previous subsection on general reasons to trust or distrust research, participants sometimes mention the ‘hidden forces’ behind a research project. This may include financial sponsors of research projects or politicians having a stake in the research. Any of these undisclosed stakeholders could unduly affect the research and its outcomes, which, even if not explicitly labelled as such, are considered to be malpractice by some of our participants:

“But he doesn’t want to publish these research results. And then you just wonder what, is it not done well enough, or does he just not want to come forward? Is there someone there, does he have another agenda? Is there someone he’s trying to - is there a pharmaceutical company behind it that he needs to benefit in some way?” (male, 40-60 years, group 2, case 1)

This testifies to a rather broad understanding of research integrity and misconduct practices among our participants, not only including the traditional ‘FFP’ (Fabrication, Falsification and Plagiarism), but also covering notions like conflicts of interest, unwillingness to share data, and a lack of standardised protocols. Even if the participants did not explicitly label these as ‘research misconduct’, these practices were considered sub-optimal ways of conducting science and henceforth have the potential to negatively affect attitudes.

Lastly, as mentioned in section 2.2, we note that participants in two groups made references to historical cases of research misconduct, that were not mentioned in any of the stimuli material or the expert talk. Hence, it is clear that at least some participants had prior knowledge about RI-related issues.

3.4 Public Integration in Science and Trust

Participants in several of the groups shared experiences of themselves being engaged in scientific projects. Some of these resembled, and were triggered by, the research project described in case 4:

“Yes, I have participated in such a project myself. [...] We had to drive around with a net on our car [...] and had to collect insects [...] and then send it to the National History Museum or something like that.” (female, 40-60 years, group 3)

Other participants shared experiences of being part of a medical research project, not in the sense of ‘citizen scientist’ but rather as a research subject.

These experiences were usually met with approval of the other group members, who, despite ‘not seeing themselves doing it’, agreed that there were multiple potential benefits to this.

More generally, participants approved of the intentions of the project described in case 4. They figured that these kinds of projects might target very specific audiences, not necessarily including themselves. Most notably, they considered these projects particularly interesting for children and/or their (grant) parents or school teachers as well as for retired people. Even though many of the participants themselves were retired, these participants still not expressed to be very willing to engage themselves. Note here though, that about one-fifth of our participants indicated to have previously participated in similar workshops as ours and hence engaged with scientific projects before (see section 4 on the questionnaires).

After the more critical discussions related to case 3 (see below), the participants agreed that one of the attractive elements in the project described in case 4 was that one could contribute, even if one lacked specific knowledge or background information; i.e. one need not be an expert to meaningfully contribute. This led to the conclusion that such initiatives are highly welcome:

Participant: “we all immediately say, clapping our little hands, well, we think it's fine.”

Moderator: “At least you can say, we want to be a part of this. Isn't that what it is?”

Participant: “Yes, immediately. We would like to have something like that”. (group 4)

In relation to case 3, the public hearing about vaccination among children, participants were markedly more critical. The general tendency and opinion seemed to be that involving the public in such a way was problematic for multiple reasons: (i) the decision had already seemed to be made, so citizen participation could not have a real impact through the hearing, (ii) this was a decision that needed to be made by experts, because the general public lacks the required knowledge or expertise to contribute, and (iii) the motives and intentions of politicians and researchers to stage a public hearing were questioned. These discussions resemble discussions within the academic literature about various modes of public participation and the rationales of them (e.g. the notion of ‘preferred participation’, Mejlgaard & Stares 2013).

In relation to (i), some participants expressed a general interest in involving the public, but not under these conditions:

“Well, I certainly believe that the population must be involved. And those who want to be at the hearing, they should be at the hearing. 100 percent. But it just seems a bit pointless, because it seems like they've already made a decision. So I can understand why some people might think, ‘Well, it doesn't matter.’” (female, 40-60 years, group 4)

Another participant compared the public hearing to raising their own children:

“Well, when I read it, I think back to when I was raising my children. ‘I can hear what you're saying, and I can understand that you want to do all that, and it makes perfect sense, BUT I'm the one who decides.’ [other group members laugh in agreement]” (female, 61+ years, group 3, case 3)

In relation to (ii), participants were rather vocal and clear about the role that the public could or should play in these circumstances:

“The first thing I would think is that it should not be up to the public to decide whether children should be vaccinated. It should be, it should be the working group that is working on it, who know what they are dealing with.” (female, 61+ years, group 4)

“I think it's difficult for lay people to go in and see what significance this has. When you have some researchers, it must be that we have to lean a little bit towards those

researchers. [...] Now I'm a mechanic, and what the hell do I know about that?" (male, 61+ years, group 4)

Alternatively, one of the science-critical participants took another stance. Even though this participant agreed with the others that involvement in this particular case was not meaningful, she believes that, generally, researchers should be much more open to including public voices in their research:

"and that's why I'm very, I'm probably quite negative towards scientists, because I think scientists are extremely protective. They don't want to accept any mistakes. 'I'm not making any mistakes' We can have that debate about wild horses¹ and stuff like that. Why don't you sit down and listen to what is actually being said out there in society. [...]. No, they're more adamant that 'We've done the research. Our machines and our data, they speak the truth.' So the people are kind of the stupid ones. Like... 'You know what, you don't know anything about this. We're the ones who know something about this.' " (female 61+ years, group 3)

In relation to (iii), some participants were rather explicit in formulating their opinion, calling the hearing "manipulative" (male, 61+ years, group 4), only trying to make it seem like every one had the chance to participate. This came with a general concern about politicians' and researchers' motives and subsequently, an implicit lack of trust in these actors' benevolence.

Most participants therefore agreed that they would rather not contribute to the hearing. Some were a bit more positive though, indicating that they would consider it. In these cases, they would however not contribute in order to affect the decision, but rather to be properly informed:

"If I come to the meeting, I want to hear their opinion and several different opinions. So, I don't feel manipulated. On the contrary, I feel like I'm being informed about where they are." (male, 40-60 years, group 2)

Apart from the reasons to participate in scientific endeavours mentioned so far, one of the participants particularly mentioned another reason, closely related to activism:

"Well, I would also like to participate, because then I would set up at Thy National Park and film all those suffering, wild animals as they slowly starve to death. I would take all the pictures I could and send them to the researchers so they can see what they do to these animals" (female, 61+ years, group 3)

Some of the participants envisioned a clear division of labour between researchers and citizens when both are to collaborate on a single project. For example, when discussing case 4, the following conversation between two participants in group 3 expressed a rather traditional division of labour, in which the public's role is sometimes referred to as 'data drones':

"The role of the researcher is to set the framework for what should be counted, or for example, 15 minutes. That they set the framework for each individual. And then keeping track of all the individual participants, who gather the information and get it home. Isn't it?" (female, 40-60 years, group 3)

"Yes. They're the ones who do the statistics." (male, 40-60 years, group 3)

¹ There is an ongoing debate about nature conservation and the introduction of wild animals in Denmark, which was also referred to in the expert talk

“We’re the ones doing the work. They are the ones who finalize it.” (male, 40-60 years, group 3)

In group 1, a participant conveyed somewhat similar opinions, when stating that researchers are to monitor and improve the quality of the data delivered by citizens: “And I think the researchers KNOW they are getting bad data. They know we’re amateurs, I think they know they’re getting bad data. But they can process it with the reservations that are inherent in it, I think” (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 4)

Participants expressed that, in general, it is difficult to say whether public involvement increases or decreases public trust in science. This really depends on the conditions and specificities of the case at hand. One of the concerns repeatedly voiced was that of a lack of expertise of the public, potentially leading to lower quality and validity of data, which appeared across groups in discussions related to both case 3 and 4.

Among the most commonly expressed advantages of incorporating the public in research projects were the ability to get more or more diverse data; the inspiring effect it might have on people, especially children, to become a researcher themselves; the opportunity to reach out to people who might be interested in or affected by research; and giving people the opportunity to affect decision making.

3.5 Communication Channels and Trust in Science

Communication channels and their trustworthiness in relation to research were undoubtedly among the most extensively discussed and debated topics during the Danish workshop. Participants had very outspoken opinions and ideas about which mediating actors are to be trusted and which actors are not. It also became clear that the medium through which an actor communicates has considerable impact on the perceived trustworthiness of the source and the research reported on.

Type of actors

Participants in all groups discussed what type of actors were considered to be trustworthy. One of the main characteristics mentioned here was that actors should be independent of the issue at stake. For that, it doesn’t matter who the actor is (‘a company, a university, a researcher, ...’). Too close ties to the issue or people involved negatively affects trustworthiness. This is nicely exemplified in the following discussion in group 1:

“Isn’t it his colleague. It’s all wrong with the sender. (female, 40-60 years)

“Yes, it says so here, he works there, yes. (female, 61+ years)

Moderator: “So it also creates doubt that it’s a colleague?”

“Yes, he represents East Anglia University and then he confirms that they are right in their research, even though he didn’t do it himself.” (female, 61+ years)

“And you could say, as a colleague, you also have a stake, uh... representative role. [...] so again, you can say whether it’s a company he works for or whether it’s his

colleague; in that way, he has shares in it, and he's also from that university, so in order to protect himself, he should also promote his colleague. So that makes the credibility worse" (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

In group 2, one of the participants made a remark conveying the same opinion:

"And then he said that the funny thing is that they are used as a basis for dismissals, as if they had been an impartial investigation. But they have been ORDERED by someone, and it is usually employers who hire, so how independent are they really? And that's why I think I'm missing something to know whether ..., I think it's important for me to know to use it as a basis for whether I believe the content or not." (male, 39-years, group 2, case 2)

Related to this, a second major characteristic that was discussed in relation to various actors' credibility, was the source of funding or support for these actors. Some participants suggested that privately funded research or research conducted by private firms is less trustworthy because of the company's stakes (interest?). However, other participants downplayed the link between financial interests and research outcomes or objectives:

"Yes, but you can't JUST say because it's Novo [i.e. a pharmaceutical company], because they also put money into, you could say, things that don't go directly into their pocket. [...] and you could not say that just because it's private, we can't say that they're evil. And because it's the state, they are good..." (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

Or participants question the impact that such companies have on research output: "I don't know if they are correcting the research, but they are TARGETING the research." (male, 61+ years, group 1, case 2)

No matter which actor is discussed, for all actors goes that participants question their motives and the reason for using particular channels to communicate. When summarising their discussions after cases 1 and 2, one participant of group 2 concludes: "I just think, it's like the essence of most things, it's like, what is the motive behind choosing to do this." (male, 40-60 years)

In many of the media reports in the cases, experts are called upon as trustworthy sources. However, participants felt that calling someone an expert, does not necessarily make them trustworthy. "who is the expert, what is the credibility of the expert, and uh is it really an expert? [...] because anyone can be an expert." (Moderator of group 2 summarising discussions of case 1 and 2). Also, experts should stay close to their expertise and not get involved in discussions too distant from it:

"What strikes ME when I read this is that, uh, it is emphasised that it is the work group leader, who is not named, uh, that she is a TECHNICAL leader. As far as I know, when you use a word like "technical", there must also be a professional leader, and therefore it catches my eyes a little when I see that a technical leader starts talking about professional content. I think that's a problem." (male, 61+ years, group 2, case 3)

On the other hand, experts that are part of a recognised group are generally trusted as exemplified by this exchange:

"It is the expert group. It is their recommendation." (male, 61+ years,)

Other participant: “So, there’s no need to hold a public meeting or show up because we trust, or you trust, uh, what the experts recommend. Yes.” (male, 40-60 years, group 4, case 3)

This questioning of the position of the expert, resulted in participants feeling the need to read original sources. They felt that when mediating actors get involved, they might adjust parts of the original source according to their own agenda:

“So it’s also a, well, it’s probably a matter of separating it. But it quickly becomes difficult, right, because, well, politicians also communicate research, and what kind of things they emphasise over others. It’s a bit like the media, who also take some things over others. So I also think that if you really wanted to believe in the research, you should read the original research. You’d have to go and find the original source and then read it yourself with your own glasses on.” (male, 40-60 years, group 3, discussing case 1)

This then finally resulted in the observation that it is sometimes difficult to assess the credibility of sources, especially when different sources disagree:

“But I think it’s sometimes, when you see on the TV news, when you see politicians and professors, how much they can disagree about medicine. We saw [that] during Covid-19, didn’t we, and there we sit as lay people, wondering who exactly we should side with. Who do we believe is telling the truth?” (male, 40-60 years, group 3, case 1)

In general, we conclude that trust in a particular actor is not only based on characteristics of this actor, but also on the relation the actor has to the issue at stake. Independence and a lack of conflicts of interest (financial or otherwise) seem to be most prominent for our participants when assessing credibility. In addition to this, an actor’s reputation and perceived expertise play important roles.

The role of mediating actors

In their deliberations, a majority of participants highlighted several distinct roles that they felt mediating actors should perform. First, it is the role of the media to make readers aware of the potential issues with research, hence allowing an assessment of its trustworthiness:

“But then again, I think it’s the media’s responsibility when they present it to us to draw attention to the fact that this is actually problematic” (female, 61+ years, group 1, case 1)

“But that’s where the media’s role is also to be, what do you call it, a watchdog and go out and say, listen, there’s something wrong here.” (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 1)

Second, it is the media’s role to give opposing views the opportunity to speak up: “There were some vaccine-sceptics that never got broadcasting time.” (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 1). This also includes the role of mediating actors to give researchers the chance to clearly, though also in detail, express themselves in the media. Participants noticed though, that researchers might

not always be capable of striking this balance. The media, or someone else, should therefore help them:

“Researchers should have a spin doctor. Well... [several other participants agree] They should have someone who could make them super sharp in front of the media, so “How do you explain this so that you can still stand by yourself, but also communicate it in a way that Mr and Mrs Jensen or (unclear) understand it?” (female, 39- years, group 3, case 2)

Third, participants felt that the media’s role is to be neutral, to give information, but not to persuade: “I like the fact that he [the journalist] informs you that there is a hearing and can participate in it so that you are active in the process, but I think he goes too far, I mean at the end, to end there [when the journalist gives a recommendation about vaccination], I think that’s unpleasant.” (male, 40-60 years, group 4, case 3)

Related to this, participants expressed scepticism when mediating actors used language that is not considered neutral, hence suggesting that the mediating actor had other objectives than merely informing:

“I would like to be critical of the JOURNALIST’S way of describing. JOURNALIST’S way of describing. Because I think, I sit and think that - and I don’t attribute any motives to the journalist. But the journalist starts by saying that a new study from Argentina “claims”. You could also say “informs”. “Claims” is already an idea that this is something that may be on the edge of credibility. So a kind of tone has already been set here.” (male, 40-60 years, group 2, case 1).

Hence, participants expressed clear opinions about the role of mediating actors, which mainly consists of being a ‘watchdog’, providing opportunity for diverse expertises to be voiced, while themselves maintaining a neutral position.

Trustworthy channels

Apart from the trustworthiness of actors, participants devoted considerable attention to the specific channels that actors used to transmit their messages. Participants for example compared channels with respect to the level of detail and background information they can provide. In all groups, participants concluded that traditional, quality newspapers are probably on top of the credibility hierarchy, followed by tv and radio news, and social media channels lagging behind.

More generally, reputable media channels (such as DR – the Danish national broadcast service, equivalent to the BBC) are in principle trustworthy, but under the condition that they are transparent about their sources:

“I didn’t doubt for a moment that when it says “DR journalist” here, it represents a very high degree of credibility, because I associate DR with a very high degree of credibility. Whereas if it had said “Fox News”, I might have thought “aah”, maybe it was someone they had found themselves.” (male, 61+ years, group 2, case 1)

“I’m very sceptical about this and what she writes. And as [other participant] says, these so-called experts that many media outlets often refer to. An expert says such and such, an expert says such and such, we never get to know what kind of expert

they are, what they are an expert in. It's kind of the same thing. It annoys me a lot."
(male, 40-60 years, group 2, case 1)

As the first of these quotes indicates, just as we mentioned before in terms of general trust in science, nationality of (media) channels plays some role. In another group, this was mentioned explicitly:

"So, of course, we have a certain level of trust in the Danish press compared to some other countries, but yes, they're not, uh, they're not really on the top on trust." (male, 61+ years, group 1, case 1)

Some of the cases used as stimuli material included a certain mix of mediating actors and channels, with social media being used by actors from traditional sources (e.g. DR journalists). When such sources are using other platforms or channels, e.g. Facebook, their trustworthiness quickly declines, according to various participants in multiple groups. This is partly because the use of social media cast doubt about the actor's motives: "It is an informal, informal medium that is being used here. It is the private individual and what are his motives?" (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 3)

In the Danish context, it should be noted that Twitter is hardly used, while almost all Danes are on Facebook. This reflects in participants perceptions of different social media channels. While it is acknowledged that "anyone can go into Facebook and write things" (male, 61+ years, group 2, case 1), hence Facebook posts should be treated with caution, they are still considered to be at least somewhat useful. In case of Twitter, this is very different. In fact, the groups receiving cases with material from Twitter, almost immediately discarded the cases, treating them as not worthwhile to consider: "This is not even in the media, it's just Twitter..." (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2); "We started with talking about Twitter, which we agreed did not have any trustworthiness" (group 3, case 2). Some participants that are not familiar with Facebook, had the same experience when reading a Facebook post though: "Yes, so I would not even read further. I really don't feel like it." (male, 61+ years, group 4, case 1).

This suggests that familiarity with channels is an important predictor of the channel's trustworthiness. Very generally, participants strongly value to know who a sender, a source or a channel is. As has become clear in the proceeding sections, the historical context and reputation of a source or channel is of critical importance. In the discussions of case 2 in group 4, one of the participants conveys this sentiment very concisely: "I just need to know who this is!" (female, 40-60 years). Related to this, we should note - and this was also suggested by a participant in a box note - the slightly skewed age distribution of our sample. The negative attitudes towards the use of some social media might not be representative of the wider public.

The importance of familiarity was again reflected in the poor reputation that Twitter had among our participants. They criticized it for not allowing to trust the source of the message, because the person is unknown and not supported by an institutional affiliation, nor does the channel allow for proper documentation or explanation of the argument being made:

"But I don't know him. To me he is 'nobody'. I don't know if what he writes is rubbish, I don't know anything." (female, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

"And again, you could say that this is a one-way documentation. There is no, no such major evidence for what he writes, or reference to anything. He just writes it as if it's complete facts, and then you have to know the man to be able to [trust him] [...] But you could say that, for us, we can't really conclude much from it because we lack

trust in the man, that trust. Because we don't know him, and the case hasn't been built up." (male, 40-60 years, group 1, case 2)

Summarising, participants' attitudes towards communication channels seems to be prominently based on the degree of familiarity and past experiences with the channel. In addition, certain actors are expected to communicate through specific channels (e.g. journalists through the newspaper/broadcasting service that they are affiliated with). Using alternative channels raises doubts about actors' motives. In addition, our participants preferred modes of communication that allow for proper documentation of substantiation of the arguments made, with significant levels of detail. As a consequence of all these factors, traditional media were considered to generally constitute more trustworthy sources than social media.

Reasons to trust or distrust

Apart from the reasons to trust or distrust particular channels as mentioned in the previous subsection, we will here highlight a few additional characteristics of channels and messages that affected participants' perception of their trustworthiness. One particularly prominent factor in this regard was the use of plain, understandable language:

"And then there's the last one, uh, because it's written in good, down-to-earth language, to get us to include us and help, you could say, a small step on the way to making us a little interested in that." (male, 40-60 years, group 4, after all cases)

"I just think that if the average Dane is confronted with these two, they would attach much more meaning, significance and trust to this one than they would to this one, based on language alone." (male, 61+ years, group 2, comparing cases 1 and 2).

In addition, related to what we noted before about the need to verify the original source and read additional information, participants highlighted that new, online media give the opportunity to directly link to original sources, so a reader can go in and check the validity of claims. Using this opportunity was considered to strengthen trustworthiness:

"He could just as well at the same time add the link to either the hearings, which can say something about this, and otherwise also with the working group and their statements, so that you can go in and see the text behind it yourself. Because in that way, you could say that he's putting something in someone's mouth that you have to dig for yourself to see if it's right or wrong." (male, 61+ years, group 1, case 2)

In another group, participants also discussed going into original sources or actively searching for additional information:

Moderator: "But if you see something about research on Facebook or Twitter, Snapchat..."

"Then I Google it. If it catches my interest, I'll Google it in bits and pieces until I feel OK. [...] It's because, if, I would start googling, who is John Doe and who is this university and what was this scandal and what is the name of his colleague. I would google him too and then I would google climate and weather stations. It's just because if I get interested in something, I just google things. I think it's really exciting." (female, 40-60 years, group 3, case 2)

While this participant notes to not trust Google blindly, she also expressed that there is a limit to how much additional effort one can do to find information: “Of course, I scroll down and see some others. I don’t just see the first two or three things. I scroll a bit. But no, I haven’t Googled Google. I won’t. Because I don’t want to go to the library and find the relevant books.” (female, 40-60 years, group 3, case 2).

This demonstrates this participant’s willingness to move beyond individual sources, at least to some extent, to circumvent the potentially biased or fragmented reporting from single actors.

3.6 Other themes

All major themes discussed during the public deliberation workshop were covered in the preceding sections.

3.7 Card sorting exercise

For the concluding plenum session, a rapporteur from each group presented the main analytical points from each of their case discussions, providing the other groups with the opportunity to gain insights into the collective deliberations (please see section 2 for a descriptive summary of the individual case deliberations). Participants were particularly occupied with the content of the discussions, rather than accounting for the ranking of the cases. Nonetheless, three of the four groups ranked all of their cases. As displayed in table 1, the three out of four groups agreed to case 1 and 4 being the cases worth highlighting for, in some way or the other, making the greatest impression. In terms of case 1 on finding a treatment to prevent Covid-19, the groups agreed that this case sparked many discussions on lack of trust in science and also created debate on mediator impacts. While case 1 provided a clear negative example on lack of trust, the citizen science project in case 4 oppositely represented a very positive example of public engagement, science communication and science education that participants generally agreed could increase the public’s trust in research.

Pictures of the posters made by the groups, including the results of the ranking exercise, are added to the Appendix.

Table 1. Trust in science: Results of the group ranking

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1A	4	4	1B
4	1B	1A, 2B, 3A	2A
3B	x		4
2B	x		3B

4 Attitudes towards Science & Technology

Participants were asked to fill out questionnaires before and after participation in the deliberative workshop. In these questionnaires, they were asked to indicate demographics (see section 1.2), a short battery of attitudes towards science, questions on prior and future interaction with the theme, and a series of open questions (see section 3.1).

Table 2 presents the results from the science and technology attitudes battery. All questions have been coded so that high value (5) indicates a positive attitude, while low (1) indicates a negative attitude, on a 5-point Likert scale. This means that two questions, 2 and 3, are reversely coded. This is indicated by “(R)” whenever relevant. For all questions, we indicate the mean, standard deviation, and percentage indicating the two most positive options (% agreement). We also indicate the difference in means across the two questionnaires, positive value indicates an increase in mean, while negative indicates a decrease in mean. Additionally, figure 1 indicates the change in percentage indicating one of the two most positive categories between the pre- and post-questionnaires. Full distributions (non-reversed) can be seen in appendix table A1 and A2.

Table 2: Attitudes towards Science and Technology before and after the Workshop

Item	Before			After			Difference in means
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.30	0.72	93	4.11	0.80	89	-0.19
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast. (R)	2.67	1.21	30	2.63	1.21	19	-0.04
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith. (R)	3.33	1.44	52	3.27	1.28	44	-0.06
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	2.11	1.25	19	2.30	1.14	19	0.19
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	3.04	1.29	52	2.63	1.33	37	-0.41

Notes: n = 27, except for question 3-after, in which n = 26. Item 2 and 3 are reversed so that higher values are more positive towards science. For reversed items agreement percentage is also reversed to indicate proportion disagreeing with the statement, i.e. more positive towards science.

For the first question, on the ability of science to make lives better, the evaluations are very high, with the mean being above 4 both before (4.3) and after (4.11), and the proportion agreeing being around 90 percent for both questionnaires. The rating of this question does however fall very slightly (.19/4%) between the pre-and post-workshop questionnaires. The second question, on whether science and technology make life change too fast (reverse coded), the attitudes of the participants are slightly more negative, just below the centre-point of the scale, 2.67 before and 2.63 after. There is hardly any difference in the mean before and after the workshops. However, the percentage that picks the positive categories falls by 11 percentage points. This is largely due to more than a doubling of participants picking the middle category. The third question, on trusting science rather than faith too much (reverse coded), shows a mean just above the centre category for both the pre- (3.33) and post-workshop (3.27) questionnaire, with hardly any difference across the two measurements. The proportion that picks the two most positive categories does, however, fall by 8 percentage points between the two measurements. For the fourth question, on whether scientists know best what is good for people, the participants are the least positive with a mean of 2.11 before, and 2.3 afterwards, a small positive change, but a stable 19% agreeing to the question. Finally, the last question on whether we have no option but to trust those governing science and technology, the participants indicate a mean almost at the middle of the scale at 3.04. However, this question shows a considerable decrease in the mean rating of .41 at the post workshop questionnaire, and a drop of 15% points in proportion agreeing with the statement.

Figure 1: Attitudes towards Science and Technology, Percentage Agreeing

Note. n = 27, for questions reversed (2 and 3) indicates percentage disagreeing, i.e. positive attitudes towards science and technology.

These results indicate a few points of interest. First, the general question on whether science and technology increase life quality meets very strong support; the participants generally agree that science is a force for good. Second, the most negative evaluations are on the question regarding whether scientists know best what is good for people. This indicates that there is some doubt on the role of scientists as the highest societal authority, and further follows general trends in prior studies showing that scientists are evaluated less positively than science itself (Mann & Schleifer, 2020; Yen & Zampelli, 2022). Third, the largest change in attitudes before and after the workshop

is regarding question five, on whether “we have no options but to trust those governing science and technology”. This is of special interest, as this speaks to the core of the workshops, i.e. discussing reasons to (dis)trust science. Perhaps this indicates that such discussions have sowed some doubt regarding the trustworthiness of scientific conduct. Finally, the results in appendix table A1 and A2, showing the raw distributions across all questions, indicate that for all but the first question, we see a higher proportion picking the centre category. Whether this indicates more nuanced attitudes, participants feeling less sure, or simply fatigue, is an open question.

In the post-workshop survey, we then asked participants to indicate whether they had participated in other events in which the public is invited to discuss science. 19% indicated that they had participated in a similar type of event prior to the workshop. Moreover, 26% indicated that they participated in this event to “have the chance to discuss with others about science and technology”, 48% indicated that they participated to “find out more about science and technology and research practices”, 33% indicated that they participated to “have my say on science and technology issues”, and 37% indicated other reasons for participating. Self-described reasons for participating mostly centred on interest in the topic. Additionally, we investigated whether prior participations might relate to what attitudes towards science and technology the participants exhibit. To investigate this we look at the pre-workshop attitudinal items. Interestingly, participants with prior experience are consistently less positive than first-time participants, in particular regarding the last three attitude questions (see figure 3). This indicates that, perhaps in opposition to expectations, repeat participants are not the necessarily overly techno-optimistic, but rather demonstrate more critical attitudes towards science.

Figure 3: Attitudes towards science and technology for people participating for the first time in an event like this, or having prior experience with similar events.

We then asked about the impact that the event will have on future engagement of participants. See results for this in table 3. The majority indicated future engagement with the issues. Interestingly, the pick rates for these seem reversely related to the resources required to the type of engagement with the subject, i.e. participants selected forms of engagement requiring considerable time investments. As such, as much as 70% indicated that they would be willing to be involved with similar events in the future, 63% indicated that they would talk with friends and family

about the issue, and 59% indicated that they would follow news stories about the issue. The 11% that filled out the “other”-category, indicated that they would follow societal debates on the subjects more closely. If we look closer at the scores for attitudinal items in the post-workshop questionnaire, differences between the people who indicate future engagement, and people who do not, vary. For the first question, on future participation in similar events, those indicating interest in future participation hold more positive science attitudes than those who do not. However, for the two other forms of engagement, differences are non-uniform and smaller. Figure 4 presents an overview of these results.

Table 3. Impacts of event on participants: Results (%)

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	70%
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	63%
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	59%
4. Other	11%

Summing up, the participants had more varied attitudes towards science and technology than might be expected. For the general item on science and technology as a force for good, the participants were overwhelmingly positive, but for the other items, support was lower. Least support was giving to the idea that “scientists know what is best for people”. Moreover, attitudes did not undergo large changes between the two questionnaires, with the exception of the question on whether we “have no option but to trust those governing science and technology”, in which participants became a bit more negative, or nuanced given the reading of the results, which may speak to the deliberative effects of our workshop. The participants skewed older and male (see 2.1), and a non-negligible portion had prior experience in similar types of events (19%), but these participants were, interestingly, less positive regarding science and technology in the pre-workshop questionnaire. Finally, the participants indicated quite high interest in interacting with similar events and themes in the future, and the participants that indicated that they would be willing to engage with similar events were more positive than those who did not.

Figure 4: Attitudes towards science and technology for participants indicating the workshop to have diverse impacts on their future engagement with science and technology.

Appendix

Table A1. Questionnaire 1: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	41%	52%	4%	4%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	15%	41%	15%	22%	7%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	19%	7%	22%	26%	26%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	4%	15%	15%	22%	44%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	7%	44%	7%	26%	15%	0%

Table A2. Questionnaire 2: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	30%	59%	4%	7%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	19%	30%	33%	7%	11%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	11%	15%	26%	26%	19%	4%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	0%	19%	26%	22%	33%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	4%	33%	15%	19%	30%	0%

Pictures of the posters made by the participants

GRUPPE 3

CASE 1

- Forståelige roller: Medier, politikere, befolkningen og forskere
-

CASE 2

- Twitter virker umiddelbart ikke som formidling
- Forskning kræver flere ord
- Forskning skal være firkantet □ ??

CASE 3

- Beslutningen er taget, det giver ikke mening at høre befolkningen
- Ekspertise vs. private valg

CASE 4

- Nutidig historiskrivning gennem befolkningen
- At befolkningen kan komme tættere på forskning. + forstå den
- De lære noget om sig selv - inspireres til uddannelse + job

2

ttager (iflht medie) r foros vation/aktie i emnet

RANKING

4

GRUPPE 4

CASE 1

- UREDIGERE DISKUSSION
- MOTIVATION
- VIDENSKABELIG UREDELIGHED

CASE 2

- FORMIDLING!
- AFSENDER

CASE 3

- ETIK
- MANIPULATION
(HOLDNIN TIL KENDEGIVET)
- TILLID TIL DET LÆGEFAGUGE
- MERE VIDEN

CASE 4

- VIL GERNE DELTAGE
- FORSKNING VS. ANEKDOTER
- ØGER DET BESKYTTELSEN
/INTERESSEN FOR
NATUREN
- FORSKNINGODESIGN

RANKING

CASE NR. 1: MEDIE, FOR OG IMOD-ARGUMENTER

CASE NR. 2: SVÆR AT FORSTÅ

CASE NR. 4: STOR INTERESSE - "KOMMER TÆT PÅ"

CASE

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Annex B: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – France

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *France*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Michel Dubois, Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)*

1. Introduction

This national report outlines the outcomes of a productive public deliberative workshop that took place on July 7, 2023, at the Maison de la Recherche, Sorbonne University, in the city of Paris.

The workshop spanned half a day and was structured around a central research question — is public trust in science affected by research integrity values and societal integration in science? — , fostering insightful discussions among the participants.

Divided into two group work sessions, the event facilitated in-depth exploration and analysis. The participants delved into thought-provoking case studies, thoughtfully prepared in advance, which served as catalysts for stimulating collective conversations concerning their perspectives on confidence in science.

Throughout the workshop, an atmosphere of collaborative learning and critical thinking prevailed, nurturing a fruitful exchange of ideas among the attendees. This document presents some of the valuable insights gained from the participants' varied experiences and expertise.

1.1. Set up of the event

On the afternoon of July 7, a deliberative workshop took place in The Maison de la Recherche at Sorbonne University. The Maison served as an ideal venue due to its central location in the 6th arrondissement of Paris, easily accessible by public transportation.

This event was organized with the support of the sociological studies company n-clique, a professional group led by former students of the sociology department at Sorbonne University. Their expertise and dedication added a rich layer of insight and professionalism to the workshop, elevating the overall experience for all attendees.

The choice of setting and the collaborative efforts of n-clique ensured a stimulating environment, fostering meaningful discussions and encouraging diverse perspectives on the matters under exploration. Valentin Riboule, n-clique representative, played the role of facilitator.

Public workshops invariably grapple with the pivotal challenge of participant recruitment. It is essential to incorporate a self-selection process that transcends conventional academic boundaries, thereby ensuring a more diverse and enriching interaction.

Several measures have been deployed to reach this goal:

- The GEMASS laboratory's website and social media platform (twitter) have been leveraged for widespread online communication (<https://www.gemass.fr/7-juillet-2023-dans-le-cadre-du-projet-europeen-poesis-le-gemass-organise-un-forum-deliberatif-consacre-a-la-question-de-la-confiance-du-public-a-legard-de-la-science/>).
- Information about the workshop has been strategically circulated across dedicated scientific culture mailing lists, exponentially increasing the potential participant reach.
- Through collaboration with CNRS Sorbonne University's 'Science, Culture and Society' department, the workshop details have been promoted on these institutions website, tapping into a wide academic community (<https://www.inshs.cnrs.fr/fr/evenement/forum-deliberatif-sur-la-confiance-dans-la->

<https://lettres.sorbonne-universite.fr/evenements/examiner-l-impact-de-l-integrite-scientifique-et-de-la-participation-des-citoyens-sur-la-confiance-dans-la-science>).

- The network of science journalists, meticulously identified by the national coordinator, has been utilized as an additional information dissemination channel.
- Collaborations with the cultural services of the town halls from the 6e et 17e arrondissement in Paris.
- Universcience network, France’s premier science outreach network, has been engaged for broader information dissemination.
- Manual poster distribution in the 6th arrondissement of Paris, close to the Maison de la recherche.

This multi-faceted strategy was designed to facilitate a more inclusive and engaging participant selection process, addressing the unique challenges of public workshop recruitment. Despite concerted communication efforts, it must be acknowledged that the outcomes in terms of participant recruitment have been uneven, underscoring the crucial nature of this issue.

For this national workshop in Paris, attendance hinged upon online registration. Out of 21 individuals who expressed initial interest and registered, only 9 participants came to the event, translating to an alarming drop-off of over 50% in turnout.

This stark discrepancy between registrants and attendees necessitates analysis to understand the underpinnings of such a limited participation rate. Several hypotheses warrant discussion regarding the subject of confidence in science. One possibility is that the topic may seem too distant from the everyday concerns of the general public. While people may hold opinions on the matter, its technical nature might deter them from actively engaging in discussions. Another hypothesis relates to the challenge of effectively reaching potential participants. The workshop could have encountered fewer obstacles if it had access to a well-defined pool of volunteers for participatory research exercises. Interestingly, Sorbonne University is currently exploring the creation of a dedicated platform for participatory research, which could serve as an interface connecting with the public interested in these initiatives.

1.2. Participants in the event

The sample present at the workshop is described in terms of gender, age and education variables in Table 1 below.

Male	4
Female	5
18-24	1
35-39	1
40-44	2
50-54	2
55-59	1
60-64	1
65+	1

Bac	1
Bac + 4	1
Bac + 5	3
Bac > 5	4
Total	9

Table 1

This small sample demonstrates a relatively balanced representation in terms of gender, encompassing a diverse range of age categories. However, it lacks diversity concerning the participants' educational backgrounds, with minimal variation observed in their levels of education. Among the nine participants, only one reported no professional affiliation with science, indicating that the sample was overwhelmingly composed of individuals with academic backgrounds. This predominance further underscores the challenges faced in attracting non-academic participants from the broader civil society. Interestingly, despite their professional ties to the field, the majority had not previously experienced an event of this nature, where public discourse about science is actively encouraged. They expressed a strong interest in attending similar gatherings in the future. Primary motivations for participation included the prospect of engaging in conversations about science and technology, the opportunity to contribute to the laboratory's projects, and the intrinsic interest generated by the topic of discussion.

2. Discursive summary of cases

The Paris deliberative workshop took place on July 7th, spanning from 2pm to 6pm. Valentin Riboule of n-clique led the proceedings as the facilitator. He welcomed the attendees and succinctly outlined the sequences of tasks for the half-day session, starting with the completion of the initial questionnaire by the participants.

2.1. Phase 1 – Expert talk

Subsequently, Michel Dubois, CNRS sociologist and national partner for the POIESIS project, delivered a 30-minute presentation focusing on the workshop's theme.

This session served dual purposes - firstly, it allowed an examination of how public discourse leverages the concept of trust with respect to science and scientific institutions. Secondly, it presented a chance to elucidate the current understanding of the transformation of public opinion, both domestically in France and internationally.

The presentation was also an opportunity to revisit the public discourse surrounding the correlation between the pandemic and public trust in science. On one side of the spectrum, there are individuals who perceive the pandemic as a testament to scientific prowess - evident in the mobilization of resources, generation of data, groundbreaking discoveries, and a surge in scholarly publications. They assert that such achievements can only bolster the public's regard

for scientists and deepen their faith in scientific outcomes. Conversely, there are those who argue that the crisis starkly exposes the public to the challenges researchers and physicians face in maintaining a unanimous voice. More fundamentally, it uncovers the ubiquitous uncertainties inherent in scientific endeavours. They posit that these realities could potentially undermine the public's conventional trust in the scientific community.

The presentation demonstrated that the evolving perceptions of the French population towards science significantly deviate from the dichotomous framework that has predominated media narratives over the past three years.

2.2. Phase 2 – Focus groups

A brief 10-minute discussion amongst the participants ensued, post which they were divided into two groups. Two work sessions have been organized: the first from 3pm to 4pm and the second from 4.30pm to 5.30pm. A half-hour coffee break allowed participants to relax between sessions. The workshop ended with a plenary session from 5.30pm to 6pm, during which the main findings from each group work were shared.

The subgroup activities were centered around a collection of case studies: two focusing on scientific integrity, and two on citizen participation in science. A majority of these cases (1, 2, and 3) featured two variants (1a, 1b, 2a, 2b, 3a, 3c).

Case 1 revolves around a significant study conducted in Argentina that professed to have discovered a drug, ivermectin, that could prevent COVID-19 in 100% of the instances. However, due to inconsistencies in the study, experts have cast doubt upon its scientific robustness. Variant A of this case is disseminated through a well-known media outlet, while variant B is propagated via a Facebook page.

Case 2 pertains to the online leakage of over a thousand emails from a dedicated climate research unit, an incident infamously known as the "Climategate" scandal. Variant A of this case is divulged through an institutional press release, while variant B is discussed in a social network thread.

Case 3 illustrates the efforts by a technical advisory group for the government in organizing a public consultation on COVID-19 vaccination. Variant A of this case is communicated through a recognized media outlet, while variant B is conveyed via a Facebook page.

Case 4 introduces the Vigie nature participatory science program, a platform that allows anyone with an interest in nature to contribute to our collective understanding of biodiversity.

This design was intended to examine the potential influence of different communication media on the nature of interactions.

The subsequent table provides a detailed distribution of case studies and their respective variants, as per each working group.

	Group 1	Group 2
Case 1	Variant A	Variant B
Case 2	Variant B	Variant A
Case 3	Variant B	Variant A
Case 4	Case 4	Case 4

Table 2

All of the aforementioned cases sparked lively discussions, often characterized by strong opinions. Notably, during the COVID-19 period, numerous public controversies arose surrounding Professor Didier Raoult in Marseille, and these controversies remained fresh in the minds of the participants. Given the predominantly academic background of the attendees, the discussions delved into technical intricacies, allowing for an in-depth exploration of various aspects.

One participant, specialized in scientific mediation, notably enriched the discourse during the discussion of Case 4. This particular case centered around participatory science, fostering a profound exchange of ideas concerning different approaches to the subject, and even generated some insightful proposals for future endeavours. The engagement of the participants led to a highly fruitful exchange, further enhancing the overall quality of the event.

3. Integrity and integration & trust in science

This section presents the main results of the analysis of the transcripts of the exchanges between the participants in the working groups. To provide a comprehensive analysis, we have opted to present short transcripts of the discussions that took place during the working groups, where relevant and insightful. These transcripts offer direct insights into the participants' viewpoints, capturing the nuances and depth of their opinions on the place of science in society, trust in science, and the various actors involved in scientific communication.

3.1. General attitudes towards science

In the course of the collective discussion, participants manifested positive or neutral sentiments towards science and technology, accentuating their crucial contributions to social progress and advancement.

A majority (5 respondents) perceived science and technology as synonymous with progress and innovation, while also highlighting the need for their effects on social and environmental domains to be thoroughly assessed. For others (3 respondents), science and technology epitomized the expansion and enhancement of knowledge. One respondent aligned science and technology with elements of interest, comfort, and problem-solving solutions.

For another participant, science and technology fostered an open and critical mindset, while yet another linked them with the democratization of knowledge. From an institutional standpoint, one participant viewed 'science' as encapsulating institutions, elite schools, researchers, and the

pursuit of knowledge. Another participant conceived science as a reasoned approach towards understanding the world through the scientific process.

Certain participants perceived science and technology as social phenomena, with technology representing an analysis of various techniques deployed by humans. One respondent cited the transformation of science into 'technoscience', facilitated by the proliferation of technical tools and measurement methods.

The term 'rigour' was recurrently (four times) used to describe the scientific study process, which was seen as grounded on a rigorous analysis method, collective scientific criteria, and empirical proof. The principles of logic, rationality, objectivity, and hypothesis testing were also prominently featured.

While the participants expressed positive or neutral views towards science and technology, their discussions also revealed significant concerns.

A primary worry centered on the funding and allocation of resources for scientific research. Participants underscored the challenges posed by the complexity of financial structures and its impact on the time dedicated to research and knowledge dissemination. Apprehensions about the appeal of scientific careers and the financial backing for scientific pursuits were articulated, as was concern about a lack of resources for research without directly identifiable applications.

Further, participants were apprehensive about potential manipulations of science. They emphasized the necessity for good scientific practice to inform public opinion and foster a healthier democratic process. **They expressed fears about science being used to justify misinformation, manipulate public sentiment, or legitimize harmful actions, referencing historical instances.** There was also worry about science and scientific research being influenced by political entities and major corporations (private interest).

Lastly, the potential of science to offer sustainable and effective solutions that can enhance our lives was a topic of concern. **Participants highlighted the need for fundamental scientific investigations to broaden our perspectives and address current challenges like energy, climate, and food security.** Questions were raised about the prudence of trusting those who claim to 'know' and rely on their promises to enhance our lives and mend the damage done.

To sum up, participants voiced several concerns, ranging from research funding and potential manipulation of science, to the capacity of science to provide viable, long-term solutions to current issues.

The table below shows original verbatim regarding the concern of manipulation of science with the English translation.

Original version	English Version
« [Ce qui me frappe c'est] la facilité avec laquelle la population peut se laisser manipuler. Plus il y a de débats scientifiques et plus ça doit être facile... »	« [What strikes me is] how easily the public can be manipulated. The more scientific debate there is, the easier it must be... »
« Si je pense aux abeilles, après le conseil européen va décider de supprimer les OGM. Mais en fait, ils vont nous manipuler autrement.	« If I think about the bees... after the European Council decides to abolish GMOs. But in fact, they're going to manipulate us in other ways.

<p>Ils vont faire d'autres... ils vont modifier génétiquement d'autres choses et puis ils vont les remettre sur le marché parce que il y a trop d'intérêts financiers en jeu.»</p>	<p>They're going to genetically modify other things and then put them back on the market because there are too many financial interests at stake. »</p>
<p>« je suis très méfiante, pas parce que je craindrai que le public ait une influence sur la décision, mais j'ai l'impression qu'une participation publique, c'est une façon de manipuler l'opinion pour valider une décision qui est déjà prise. C'est parce que j'ai déjà vécu ça dans le domaine de l'éducation et de la grande participation pour la réforme du lycée, je crois. »</p>	<p>« I'm very wary, not because I'm afraid of the public having an influence on the decision, but I have the impression that public participation is a way of manipulating opinion to validate a decision that has already been taken. That's because I've already experienced this in the field of education and the great participation in the reform of the lycée, I think. »</p>
<p>« Ce sujet me touche particulièrement parce qu'en tant que Brésilienne, j'ai vécu cette manipulation de la science par les acteurs politiques et au Brésil, notamment pour éviter les confinements et pour éviter une crise économique. C'était vraiment un sujet qui a été bien mêlé dans la vie, dans la politique brésilienne. Et là, plusieurs personnes sont tombées dans les pièges. (...) Moi, je suis encore révoltée par cette situation. »</p>	<p>« This subject is particularly close to my heart because, as a Brazilian, I've experienced this manipulation of science by political actors in Brazil, particularly to avoid confinement and to avoid an economic crisis. It was a subject that was very much involved in Brazilian life and politics. And a number of people fell into the traps. (...) I'm still outraged by the situation. »</p>

Table 3

3.2. Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

In the course of the discussion group, participants revealed a spectrum of reasons explaining their trust in science and its various stakeholders.

Foremost, a general trust was extended towards the larger scientific community, with the peer review process perceived as a vital check and balance system. The autonomy of researchers was recognized as a significant driver of confidence. Participants believed that this independence facilitates an unbiased approach to research, unaffected by external interests. Transparency emerged as another cornerstone of trust. This included the transparency of funding sources, the methodological procedures, and the disseminated information. Additionally, participants emphasized the necessity of data accessibility to sustain trust.

Ethical conduct of researchers was also seen as a crucial trust-enhancing factor. Participants particularly valued transparency in research processes and accepted that doubt is intrinsic to research. The importance of community validation and the role of regulatory institutions in maintaining trust were also stressed. Lastly, **participants mentioned the possibility that citizen participation could boost confidence in science, but with the risk that this confidence would only concern the most aware part of the population.**

However, participants' trust in science was not without reservations. They voiced several concerns and factors triggering distrust. Prominent among these were conflicts of interest, encompassing financial gains or affiliations with governmental bodies or industries. This also bred fears about the potential for these entities to manipulate scientific outcomes. **While transparency was generally seen as a trust builder, it could paradoxically also seed distrust. Some participants argued that too much transparency might reveal instances of malpractice or fraud, negatively impacting public confidence in science.** Participants also expressed distrust arising from sensationalized announcements and unfulfilled promises. They underscored the inherent conflict between the long-term nature of scientific research and the media's haste to disseminate information. Finally, doubts were expressed about the reliability of information sources and data. Concerns were raised about data leaks, attempts to undermine researchers, and suspicions of fraud. Moreover, attempts to destabilize researchers, especially in the context of heated debates like climate change, were noted as significant trust erodes.

The table below shows original verbatim regarding accessibility and transparency with the English translation.

Original version	English Version
« [l'implication du public dans les décisions scientifiques] Moi, je pense que ça peut augmenter la confiance, parce que par exemple si j'ai participé à un truc du muséum d'histoire naturelle, j'aurais davantage confiance en cette institution, je la connais, j'ai participé, j'ai échangé avec des gens de chez eux, etc., et on sait que l'inter connaissance c'est quand même un premier facteur d'attribution de confiance à tort ou à raison, mais par contre je pense que ça aura quand même un effet très limité, parce	« [public involvement in scientific decisions] personally, I think it can increase confidence, because for example if I took part in something at the Natural History Museum, I'd have more confidence in that institution, I know it, I've taken part, I've talked to people from there, etc., and we know that mutual knowledge is a primary factor in attributing confidence, rightly or wrongly, but on the other hand I think it will still have a very limited effect, because it will concern the convinced. As soon as you get

<p>que ça va concerner les convaincus. À partir du moment où vous vous lancez dans une affaire comme ça, c'est qu'on est plutôt favorable »</p>	<p>involved in something like this, we're pretty much in favour". »</p>
<p>« (...) ce que je trouve rassurant, c'est que justement ces relectures sont aussi transparentes, c'est-à-dire qu'on peut y accéder, qu'on s'en fait l'écho, qu'on n'a pas justement uniquement l'écho d'un résultat. On a aussi l'écho de tout ce qui est fait derrière pour évaluer et pour dire « attendez, l'étude, elle pose problème ». Ce qu'on a encore une fois, vachement, ce à quoi on a été énormément exposé durant le COVID et qui a rendu toute cette évaluation post-publication grand public. Sur les pré-print, on a vu comment des réseaux de chercheurs s'étaient organisés, puisque c'était tellement énorme pour justement checker dans une discipline, dans un truc, dire « OK, on va se faire les études, parce que les gens dans les hôpitaux n'ont pas le temps ». Il y a des projets qui se sont montés comme ça et qui ont checké. Moi, personnellement, je trouve que ça redonne de la confiance parce qu'il y a une relecture, parce qu'il y a des choses qui sont pointées, parce qu'on demande plus de réponses sur certains résultats troubles et tout ça, on peut avoir accès.»</p>	<p>« (...) what I find reassuring is that these reviews are also transparent, meaning that they can be accessed and reported on, and that we don't just hear about the results. We also hear about everything that goes into evaluating the study and saying "wait a minute, there's a problem with this study". Once again, we had a lot of exposure to this during COVID, which made the whole post-publication evaluation process public. On the preprints, we saw how networks of researchers had organised themselves, because it was so huge to check out a discipline, a thing, to say "OK, we'll do the studies, because people in hospitals don't have the time". There are projects that have been set up like that and that have worked. Personally, I find that it restores confidence because things are re-examined, because things are pointed out, because we ask for more answers about certain troublesome results and all that, we can have access to. »</p>
<p>« (...) c'est vrai qu'on parle beaucoup de la transparence de la science comme étant un critère qui pourrait bâtir la confiance. Moi, je ne suis pas sûr du tout que ça augmente la confiance du public, au contraire, je pense que ça peut la diminuer pour de mauvaises raisons, c'est ce qu'on a vu potentiellement avec le COVID ou justement, on voit qu'il y a des gens qui travaillent mal, il y a des gens qui fraudent, etc. Et ça peut diminuer la confiance dans des résultats qui n'ont rien à voir avec cela, avec des résultats solidifiés comme ceux sur le dérèglement climatique. J'ai l'impression qu'il peut y avoir un effet pervers à la transparence. Alors, je ne dis pas que l'opacité c'est une meilleure méthode, mais peut-être que les scientifiques devraient être plus prudents quand ils communiquent leurs résultats »</p>	<p>« (...) It's true that there's a lot of talk about the transparency of science being a criterion that could build confidence. I'm not at all sure that it increases public confidence, on the contrary, I think it can reduce it for the wrong reasons, as we saw potentially with COVID, where we see that there are people who work badly, people who commit fraud, etc. And that can reduce confidence in results that have nothing to do with that, with solidified results like those on climate change. I have the impression that transparency can have a perverse effect. I'm not saying that opacity is a better method, but perhaps scientists should be more careful when communicating their results.»</p>

Table 4

3.3. Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

The collective discussion underscored diverse perspectives regarding the critical role of scientific integrity in fostering public trust in science.

While 'integrity' is frequently framed within the boundaries of the governing principles and standards pertaining to scientific endeavours, attendees emphasized the significance of scientists' capacity for introspective scrutiny of their work, keeping in mind their scientific and social duties. **In this context, integrity dovetails with the concept of 'reflexivity'** - the aptitude to ponder on the process of knowledge acquisition and its social pertinence, a point underscored during the discussion.

A core component of scientific integrity identified was the presence of mechanisms to critically assess scientific results, with peer-review emerging as a prominent example. One participant posited that a comprehensive policy on scientific integrity must incorporate principles of open science, encouraging transparency in data and result dissemination.

However, the importance of integrity, while widely acknowledged, also brought to light certain apprehensions. **Participants voiced concerns over compromised integrity due to conflicts of interest, unwarranted political affiliations, over-promised expectations, and occasionally, the questionable roles of certain institutions.** A breach in a researcher's ethics was cited as a hallmark of integrity deficit.

The attendees firmly dismissed the simplistic assumption that researchers are inherently truthful and immune to any form of influence or pressure. They acknowledged the reality of scientific fraud and its potential ramifications on the public perception of science.

The forum unanimously agreed that subpar research practices not only erode trust in science but also have far-reaching detrimental social effects. Several contributors to this trust deficit were identified. **Data manipulation, be it due to scientific fraud or interference from politics and media in interpreting unverified results, was pinpointed as a primary factor undermining confidence.** Furthermore, an absence of community-led review and regulatory mechanisms in science also emerged as a cause for concern.

Attendees emphasized that such malpractices tarnish the reputation of science as a reliable source of knowledge and solutions, negatively affecting the scientific community, research culture, and society at large.

The table below shows original verbatim regarding scientific fraud, reflexivity and the tension between peer review and public communication, with the corresponding English translation.

Original version	English Version
« (...) pour quiconque qui est dans la science, malheureusement, on sait que ça existe, la fraude de la construction de données de A à Z. (...) ça me paraît malheureusement être aussi une des formes du fonctionnement normal de la science, enfin pas normal, on va dire, un peu déviant »	« (...) for anyone involved in science, unfortunately, we know that it exists, the fraud of constructing data from A to Z. (...) this unfortunately seems to me to be also one of the forms of the normal functioning of science, well not normal, we'll say, a little deviant... »
« (...) on nous dit : 'l'intégrité scientifique, de toute façon, on la pratique parce qu'on est, on est scientifique'... mais on ne réfléchit pas dessus, on ne l'explicite pas, et on forme nos étudiants à acquérir des savoirs, mais on ne les forme pas à réfléchir sur la façon dont on acquiert des savoirs, sur les raisons pour lesquelles on les	« (...) We are told that "scientific integrity is something we practice anyway because we are scientists". But we don't think about it, we don't make it explicit, and we train our students to acquire knowledge, but we don't train them to think about how we acquire knowledge, why we learn it, what meaning it has in the society in

<p>apprend, sur le sens que cela a dans la société dans laquelle on est... Autrement dit, une fois de plus, ce sont les contenus qu'on déverse et ça n'est pas une capacité à, si je puis dire, prendre position, assumer une responsabilité à l'égard de ces contenus informatifs, et c'est ça qui me semble semer la confusion. »</p>	<p>which we live... In other words, once again, it's the content that's being dumped on them and not the ability to, if I may say so, take a stand, to assume responsibility for this information content, and that's what I think is confusing. »</p>
<p>« (...) la relation entre intégrité et science ouverte et ouverture de la science, c'est une question délicate, il me semble, pour de multiples raisons, parce que les données, elles sont produites dans des contextes où il y a toujours des pratiques qui ne sont pas forcément explicites ou qui ne peuvent pas être totalement décrites, et la compréhension de certaines données brutes d'un chercheur requiert un dialogue souvent entre ceux qui souhaite par exemple reproduire une expérience et le chercheur qui a produit les données de la première recherche qu'il a faite à partir de ces données. Je ne suis peut-être pas très clair, mais ce que je veux dire, c'est que, ce qui est important, c'est que l'ouverture des données, la publication soit l'occasion d'un dialogue entre les chercheurs et d'autres collègues qui soient à même de comprendre ce qu'il a fait, pour expliciter ce qu'on n'a pas forcément eu la possibilité d'expliquer. »</p>	<p>« (...) The relationship between integrity and open science and the opening up of science is a delicate issue, it seems to me, for many reasons, because data are produced in contexts where there are always practices that cannot necessarily be explained or fully described, and understanding some of a researcher's raw data often requires a dialogue between those who wish, for example, to reproduce an experiment and the researcher who produced the data from the first research he carried out using these data. Perhaps I'm not being very clear, but what I'm trying to say is that what's important is that the opening up of data, the publication of data, should provide an opportunity for dialogue between researchers and other colleagues who are in a position to understand what the researcher has done, in order to explain what we haven't necessarily had the opportunity to explain. »</p>
<p>« (...)ce que ça m'a évoqué, c'était vraiment le côté d'argent un petit peu, mais plus encore ce côté d'annonce. Et déjà, ce qu'il y a c'est que ce côté effet d'annonce, on l'a régulièrement dans un journalisme même si c'est très scientifique, on peut aller vite en besogne. Quelque chose qui tout d'un coup arrive et on a tout de suite sorti un article sans même que ce soit vérifié par les pairs. Ce qui peut arriver parce que normalement il y a un écho relativement faible, donc ça n'a pas d'impact visible dans la sphère publique »</p>	<p>« (...) what it reminded me of was the money aspect, but even more so the announcement aspect. And first of all, the announcement side of things is a regular occurrence in journalism, even if it's very scientific. Something happens all of a sudden and an article is immediately published without even being peer-reviewed. This can happen because normally there is relatively little echo, so it has no visible impact in the public sphere.»</p>

Table 5

3.4. Public integration in science and trust

Throughout the discussion, various perspectives emerged on the role of public participation in scientific research and its potential effects, both positive and negative.

Many participants underscored the essentiality of public involvement in all stages of the scientific process, from hypothesis formulation to result dissemination. They proposed that such involvement nurtures a **virtuous cycle where the public becomes fully invested in scientific endeavours, thereby amplifying their trust in science**. They contended that participatory research democratizes science by not only encouraging public engagement but also by fostering responsibility and active citizenship. Such engagement enriches scientific culture and serves as a

catalyst for progress, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of scientific knowledge. Additionally, several participants highlighted the importance of citizens' committees, which would have a permanent presence in research organisations in order to reduce as far as possible the egotism and self-interestedness of the scientific community.

However, alongside the undeniable benefits of public involvement in science, potential pitfalls were also emphasized. Paramount amongst these was the **need for adequate scientific oversight to mitigate potential misuse**, notably in the context of data collection gamification. Furthermore, some participants cautioned that the lack of knowledge amongst laypeople could be detrimental to scientific advancement. They advocated for a balance, positing that while public involvement is valuable, science fundamentally remains a domain for experts and excessive public participation could hamper its intrinsic evolution.

Public involvement was identified as a vital contributor to fostering trust in science. Participants noted that it facilitates public awareness of the collective nature of scientific work, improves comprehension of specific topics, and may even inspire scientific vocations. However, while acknowledging its positive impact, **some participants nuanced the effect of public involvement on the trust in science. They emphasized the importance of training and education in scientific data collection as a cornerstone of trust-building**. Moreover, they posited that the impact of public involvement on trust could be influenced by **the potential manipulation of participatory mechanisms**.

In sum, while public participation in science undeniably provides myriad benefits, particularly in terms of education and bolstering confidence in science, the associated challenges of public involvement in the scientific process must be considered. To maximize the benefits and minimize the drawbacks, a balanced approach is necessary. This encompasses appropriate scientific oversight, effective training and education, and transparent communication about the public's role in the scientific process. Thus, with carefully managed implementation, public participation can become a powerful instrument in fortifying trust in science and fostering public engagement in scientific research.

The table below shows original verbatim regarding social integration, literacy and trust with corresponding English translation.

Original version	English Version
« (...) peut-être qu'il faudrait remplacer consultation par observation avec des structures citoyennes qui soit là pour vérifier le débat scientifique dans les conditions optimale de sorte que chacun ait son mot à dire sur tous les aspects. Signifiant bien aux citoyens qu'ils ne sont pas pour donner leur avis parce que malheureusement leur avis ne tient pas la route mais pour se forger une opinion. Peut-être leur présence, en tant qu'observateur pour vérifier que les sciences se font dans leurs conditions, suffirait déjà à avoir moins de défiance. »	« (...) perhaps consultation should be replaced by observation with citizen groups there to verify the scientific debate under optimum conditions so that everyone has their say on all aspects. To make it clear to the public that they are not there to give their opinion, because unfortunately their opinion doesn't hold water, but to form their own opinion. Perhaps their presence, as observers to check that the science is being done under their conditions, would already be enough to reduce mistrust. »
« [la participation citoyenne] ça permet de montrer très concrètement au public que la recherche [ce n'est pas nécessairement] des	« [citizen participation] allows us to show the public in a very concrete way that research [is not necessarily] about incredible discoveries (...)

<p>découvertes incroyables (...) quelque chose qui est toujours dans l'extraordinaire. (...) moi je trouve cela très chouette parce que, à la fois, ça rend la chose accessible, en terme de participation, et en même temps, c'est une image assez fidèle de la recherche en général. On va étudier la force des choses juste à côté de chez soi. Et peut être même plus qu'on ne le pense. »</p>	<p>something that is always extraordinary. (...) I think it's great because it makes it accessible, in terms of participation, and at the same time it's a fairly accurate picture of research in general. You get to study the power of things right next door to you. And maybe even more than you think. »</p>
<p>« j'ai déjà connu des cas [de participation citoyenne] qui ont dérivé... enfin, ça dépend de protocoles. Et surtout pour l'interprétation des données qui va suivre la collecte participative avec les citoyens. Parce qu'il y a des cas où des conclusions ont été précipitées, qui ont envoyé une fausse information ... Enfin c'était dans l'observation des insectes dans une zone. Donc il faut aussi faire attention à tous les critères de sélection des personnes pour pouvoir utiliser les données collectées »</p>	<p>« I've already seen cases [of citizen participation] that have drifted... well, it depends on the protocols. And above all for the interpretation of the data that will follow the participatory collection with the citizens. Because there are cases where conclusions have been precipitated, which have sent out false information... Well, it was in the observation of insects in an area. So we also have to be careful about all the criteria for selecting people to be able to use the data collected. »</p>

Table 6

3.5. Communication channels and trust in science

Participants expressed a degree of trust in institutional communication channels, which are typically perceived as reliable and credible. These channels are often well-known for their role in disseminating information and scientific results to the general public. Thus, they exert influence on the reception and interpretation of scientific information.

However, **mass media outlets and social networks were identified as less trustworthy.** These platforms were criticized for their propensity to disseminate premature scientific findings, often sourced from pre-printed material related to hot topics, such as COVID-19. Social networks, in particular, were singled out for their potential to manipulate public opinion. Some participants expressed concern over these platforms' editorializing role, forcing traditional media outlets to engage in debates with insufficient data.

Nevertheless, **some participants argued that the responsibility for trust or distrust in scientific communication primarily falls upon individual journalists rather than the platforms they use.** They emphasized the role of the communicator in shaping the information's reception rather than the communication medium used. It was suggested that a journalist's professional responsibility involves seeking expert insight and ensuring they possess a fundamental understanding of scientific processes before disseminating information.

Credibility in communication channels is often associated with formats that cross-reference information with expert scientific opinions. Furthermore, channels that help the public understand their role in scientific endeavours are favoured. Conversely, participants expressed scepticism towards channels characterized by sensationalism, rapid information turnover, lack of thorough research, and inadequate explanations of the scientific process. Such communication styles can quickly lead to mistrust.

Influence of communication on trust in science is multifaceted. **Participants noted that sensation-driven, hurried, and current-event-focused communication, often associated with journalistic coverage, tends to undermine public trust in science.** Over-publicizing cases of poor scientific practices contributes to science's discredit. Simultaneously, the lack of transparency, clarity, and accessibility in communicating scientific results weakens public trust.

The communication of scientific information needs reconsideration as it currently fosters more distrust than confidence. The current media communication is deemed unsatisfactory, if not detrimental. **Research institutions might benefit from modifying their communication strategy,** bypassing the traditional media channels. Doing so could increase transparency, promote clear understanding, and subsequently, enhance public trust in science.

The table below shows original verbatim regarding social media and scientific journalism with the English translation.

Original version	English Version
« (...) ce que je vois dans cet article, c'est le rôle qu'ont pris les réseaux sociaux comme forme d'éditorialisation, comme rôle d'éditorialiste de l'information (...) les médias sont dans une position de faiblesse où ils doivent réagir à des polémiques sur lesquelles on n'a pas de données suffisantes pour se prononcer. Et ça, je crois vraiment que c'est ce qu'on... Souvent on dit que les réseaux sociaux ont augmenté la désinformation, etc. C'est probablement vrai, mais surtout, c'est que ça a donné à ces réseaux un rôle d'éditorialisation, les journaux sont presque obligés d'en parler, alors qu'ils n'auraient pas dû en parler en l'occurrence... »	« (...)what I see in this article is the role that social networks have taken on as a form of 'editorialization', as a role of editorialist of information (...) the media are in a weak position where they have to react to controversies on which we don't have sufficient data to give an opinion. And that, I really think, is what we... We often say that social networks have increased disinformation and so on. It's probably true, but above all it's because it's given these networks an editorial role. Newspapers are almost obliged to talk about it, when they shouldn't have been talking about it in the first place... »
« (...) je ne sais pas s'il faut communiquer sur la science qui est en train de se faire ou sur des résultats frais, je ne suis pas sûr. Et quand je vois d'autres qui le font, parfois ça m'énerve parce qu'on voit des journalistes qui se jettent sur le dernier traitement contre le cancer en disant peut être ça, ça va marcher, etc. Puis je me dis 'bon bah pourquoi on n'attend pas quelques années avant d'en parler ?'», je ne sais pas... »	« (...) I don't know whether to communicate on the science that is being done or on fresh results, I'm not sure. And when I see others doing it, it sometimes annoys me because you see journalists pouncing on the latest cancer treatment, saying maybe this will work and so on. Then I say to myself, "Well, why don't we wait a few years before talking about it? »
« (...) C'est là où je trouve que la responsabilité du média n'est pas assumée correctement, à partir du moment où on sait que les données n'ont pas été publiées et ne sont pas communiquées, pourquoi écrire ça de cette façon-là ? D'une façon qui laisse quand même planer un doute,	« (...) That's where I think the media's responsibility is not being properly assumed, since we know that the data has not been published and is not being communicated, why write about it in this way? In a way that leaves room for doubt, even though the media should say no? If it

alors même que le média devrait dire non ? Si ça circulait sur les réseaux sociaux, il est de la responsabilité d'un média, même s'il n'a pas l'autorité scientifique, mais compte tenu de la déontologie du métier de journaliste, on ne va pas écrire un article qui dit tout et son contraire en même temps ! »	was circulating on social networks, it is the responsibility of the media, even if it does not have scientific authority, but given the ethics of the profession of journalist, we are not going to write an article that says everything and its opposite at the same time!
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Table 7

3.6. Card sorting exercise

During the workshop, the classification exercise was supposed to take place in two phases. In the initial phase, participants were divided into sub-groups and were supposed to identify the main themes associated with each case. They were then required to collectively rank them based on their significance. The second phase aimed to classify the cases themselves. Regrettably, this second phase couldn't be executed due to time constraints caused by the Maison de la Recherche operating on a more limited schedule during the summer period. In this section, I will present the original thematic rankings and suggest how the cases could have been ranked based on the importance of the comments they generated among the participants.

The first exercise led to the creation of a list of 22 themes discussed during the sub-groups, with three themes being discussed identically in the two sub-groups: “participation makes science more accessible”, “participation requires scientific supervision”, “professional ethics of researchers”.

The table 8 below shows the ranking of all themes for all cases and all groups.

rank	Case1		Case 2		Case 3		Case 4	Case 4
	A	B	A	B	A	B	Group1	Group2
1	professional ethics of researchers	Transparency and data accessibility	confidence undermined by institutions trying to protect their image	scientific consensus creates trust	a virtuous system, but subject to conditions	confidence undermined by social networks	makes science more accessible	makes science more accessible
2	Science requires reflexivity	Expertise based policy	professional ethics of researchers	raise public awareness of the scientific method and critical thinking	setting up citizens' councils in research organisations	Participation requires scientific supervision	Participation requires scientific supervision	a citizen participation initiative can create vocations
3	data accessibility	confidence undermined by unkept promises	science undermined by private interests	scientific community as the only legitimate review body	strengthening the link between citizen participation and political decision-making	public consultation has only a limited effect on confidence in science	data collection is too limited an approach to participation	there is a risk that citizen participation will be manipulated
4	control and evaluation mechanisms				a system that appears democratic but is used to manipulate public opinion			

Table 8

Given that the exercise couldn't be fully carried out due to practical limitations, the coordinator and the facilitator used the notes gathered from the group discussions. The cases were then classified based on the extent of discussion they inspired and the level of interest they evoked among the participants.

The table 9 below shows this reconstructed ranking.

Group 1	Group 2
Case 3A	Case 4
Case 1B	Case 1A
Case 4	Case 3B
Case 2A	Case 2B

Table 9

In both groups, while the issues of research ethics and scientific integrity appear to maintain a clear connection with trust in science, views are less decisive regarding the impact of citizen participation on this trust. For some, this trust is already present, given that the citizens who agree to engage in these practices willingly rely on scientists for the processing and analysis of data they help gather. The discussions underscored the challenge these mechanisms face in reaching beyond the circle of interested amateurs and in fostering trust without pre-existing interest. Furthermore, these participatory processes sometimes elicit ambivalent feelings: although they serve as tools for scientific and technical democracy, they can also be used to lend a consultative sheen to decisions that have already been made upstream. The discussion highlights the importance of moving beyond a purely symbolic use of citizen participation and ensuring its scientific robustness (through proper guidance) and the significance of citizens' engagement.

4. Attitudes towards science & technology

In this section, I present the main results of the questionnaire administered to the workshop participants.

The questionnaire began with a series of questions that allowed for open-ended responses. For example, participants were asked "What comes to mind when you think about science and technology?", "What does it mean to study something scientifically?" and "What concerns do you have about scientific research?".

Next, the questionnaire continued with five statements and participants were asked to state their degree of agreement or disagreement with each of them.

Finally, the first questionnaire ended with a series of questions designed to gather more information about the participants' profile.

The second questionnaire introduced three open questions allowing participants to express their concerns about bad practice in research, their thoughts on the way in which scientific results are communicated to the general public, and their views on the participation of citizens and society as a whole in discussions on scientific and technical developments.

After this first series of questions, participants were again asked to indicate their level of agreement with the same statements as those presented in the first questionnaire. Naturally, the aim of this methodology is to study how the forum can influence participants' points of view over time.

Finally, in a last series of questions, participants were asked about their experience. They were also asked about their previous participation in a similar event and why they chose to take part in this one. Finally, they were asked to consider the potential consequences of their participation - in particular, could it lead them to participate in similar events in the future?

4.1. Questionnaire 1 : Three Open Questions

« What comes to your mind when thinking about science and technology... »: Through their answers most participants defined science primarily as a reasoned way of apprehending the world through the scientific method. The concept of science is intertwined with technological progress for many, who see it as a path towards critical thinking, increasing knowledge, and democratizing information.

Participants referred to major scientific and technological advancements, such as progress in medicine, robotics, artificial intelligence, as illustrations of their perception of science.

This express a common perspective: science is viewed as having a transformative role in society, contributing significantly to human welfare and comfort by providing solutions to various problems. Our participants see science as a catalyst for the development of knowledge and progress, highlighting its role in advancing our understanding of the world and improving our quality of life.

« What does it mean to you to study something scientifically... »: Insofar as our sample is close to the academic world, it is striking to observe that the answers are often detailed. Adherence to a rigorous analytical method was a common theme among the participants. They stressed the importance of a method based on criteria collectively established by scientists themselves. This underscores the significance of shared standards and consensus in science, reinforcing its collective nature.

Scientific research, according to participants, requires a defined and tested methodology — an approach characterized by experimentation that provides proof through reasoning and protocols. The element of experimentation is key, as it enables the testing of ideas and theories against observable phenomena.

The participants stressed the need for rigor and objectivity, reflecting the pursuit of empirical evidence in science. They pointed to the importance of analysing concrete facts in an empirical manner, suggesting that to study something scientifically means to go beyond conjecture or subjective interpretation. Instead, it implies using measurable, objective data to establish the validity of an argument or theory. Several responses highlight the need for a methodological and theoretical framework. They see research as needing to conform to certain standards, guided by a consistent methodological and theoretical thread. This highlights the structured, systematic nature of scientific research.

« What is your main concern about scientific research... »: Many participants expressed concern over the financial intricacies of scientific research. They worried about the impact of complex

funding structures on the time dedicated to the core aspects of the profession and the dissemination of knowledge and results.

Some participants voiced apprehensions about the societal implications of research. They hoped for science to be conducted in a way that informs public opinion and enhances democratic processes. This sentiment reflects the view that science should not just be an academic endeavor but should contribute meaningfully to society and democratic governance.

Participants also voiced fears about the misuse of science. They worried about the spread of misinformation under the guise of "scientific research," manipulation of public opinion, and the misuse of theories to justify atrocities. This reflects a deep concern about the potential for science to be used unethically or harmfully. The manipulation of science and scientific research by political actors and large corporations was another significant concern. This speaks to worries about the integrity of science in the face of external influences and pressures.

Participants expressed a desire for research to be fundamentally driven and to offer solutions to contemporary issues such as energy, climate, and food. They highlighted the expectation that science should be at the forefront of addressing pressing societal and global challenges.

4.2. Questionnaire 1 : Level of Agreement

The questionnaire asked participants to state their level of agreement or disagreement with a set of statements. The details of these statements are as follows:

1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.

The raw and coded results are shown in the tables below. **The coding logic is simple: the higher the value indicated (from 1 to 5), the more positive the attitude towards science and technology.**

Questionnaire 1 before coding

	A4_1	A4_2	A4_3	A4_4	A4_5
Id_1	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree
Id_2	Tend to agree	Tend to agree	Strongly disagree	Tend to agree	Tend to agree
Id_3	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree
Id_4	Strongly agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Strongly disagree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree

Id_5	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree
Id_6	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree
Id_7		Tend to agree	Don't know		Tend to disagree
Id_8	Strongly agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Neither agree nor disagree
Id_9	Don't know	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Tend to disagree

Table 10

Questionnaire 1 with coding

	A4_1 (invert coding)	A4_2 (normal coding)	A4_3 (normal coding)	A4_4 (invert coding)	A4_5 (invert coding)
Id_1	4	4	5	3	2
Id_2	4	2	5	4	4
Id_3	4	4	5	1	3
Id_4	5	3	5	4	3
Id_5	1	5	5	1	1
Id_6	5	2	4	3	2
Id_7	-	2			2
Id_8	5	4	4	3	3
Id_9	-	2	3	2	2

Table 11

Normal coding		Invert coding	
Strongly Agree	1	Strongly Agree	5
Tend to Agree	2	Tend to Agree	4
Neither Agree nor Disagree	3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	3
Tend to disagree	4	Tend to disagree	2
Strongly disagree	5	Strongly disagree	1

Table 12

Regarding the statement, "Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier, and more comfortable," the majority of our participants being close to the academic world, it's not surprising to observe that most of them express agreement. Specifically, 75% agreed with the statement, with three strongly agreeing and three tending to agree. Only one participant, accounting for 11.1%, strongly disagreed with the statement. One participant, also representing 11.1% of the total, was undecided and answered with "Don't know". There's one missing response from one participant.

Regarding the statement, "Science and technology make our lives change too fast," participants were more divided. We can't see a clear majority on this proposal: 44.4% (four out of nine) agreed with the statement, with all four tending to agree. But another 44.4% (four out of nine participants)

disagreed, with three tending to disagree and one strongly disagreeing. Only one participant neither agreed nor disagreed, suggesting a neutral stance on the issue.

Regarding the statement, “We depend too much on science and not enough on faith,” a majority of participants expressed disagreement. Specifically, 77.8% (seven out of nine) strongly disagreed with the statement, while one participant, representing 11.1% of the total, tended to disagree. Only one participant neither agreed nor disagreed, indicating a neutral stance. It is important to emphasize the fact that none of our participants agreed with the statement. This statement clearly shows our participants’ strong commitment to science: they believe in the necessity and importance of relying on science, over faith, in their lives. This might suggest a high level of trust and confidence in the scientific method and its contributions to society and knowledge.

In response to the statement, “Scientists know best what is good for people,” the participants’ opinions varied. Specifically, 25% agreed with the statement, both tending to agree. Another 25% disagreed, both strongly disagreeing. The largest portion of the group, 37%, neither agreed nor disagreed, suggesting a neutral stance. One participant tended to disagree. There’s one missing response from one participant. These results indicate a lack of consensus among participants on whether scientists are best equipped to determine what is good for people. While a small proportion agreed with the statement, an equal proportion strongly disagreed, implying some participants might see scientists’ knowledge as specialized and not necessarily applicable to all aspects of life.

Finally, regarding, the statement, “We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology,” a significant 55.6% (five out of nine participants) disagreed with the statement, with one strongly disagreeing and four tending to disagree. The remaining 33.3% (three out of nine) neither agreed nor disagreed, indicating a neutral position. Only one out of nine participants (11.1%) agreed with the statement, tending to agree. Obviously the majority of participants believe they have options beyond blindly trusting those in charge of governing science and technology. This could potentially reflect a desire for greater transparency, accountability, or public involvement in these areas. However, the neutral responses from a third of the participants suggest some uncertainty or ambivalence regarding this issue.

One can notice that a strong consensus emerged among the workshop participants on several propositions—specifically, propositions 1, 3, and 5—regardless of whether they agreed or disagreed. However, propositions 2 and 4 did not elicit the same level of agreement. These issues seemed to divide the participants, with no clear majority forming either in support of or opposition to these statements.

4.3. Questionnaire 2 : Three Open Questions

The second questionnaire was administered in the same way as the first one, with a series of three open-ended questions. The questions were as follows:

B.1 What is your main concern when thinking about bad practices in scientific research...

B.2 Thinking about the way scientific findings are communicated to the public your main view is...

B.3 Thinking about participation of members of the public in science discussions and developments, your main view is...

Regarding the statement B.1. — « **What is your main concern when thinking about bad practices in scientific research** » — participants express fear that scientific malpractices could “prejudice all scientific research, which is the basis of any good democratic functioning, as it enlightens public debates.” This highlights the role they perceive science plays in informing and shaping democratic discourse and decision-making.

Specific concerns were raised about “data manipulation: scientific frauds.” This underlines an understanding of the ways in which unethical practices can manipulate data, leading to misleading or false results. The “instrumentalization, appropriation, and hasty use in politics” of scientific research was another area of concern. Participants pointed to the potential negative societal impact of such malpractice, acknowledging the far-reaching implications of misusing scientific findings, especially in the realm of policy-making. Participants also highlighted worries about “bias of all kinds (epistemological, political,...) insufficient scientific probity, the objective is not truth but other: success, influence,...”. This suggests an awareness of the potential pitfalls in the pursuit of scientific knowledge and the importance of maintaining the integrity of research objectives.

Lastly, participants expressed concerns about “the devastating effects these bad practices can have on ‘society’”. This encapsulates a broader apprehension about how scientific malpractice can ripple through society, affecting not just the scientific community, but also the public at large.

Regarding the statement B.2. — « **Thinking about the way scientific findings are communicated to the public your main view is** » — several participants commented on the tone and intent of scientific communication. As one participant noted, scientific findings are “too often imbued with a desire to create controversy rather than healthy discussion in public debates, which harms the proper functioning of democracy.” This sentiment suggests that sensationalism and a lack of context can distort scientific findings and their reception by the public.

Other participants emphasized the need for better “vulgarization,” or making the science understandable to non-experts, and “transparency on the methodological process of obtaining these data.” They also highlighted the importance of providing context and methodology along with results. These responses point to the need for scientific communication to be clear, accessible, and comprehensive, allowing the public to understand not just the findings but the process behind them.

Certain responses indicated scepticism or distrust in the way scientific findings are communicated. One participant asserted that there are “false communications” and that “all implications are not disclosed.” This perspective suggests that not all scientific communication is seen as honest or complete, and raises questions about trust and transparency in this process. Other participants focused on the intermediaries in scientific communication, stating that findings are often disseminated through “generalist media not always capable of satisfactorily restoring them.” One respondent suggested that “research institutions might benefit from communicating the work of their teams directly to the public,” indicating a potential preference for more direct communication channels. Lastly, one participant critiqued the clash between the pace of media and the pace of scientific work. They argued that the “timing of the media and the search for attention from the ‘public’ are devastating for scientific work and for ‘social cohesion.’” This view underscores the tension between the careful, slow pace of scientific research and the fast, attention-grabbing pace of media, suggesting a need for better alignment.

Finally regarding the statement B.3. — « **Thinking about participation of members of the public in science discussions and developments, your main view is...** » — participants’ views on public

participation in science and technology range from strongly supportive to sceptical, with many emphasizing the need for structure, inclusivity, and education. One participant found public participation to be "very positive" but noted that it often focused on the same controversial issues. This remark highlights the potential benefits of broadening the scope of public participation in science, beyond just the latest headlines or controversies.

Several participants echoed the sentiment that public participation is "fundamental," but with the caveat that the "framework and modalities" should be collectively defined. They also noted the need for "scientific supervision," "good logistics," and "more inclusive citizen involvement until the results and conclusions." These responses underscore the importance of clear guidelines, organizational structure, and inclusivity in public engagement efforts.

On the other hand, one participant expressed a contrasting viewpoint, suggesting that "it's a matter for the experts, and such public participation could harm the most fundamental developments in science." This perspective brings to light concerns about the potential pitfalls of public participation, including the risk of compromising scientific rigor and expertise. Another participant provided a more ambivalent perspective, stating that they did not have a "clear opinion on the issue." They recognized that "science is often produced from public money" and therefore, "citizens should have their say." At the same time, they acknowledged that "science is not a democratic enterprise: it is necessarily dissymmetric, some know more about a subject than others," suggesting that researchers are better positioned to make decisions on scientific developments.

4.4. Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

In this final segment, I describe the results of questionnaire 2. This survey echoed the initial one, in which participants were asked to rate their agreement with various statements. Both raw and coded results from the questionnaire 2 are represented in the tables below.

The ensuing table, depicting the mean scores for each response, demonstrates that **the workshop appeared to have no strong impact on participants' viewpoints**. The most significant change was observed in participants' attitudes towards the influence of science on the quality of life; a slight increase from an initial average of 4 in the first questionnaire to 4.6 in the second was noted. For the remaining items, results remained consistent with the initial survey. Moreover, the proportion of agreement, summed from the positive modalities, remained constant.

Naturally, considering the constraints inherent in this specific Paris workshop, drawing overarching conclusions about this type of event capacity to alter opinions becomes unfeasible. The scope of our sample remains too restricted to make any claims beyond the descriptive examination of the perspectives shared during the event.

Questionnaire 2 before coding

	B4_1	B4_2	B4_3	B4_4	A4_4
Id_1	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree
Id_2	Tend to agree	Tend to agree	Strongly disagree	Tend to agree	Tend to agree
Id_3	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree
Id_4	Strongly agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Strongly disagree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree
Id_5	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly disagree
Id_6	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Tend to disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree
Id_7		Tend to agree	Don't know		Tend to disagree
Id_8	Strongly agree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Neither agree nor disagree
Id_9	Don't know	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Tend to disagree

Table 13

Questionnaire 2 with coding

	B4_1 (invert coding)	B4_2 (normal coding)	B4_3 (normal coding)	B4_4 (invert coding)	A4_5 (invert coding)
Id_1	4	4	5	3	2
Id_2	4	2	5	4	4
Id_3	4	4	5	1	3
Id_4	5	3	5	4	3
Id_5	5	5	5	1	1
Id_6	5	2	4	3	2
Id_7		2			2
Id_8	5	4	5	3	3
Id_9		2	3	2	2

Table 14

Normal coding		Invert coding	
Strongly Agree	1	Strongly Agree	5
Tend to Agree	2	Tend to Agree	4
Neither Agree nor Disagree	3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	3
Tend to disagree	4	Tend to disagree	2
Strongly disagree	5	Strongly disagree	1

Table 15

Item	Before			After		
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable. (one missing response)	4	1,4	75%	4,6	0,5	75%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	3,1	1,2	44%	3,1	1,2	44%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	4,5	0,8	0%	4,6	0,7	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people. (one missing response)	2,6	1,2	25%	2,6	1,2	25%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2,4	0,9	11%	2,4	0,9	11%

Table 16

Figure 1

Finally, in this concluding table 17, we assess the potential repercussions of the workshop through participant feedback. Of the nine attendees, four expressed a desire to engage in similar future events. Three participants would relay their experiences to friends and family, while one stated their intention to consume more media content about such gatherings. Another participant abstained from remarking on potential future actions related to the workshop.

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	44,4
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	33,3
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	11,1
4. Other	11,1

Table 17

Appendix

Questionnaire 1: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	37.5	37.5	0.0	0.0	12.5	12.5
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	0.0	44.4	11.1	33.3	11.1	0.0
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	0.0	0.0	11.1	11.1	66.7	11.1
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	0.0	25.0	37.5	12.5	25.0	0.0
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	0.0	11.1	33.3	44.4	11.1	0.0

Questionnaire 2: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	37.5	37.5	0.0	0.0	12.5	12.5
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	0.0	44.4	11.1	33.3	11.1	0.0
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	0.0	0.0	11.1	11.1	66.7	11.1
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	0.0	25.0	37.5	12.5	25.0	0.0
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	0.0	11.1	33.3	44.4	11.1	0.0

Annex C: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – Germany

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *Germany*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Iscte)*

Author of the National Report: Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat

1 Introduction

This report analyses the results of the German public deliberative workshop that took place in the context of WP2 of the POIESIS project. After a description of the event's set up, the applied recruitment strategy and a short overview over the participants' profiles, each small group and the main arguments of their case discussions are presented. The third part of the report then analyses more specifically what participants thought about POIESIS' key themes: trust, integrity, integration and channels of communication. In the end, selected results of the questionnaires handed out in the beginning and the end of the event are presented.

1.1 Set up of the event

The workshop setting

The German public deliberative workshop, in German and here in the following called Bürger*innen-Dialog, took place on the 9th of June 2023 in Berlin. It was organised as a Friday afternoon event in the facilities of a co-working and event space called "bUm – community space for nonprofit organizations and activists" (<https://bum.berlin/en/>), located in a popular Berlin neighbourhood. The space was chosen because of its central location and its inclusive character.

Participants were invited to arrive from 13:30 with the event starting at 14:00. The Bürger*innen-Dialog then ran until 18:00, followed by a small reception with snacks and drinks. Counted altogether, 20 people participated in the event – 16 participants, three facilitators and the moderator Philipp Schrögel. Schrögel is research area coordinator and responsible for science communication at the Käte Hamburger Centre for Apocalyptic and Post-Apocalyptic Studies at the University of Heidelberg. He moderated the event, facilitated one of the small group discussions and also gave the input speech as topical expert (see also section 1.2). The other facilitators were WP1 leader Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat and two colleagues from Wissenschaft im Dialog (WiD): Imke Hedder and Lisa Mertin.

The four small groups for the case discussions were created randomly in the beginning of the event with the help of coloured dots, attributed to the arriving participants. Two groups started with three participants, one with four and one with five. The group composition changed slightly throughout the event as two participants unfortunately had to leave after the first round of small group discussions (the first two cases).

Recruitment

The recruitment process for the event started mid-April, two months before the event. In preparation of the recruitment, a multi-stage sampling strategy was developed with the objective to ensure the representation of diverse opinions and a high variation in the participants' profiles at the Bürger*innen-Dialog. The target group of the recruitment strategy was defined as 'the general public', to be as diverse as possible in terms of sociodemographic characteristics. Previous experiences with similar events organised by WiD had however already shown that many parts

of ‘the general public’ were very hard to reach for scientific events. This led to the establishment of a recruitment strategy with different stages.

The general approach of the recruitment strategy was to proceed pyramidically from broad to narrow. During the first stage of the process, the objective was to reach the widest and most diverse audience possible. In a large city like Berlin, the most promising way to do so seemed to be contacting the 32 district management offices and the around 60 community and neighbourhood centres of Berlin (in the following summarised as neighbourhood centres). These neighbourhood centres are situated all around the city but with a higher density in underprivileged districts and those with a particularly diverse population in terms of nationality. The neighbourhood centres are in constant dialogue with the citizens from their districts, organise events for young people, seniors etc. and are generally seen as places of dialogue, participation, and inclusion. We contacted all of these neighbourhood centres personally, presented the POIESIS project and its objectives to them, and asked whether it was possible to advertise our event via posters and flyers in their facilities. The overall response was very positive and so, by the end of April, posters and flyers advertising the event were distributed in nearly of these neighbourhood centres all over Berlin. In a majority of cases, the material was brought there in person to leave a personal impression and make sure that the material would not get lost among the many things they receive. Some of the neighbourhood centres offered to additionally share the event via their online channels.

Still within stage 1 of the recruitment process, online and offline advertising material was also provided to the bUm, the location where the event took place. Following the recommendation of the head of one of the neighbourhood centres, the idea came up to additionally contact the Berlin Volkshochschulen, public places of education for adults with various backgrounds. All 12 Volkshochschulen were contacted. However, they were less receptive: all of them either responded negatively or not at all to the request to share material on the event.

It was consciously decided not to contact any climate change associations, civil society organisations, NGOs etc. during this first stage of the recruitment. There were two main reasons for that: in a city like Berlin, the sheer number of such organisations would have been too high to be entirely covered by invitations. Keeping this in mind, there were no clear criteria which of these associations to choose without biasing the profile of the participants. Secondly, the question whether a discussion with activists, for example in the field of climate change, would be the same as with the general public can very likely be answered with No. This is why our approach focused truly on ‘the general public’ in this first step, trying to reach as many people as possible from an audience not necessarily linked to science or any of the event’s thematic foci (climate change and Covid-19) in the first place.

In the second stage of the recruitment process, we targeted what we called the ‘interested public’, meaning people who might not work in but are in more or less frequent contact with science. This second step started in the beginning of / mid-May with an advertisement of the event through the WiD online channels, meaning its social media accounts (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter) and its email newsletter. Additionally, the citizen science platform managed by WiD (<https://www.buergerschaftenwissen.de/>) advertised the event and the responsible colleague also shared the information via an internal email list of citizen science project initiatives in Berlin. Flyers were also distributed on the science ship MS Wissenschaft during its stay in Berlin as well as at a fair for Volunteers in Berlin. In both cases, the responsible colleagues from WiD were given an introduction to the POIESIS project and the objective of the Bürger*innen-Dialog to be able to answer potential questions coming up on site.

Reaching the tip of the pyramid behind our recruitment strategy, in stage 3, then, numerous associations with a focus on climate change in the widest sense (Fridays for Future, Berlin Vegan etc.) and science associations in Berlin were contacted in order to recruit people from what could be called an ‘informed public’, meaning those already engaged in some kind of association or organisation with a link to science or one of the thematic foci of the event.

The objective of the sampling strategy’s pyramidal structure was to recruit as many people as possible from the ‘general public’ in the beginning of the process and then complete the number of desired participants with people from the ‘interested’ and in a last step the ‘informed’ public. However, as in the end of May still not many people had registered for the event, we reflected on this strategy and decided to go back to stage 1, mobilising all efforts once again to reach out and make the event known to as many people as possible. In this regard, WiD published an official press release on the 26th of May that was sent to over 700 recipients (local media, contacts of the Berlin city administration, universities, research organisations etc.). Student groups of all Berlin universities and all kinds of cultural and neighbourhood associations were contacted. The bUm (the event’s location) and some of the neighbourhood centres were re-contacted and asked whether they could share the event once again via their online channels. Further, the Bürger*innen-Dialog was advertised on even more social media platforms: nebenan.de (a neighbourhood platform for events, exchange etc.), MeetUp (a platform for local events) and Berlin specific facebook groups. Semi-private channels were also activated such as alumni lists of specific university degrees located in Berlin etc. In the beginning of June, the WiD Head of Press and Public Relations personally contacted three big Berlin newspapers following up on the press release and asking them whether they could advertise the event. One of the newspapers sent a journalist to the event (leading to a detailed article about trust in science in the end of June), and one newspaper actually realised an interview with the local project leader, Anne-Sophie Behm-Bahtat, and published a long article – online and in print – the day before the event.

Altogether, extensive recruitment efforts have been carried out all over Berlin and targeting very different audiences in order to motivate people to come to the Bürger*innen-Dialog. Most successful in this were the platform nebenan.de and the email newsletters of the neighbourhood centres. Nevertheless, it turned out to be extremely difficult to reach people who might be interested in such an event.

In total, 20 people registered for the event, either via the platform eveno.com or via email. 16 participants came to the event (two of which had not registered). One person however showed a very critical attitude towards the event from the start and then left directly after the introduction. Therefore, the dialogue started with 15 participants and four facilitators into the small group discussions.

1.2 Participants in the event

16 participants filled out the first questionnaire which included questions on their sociodemographic data². 12 of them answered the relevant questions on their personal profile.

² To avoid too many repetitive questions, items on sociodemographic data were not included in the 2nd questionnaire. To be able to match the answers to questions A4 and B4 anyhow, a personalised code was included in both questionnaires.

The following description of the participants is based on the answers from the questionnaires paired with observations from the facilitators.

Sex (based on observation, n=16)

Female	Male
11	5

Age (based on questionnaire, n=12)

18-24	25-29	30-34	35-39	40-44	45-49	50-54	55-59	60-64	65+
0	2	0	1	1	2	0	2	2	2

Education (based on questionnaire, n=12)

Primary education	Low secondary education	Upper secondary education	Bachelor's or equivalent level	Master's or equivalent level	Doctoral or equivalent level
0	0	3	1	6	2

Link to science (table based on questionnaire (n=12), further observations added in the text)

I'm a scientist/researcher	I am a science student	It is part of my work	Indirectly or occasionally	No/Not really
2	0	6	2	2

In the beginning of the small group discussions, participants were asked to shortly introduce themselves and answer the question whether and where they get in touch with science in their daily life. The participants' answers reflect the ones in the questionnaires for the participants with a strong link to science (scientists or science as part of their work). However, more participants than the questionnaires would suggest stated in their self-introduction that they have no or no strong link to science (n=6). Thus, even though there was a small majority of participants dealing with science professionally in their daily lives (or having dealt with it in the case of pensioners), quite a few people participated in the event who normally do not get in touch with science much. The mix of both turned out to be very valuable for the small group discussions.

2 Discursive summary of cases

The following chapter summarises the composition of the four small groups, their dynamics, and the key aspects of their respective case discussions. Very generally, it can be said that the case discussions had very diverging foci in the groups. Talking about the same case, groups partly took totally different roads: for one case, one group concentrated nearly exclusively on political aspects and conflicts of interest while this did not come up once in other groups. For another group, this same case was all about language while this did not appear to be an important aspect for others. The presentation of the cases via different channels of communication certainly

influenced the direction of the debate (see section 3.5) but the profile of the participants and different group constellations equally seemed to have an impact in this regard.

2.1 Phase 1 – Expert talk

For the Berlin Bürger*innen-Dialog it was decided not to invite an external expert to talk about either climate change or Covid-19 but to use the expertise of our facilitator, Philipp Schrögel, an expert in science communication, to set the scene. To make the introductory plenary session more interactive, on their arrival, participants were asked to fill post-its with their thoughts on the question “What is trust?” from a very general perspective. The answers on this “trust wall” (picture attached in Appendix B) were used as an entry point for a stimulating input by Schrögel on trust, trust in science and how the latter relates to science communication. The expert talk also included two short video sequences, in which scientists, one from the field of climate change and one from medical research, told the participants about their view on science and their personal experiences with science communication in their field. The expert talk was kept short on purpose in order to allow as much time for the small group discussions as possible.

2.2 Phase 2 – Focus groups

2.2.1 Group 1 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3B, 4 (green)

Group 1 was due to some particular circumstances in the composition of the participants the smallest group. In the first discussion phase, there were three participants and the moderator, in the second and third phase only two, one of them having been ‘transferred’ from Group 2 to keep the group working. The only member of the group (except for the moderator) who constantly participated in Group 1 was a science journalist himself and therefore had a very interesting but very specific perspective on the cases and questions asked. The moderator did his best dealing with the situation and the journalist reported that the participants’ perspective during the event was very interesting for him as well.

Group 1 discussed the **Ivermectin study** based on a newspaper article from DIE ZEIT, a renowned, nationwide weekly newspaper in Germany. The journalist remembered having treated the case with his own team as well. Nevertheless, the discussion revolved mostly around the more general context of Covid-19, vaccination and how science (and politics) should or should not have behaved in this context than on the case itself. The debate had a strong focus on trust. The newspaper article as such was perceived very positively by all participants. In the ranking exercise, this case was not considered to have any influence on trust, though, as the back and forth between scientists – some saying one thing and others claiming the contrary – was perceived as happening on a daily basis.

The **climate gate scandal** was presented to the group via a Twitter thread posted by a scientist working at the University of East Anglia. One participant had problems to understand the format of a Twitter thread as such but also stated never to use social media. All three participants however showed confusion – as in all other groups – regarding the actual setting of the story and what really had happened: did data disappear or not? Who did what? The general confusion led away from the actual points of discussion, and this was something observed across all groups. In Group 1, participants agreed that debates like this – about potential fraud or mistakes in research (and here the discussion shifted back to Covid-19) – should take place in public. However, that it is

also important to always consider the interests behind any kind of communications and that scientists themselves should constructively participate in these debates as well (as opposed to data published by hackers with no chance for scientists to set the context). Despite the confusion, the case was perceived as rather positive for the participants' trust in science in the sense that social media played a positive role in the dissemination of important information here and that a fellow scientist spoke up, ensuring some kind of peer review in the process.

The **public consultation** was discussed based on a facebook post posted by a TV journalist working at RTL, a private entertainment channel. The case raised a lot of critique for two main reasons: on the one hand, the consultation was seen as irresponsible in the sense that citizens would clearly lack the necessary knowledge for having a say on this topic and that even for scientists, the data was insufficient to take such a decision. On the other hand, the so-called 'public participation' in this case was perceived to be fake, as it was suspected that politicians only used this consultation to publicly confirm an already scheduled political measure. The general opinion was that this consultation had nothing to do with science as citizens may certainly give their opinions, but those opinions were not necessarily based on any scientific evidence and would not contribute to gather evidence either (as in actual citizen science projects). Once again, the science journalist contributed numerous insights from his daily work during the pandemic as he was in steady contact with experts and also politicians. The most important take-away of this discussion was a critique of lacking transparency towards science and politics during the pandemic: despite many efforts of scientists to be transparent, the actual political decisions and the scientific evidence on which they were based were very untransparent for citizens. Interestingly, the rationale of the ranking exercise here concentrated rather on the doubtful scientific nature of the working group cited in the case than on public engagement. According to the participants, the group pretended to have scientific evidence they could not have at this stage. The case was therefore perceived rather negative for their trust.

The **Vigie-Nature case** was discussed much more positively in the group. Citizen science projects like this one were perceived as good as much for science as for the citizens. It was however underlined that it is important to not only 'use' citizens as data collectors but also take the opportunity to inform participants about what will happen with their data, the scientific method etc. Participants agreed that a similar project conducted exclusively by scientists would not inspire more or less trust among them because they considered both to be different methodological approaches but with a similar qualitative nature in principle. In conclusion, the participants agreed that this project would have a rather positive influence on their trust in science: it represents an actual participation of citizens in a scientific project and has the side effect to bring science closer to the public – a potentially trust-increasing measure.

2.2.2 Group 2 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3A, 4 (orange)

Group 2 was the biggest group with one moderator and five participants in the first group phase and four participants in the second phase (one moved to Group 1 after the break). Most participants of this group worked in science themselves or very closely to it except for one who therefore acted as bringing in the 'laypeople's' perspective. The group clearly tried to be self-reflective and -critical regarding the professional biases in their views on the questions at hand. Nevertheless, their closeness to science became pretty obvious when comparing the main arguments of their discussions with other groups that had less scientific background. They debated much more on the meta-level and questioned much more often the presented material,

the context, the potential study designs etc. The group dynamics were very good and the discussions lively but respect- and also joyful.

In the discussion of the first case, the **Ivermectin study** based on a facebook post written by a journalist working at DIE ZEIT, language played an important role. The discrepancy between the rather sensational style of the post and the more ‘serious’ reputation of the newspaper was brought forward several times. It was however noticed that the post matched the medium of facebook rather well. The different use of language opposing the individual actors (Carvallo rather “claims” and the experts rather “suspect”) was identified as leading to different feelings towards the respective actors. In general, the post raised mistrust – on the one hand towards the media as the language used did not inspire trust among participants and the medium facebook in general did not either; on the other hand, also against science more generally given the unethical behaviour of the study’s leader Dr. Carvallo. Open science was mentioned as an important factor in this regard. In the ranking exercise, participants could not agree on a common evaluation of the case with individual results ranging from rather positive over no influence to rather negative influence on trust.

The **climate gate scandal** was discussed based on a press release by the University of East Anglia. From the beginning, the case raised lots of confusion as to what was exactly the issue, who was who and what the involvement of industry was here. The debate clearly circled around the research design of the scientist’s study and how it was not clear to which aim it was actually conducted. The hackers’ role and also the potentially unethical behaviour of the scientists were not discussed much. Once again, language played a role in the discussion and how important it is how things are formulated because most people rather skim over a text than reading it in much detail. Not very often texts are analysed as profoundly as in the context of this dialogue. Therefore, according to the participants, it is often the first impression a text gives that remains in the head of the reader. With one abstention, the group agreed on a rather negative influence this case had on their trust in science.

The case of the **public consultation** in Brazil was presented to the participants as an RTL TV report. Here, the discussion clearly revolved around the dominant idea that the consultation was not a true case of public participation. The feeling prevailed that the consultation’s result was pre-determined: politicians wanted to vaccinate children and basically organised this consultation in order to scan the public opinion and to see how much opposition they would have to expect (and how this might impact their re-election chances). The consultation was therefore seen rather critically in terms of ‘participation’. However, one participant who felt affected by the topic as she has a young daughter said she would use the occasion as a source of information. Building on this, the question was discussed which degree of public participation is actually desirable, how effective but also representative citizens councils are, and how to reach different kinds of target groups. While other groups focussed strongly on the more general context of Covid-19, vaccination, and the role of politics and scientists in this regard, this did not come up in this group. As participants mostly agreed that this consultation had more to do with politics than with science, they came to the common conclusion that the case did not influence their trust in science.

The reaction to the **Vigie-Nature case** was mainly positive in the group. All participants were in favour of these kinds of projects even if not necessarily personally interested in participating. Even if participants had some doubts about the quality of the results because citizens might not have the same knowledge as scientists in conducting the research, it was stated that such projects might also fulfil other purposes of science than just generating new knowledge. Inclusion was named in this context and also raising interest and creating passion for particular

topics among the public. Getting to know more about nature and becoming interested in it might lead to making more efforts for protecting nature as well. In the course of the discussion, participants revised their initial opinion on the quality of the data by arguing that it will potentially be already interested and therefore informed citizens who participate in for example counting birds. All in all, participants ranked this case as rather positive for their trust in science.

2.2.3 Group 3 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3A, 4 (red)

Group 3 was composed by three participants and one moderator. It was an all-female group with a great dynamic in the discussion. All participants shared rather similar basic views on the different topics, but the various backgrounds of the participants allowed for different perspectives anyhow. All participants appreciated one another and treated the others with much respect. The dynamics developed positively over the afternoon and led to them joking and laughing together in the end.

The group discussed the **Ivermectin study** framed in a newspaper article published in DIE ZEIT. In relation to research integrity, it was discussed that there were different interests at stake behind any study but also behind any communication and that for the reader, those interests are not necessarily clear. The study as such was seen very critically by all participants and the engagement of the expert group to denounce this fraudulent study was perceived positively. At the same time, it was also brought up that sometimes scientists have good reasons not to publish all of their material (in relation to the fact that Mr. Cavallo would not allow access to the data) because it might be stolen. Another point of discussion was the communication channel and the way in which the reporter of the newspaper tried to present both sides of the story. Trying to be objective was perceived positively. At the same time, it was argued that the reader might have difficulties to assess whom to trust among the actors involved. The ranking exercise showed that while all participants thought that the initial study was to be judged negatively, the actions taken by the expert group to denounce bad practices was perceived very positively, so that the rather positive influence on their trust prevailed.

The group discussed the **climate gate scandal** via a twitter thread posted by a scientist. The case – again – caused lots of confusion: on the one hand because of its format as not all participants were familiar with twitter, on the other hand because of its content. The intentions of the thread's author were not very clear to the participants and while they supported the fact that the story was brought up again after a few years to keep people informed, participants did not perceive twitter as a very serious source for scientific content. It was too 'personal' for them and not official enough, so they would not have much trust in the message conveyed. The issue of data protection and hacking more generally (not in relation to science) was also discussed. The participants agreed on two different judgements of this case in the ranking exercise: a rather positive influence for reporting the story and bringing it back to people's minds, underlining that the scientists at the time had worked properly and defended themselves; but at the same time, a rather negative influence regarding the format and the communication channel through which it was done.

The **public consultation** was discussed on the basis of an RTL TV channel report. In principle, all participants expressed support for public consultations but not on this particular topic (vaccination of children against Covid-19). It was very clear to the participants that laypeople do not have enough expertise on the topic to be able to take such a decision. Further, they argued that a government asking people to express their opinion on this would rather make them feel insecure, because it could imply that they themselves did not know what they were doing. The communication channel did not have such a big impact on the participants' opinion on the case

as it had before. Upon demand, they noticed that RTL might not be a very serious source of scientific content, but it was anyway not a source they would turn to for it. Without much discussion the participants agreed on a rather negative influence of this case on their trust in science in the ranking exercise.

The **Vigie-Nature case** received strong support from all group members who really liked the idea of the project and were really enthusiastic about the kind of public involvement offered here. It was explicitly mentioned that here, the burden of responsibility and the danger to do something 'wrong' was not comparable to the vaccination-case. Therefore, they agreed that it was indeed positive to rely on the knowledge and help of citizens for this project. It was also brought forward that through this kind of projects, science can not only benefit from public support but also becomes tangible for citizens and therefore might increase their trust in science. All participants agreed in the ranking exercise that this project was very positive for their trust in science.

2.2.4 Group 4 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3B, 4 (blue)

Group 4 was a mixed group, composed of four and after the first round of discussions three participants (one had to leave early but was very sad about that) and one moderator. The dynamics of the group were complicated because one participant clearly tried to dominate the discussion and turned all questions towards her own personal life and difficult fate. She was very emotional which made it difficult for the moderator to guide the discussion back to the topic. This group's participants were, with one exception, generally rather critical towards the cases and there were some very divergent perspectives on the topics discussed. However, they all shared a very negative view on politics and politicians assuming that the latter would only pursue their own interests instead of the common good. Science was perceived as being too strongly influenced by politics. This theme was very dominant in the discussions and kept coming up even after specifying that the focus of the debate ought to be science and not politics. After the ranking exercise, in which it became apparent once again how different the opinions in the group were, one participant noted that their only 'uniting factor' was the clear distrust in politics and all agreed.

The group discussed the **Ivermectin study** presented as a facebook post by a journalist working at DIE ZEIT. The group expressed the opinion that cases like this one, where two opinions stand against each other ('I have found a drug against Covid-19' vs. 'No, your study is fabricated') are omnipresent in the media, especially in social media. It was discussed whether the journalist presented the study this way to inform people of both sides or rather not to put off any potential reader of the newspaper. It was argued that from a very general point of view, it is very difficult to know the 'truth' nowadays because anybody can claim to be right. As a 'normal citizen' one has great difficulties to know who is right and who is wrong, and many actors consciously use this general insecurity to mislead people. Scientists were included in this rather pessimistic view. For example, the expert group and their attempt to inform people that the study was probably fraudulent was not perceived as something positive by the participants, but rather as just the second side of the coin without any clues of who is speaking the truth in the whole story. In the ranking exercise, this thought-to-be objective reporting was the crucial reason for agreeing on a rather negative influence on trust (not the potentially fraudulent study as such).

Group 4 discussed the **climate gate scandal** presented as a press release by the University of East Anglia. The first thing discussed in this regard was the place in which the research was taking place, China, which led to clear mistrust towards the results from the very beginning. Concerning the communication channel, participants did not agree at all on the

question whether a press release from a university was a more trustworthy source than a social media post: some said yes, as there was an institution behind it, while others underlined that particularly this institution had an interest in presenting things ‘their way’. One participant put forward the clear opinion that one cannot trust a communication just because it comes from a specific actor, but that it is one’s own responsibility to read, to reflect, to compare with what one knows, with what exists elsewhere and then form an own opinion on whether something might be true or not – no matter via which channel one had received the news. It was also expressed that the hackers clearly had their own interests in mind as well and that digital material can always be fabricated so that it is not even sure whether the published emails were actually real. In the ranking exercise, participants agreed that it was positive that the debate had been made public and not covered up. There was however no common result because one participant insisted that the debate becoming public was not a voluntary decision of the scientists but involuntary due to the hackers. This gave the impression that there was something to hide and therefore the whole story finally had a rather negative influence on this participant’s trust.

The third case, the **public consultation** on the vaccination of children, was presented to the group via a facebook post by a journalist working at the TV channel RTL. The general opinion was that medication of children and especially the development of it is a very sensitive and emotional field and not much trust was expressed towards science in this regard. A more general discussion about scientific developments during the Covid-19 crisis emerged with the general opinion that vaccination was good (for adults) but that the mRNA-vaccines were to be seen very critically because they had not been tested long enough. One participant reported to suffer from fatigue-syndrome since her last vaccine making her disabled but without receiving any medical recognition for it. On the question whether participants would participate in this public consultation, one said she would not because she does not have the necessary medical knowledge for it. Another one would only participate – and only trust in the results – if transparency in who organises the consultation, to which aim and with which methods (who analyses the contributions etc.) was guaranteed. The third one would participate via email to make her opinion known, but always under the general preliminary assumption that very likely, the aim would be to manipulate citizens by making them think that their opinion was desired even if this was not actually the case. In the ranking exercise, it became clear that all of them generally supported the idea of public consultations – if organised under strict transparency rules and on other topics than vaccination for children.

Interestingly, the **Vigie-Nature case** has been the most controverse case in this group while it was the most consensual one in all the others. The whole question of ‘what is science? And what is scientific?’ emerged in this context and while one participant was clearly in favour of public involvement in science in form of such projects, the others were clearly against it stating that an involvement of laypeople would make the project unscientific. Consequently, the first participant stated she would not trust the results of the study more if it was conducted just by scientists – rather on the contrary – while the two others stated that they would. Interestingly, the first participant convinced the others slightly with her argument that engaged laypeople who participate in order to do something for the environment might be better observers than ‘uninterested’ scientists doing this only for financial benefit. Anyhow, no agreement could be reached on this case in the ranking exercise – on the contrary: the answers ranged from a positive influence, over no influence, to this project having a negative influence on the participants’ trust in science.

3 Integrity and integration & trust in science

Chapter 3 of this report presents an analysis of the most important aspects and arguments participants discussed during the Bürger*innen-Dialog in relation to topics that are of particular relevance for POIESIS' research questions.

3.1 General attitudes towards science

While not a topic of debate as such, the participants' general attitudes and feelings towards science came up several times during the case discussions. Participants expressed **positive feelings** towards science such as gratefulness for scientific achievements, curiousness, and relief when learning about new scientific findings: "I always thought it was too late to learn a new language, but now they found out that it is still possible even when people are old" (female, Group 3). Participants also said they respected the work of scientists who work honestly. In general, the interest in science was rather high.

At the same time, however, also more **negative, critical thoughts** were raised. Maybe the most important and recurring one was a critique towards the idea of one general 'science': "There is not THE science. Scientists contradict each other all the time. Some scientists still deny climate change" (female, Group 4). The argument that scientists are often telling different stories about the same topic and therefore contradicting each other came up in all groups. This is perceived as happening constantly and representing an ongoing struggle for laypeople, because they do not know whom to believe. Another negative point that was brought up, especially in the context of climate change, was a kind of resignation, a feeling of 'it is already too late' that was related to science but also to politics (see also section 3.6). With regard to the Covid-19 pandemic, participants expressed the feeling that the people's trust has been 'played' by different actors. Participants felt that citizens' trust in scientific findings was just demanded by the authorities during the pandemic but without proper explanations or enough transparency behind the decisions that were taken (vaccination, closing of playgrounds etc.). This raised negative sentiments towards the implicated actors – mostly politicians but also scientists.

While reflecting on the rather precise cases, much more general and superordinate questions were raised by the participants such as 'what is 'good' science?' but also 'where do we want to go as a society and how can science contribute to that?'. Participants in all groups further made comments that can be summarised under two headlines: 'how science should work' and 'how to behave towards science'.

How science should work

Participants argued that the aim of scientists should be to **inform** the public as much as possible about what is going on. They should not hide behind technical terms but seek the connection with 'normal citizens' on the level that we all are humans. At the same time, science communication should **not be too emotional**.³ People seek guidance from science and scientists especially when

³ All arguments presented in this chapter reflect the opinions of the Bürger*innen-Dialog's participants. For better readability, this is not specified for every one of them.

it comes to controversial topics like the vaccination of children. That does not mean that decisions on such topics should be imposed on individuals by scientists, but that scientific evidence might be reassuring when in doubt and too many emotions in the communication process could get in the way of that. In the eyes of the participants, science should be **verifiable**. Scientists should use reliable methods and procedures that are subject to constant reflection and ensure comparability across studies. Science should work in a way that scientists get the feeling that conducting ‘good’ science, meaning investing time and resources, working according to standards etc., is rewarded. This would mean decreasing pressure and creating an atmosphere of **fairness and mutual support** instead of the current high competitiveness in research, which was perceived as problematic by the participants. Finally, scientists should reflect on how they can **contribute to society**. For this, participants argued that input from citizens towards scientists is important, just like it was made possible by the Bürger*innen dialog.

How to behave towards science

In the same way as participants’ ideas about how science should ideally work were very much comparable across groups, most of them also shared similar ideas about how one should behave towards science (not necessarily meaning that this was always the case for themselves). The most pressing issue in this regard was the question of how to find out whom to trust when being confronted with scientific quarrels or also new scientific findings. Instead of directly believing all scientific information one receives, participants underlined that it is very important to ask what **interests** might be behind a particular study and who the author but also the funding body is behind it (see also section 3.2). Further research into sources and alleged experts is often needed. One should **critically scrutinise** what one knows and where one should learn more in order to be able to judge whether something might be true or not. **Common sense** should also not be left aside, and some participants also referred to their gut instinct when being confronted with scientific information – most of them however indicated that they would not use their gut instinct for their final judgement but rather to raise doubts about something leading them to go deeper into research. Most participants were however aware that such critical scrutiny is more of an ideal than a reality as most people rather skim over headlines and make a quick judgement than going deeply into the information and conducting background research (see also sections 3.2 on the question of trust and 3.5 on the role of communication channels in this regard).

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

Moving along their general attitudes towards participants’ trust in science, one can say that the latter was rather high among most participants. Trust was however also described as a rather ‘settled feeling’ not easily influenced. In this regard, one participant mentioned that it was not the case studies that had an impact on his trust in science but rather that his initial trust in science influenced the way he read and perceived the case studies. This argument – that individual feelings, pre-knowledge, personal characteristics as well as the own story influence the way one sees science and perceives scientific news – was a recurring one in the small group discussions: “I generally trust science because I know a lot of people [in science] and I know how much preparations they have, how much material they collect, etc. and how they have done seriously great things” (female, Group 1). It was also mentioned several times that this is working the other way around as well: those who distrust science will have a totally different and more negative perception of any scientific news than those who generally trust in science or scientists. The actual

judgement of whether to trust something or not often happens out of an initial feeling, according to the participants, and not really based on rational arguments. This is why the communication of scientific content, which strongly influences this initial feeling, is so important.

But what factors may affect trust or distrust in science? Apart from arguments related to integrity, public integration, and communication channels (see upcoming sections), there were a few more overarching variables that were mentioned several times in relation to the participants' trust.

Insecurity was one of the leading themes in the small group discussions. Participants expressed that they oft felt insecure whether to trust scientific content or not: is this true? Is the source trustworthy? How to make the difference between an actual research institute and just any organisation calling itself institute while conducting sloppy or biased research? "In our days, it is difficult to know the truth" (male, Group 4).

Secondly, **language** was brought up as a crucial factor for trust. This relates to the fact that most people rather quickly scan a text and then decide whether its content is trustworthy or not than making detailed background analyses. The use of language in any kind of communication is therefore of great importance for people's trust. Several participants noted that the use of certain expressions in a text may from the very beginning influence the readers' trust or mistrust in the actors described: expressions like a "renowned study" and "independent group of experts" were perceived to be rather positive for their trust, while saying that something was "100% effective" directly raised doubts among all participants. One participant however also stated that the fact that the study in the Ivermectin case was said to be "renowned" and then described in the entire opposite way as what she would expect from a renowned study was impacting her trust negatively. With regard to the use of language, **accessibility**, or the lack of it, was also mentioned as an important variable for trust. This concerns scientific texts but also the presentation of homepages or any other kind of communication.

A somewhat different influencing factor of people's trust, but which has been discussed in all groups, is the scientists' **'origin' or place of work**. While one participant stated: "I somehow trust scientists from Germany" (female, Group 3), scientific results from China, Argentina and Brazil were confronted with more scepticism: "Okay, the scientist is from Argentina. I admit that perhaps this is a prejudice, but I do not know much about the country. Not politically. And there is, I think, also a certain reservation. I would first have to find out what the conditions are like. What is the research like? I would need a bit of background" (female, Group 3). "When I read China, I'm already suspicious. I know that this is an authoritarian system and that there, economy comes first and the environment last. So, I wouldn't necessarily believe that" (male, Group 4).

In all statements of the participants on this topic, it became clear that their distrust was not directed towards the abroad scientists and their work as such (in the context of the climate gate scandal, participants were also aware that it was a scientist from the UK conduction research in China). They rather doubted the political system and were convinced that in these countries, scientific results are influenced by political interests even stronger than they are in Germany (see also section 3.6): "I didn't mean to say that I don't trust science in Brazil in general, but that I doubt that this is really a scientific working group" (female, Group 1). It would have been interesting to confront participants to a case maybe from another European country to see whether similar thoughts would have arisen.

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

The integrity of science as a system has already been touched upon in the context of scientists' place of work as a factor of trust. The integrity of communication channels was also a heated topic of debate (see section 3.5). This section concentrates on the integrity of individual scientists and their work, though.

Generally, one can say that this has been the topic least discussed by participants. Even though the term "integrity" was used in the text of the climate gate scandal it has not been taken up in the discussions. Nevertheless, some recurring arguments of the participants can be linked to the dimension of research integrity practices and (dis)trust, namely: the influence of particular interests, the importance of peer-review mechanisms, transparency, and open science.

Very generally, participants made clear that they consider bad practices in research being rather an exception than the norm. This might explain why they mostly did not focus their discussions on the question whether the scientists actually had done something wrong or not. Other aspects were more important for the participants. Maybe the most dominant among them was the **influence of particular interests**. It was considered that such interests are 'hiding' behind nearly all scientific studies and also behind their communication – this might be third-party interests such as political or commercial ones, but it might also be the scientist's proper interests in fame, funding etc. "I wouldn't say that you can generally trust science or not. But there are always certain interests behind it. And the better you take them into account, the more you can come to the conclusion whether to trust it or not" (female, Group 3). "My trust in science, if I may emphasise, is not unlimited anyway. Because science always takes place under certain framework conditions, is made by people, and functions on certain data bases. It is also linked to many interests, so you always have to look very carefully..." (male, Group 1). A concrete example for such particular interests was brought up by one participant who suspected Kyle Sheldrick, the scientist voicing his doubts about the Ivermectin study, to pursue his own interests by going public with his accusations. These interests do not necessarily need to be negative, they should only always be considered when judging any kind of scientific content. At the same time, participants also claimed that it increases their trust in science when they perceive research to be done "for the common good" (female, Group 3).

The role of Kyle Sheldrick has not only been discussed in regard to particular interests but much more in relation to the **importance of peer-review and scientific self-control mechanisms**. As stated above, participants were convinced that in most cases, research is done right. But when there are mistakes, it is seen positively when these are discovered and discussed by academic peers: "science as a system is functioning" (male, Group 2). When potential problems with research data are published by hackers as it happened in the climate gate scandal, however, this does not have the same effect.

This leads to the next important aspect participants brought up in relation to research integrity: **transparency**. Mistakes can always happen and, as such, participants did not perceive them as a huge impact factor for their trust in science. Much more important was the way they were handled. Self-reflection of scientists and the courage to admit mistakes were named as inspiring trust. Handling allegations of fraud with general 'blah-blah' instead of concretely refuting them one by one on the other hand fuelled mistrust (as perceived to be the case for the university's press release). Participants wished for open and public debates with scientists being an active part of them, for example in the reflection of the Covid-19 pandemic. They however expressed the feeling

that this was not something supported by the responsible political actors and public culture more generally.

The last important factor discussed by participants in the context of research integrity was **open science**. While the term as such was used rather by participants working with science or scientists, also those not dealing with science in their daily lives underlined the importance of sharing data and how this influences their feeling of trust: “If there is really some truth behind it, then I am willing to share. If it serves all of humanity, I would reveal that. I would do that if I knew I was really doing something for the common good, because then I wouldn’t have to hide anything. And that’s something that makes me doubt” (female, Group 3). Altogether, participants agreed that open science was something inspiring trust, and vice versa that scientists refusing to publish their data made them think they had something to hide. However, in two of the small groups the question also arose whether scientists really should always share their data. One argument in this regard was that scientists might regret sharing because others could steal their ideas, once again criticising the atmosphere of strong competition between scientists (see also section 3.1). From a totally different perspective, it was also brought up that some scientific discoveries or knowledge might make people insecure or might have other societal side effects difficult to control, especially when discoveries are not entirely confirmed, yet. So, they might be better kept secret. Contradicting this point of view, others argued that ‘non-communication’ by scientists might be dangerous as well: if not publicly discussed, new knowledge might be (mis-)used by certain groups of actors for their own particular means.

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

The following section analyses participants’ opinions on various forms and degrees of public involvement in science and its potential influence on their trust in science. Very generally, discussions about public participation were much more fluid and livelier than those about research integrity. Participants seemed to feel much more inspired and maybe also entitled to give their opinion. The topic seemed much more accessible for them.

3.4.1 Personal and desired involvement

Personal experiences with scientific involvement

Participants had very different own experiences of participation in the scientific process. Some had already taken part in citizen science projects like Vigie-Nature, others found it interesting but would not participate themselves because of a lack of time or also because they doubted having enough knowledge and the capability to conduct data collection appropriately. One participant stated that she had always been interested in nature-related projects but thought: “But on my little balcony, what could I possibly see there?” (female, Group 3). All underlined how important it was to be interested in the topic at stake in order to be willing to participate. They all stated that their own motivation to participate in such projects would stem from their personal perception that the topic was important rather than from the willingness to contribute to science as such.

Confronted with the fact that they were participating in a scientific project right now, participants expressed that they would not necessarily prioritise their contribution to science in this regard but that it was interesting for them to discuss topics which one would normally not reflect on as much in a group with other citizens. This led to a self-reflection process and for one participant also to

a broader definition of what is ‘science’. One participant also shared the thoughts he had before the event: “I came here with a very open mind, without prejudices, and wanted to get an idea of whether the whole thing makes sense and how it came into place. And whether there is perhaps some bias or whether there are perhaps some people who are pursuing particular goals or have certain ways of thinking that are all the same. Or whether there are actually citizens with different opinions” (male, Group 4). The dialogue was also seen as a way of communicating towards science – an important aspect for science communication which should, according to one participant, always go into both directions.

Desired public participation

In terms of desired public involvement in the scientific process, participants agreed on several main aspects across the small groups. First of all, they all underlined that the desired degree of public involvement had a strong **topic dependency**. There were two key aspects mentioned in this regard: the most important one was that providing citizens with decision-making power in sensitive, controversial topics requiring lots of specific knowledge, such as the vaccination of children, is not appropriate and even irresponsible. Citizens should not be able to take such decisions in the name of others and it also unfair to lay that burden on them: “It seems as if citizens are supposed to take a position on a scientific topic, which is not their task. As if responsibility is handed over” (female, Group 1). At the same time, participants also expressed that asking citizens to take such a decision gives a weird impression of ‘science’ and creates a feeling of insecurity among the public: why do the experts need our opinion on that? Don’t they know what is right? Other participants, particularly parents, noted that they would be glad to be included in the debate about a topic such as vaccination for children. Not in the way that they would like to take any decision, though, but that their voices and concerns would be heard, that they could exchange thoughts with medical experts on the topic and maybe provide a new perspective.

From a more general perspective, the participants made very clear that the underlying **intention** and motivation for public integration in science is important. Three out of four groups expressed the opinion that the public consultation on the topic of children’s vaccination was not an actual public participation in the scientific process (in the remaining group, the responsibility aspect was much more dominant). Participants perceived the entire process as a manipulation of the citizens during a highly controversial political process disguised as scientific involvement: “citizen participation as a fig leaf!” (male, Group 1). Participants had the clear impression that political actors only used citizens to legitimise a decision that had already been taken and instrumentalised the scientific expert group for their aims. Citizens were manipulated in thinking that they would participate in the decision-making process without actually having any say in it. In the eyes of the participants, disguising this political manoeuvre as scientific involvement might have adverse consequences for actual citizen science projects. One participant summed this discussion up in stating that it is good to make people participate and ask about their opinion, but only when it is a transparent process that is not influenced by politics.

This leads to a number of other important aspects that participants identified for public involvement in the scientific process concentrating less on the desired degree but rather on the desired way for it to be done. The first one among them is, once again (see section 3.3), **transparency**. The actual role citizens play in a scientific project needs to be made clear and it should be ensured that citizens understand the scientific methods used and the decisions taken. It is also important that participants can talk to experts and ask questions about the project. In the same vein, different groups underlined that it is important that citizens’ **participation in the entire**

scientific process is ensured. Relating to the Vigie-Nature case, participants made clear that citizens in citizen science projects should not only be ‘used’ as unpaid data collectors (“degraded to data counters”, “unpaid scientists”, “exploitative”) but that their contribution needs to be valued and that they should be taken along in the entire course of the project – through explanations of the scientific methods, communication of the results etc.

The last aspect that participants underlined to be important for public involvement in science was the **representativeness** of the citizens who participate. Participants expressed an overall desire for more participation including groups of society that are difficult to reach – the question being however how to reach them.⁴ The concern was expressed that without proper representativeness, certain opinions in a process such as a public consultation may be overrepresented and mostly this would be those of the ‘louder’ people, not necessarily representing the majority of citizens. A few ideas how such representativeness could be reached were a mixed on- and offline recruitment, the random selection of participants, for example for bodies like citizens’ councils, and support that one would need to provide for participants, e.g., babysitting facilities enabling young parents to participate.

3.4.2 Benefits and problems of public integration in science

Some of the important variables participants identified with regard to how public integration in science should look like already hint at potential problems that may emerge when aiming to involve citizens in the scientific process. Overall, for the participants, the benefits of such involvement seemed to exceed the problems that may arise, though. The following sub-section analyses the most important benefits and problems participants discussed for public integration in science, distinguishing between the scientific and the societal contributions public integration can make.

Scientific contributions – expertise vs. passion

Most participants saw citizen science projects, such as Vigie-Nature, as a successful way to contribute to scientific findings and in the bigger picture also to larger topics such as climate change. It was seen as very positive that some citizen projects actually become known nationwide and receive large attention also in the scientific field.

Concerning the quality of the scientific results, there were diverging opinions among the participants: some stated that citizens’ involvement might decrease data quality because citizens do not have the necessary expertise. Further, there would be a lack of standardisation in the data collection process. Contrarily to that, other participants saw public integration increasing the quality of scientific studies: by providing perspectives outside the scientific bubble (in the case of consultations or dialogues) and by allowing more comprehensive data sets (in the case of projects like Vigie-Nature). Lots of citizens participating in a citizen science project are able to cover more time and space with their observations than a small group of experts. Participants in citizen science projects were even identified as the “independent experts” (female, Group 3) everybody should wish for, because they are not paid, they have no incentive to cheat, and no third-party interests are likely to influence their contribution. They participate because they have

⁴ It is interesting that participants discussed the exact same question all POIESIS teams were confronted with during the recruitment process for the event.

a passion for the topic, and this might make them better data collectors than overwhelmed scientists with the pressure to finish as many scientific projects as possible in a short amount of time.

Societal contributions – access to the ivory tower and self-efficacy

While the contributions to science that citizen science projects can make⁵ was important in the eyes of the participants, the societal role public involvement in science may play seemed to be even more salient for them. Citizen science projects were seen as a way to raise enthusiasm and awareness for particular topics but also for science in general. By making science accessible and increasing the transparency and comprehensibility of scientific work for people who normally do not get in touch with science much, such projects may contribute to **increased trust in science**. Participants used different expressions such as “stepping down from the ivory tower” and “opening the black box”, making clear that science is perceived as something distant and far from citizens’ daily life – an impression participants said might change through the participation in a citizen science project. Feeling closer to science might also increase the general acceptance of new scientific findings among citizens on the one hand, and on the other hand also provide them with the ability to critically access information and scrutinise potential new scientific findings. As many expressed insecurity in judging the trustworthiness of sources and information to be an important problem, to better understand scientific methods and processes might help citizens to feel more confident in this regard.

Participants also saw increased public involvement in scientific processes as a way to **exchange perspectives** – with other citizens as a useful form of processing and discussing important topics instead of “getting angry alone in front of the TV” (female, Group 3); and also between citizens and scientists in a process of ‘crossing bubbles’: “And that’s where we need, actually, the people, maybe you [the organisers of the event] too, who create such a connection. I think that’s really important, because I notice that those in science have their bubble, their scientific bubble, and we have our everyday bubble, and we need to find an overlap. And I think everyone can benefit from that” (female, Group 3).

As a last aspect, several participants also saw the participation in a scientific project as an **experience of self-efficacy**. By contributing actual data to a scientific project, citizens feel needed, seen, and important. They can make a difference in science and science becomes tangible. This might help people to identify with this often distant ‘ivory tower’ more easily. The other side of this coin is the importance that citizens’ contributions are truly **valued** in any scientific project open for participation (see also above). If this is not the case, the initial positive effect of getting closer to science through an experience of self-efficacy might backfire and lead to frustration and ultimately decreased trust in science.

3.4.3 Influence of public integration on trust in science

Reflecting on the question whether public integration had an influence on their trust in science, it became apparent that participants weighed the arguments in favour and against participation

⁵ The debate on this topic concentrated very much on actual citizen science projects such as Vigie-Nature as most participants did not perceive the public consultation as a form of public involvement in science but in politics.

differently, therefore leading to different consequences for their trust in science. Asked whether they would trust a citizen science project more than a project carried out entirely by scientists, some participants stated that they would not, because citizens lack the necessary expertise, while others said yes, because citizens have a stronger personal motivation and involvement leading to better results. Generally, trust in citizen science projects was said to be higher when there are clear rules and procedures to follow for the citizens who want to participate.

Those participants who stated that public involvement in general had a **positive influence** on their trust in science particularly stressed the increased insights into scientific work that one might gain ("behind the scenes" (male, Group 1)) and the fact that science would become closer to their personal life: "Making this connection that science is not something that takes place or explores things split off from me or my life, but that it has something to do directly with me, with me in my environment" (female, Group 1).

Other participants stated that there was **no influence** on their general trust in science either because citizen projects were not seen as being actually 'scientific'; or because they have no scientific weight ("a nice little citizen project" (male, Group 2)); or because as such, they are not any different than other scientific projects. In this view, they represent a scientific method as any other and therefore have no influence on one's trust in science – neither positive nor negative.

One participant also stated that because citizen science projects were not scientific, as citizens lack expertise and objectivity, they rather have a **negative influence** on her trust in science. The large majority of participants did however not share this opinion but saw citizen science projects and public involvement very positively (see also section 3.7). One participant even reflected in the following way on her personal relation to science: "It's not that I have to do something big, but that I can make a difference on a small scale. That's what I want for every single citizen. If everyone joins in, we can achieve a lot. Yes, to the positive. So, if we can also make a lot of negative things happen, we can also do the same in the other direction" (female, Group 3, no scientific background).

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

Communication channels, their roles, responsibilities, and trustworthiness were a highly debated topic throughout the entire event. Before going more into detail into the participants' perspective on communication channels, three crucial and overarching variables have been identified among the participants' arguments:

Nearly all participants expressed a feeling of being overwhelmed, confused and insecure in the face of an **overflow of information** coming from a sheer endless number of sources. They were generally unsure about appropriate criteria of trustworthiness and this especially with regard to online sources. They also had the feeling that important information and topics get lost because there is just too much information available.

Another recurring argument regarding all kinds of communication channels was the balance between **comprehensibility of content** and what could be judged unscientific writing. According to the participants, purely scientific texts are nearly inaccessible for laypeople. Breaking scientific content down too much, on the other hand, might lead to oversimplification and platitudes. Channels of communication are held responsible for managing this difficult task: "[...] That lay people and experts can also check it [...] you would have to create two texts or two ways of

approaching the matter somehow. Because I don't understand the scientific language, or I don't want to deal with it for so long until I understand. [...] That's why I wish that communication would do something about it. [...]" (female, concluding plenary debate, full quotation in Appendix D).

Several groups also raised the general question of what is more important: the **content or the channel of communication** when judging the trustworthiness of any kind of communication. Participants had mixed opinions about that with some stating that they had a basic trust in particular sources and all their communications while others underlined that any kind of source might be used to spread false or biased information: "That's why I don't care who publishes it or which newspaper publishes it or what. What matters to me is the content, which can either be true or partly true. And I check this on the basis of my life and knowledge experiences" (female, Group 4).

3.5.1 Reasons to trust or distrust communication channels

Many different reasons for trusting or distrusting different channels of communication were discussed in the small groups. Participants saw the channel's **reputation** and seriousness as crucial influencing factors for trust. They also mentioned that it was important to them whether they see any **specific interests** behind the reporting, like earning easy money or attracting new readers rather than concentrating on sharing scientific evidence.

While these factors rather had to do with the channel of communication itself, other factors were directly linked to the way the news were presented. The degree of **detail and elaboration** were named in this regard: communications that seem too short or superficial might be misleading or appear to be not well researched. Articles should use **references** in the sense of classical scientific references to make it possible for the reader to dive deeper into the topic. There should also be references to persons or institutions of interest for the topic. The **layout** can also have an influence on trustworthiness as an excessive amount of pictures is perceived as untrustworthy or challenging for processing the content. Finally, the use of **language** was important here once again (see also section 3.2): while strong wording ("bold", "dramatic") seemed not trustworthy to one participant, too carefully phrased wording ("assuming" vs. "knowing") seemed not trustworthy to another. One participant suspected that very emotional language might influence the judgement of some readers more than the actual content of the news.

The probably most important aspect in judging the trustworthiness of any channel of communication were however personal **preconceptions** about certain forms of communication channels in general, particular publishers, or institutions. Participants stated that certain newspapers for example directly inspired trust or distrust. The same newspaper can evoke entirely opposite feelings among citizens, though, and whether it is trust or distrust depends very strongly on the own personal and also political convictions. One participant reported how this however has changed for her very personally over the years: "I come from a very simple background and grew up with Bild [the biggest German tabloid]. And then I did my Abitur [German school-leaving diploma] and suddenly I had other newspapers in front of me. At first, I was completely overwhelmed by all the long texts. [...] now I see the other ones in comparison and I would say they are brainwashing, yes." (female, Group 3, full quotation in Appendix D).

Trustworthy and non-trustworthy channels of communication

This leads to a more general analysis of trustworthy or non-trustworthy channels of communication in the eyes of the participants. As already stated, the newspaper used for presenting the Ivermectin study article to two of the groups is a renowned weekly German **newspaper**, called 'DIE ZEIT'. All participants discussing this newspaper (and also those discussing the facebook post by a journalist from this newspaper) underlined the seriousness of the newspaper. One participant acknowledged that she generally trusts this newspaper and its articles. She feels familiar with it and therefore trusts in what they are reporting. Universities and **scientific institutions** were as such also perceived as rather trustworthy channels of communication. However, the press release about the climate gate scandal raised some serious doubts among the participants whether the university's press department was pursuing particular interests with this communication rather than giving a neutral statement. This led to the initially mentioned question what to focus on more: source or content.

The list of non-trustworthy channels of communication identified by the participants is somewhat longer or at least more comprehensive. Online sources and especially all forms of **social media** were seen very critically by a majority of participants. Facebook was judged as a source not to be taken seriously and as not being the right platform for sharing scientific content and information. Twitter received even worse feedback from most of the participants: it was perceived as very confusing, overwhelming, and its content as being only small talk. One participant stated that the same text presented in form of an email instead of a thread would have been much more accessible to her and therefore, she would have been able to actually evaluate the content of the text. In the format of the thread, she did not even get this far. There were only two participants who voiced different opinions concerning the twitter thread and interestingly, it was two participants who were very familiar with this medium due to their professional background. They actually judged the thread to be a very positive form of science communication and stated that scientists often use twitter to communicate to the outside. This discrepancy and the strong rejection many of those participants who were not very close to science in their daily lives showed towards this medium, might provide food for thought when thinking about appropriate measures of science communication.

Besides social media, **tabloids** and also certain **TV channels** were mentioned as non-trustworthy channels for scientific content. In general, digital content rather raised suspicion among the participants because much of it seemed confusing and messy to them. The same applies to hackers and **whistleblowers** as channels of communication: participants were generally in favour of open debates and also uncovering fraudulent studies but at the same time, these actors' interests were said to be so unclear in most of the cases, that information from such sources should be taken with caution.

3.5.2 Role and responsibility of channels

The participants' opinion on the role and responsibility of channels of communication can be seen as a kind of summary derived from their reasons to trust or distrust certain sources. The most important issue in this regard identified by the participants was that most people (themselves included) read very quickly through any kind of article, news etc. All media therefore have the very challenging task to attract the reader's attention in a short amount of time while still spreading a correct and most objective message.

This leads to the crucial question of how media should present scientific content: by sticking as closely as possible to the original results without bringing in any emotions; or by trying to engage people (including decision-makers) in adapting the language and also the complexity of the presentation. As the science journalist who participated in the event underlined several times, this question also pre-occupies journalists themselves who equally face an overload of information and scarcity of resources.

While this very broad question could of course not be answered in the course of the event, participants however identified some key variables that should be respected by any channel of communication in conveying scientific but in the end any kind of information:

First of all, participants underlined the necessity to receive **sufficient information**. Articles should not be too brief, only delivering headlines, but should give people the chance to inform themselves.

In the same vein, a **diversity of perspectives** presented to the news recipients was perceived as important and at the same time controversial. On the one hand, research findings should be put into perspective, e.g., by presenting several or even opposing points of view. On the other hand, presenting several perspectives might also be confusing (“Which would one believe then? [...] It is negative for me that you now have two sides practically for you or against you and actually have no statement” (male, Group 4)) or even counterproductive when addressing controversial perspectives (“the moment you bring it up, of course, is in the head” (male, Group 2)). Nevertheless, generally, participants were convinced that the media⁶ should present different voices in order to allow readers to paint their own ‘objective’ picture. Equally, media should ensure their **objectivity** and not polarise with overly emotional statements. This aspect leads once again to the use of language and the importance of **comprehensibility** as a responsibility for channels of communication. In this regard, the **awareness of the target group** for any kind of communication was seen to be crucial. Is the article addressed to a scientific or a non-scientific public? How to make sure that the reader receives the ‘right’ message from the communication? Participants observed that depending on their background – even within the small groups – people read and judged content differently and this needs to be taken into account by channels of communication.

Finally, participants underlined the importance of the **transparency of the sources** used in the communication – who is stating what and based on which scientific references – and that the channel of communication is not pursuing any self- or third-party interests with its communication.

3.5.3 The influence of communication channels on participants’ perception of content and trust

The influence of specific communication channels on people’s perception of trustworthiness was perceived to be high among the participants: most of them stated that their judgement of trustworthiness is strongly influenced by the media in which the content is presented. Sometimes, they said not even to get to the content of a communication because they would be too much impacted by the communication channel or an inaccessible form of presentation (such as a twitter thread). Participants also suspected that for most people, scientific news in the media would rather directly impact their trust in science than their trust in the communication channel because ‘normal citizens’ would not necessarily question the quality of the reporting but just the news behind it.

⁶ It should be noted that most of the discussion focussed on media. Mediators or other channels of communication were not really part of the discussion.

Interesting observations in regard to the influence specific channels of communication can have on the perception of scientific content have been made comparing the discussions in the small groups that discussed cases based on varying channels of communication. The public consultation on children's vaccination against Covid-19 was presented to the participants either in form of a TV report or a facebook post, authored by a TV reporter. No diverging observations concerning the content of the news were made by the different groups in this context. The text for the climate gate scandal took the form of a university press release in two groups and a twitter thread in two other ones. In both cases, the format of the communication was judged mainly negative: the twitter thread created lots of confusion (see above) and the press release was seen very critically as well. An important difference in appreciation could however be stated between the groups that received the text for the Ivermectin study in form of an article, allegedly published in a renowned German newspaper, and those reading the same text in form of a facebook post, authored by a journalist from the same newspaper. The latter groups were much more critical towards the way the case was presented. It was said that the journalist just threw in different opinions without taking sides and therefore confusing the reader. The groups with the newspaper article rather perceived this presentation of the different perspectives as positive and 'objective'. The same text, presented through different channels, therefore created very different impressions among the readers.

3.6 Other themes

Even if already mentioned several times before, especially in relation to influencing factors of trust (see section 3.2), the role **potential conflicts of interest between science, politics and the economy** played in the small group discussions was so important that it is analysed in a bit more detail here. In all groups, this topic was discussed extensively and in Group 4, the one with the participants who were all 'united by their distrust in politics', it was actually dominating the entire debate (see also section 2.2.4). It has already been stated that participants generally agreed on the idea that nearly all research and also science communication were influenced by particular interests. Very important in this regard were potential economic and political interests. It was assumed that researchers are very often influenced by who is funding their research and therefore by the question whom to please in order to receive money. All kinds of funding were seen as problematic in this regard: public funding because scientists were suspected to work for the government and private money because they might do research in the direction of specific economic interests. Many studies were also seen as being biased from the start in the sense that scientists would already know what they wanted to show and then work towards this result instead of proceeding with an open mind.

In general, the view on politics and politicians among participants was rather negative. Politicians were said not to listen to scientific findings enough, and when they do, then only to those findings supporting their own perspective. Therefore, it was said that when scientists get involved with politics, they should try to find a way not only to be seen as the longer arm of the politicians.

The participants' suspicion concerning the strong influence of political or financial interests was not only related to scientists but also to the media: it was argued that media reporting is also influenced by the question how much money anybody would want to make with what kind of news. This has a strong influence on which (scientific) news citizens actually receive.

Two other themes that were discussed, but to a smaller extent, were **globalisation** as an important factor in the pandemic but also in the climate crisis (not in a negative way but just in the sense

that it needs to be considered in this context) and **data protection**. Some participants mentioned they were not surprised by the hacking of scientific data. One stated she did not possess a smartphone so that she could not be tracked and would “not send any data to the US” (female, Group 1).

3.7 Card sorting exercise

The card sorting at the end of the small group discussions was challenging for most of the groups, but it also turned out to be an interesting reflection exercise about the most important take-aways of the afternoon.

To gain detailed insights into their appreciation of the cases, participants were asked to answer the question: “How would each of these cases affect your trust in science?” and to place each case on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from positive to negative with the middle point being ‘no influence on my trust’. This was first done individually by each participant. Then the results of the participants were collected on a flipchart in each group, and it was discussed which were the most important aspects for the individual decisions and whether a group decision could be reached. This was not always the case. The results from the four small groups were then reported to the facilitator and discussed case-wise in the concluding plenary session (photos of the group results and the final comparative slide on which basis the discussion in plenary took place are attached in Appendix C).

Comparing the results from the small groups is rather difficult as the rankings were made on the basis of very different dimensions of the single cases (for more detailed insights on this, see also section 2.2). A good illustration for this is the double ranking of case 2B by Group 3: they could not agree on one single result because they perceived the content of the climate gate story rather positive but were very confused and frustrated by its presentation in a twitter thread, impacting their trust negatively (because in real life they would not even have gotten to the bottom of the story). In general, **case 2** raised a lot of confusion and was perceived very differently across the groups.

Turning to the other cases, **case 4** was generally perceived to have a positive or rather positive influence on participants’ trust in science. An exception to this were two participants in Group 4 who considered that a project like Vigie-Nature was not ‘science’ and that therefore, it would either have no or even a negative influence on their trust in science. The third participant of the group judged the citizen science project to have a positive influence, so no group result could be reached.

Case 1 was either perceived to be rather positive or negative depending on the focus of the debate: the communication channel, which in case of the facebook post was perceived negatively, or the fact that through some kind of ‘peer review’, the fraudulent study had been discovered, which had a more positive influence on trust.

Case 3 was perceived negatively or as having no influence by three out of four groups. The justification was similar for all of them: most importantly, the topic of children’s vaccination should not be part of a public consultation according to the participants. Secondly, however, it was argued that this was not even an actual public involvement in a scientific but rather in a political process, disguised as a scientific participation. In Group 4, again, opinions were very divergent, but all participants agreed that as such, asking the public about important topics (even if not necessarily about this one or in this form) had a positive influence on their trust.

Altogether, even if it was a difficult task, it seemed that participants enjoyed sharing their views, exchanging their arguments, and sometimes noticed how initially totally different individual rankings came together as one group result when talking through the different dimensions of the cases. Participants were also very keen to share their arguments and group decision processes during the plenary session.

Table 1. Trust in science: Results of the group ranking

Influence on trust	Group 1 (green)	Group 2 (orange)	Group 3 (red)	Group 4 (blue)
Positive			4	
Rather positive	2B, 4	4	1A, 2B (content)	3B
No influence	1A	3A		
Rather negative	3B	2A	2B (form), 3A	1B
Negative				
No group result		1B		2A, 4

4 Attitudes towards science & technology

This section shortly presents some of the results from the questionnaires distributed to the participants before and after the event. Even though the data comes from only a small sample of people, the descriptive statistics can provide some insights into the participants' general attitudes towards science and technology (S&T) and how this might have changed during the event. It is also briefly explained whether this was the first time the participants have been part of an event like this dialogue and what impact their participation might have on them in the future.

4.1 Attitudes towards Science and Technology

The first and second questionnaire both contained questions on the participants' attitudes towards S&T. They were asked to indicate their agreement with the statements listed below on a 5-point Likert scale. Table 2 and Figure 1 show the participants' answers before and after the event. For the calculation of the mean, some of the items have been reversed (indicated by an R), so that higher values always indicate a more positive opinion towards S&T.⁷ The percentage of agreement is left in its original form.

Table 2. Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

	Before	After	
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⁷ This means, the higher the mean, the stronger the agreement to a statement that reflects a positive view on S&T (3,0 = neither nor). To correctly interpretate the mean of items 2 and 3 they need to be read as follows: "Science and technology DO NOT make our lives change too fast." and "We DO NOT depend too much on science and not enough on faith."

Item	Mean	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	Mean	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	Difference in means
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	3,27	1,27	55%	3,85	0,55	77%	0,57
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast. (R)	3,00	1,25	36%	3,23	2,09	31%	0,23
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith. (R)	3,82	1,66	27%	4,31	1,11	15%	0,49
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	2,30	1,16	18%	2,23	0,73	0%	-0,07
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2,45	1,21	27%	2,38	1,33	23%	-0,07

Note. N range = 11-13

Figure 1: Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

Note. N range = 11-13

Right before the event, a small majority of the participants agreed or strongly agreed with the statement “S&T make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable”. After the event, more participants, precisely 3 out of 4, considered this to be true. This is the item with the strongest and with a very positive evolution throughout the event. In the same vein, the agreement with the statement “S&T make our lives change too fast” slightly decreased from before to after the event.

Already in the beginning, it was however only 36% of participants who indicated that they agreed to that. Only a minority of participants agreed to the idea that “we depend too much on science and not enough on faith” (27% before and 15% after the event).

Considering these three items, we can conclude that in the eyes of the participants, science has a positive and not a too important role in our society. Items 4 and 5 show nevertheless, that this does not mean that the participants would be willing to blindly follow scientists’ opinions. The agreement to the statement “scientists know best what is good for people” was already very low before the event (18%) and after the event, none of the participants (0%) actually still believed this to be true (38,5% indicated however that they neither agreed nor disagreed). “We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology” also received decreasing agreement before and after the event (from 27% to 23%).

With such a small number of participants, one needs to be very careful with general conclusions drawn on this data. Nevertheless, the overall picture seems to indicate that the general image of science among the participants was a better one than the one of scientists. Or to specify a bit more: participants were generally convinced that science is positive for them and for society, but this does not mean that they would give absolution to scientists believing that all they do is beneficial as well.

4.2 Participation in the event

For most participants (9 out of 13 who answered the question, 69%), it was the first time that they had participated in an event like this where the public was invited to discuss science. A few of them (31%) had however already done so before.

Most participants indicated several impacts that this event might have on them. The answers (displayed in Table 3) reflect the generally very positive feedback on the event that was also expressed during the discussions. The majority of participants were very enthusiastic about the event and the possibility to discuss these matters with other citizens. It is therefore not surprising that a huge majority of them also indicated that they would get involved in events like this in the future and talk to friends and family about this issue (both 77%). A small majority will also follow news stories on this issue. Only one participant did not see any of these impacts but indicated “we will see” in the open text field. Additionally, to the other impacts, one participant stated to be very interested in the results and more possibilities of feedback.

Table 3. Impacts of event on participants: Results (%)

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	77%
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	77%
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	54%
4. Other	8%

Note. N = 13

Taking a very general perspective on the survey data, the participants appeared to have a rather positive view on science and an even more positive feeling when leaving the event. They also seemed to have gained some confidence or inspiration during the event as their answers to the open questions in the questionnaires are much longer and more detailed after than the ones before the event.

5 Appendix

A: Full results from Question 4 in the Questionnaires

Table 4. Questionnaire 1, question 4: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	9,1%	45,5%	27,3%	0,0%	18,2%	0,0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	9,1%	27,3%	18,2%	27,3%	9,1%	9,1%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	18,2%	9,1%	0,0%	18,2%	54,5%	0,0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	0,0%	18,2%	18,2%	27,3%	27,3%	9,1%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	0,0%	27,3%	18,2%	27,3%	27,3%	0,0%

Note. N = 11

Table 5. Questionnaire 2, question 4: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	7,7%	69,2%	23,1%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	23,1%	7,7%	30,8%	30,8%	0,0%	7,7%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	0,0%	15,4%	0,0%	23,1%	61,5%	0,0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	0,0%	0,0%	38,5%	46,2%	15,4%	0,0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	7,7%	15,4%	15,4%	30,8%	30,8%	0,0%

Note. N = 13

B: The “trust wall” (introductory plenary session)

Translation (from left to right):

What does 'trust' mean for you?

First row:

“Positive attitudes towards something lying in the future”

“Certainty of expectations”

“In any case, no ‘blind’ trust, e.g. as far as ‘the’ science is concerned”

Second row:

“Relief to hand over responsibility”

“Not to be afraid of being taken advantage of”

“The assumption that someone is acting (also) in my interest”

Third row:

“Trust is good, control is better”

“To be able to rely without restriction”

Fourth row:

“To believe is not to know”

C: Results of the ranking exercise

Small group results:

Group 1 (green)

Group 2 (orange)

Group 3 (red)

Ivermectin-Studie
(Corona)

Climategate-Skandal
(Klima)

Öffentliche Konsultation
(Corona)

Vigie-Nature
(Klima)

Group 4 (blue)

Comparative slide with all group results for the plenary session:

D: Full quotations

“Well, I think that somehow you have to try to manage the balancing act, so that the scientific aspect always remains in the back of your mind, of course. That lay people and experts can also check it out, at least as far as possible. Or they can get an idea of who financed it, etc., how the data was collected, but that people like me can also understand it. I would still like to have a communication, a simpler communication. And for that, you would have to create two texts or two ways of approaching the matter somehow. Because I don’t understand the scientific language, or I don’t want to deal with it for so long until I understand. It takes too long for me to build up the knowledge. And then I switch off before that. That’s why I wish that communication would do something about it. The simple version, and then you can dive deeper into it. Everything has to be transparent.” (female, concluding plenary debate)

“I come from a very simple background and grew up with Bild. And then I did my Abitur and then suddenly, I had other newspapers in front of me. At first, I was completely overwhelmed by all the long texts. I was completely overwhelmed by all the long texts, because I had grown up with bold and simple newspapers. Yes, really, but without any judgement. But that was just the way it was and it was too much for me at first. And now I am grateful that I have read more and more into it, because now I see the other ones in comparison and I would say they are brainwashing, yes.” (female, Group 3)

Annex D: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – Greece

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *Greece*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

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1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the event

The public deliberative workshop (WS) in Greece took place at the center of Athens, on Saturday the 13th of May 2023, from 16:00 until 20:00 at the Titania Hotel. The place was selected, because it is conveniently located at an area that is supported by various means of public transport. A non-working day was selected so as to be possible for people to be able to participate, without having to take a leave from their employers, something that would have put a significant risk of having reduced participation.

A total of 32 people attended the Greek public deliberative WS. Four groups were created, each of them having eight participants. The public deliberation WS was facilitated by a professional facilitator, who was aided by a member of the NTUA team (P. Kavouras). Each of the four groups was moderated by one member of NTUA team (N. Sarla, L. Ananiadis, V. Stavridi, E. Spyrou); as a result the total number of facilitator and moderators was six.

Experts: Two experts introduced the participants to the event. The first expert made a presentation on COVID-19, the development of the vaccine, and the political decisions that had to be made and the second expert made a presentation on Climate Change. Some details with regard to the experts follow:

- First expert: [Iris-Theodora Vlachantoni](#) (female), medical doctor specializing in Pulmonology. He holds a Master's degree in Public Health from the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (London) and a PhD in Public Health from the London School of Hygiene and Public Health (Athens Medical School). After her specialization in Athens, she worked for for seven years in London as a clinician. She worked for seven years as a clinical physician in public hospitals (St Thomas', Kingston, North Middlesex Hospital) and as a clinical fellow at St. Thomas's Hospital, Kingston, North Middlesex Hospital) and as a clinical fellow at research projects (Imperial College). Since 2022 he has been living in Athens and working at Sotiria Hospital as a curator. She has a special interest in preventive medicine (in particular the screening for lung cancer) and in improving access to the system access to health care for people belonging to socially disadvantaged groups and vulnerable groups.
- Second expert: [Elissavet Feloni](#) (female), is adjunct lecturer at the Department of Surveying and Geoinformatics Engineering, University of West Attica. As a postdoctoral researcher, she collaborates on projects with the Centre for Hydrology and Informatics (Department of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens), with the Laboratory of Climatology and Atmospheric Environment (Faculty of Geology and Geoenvironment, University of Athens) and she is a postdoctoral fellow at the Department of Mechanical Engineering and Materials Science and Engineering (Cyprus University of Technology) with a full postdoctoral scholarship by the Bodossaki Foundation. She holds Bachelor in Geology and Geoenvironment from School of Science (NKUA), MSc in Water Resources Science & Technology (NTUA), MSc in Prevention & Management of Natural Disasters (NKUA) and PhD from the School of Civil Engineering (NTUA) that was financially supported by the Onassis Foundation Scholarships Program. She

has over eight years of experience as a researcher in EU and GR funded research projects in the research fields of water resources management, hydrology, hydrometeorology, climate change, floods, renewable energy and relevant GIS applications. She has co-authored more than 40 articles in international peer-review journals and international conferences and is a reviewer on numerous scientific journals

Sampling strategy: Based on prior discussions within the POIESIS consortium and, especially, on the decisions taken during the Executive Board meetings that preceded the 2nd General Assembly (Athens, Greece, 22-23 May 2023) the sampling strategy followed by the NTUA team was aiming to attract participants that were gender balanced, from all age categories, educational levels, and occupational profiles. The consortium decided that we should strike the right balance between avoiding being societally non-representative and avoiding being too picky that would result in low number of participants. The recruitment strategy followed by the NTUA team (see section 1.2) was successful in tackling both risks, as seen by the demographics that are presented below as pie charts.

Recruitment strategy: The recruitment process initiated approximately one month before the Greek public deliberative WS, via the advertisement of the event via the following pathways:

- Distribution of the event afichette at the NTUA campus and, more specifically, to students' cafeterias and to the announcement boards of all secretariat offices.
- Via the social media of the research group where the POIESIS beneficiaries from Greece are members of.
- The NTUA members directly informed about the event their friends and acquaintances, in order to utilize them as "ambassadors" of the event to their social circle, with which the members of the NTUA team did not have any connection (snowball sampling).

The only challenge faced was related to the third recruitment pathway; specifically, it was challenging to explain as accurately as possible the aims of the public deliberative WS and to articulate the reason of the need of lay people. According to the discussions NTUA members had with the "ambassadors" of the event, there were concerns from their side and from the side of the people they contacted relevant to their perceived incapacity to participate in a scientific event, since they were lay people.

The last week before the event 43 individuals had signed up for the event; 32 showed up and participated at the event.

1.2 Participants in the event

Figure 1 contains the quantitative presentation of the sample that comprised the participants of the Greek deliberative public WS and, more specifically, the gender balance, the age distribution, their educational level, and their link to science.

Figure 1: Demographics of the Greek public deliberative WS.

From the pie charts of Figure 1 it is evident that the Greek sample was not gender balanced; almost the two thirds were female participants and the remaining were male participants. None of the participants declared to be non-binary. The age distribution can be considered to be relatively representative. Despite of the fact that there was an underrepresentation of the age categories below 24 years old and above 60 years old, the remaining age categories (with the exception of the 44-49 years old category that was not represented) are relatively equally represented.

Educational levels from high school and above were satisfactorily represented. However, there is an evident lack of participants that were graduates from Gymnasium (in Greece this represents

people that followed education until they were 15 years old) and from Elementary school (in Greece this represents people that followed education until they were 12 years old). This is, most possible, due to the fact that public education in Greece is obligatory until the end of Gymnasium, while – especially in non-rural areas like Attica from which recruitment was applied, most people graduate from High schools (in Greece this represents people that followed education until they were 18 years old).

In the sample of Greece, a little less than half of the participants (43,75%) did not have a direct relation with science, i.e. they responded as either been indirectly or occasionally related to science or having no relation to science. The rest of the sample declared having some relation to science.

In Table 1 there is a description of the occupation of the participants. Since the specific question was not a multiple choice one it was not possible to create a pie chart. The responses of the participants are reported in the table below; the level of aggregation was made only where the questions were identical or very similar.

Table 1: The occupation of the participants.

Occupation*	Number of participants	Occupation*	Number of participants
Private employee	4	Psychologist	1
Engineer	3	Data Scientist	1
Freelance professional	2	Pensioner	1
Kindergarten teacher	2	Researcher	1
Administration	2	Teacher	1
Social worker	2	Unemployed	1
PhD Candidate	2	Digital expert	1
Lawyer	2	Soldier	1
Student	1	Pensioner	1
Medical doctor	1		
* Two participants did not fill this question			

2 Discursive summary of cases

This section is a description of the Greek public deliberative WS. It consists of: (a) a concise summary of the two expert talks and the Q&A session that followed and (b) a synthesis of the main ideas discussed in the four break out focus groups.

2.1 Phase 1 – Expert talk

In this first phase of the Greek public deliberative WS two experts provided information on COVID-19 and Climate change. The first expert presentation included information on the virus that produced the COVID-19 pandemic, the course of the pandemic, the reasons that caused the mortality of the COVID-19 virus, the reasons that the pandemic induced extreme strain in most national health systems, information on the development of the COVID-19 vaccine. In the end the expert on COVID-19 presented her opinions on the reasons that the vaccination campaign caused such an upset in many countries. This presentation was very interesting, not only because it provided in an easy-to-understand way the issues with the pandemic, but mainly because the information came from a person that had a direct experience of the whole situation of the course of the pandemic in Greece from the perspective of a medical doctor working in a Greek public hospital.

The second expert presentation provided a wealth of information on the evidence that support that the climate change exists and that it is caused by human activities. The expert devoted a substantive part of her presentation in describing the effects on public trust in science produced by scientific fraud that was related to research on climate change.

The audience posed a number of questions and one of the participants expressed its criticism, quite acute. The criticism revolved around the notions that whatever is funnelled via academic means of communication is not necessarily correct and that the measures imposed by governments, to deal with crises like the pandemic of climate change, are abused and they take the form of measures to discipline or manipulate societies. Two characteristic quotes follow:

“I’m sorry, who’s judging that, the same people doing the research? Do they not accept outside criticism?”

“Where is this complaint? This complaint that it is a population disciplining measure cannot be ignored, it has been written so many times.”

The first quote was during the presentation, when the second expert presented evidence on climate change that was published in the scientific literature. The second quote was at a point when the second expert mentioned that people do not usually understand the connection between individual and global actions and responsibility.

The questions that the participants made were mostly connected to the harshity of the measures most governments took during the pandemic and to the risks that were posed from the use of the COVID-19 vaccine. Some, characteristic, quotes follow:

“Do you feel that ultimately the weighting that the states did in the pandemic response was justified?”

“So was this restriction on freedom of movement and freedom to practise religious freedom in the form of the permanent practice of religious worship justified?”

“(…) was whether the trade-off between health risk from COVID and risk to humans from experimental vaccines, in your opinion always, if it comes out in favor of the vaccines?”

“But no doctor gives me a written statement that yes, it's the vaccine's side effects and since there is no research, how do we know that a vaccine doesn't have these side effects?”

2.2 Phase 2 – Focus groups

2.2.1 Group 1 (RED) – Cases 1A, 2B, 3B, 4

The discussion in Group 1 (RED group), which was conducted in a civilised and friendly manner despite the occasional disagreements between members of the team, focused mainly on public integration in science and chains of mediation. Somewhat surprisingly, the participants mentioned their concerns about RI practices (or the lack of them) quite often, mainly implicitly. Trust in science as an abstract entity was present in the vast majority of the participants, but this was slightly diverged considering scientific and communication actors.

The group faced challenges in understanding Case 2B and this didn't help the discussion in this particular case, despite the fact that the moderator provided them with some additional information. Therefore, the discussion there focused and was treated by most of the participants as an example of bad communication. Participant 1 (G1) attempted to dominate the discussion, but the moderator succeeded to avoid this issue and helped almost every one of the participants (except participant 8 (G1)) to speak in every case. Unfortunately, the moderator failed to entirely prevent some of the participants acting as “science detectives” in the first 2 cases, trying to solve who has the “blame” in the cases, rather than evaluating them. Participant 8 (G1) completed the ranking exercise by placing the cases by the order they were presented, raising questions about its actual interest for the exercise, bearing in mind its overall involvement in the public deliberation WS.

2.2.2 Group 2 (GREEN) – Cases 1A, 2B, 3A, 4

The discussion in Group 2 (GREEN group) included all cases, two of them in a more analytical way, namely 1A and 4. The discussion was very rich during the examination of the cases. One of the two experts also participated in this group. Her presence didn't seem to affect the group discussion. In the first part, the conversation focused mainly on the communication channels and the integrity of the mass media. A common assumption in examining Cases 1A and 2B was that communication channels are primarily motivated by political power and industry influences. Their use for the communication of science, either by the scientists themselves or by other actors, creates a state of suspicion in the public (receiver of the scientific content). Additionally, an issue raised was that the integrity of science as a social issue is relatively low on the list of citizens' concerns, mainly because they are more preoccupied with matters of survival and the quality of their daily lives.

In the second part, the interest shifted to the discussion about the public's involvement in research. Most participants view citizens' participation in science positively; however, issues concerning the extent of this involvement were raised. The level of citizens' engagement in science would

determine the reliability of the scientific outcome, and there were also concerns about the voluntary nature of this participation. According to most participants, citizens' contribution to science constitutes a real work and should, therefore, be rewarded. Furthermore, a view expressed was that science is a system and as such is obliged to operate with its own rules. When science leaves room for intervention by non-scientists, then it risks losing its scientificity and its integrity.

In this specific group, there were no extreme views, and the participants seemed to agree on many occasions. The prevailing sentiment within the green group was the perception of communication channels as unreliable due to their association with political power and industry. The participants appeared that they prefer more traditional media for their information, such as newspapers, as relatively more reliable sources of information. Furthermore, all participants had an entirely positive attitude towards science itself, but not necessarily towards scientists and the ways in which they contact their science and choose to communicate their scientific views.

2.2.3 Group 3 (YELLOW) – Cases 1B, 2A, 3A, 4

The discussion in Group 3 (Yellow group) was smooth, without particular disagreements. Six out of eight participants were actively involved in the discussions, whereas the other two remained mostly silent or consented with other participants' remarks by nodding. However, at the end, they all made their own rankings and confirmed the group's final ranking. Cases 1B and 2A were discussed during the first part of the focus group and Cases 3A and 4 were discussed in the second part. It is worth mentioning that in both parts, the participants had a general discussion based on the topics that were central in the cases first, and, then, discussed the particular cases. This happened spontaneously and allowed the participants to be involved in the discussions and express themselves more openly. Based on the main topics raised in the cases, participants discussed about the COVID-19 pandemic and the vaccines, the way media- both traditional and social- work, the active participation of citizens in decision making, and citizen science. Regarding the two main topics that the experts had analysed plenary, COVID-19 and climate change, the participants of this group focused their discussions more on the first topic.

As far as the topics of integrity and integration are concerned, the participants seemed to have an idea about RI and most of them were aware of good research and publication practices, without, however, using the term 'Research Integrity'. The 'integration' part seemed to be more familiar for the participants. An important part of the discussion was allocated to different aspects of science communication and participants tended to use examples from their own professional and research experience in many instances during the discussion.

2.2.4 Group 4 (ORANGE) – Cases 1B, 2A, 3B, 4

The group discussed at length the first case of each category, while less time was devoted to the other cases. This may be explained by the dynamic of the group, since the first case prompted the interest and emotional reaction of the participants and this spirit remained. Among the eight participants of the group (one of the two experts also participated in this group), two seemed to be dominating the discussion, taking more time to express themselves; three were participating with interest discussing every case; and the last three were not participating that much, but expressed their opinions when asked.

The first group of cases, concerning integrity, profoundly moved some of the participants, since anger was expressed concerning the responsibility of informing/misinforming the general audience. At the same time, the opposite opinion was expressed, concerning the acceptance of the humane aspect of the researchers, without idolizing them. It seemed that the intense discussion of the integrity cases of the first part had an impact on the participants.

At the beginning of the discussion of the integration cases, though the theme was different, the participants were intense and expressed feelings of anger and disappointment, even though this reaction was not in accordance with the theme. This was realized when discussing the final case (4) where the tones were down and the participants followed the spirit of the case.

One interesting note was how participants with scientific background (either as students of science or researchers) seemed to express ideas that nobody else did, like compassion for the researchers, as well as highlighting the concern of citizens involvement in scientific endeavor. Finally, the participants seemed to be more expressive when the case somehow affected them (mothers were reacting more intensely to vaccinating children, researcher were reacting to the administrator's support or lack of it, etc.).

The sense of the group, overall, was that the participants were more eager to discuss their distrust in science and cases of misconduct that troubled them. At the same time, there was little or no reference to their trust in science.

3 Integrity and integration & trust in science

3.1 General attitudes towards science

Group 1 (RED)

There were mostly positive feelings about science that were expressed mainly implicitly by more than half of the participants, namely from five of them. Those people expressed the belief that science serves the “common good” of society in general (participant 1 (G1))⁸, the importance of trust in science (participant 3 (G1)), their trust in scientific methods and procedures (participant 6 (G1)) and their concern about what is useful for science (participant 4 (G1)). Even the fact that some of those participants were hesitant to trust the public integration in research, the way that they expressed it implicates trust in science and its main actors, i.e. the scientists: “*I would have more trust in science rather in citizens, not everyone is an expert*” said participant 8, while participant 4 (G1) stated “*I would prefer a briefing from scientists, because I trust them, rather than participating in a public consultation about this specific matter*”. Only participant 7 (G1) expressed explicitly negative feelings about science in general: “*I have completely lost my trust! I think that everything was done for the money. I suffered a thrombosis after the 1st vaccine. No one seemed to care!*”

Group 2 (GREEN)

In general, all participants were positively disposed towards science as a process and abstract entity. The statement indicating emphatically a positive attitude toward science came from participant 3 (G2), “*I always believe in science and what my doctor will tell me*”. During the discussion, all participants agreed on the experimental nature of science and on the fact that it cannot give definitive answers. Such answers made them suspicious of the person making them. As it was stated by participant 3 (G2), “*(...) but I think the doctors themselves, going on the basis of small little steps, based on what they saw. I like to think so, because if they weren't experts, they would say here's the miracle drug I know, it's found and it's over.*” Therefore, the inability to provide definitive answers is not seen as undermining reliability.

However, some participants expressed reservations, not in relation to the science itself but concerning the instrumentalization of science from political power, for the purpose of manipulating the masses and from industry, for the purpose of profit. Specifically, the discussion that highlighted this view was the one related to the case concerning COVID-19 (1A). The participants brought up the concerns of citizens that prevailed during the pandemic, regarding vaccines and the explanation of the COVID-19 virus. A characteristic view came from participant 2 “*(...) produce a drug which, whether it works or not, is marketed as effective for profit. This is something that, during the pandemic, was heard a lot...was heard a lot, and it is also an aspect, so to speak, which raises doubts, suspicions, etc. as to the ethics and integrity, so to speak, of the research process and the production of medicines, and in this particular case.*”

⁸ The reference to participants is done by numbering them, according to the sequence they made their comments in each group. I.e. the first participant that made a comment to Group 1 (RED) is coded as participant 1 (G1).

GROUP 3 (YELLOW)

All participants seemed to have, in general, a positive attitude towards science as a whole, as it affects different aspects of people’s lives in various positive ways (their health, quality of living, and education). For this reason, they expressed various expectations on science and scientists and the idea that people have to trust science for the improvement of their lives. As participant 5 (G3) said: that if people have evaluated their life experiences with reflection, “[they] can understand how important science is and [they] can understand the scientist who is serious or who is an arrogant person who wants to pass, let’s say, something. [...] The doubt is always there. The doubt is also there about the children I’m raising, whether they are what I think they are. Let alone here in science. But I think we have to have 80% confidence in science.”

Trust in science as an endeavour was common among the participants of Group 3, and this should be expected as these participants were all occupied or had been occupied with professions for which they have studied in various scientific fields. Hints of distrust towards science were expressed through comments about some scientists and their questionable practices, as well as about other actors related to science, such as science media/journalists. It was, also, mentioned that the purpose of science should be to serve people, humanity, not to impose certain political decisions by using scientific justification. As participant 7 (G3) mentioned “[S]cience, however, any science, if it is far from man, it cannot listen to reality”.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

The general attitude the participants expressed was that science is the activity that advances civilization. For this reason, scientists should be integral (in terms of not being financially influenced), exactly because of the importance of the work they do. At the same time science was conceived by one participant as ambiguous. This was characterised as necessary but understandable, since it is human beings who implement science and, despite a negative outcome, it is important to know that scientists do their best. In this respect instances of misconduct are even more serious and seems to be incompatible with the science’s impact on society.

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

Table 2: Factors that affect trust in science.⁹

	Reasons for trusting science	Reasons for distrusting science
1	Code of Ethics/Code of Conduct in research/Regulatory framework	Conflict of interests/Conflicts between scientists
2	Research Integrity	Profit from research/ Commercialisation of research (The involvement of the industry, especially pharmaceutical companies)

⁹ This table presents the factors that affect trust in science aggregated for all groups, in order to avoid redundancies, since some of them have been discussed in more than one group.

3	Data credibility	Bad/unethical research practices (lack of Research Integrity and transparency)
4	Scientific Rigour	Lack of credibility for communication channels, e.g. Social media and Mass media
5	Transparency of research and data accessibility	Questioning whether a study has actually taken place
6	Public Integration (democratization of scientific research)	Involvement of political power in science
7	Social use of scientific results/Return of scientific results	The poor living conditions of citizens and the lack of access to basic needs (such as security, healthcare, and adequate wages)
8	Public funding and regulatory framework	Political management of crises related to scientific issues (e.g. the COVID-19 pandemic)
9	Responsibility and accountability	Difference of opinions among the experts
10	Proper science communication	-
11	Public Integration through enabling people to compare scientific data with people's own experiences(e.g. health issues related to pollution)	-
12	Trust to particular, acclaimed scientists (Trustworthy scientists make science trustworthy)	-
13	Independent institutes monitoring and certifying scientific processes	-
14	How science can ameliorate life conditions	-
15	Whether science can afford difference of opinions among the experts	-

Group 1 (RED)

The lack of Research Integrity, data credibility and accessibility that many participants (participants 1, 3, 4 and 6 (G1)) observed, mainly in Case 1A, highlights the importance of their existence in scientific research, according to those participants' views. Participant 3 (G1), for example, says: *"No research should be private or should remain private or its findings or data or its execution. It is the alpha and omega of experimentation. This, since the 17th century. There must be witnesses, the experiment must be repeated very generally (...) and roughly. This has been repeated, of course, and the data cannot be kept secret."*

On the other hand, the commercialisation of research and money in general plays a major role for distrusting the findings of scientific research for almost half of the participants (participants 5, 6 and 7 (G1)). As participant 5 (G1) puts it: *"The drug is a commodity, so it must be sold. So, the person who wants to sell it creates a claim so that he can make it useful, that's why! And not because it is useful necessarily, useful for him means to make a profit"*, while participants 1 and 6 (G1) speak also for conflicts of interests in general.

Group 2 (GREEN)

Among the above-mentioned factors, those considered by the group more prominent were the factors (Reasons for distrusting science) with numbers 5,6,7 at the previous Table. The way communication channels (number 6) handled the issue of COVID-19 and the issue of climate change is a decisive factor in changing citizens' attitudes towards science. All the participants believed that these communication channels, controlled by certain actors, used scientific findings, even conflicting ones, to create a sense of insecurity and fear, making citizens more susceptible to manipulation by political power. Regarding factor 7, it was almost universally agreed that when the industry is involved and profits determine the "truth," citizens become skeptical of the actors in science. That's why many participants expressed the opinion that research should be funded by the public, as participant 2 (G2) stated "*That's why it's important that the funding be public in that sense*" with adequate regulation framework in place, and overall public access to the research results (participant 2 (G2) "*the social use of the results of research (...)*"). Factor 8, was also a point of convergence for many participants. Poor living conditions and the lack of access to basic needs (such as security, healthcare, and wages) lead citizens to be suspicious of the actors in science. This issue was highlighted by participant 1 (G2). Additionally, concerning this factor, the issue of integration was raised, although not explicitly named as such. The opinion expressed regarding integration by participant 1 (G2) is that while there might be a tendency for citizens to be integrated into science, they are somewhat reluctant, due to the problems caused by poor living conditions. Therefore, any intention to integrate citizens into science ultimately benefits only a few privileged individuals.

Both integrity and integration were not explicitly mentioned in the discussion. However, concerning integrity, we could say that the preconditions for conducting a research process with integrity were implied. These include honesty in communication, reliability in performing research, objectivity, impartiality and independence, openness and accessibility, the duty of care, fairness in providing references and giving credit, and responsibility for the scientists and researchers.

Group 3 (YELLOW)

The participants of Group 3 started discussing the issue of trust and distrust in science by using examples from the shared experience of the COVID-19 pandemic and the way this crisis was managed by the State, particularly the measures of social distancing and isolation, and the vaccines. This experience created mixed feelings and views to the participants, since, on the one hand, most of them spoke positively about the vaccines, but, on the other hand, they expressed their skepticism about the way the State tried to convince, and, in some cases, to force the citizens to take the vaccine. As participant 5 (G3) mentioned: "*The approach, the way they tried to convince people to do it was not always orthodox. I absolutely agree with that. I mean, I too, who was convinced that I had to get the vaccine and was waiting for when it was going to come out, to go get vaccinated or to vaccinate my overweight mother, let's say, didn't like the way it was imposed*".

Participant 5 (G3), also, mentioned, from their own experience, cases in which the interaction with scientists helped lay people to be convinced about the need for changes in certain matters affecting their life, eg. the need to change industrial activities in a particular geographical area due to pollution affecting the inhabitants' health. To that direction, science communication and training of people to be able to understand the scientific information they receive was highlighted as crucial for enhancing trust in science.

Although the participants did not use the terms “integrity” and “integration”, they, actually, referred to principles and values related to research integrity and to the importance of involving the public in decisions related to scientific issues affecting people’s lives. Thus, data and publication practices, as well as transparency in scientific methodology were mentioned as very important, affecting science’s trustworthiness. Moreover, the various stakeholders involved in the scientific endeavour, namely scientists, scientific groups, scientific institutions and science communicators/journalists affect science’s trustworthiness by the way of conducting their role.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

The group mentioned two main reasons to trust science: (1) how science can ameliorate life conditions and (2) whether science can afford difference of opinions among the experts. The first reason implied that science provides the knowledge to advance society, while, at the same time, acknowledging the way that science already has and will continue to transform the social environment. As one participant expressed, science’s purpose is to “*bring you the quality of life.*” The second reason is related to the acceptance of the incompleteness of scientific knowledge. As one participant expressed “*when researchers fight viciously in the same field, it’s productive, it’s useful for research so and because no issue has matured.*”

The group focused on five main reasons to distrust science: (1) difference of opinions among the experts, (2) lack of rigorous methods, inability to repeat the studies, non-transparency (3) questioning whether a study has actually taken place, (4) possibility of unethical or non-integral practices by researchers affecting the results of a study (i.e. financial influence, fabrication or falsification of data), (5) dubious personal interest of the researchers affecting the results of the study. The difference of opinions of the experts, which was also mentioned as a reason to trust science, this time interpreted as ignorance, attributed even to the acclaimed experts in their fields. Reason 2 and 3 were mentioned in relevance to the example of COVID-19, specifically expressing uncertainty concerning the rapidity of the circulation of vaccines on the market. Reasons 4 and 5 focused on the personality and the psychological condition of the researchers that lead them to uptake misconduct.

Integration was not explicitly mentioned. It was implied when participants were questioning the conditions of conducting studies (see reasons for distrust). Integration was never mentioned or implied. The absence of any reference to the influence of public involvement on trust was characteristic of this.

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

Group 1 (RED)

As mentioned before, RI (or the lack of it) affects how participants evaluated Cases 1A and 2B (with all the problems that we’ve faced regarding this specific case), as well as scientists and the quality of a scientific research in general. For example, participant 1 (G1) mentioned explicitly the lack of RI on behalf of Dr. Carvalho in Case 1A: “*This is the plagiarism in scientific ethics. So, to me this is a nebulous, nebulous environment; it judges neither research integrity, nor research soundness, nor tangible results of a commonly accepted research effort.*”

In summary, practices that relate with RI issues are mentioned no less than 16 times in total by 6 of the 8 participants with issues such as plagiarism, data manipulation, data accessibility, data credibility mainly mentioned.

Barring the example of participant 7 (G1) we do not have other participants that seemed to lose their trust in science in general because of the lack of RI practices, either from examining those cases, either from their own life experiences, since we do not have an explicit statement to support it. Participants seemed to evaluate those specific cases and then they declared if they would trust those specific studies and the involved researchers, respectively.

Trust in scientists was very high in general among the group; no less than 6 participants declared their trust on them (despite their concerns mentioned in section 3.2) by stating that they would trust either only them (participants 2, 4 and 8 (G1)) or more than any other actor regarding scientific issues, with their only concern being their biases that could preoccupy the results of a research (participants 1 and 5 (G1)). There was no specific discussion nor mentions regarding the role of institutions.

Group 2 (GREEN)

Despite the fact that the participants did not explicitly mention the term "integrity," during the discussion, it was clear that the way in which the participants can trust the actors aligns with the principles of research integrity.

As mentioned above, the participants seemed to fully trust science as an abstract concept; however, some of them were skeptical of scientists and at this point raised the issue of research integrity in a descriptive way. Three out of eight participants would not trust scientists a priori. They think that there are scientists who manipulate data or produce specific results to serve their own interests or those of their funders. A claim that declares such an attitude comes from participant 2 (G2) who was referring to how scientists extracted scientific results that favored tobacco companies and mobile phone companies, in the following: *"(...) with a very quick Google search you will find many, many instances of data cooking by perfectly respectable scientists on a number of key issues."* However, there was one participant (participant 3 (G2)) that trust both science and the actors without distinguishing them. The other four participants did not express an opinion but agreed with those who expressed a suspicion toward scientists.

In general, the fact that some participants brought up examples of poor research practices (and this is how research integrity was usually defined), did not seem to affect their positive attitudes towards science. However, as mentioned by all but one participant, the distinction between science and perpetrators was highlighted throughout the discussion.

Group 3 (YELLOW)

Following the diversity of factors affecting trust in science, the participants in Group 3 expressed similar views on research integrity, particularly during the discussion on Cases 1B and 2A. As already mentioned, they did not use the term 'integrity' but they referred to what the term entails, namely to principles, values, good practices and stakeholders involved, expressing positive opinions on integrity and stressing its importance for science's trustworthiness. They, also, distinguished the different stakeholders, the scientists from the science institutions and science in

general, and the different roles they play in promoting research integrity practices. Scientists are responsible for the data they use and the way they publish their results, about the accessibility of data to other scientists, and the promotion of cross-examination of results and their replicability and reproducibility. On the other hand, scientific institutions are responsible for cross-checking and ensuring that good practices are followed. For this reason, it was considered as important to have independent institutions checking and certifying systems used, e.g. for measurements. As participant 2 (G3) mentioned: *“I, in this text can identify what is missing in order to make a proper assessment on the data. What is missing is independent bodies that communicate with each other, make comments and come up with a proposal. In other words, there may be a data set, what we call a scientific data set, an a, b, c data set, someone will evaluate it, someone will process it, and come to a conclusion. Somebody has to be involved, an independent body to see, let us say, whether the methodology was right, whether it came to the right result.”*

As equally important, it was mentioned that the way scientific results are published and communicated to the public must follow certain rules, which are rules actually related to research integrity, namely peer reviewing processes and citations; the same rules must be followed by science communicators and journalists when they inform the public about scientific developments and particular attention must be paid to the language used in science communication in order to avoid misunderstandings and the creation of hype.

Furthermore, it was, also, mentioned that the dynamics within researchers and possible competitive relations might affect research integrity and quite often the public understands that what is published in the media regarding scientific news might be the result of certain rivalry.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

When discussing cases on RI, the participants mainly focused on transparency (since non-transparency worries the public), taking responsibility of possible misconduct, institutional (top-down) regulation. Their concerns about RI were related to fabrication of data, falsification of data, misrepresentation of the information, facilitating personal interest against rigorous methods and reliability.

The participants acknowledged that research misconduct might be unintentional. They all agreed that if a researcher is found to apply questionable research conduct this might be understandable and indulgence is needed, since researchers are human beings and as such prone to mistakes. But the participants were clear that if research misconduct is proven to be purpose-driven, then there is no excuse and there should be repercussions. Concerning the role of institutions, two opposite opinions were expressed. On the one hand, institutions should check and regulate research beforehand and not try to reconcile after a case appears. The latter was supported by all participants. On the other hand, one participant clearly expressed that the institution should not take any position on an open scientific issue.

The role of mediators in RI cases was discussed thoroughly. The participants agreed that the mediators are entirely responsible for the information they communicate. In this respect issues of facilitating personal interest, the need for repercussions, and transferring personal opinion also arose. One issue that also arose was the relationship between the researchers and the mediators. This was discussed with the question of whether the mediators (i.e., politicians, journalists, etc.) can affect or obstruct scientists from presenting things in a specific way. But, exactly because of their identity only as mediators their actions were characterized also as insignificant or indifferent.

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

Group 1 (RED)

Only two of the Participants shared a previous experience about Citizen Science projects. participant 3 (G1) spoke of a project in the neighbourhood of the city where he/she resides, while participant 7 (G1) mentioned that he/she takes part with his/her children in such projects.

However, most of the participants expressed interest in such projects, especially in those such as the one in Case 4, with most of them advocating for a partial public involvement. Specifically, regarding Case 3B, 3 participants (participants 2, 4 and 8 (G1)) argued in favour of no involvement invoking either that “scientists know better”, especially regarding medical concerns (participants 2 and 4 (G1)) or that they would not be interested as the decision is preoccupied (participant 2 (G1)). Participants 1 and 6 (G1) argued that perhaps citizens could also have a more important role than the one that was set for them in this specific project, implicitly advocating for an, almost, full involvement approach. Some participants were more or less content with the role set for the public in this project (that of partial involvement).

Regarding Case 4 there were an almost unanimous view (excluding participant 8 (G1)) that this would be very interesting as long as it remained at the level of observation and data collection on behalf of the public. Most of the participants (5 in total) believed that the public involvement would be very useful for the scientific project, while participants 2 and 7 (G1) expressed their doubts, stating that they didn’t believe that they could help science this way, but it could help them evolve themselves through it.

In summary, among the benefits of public integration in science the participants mentioned are, in this particular order: (a) the importance of helping the scientists in the data collection process, (b) their own self-evolvement through these activities, (c) the capability to express your opinion and participate in something, even if in some cases the decision is more or less preoccupied, (d) the diversity of the research’ results, (e) the more popularized explanation of the scientific results and process.

On the other hand, the disadvantage that most of the participants mentioned concerns the limited knowledge that the public has in comparison with scientists. This leads to advocate either for no public involvement, especially for important matters such as health as we saw above, or for a partial public involvement on the terms that we’ve also mentioned.

In total, half of the participants stated that at least one of the public integration Cases (3B and 4) enhanced their trust in science, while 2 of them argued that while Citizen Science projects are very useful for science, they would trust more research that would be fully conducted by scientists.

Group 2 (GREEN)

Only one participant had a personal involvement in science (participant 1 (G2)). The participant’s experience shared with the others was somewhat dismissive of the processes used in participatory consultations. She mentioned specifically that she never learned the results of the project she participated in.

As previously mentioned, the specific issue was raised in Cases 3A and 4. Regarding Case 3A, three participants (participants 1,3,5 (G2)) stated that they would participate but not in decision-making, rather as mere listeners to learn more about COVID-19 due to personal interest. Two other participants (participants 2,4 *G2)) stated that they wouldn't participate because they are not experts in the consultation topic, and therefore, there would be no real subject of consultation. Additionally, they view such moves with suspicion, as they believe that involving the public in a discussion on an unfamiliar topic could easily lead to legitimizing decisions that may prove incorrect for society.

In relation to Case 4, five out of 8 participants (participants 1,2,5,7,8 (G2)) supported partial involvement of the public in science, only to the extent of simple observation. Participant 6 (G2) responded negatively to the public's involvement in science, as they perceive it as a voluntary activity with which they disagree. They believe that the entire scientific process, from start to finish, should be carried out by scientists who should be compensated.

Public involvement in science has brought about an increase in democracy and openness in scientific endeavors, as participant 7 (G2) stated. Another benefit highlighted by participant 5 (G2) is that involving the public in science could encourage those engaged to seek additional information on the subject under examination, thus furthering their motivation to acquire more knowledge. In this context, we could say that the process of public involvement in science also enhances the educational character of science actors regarding the acquisition of scientific thinking from the perspective of the public. On the other hand, certain problems were identified concerning public involvement in science. Participant 4 (G2) argued that leaving the door of science open to non-experts could be dangerous both for science itself and for society. On one hand, science could lose its integrity when in the hands of non-experts, either due to ignorance or serving their interests, and on the other hand, society could be affected by erroneous or manipulated scientific results.

Participant 2 (G2) primarily influenced by the current Greek reality where public involvement is not common in either science or policy making, would approach such a call with suspicion. Furthermore, another participant emphasized that there are many issues to be discussed with the public (daily life problems), and involving the public in science is a matter that presupposes the resolution of other more critical matters.

Participant 7 (G2) stated the involvement of the public in science indicates the democratic nature of science. Science, both as a practice and as a process, can be scrutinized and judged. The democracy in science resulting from its openness influences public trust in it.

In total, while some participants agreed with partial public participation in science, and only at the stage of observation and data recording, all argued that it should be conducted by scientists and with integrity. This alone could contribute to strengthening trust in science. Only one participant (participant 5 (G3)) argued that public involvement would be a way to contribute to trust in science.

Group 3 (YELLOW)

In Group 3, all participants had had personal involvement in science, either as University students or, even later, as professionals. Many of them (6) had been involved in other focus groups discussions for other research projects and had participated in surveys (7). With the opportunity of discussing the Case 3A, the participants expressed their opinion on different types/methods of

integration (surveys, expressing their views in writing e-mails addressed to policy-makers, public deliberation workshops) with a preference to public deliberation and discussions. Regarding the desired level of public involvement in science and in policy-making, the participants showed a clear preference on citizen science, but they, also, distinguished levels of participation depending on different types of research. So, for instance, in projects related to astronomy, amateur astronomers could be involved since they have some specialisation in this kind of research. As Participant 6 (G3) said: “There are NASA programs that are aimed at, for example, me who have a telescope and I like to observe. That’s who I’m going to put in. That’s who I’m going to work with. Yes I want their results, but I think that’s where I’m going to draw the line. I’m not going back to my sister who’s 12 years old... I mean, okay I have to address this case, I’m talking about specialised research and a more educated audience in a sense. For more general type of research, then yes and I will say get people involved, people should not only be informed, they should be involved. After all, science is for the people, isn’t it? So, given the opportunity, why not? Yes, we want some opinions and when it is so more general.”

The benefits of public involvement in science are related both to society at large and science itself. For society, it is important because certain scientific results have impact on people’s everyday life, eg. their health or the natural environment. For science itself, in certain cases it is desirable to collect as many data as possible, and to this direction lay people can help. Moreover, for policy makers, it is important to have an idea on people’s views about certain scientific issues and resulting policies in order to foresee whether these policies can be implemented and accepted, or amendments and adjustments are needed. As put by Participant 5 (G3): “*If you don’t work and help, you can’t have an opinion. That is to participate, you see the good side and the bad side, you see the one, you see the other, you can have an opinion, you can correct, you can say I want to honor P. (a specific scientist) because he made my place a better place to live and you can ... that is the value of scientific contribution, you see it through your own struggle. That’s why everyone should participate.*”

Regarding possible problems and risks in public involvement, Participant 7 (G3) mentioned the possibility people to misunderstand the research conducted and Participant 6 (G3) mentioned the possibility of people being biased when participating in such activities and, in that way, affecting the results: “*When there is bias, that in itself can create a problem in anything, whether we are talking about a simple discussion or we are talking about research.*” Another risk is these processes to give floor to extremist views, as mentioned by Participant 5 (G3). However, this can be considered as a benefit instead, since in public deliberation all sides have the opportunity to check their arguments and improve their views by taking into consideration the opposite views, following a dialectic approach. At the end, what matters is the majority formulated by democratic procedures, so the involvement even of more extreme views works for the common understanding and good. It is, also, worth mentioning that there were instances in which participants expressed themselves using phrases such as “we had to convince them, to show them scientific data and arguments”, as in the case of the discussions for the vaccination policies for COVID-19, which shows how certain parts of the public can support and advocate in favour of science.

In general, the group’s attitude towards the public involvement in science was positive, both regarding the expression of opinion about scientific issues and related policies in public deliberation procedures, and through the citizen science movement. However, all participants agreed that there are types of research that involve hard evidence and data that need to be conducted only by scientists in order to be sure that proper procedures are followed.

All participants expressed their satisfaction for their participation in the workshop, and said that, in such occasions, it is important participants to be notified about the results of the research project they have participated in, because this will make them feel that they have contributed to something important. Most of them were satisfied with the structure of the workshop, whereas Participant 7 (G3) mentioned that it would be preferable to have even more structured questions that would help the participants to give even more specific answers.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

In general, participants were positively disposed towards public involvement in science. They highlighted the democratic aspect of these projects. This aspect did not contain decision making, since the focus was on exchanging ideas and getting informed. But at the same time –especially regarding issues of health and medicine– they were reluctant or negative towards participating in projects of public deliberation. This was explained by their high trust in the expert’s opinion, exactly because of their expertise. In this respect, public involvement was conceptualized as a way to exchange opinions and ideas or to make the public feel that they participate, or as one participant mentioned “*Just be a public awareness activity and give a sense of being part of something.*” In a way public involvement seems irrelevant to scientific endeavour and there was no reference connecting public involvement and trust in science.

The participants’ view on the desired level of public participation was a bit intricate. Though they thought it was a good idea to participate in the research process (in the sense of volunteering) they were concerned about which part of the research it should be. There was a consensus that the simplest and more trivial parts of the research could be uptaken by the public. But at the same time, one participant expressed concern about whether the public was up for the task (in terms of focus and discipline) and whether this would be more safely and accurately facilitated by technological means.

The importance of the subject matter of the research was another factor in deciding the level of participation. The participants were negative towards the collection of data for an important issue by “volunteers,” where expertise is needed. One participant acknowledged the benefit of public involvement in science in conducting quantitative studies, where a large amount of data needs to be collected.

The problems arising from public involvement concerned: the public involvement in studying phenomena that haven’t matured yet (like COVID-19); coordinating public deliberation in different areas (heterogeneity in decision-making across the country), the question of the reliability of the data collected by the public, the question of the importance of expertise in data collection.

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

Group 1 (RED)

Scientific journals were identified as trustworthy by three participants (namely, participants 2, 3 and 6 (G1)) mainly because they use a scientific method in presenting their arguments, Participant 6 said that the Social Media could be used but just for some basic information, while during the discussion of Case 3B participant 6 (G1) mentioned the government platforms such as the ones used in the Pandemic for communicating such projects.

On the other hand, newspapers and social media are the most untrustworthy according to the participants. Reasons for distrusting the newspapers were their ownership, the journalists and the interests they serve (participants 2 and 6 (G1)) and the fact that the scientific articles published in the Greek newspapers are mostly descriptive and not deep enough (participant 3 (G1)). Social media are neither “rigid enough” for communicating science (participants 1 and 2 (G1)) nor reliable enough because of their anonymity (participant 6 (G1)).

In conclusion, participants stated that if a mediator wants to create a firm science communication endeavour, this should meet the following criteria: a) **simplified language but with rigid and tangible arguments**, people should thoroughly understand what happened in a case or what they are supposed to do in a Citizen Science project, b) **objectivity** (many participants condemned the language used by the journalist in Case 1A), c) **transparency**, people should know who exactly the mediating actor and the people that are mentioned in an article or a post are and they should be provided with thorough elements, d) **attractiveness**, in the case where the people are called to participatory actions the publications should be appealing.

Group 2 (GREEN)

All participants are particularly suspicious of all communication channels. Some consider them influenced by political power and industries, thus not objective, while others believe they are used by scientists themselves for personal gain. Specifically, regarding scientists using widely spread channels to express their personal opinions on scientific matters (e.g., the example of Case 2B), the goal is often to mass-influence public opinions (P1). In such cases, the acceptance of an opinion is not based solely on its intrinsic value but rather on its popularity among the public.

However, a distinction was made between traditional and new communication channels, where the majority of participants 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 (G2) would trust newspapers and scientific journals more but would verify the news from other sources as well.

Overall, communication channels seem to negatively affect public opinion about science. As mentioned earlier, all channels are perceived to be influenced by political power and industry. All participants supported the view that the involvement of power and industry in communication channels was evident during the COVID-19 case and now in the case of climate change. Their perspective on this involvement in science communication largely determines which channels they consider trustworthy and which they do not.

In conclusion, the criteria that a mediator must meet when communicating science, according to the participants' views should be objectivity, control of information, simple and understandable language, and transparency.

Group 3 (YELLOW)

Regarding the communication channels people trust to be informed about science, the participants of Group 3 expressed in general their preference to more traditional means, such as scientific journals and newspapers/journal n which acclaimed science journalists write. As participant 3 (G3) stated: *“So who we read the information from certainly plays a role, the language he uses, the references he uses, is something I totally agree with, the medium, which he uses, let's say on Facebook there is no citation, anyone can upload what they want. It is not the*

same with the various science sites.” From the discussion, it came out that the same rules of integrity apply, not only for the conduct of research, but, also, for the communication of research results to the public. Thus, the trustworthiness of the communication channels influence the trustworthiness of research.

Regarding the role of mediators in science communication, the participants expressed their trust more to scientists talking on scientific issues (via the various communication channels) compared to journalists and politicians, and for this reason they acknowledged the importance of having the experts at the beginning of the workshop presenting the selected scientific topics. To the same direction, between the Cases 2A and 1B, the participants considered 2A as more important to contributing to the trust in science, as it is the University’s Communication Office which informs the public about the problem that came up. The fact that it is an official authority seems to make the message conveyed as more trustworthy, compared to Facebook post. Moreover, between the traditional mass media and the social media, the participants seem to be more sceptical about the social media, particularly because they reach out to great numbers of people simultaneously and there is no particular monitoring of what is being published through them.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

Social media and specifically personal accounts (i.e., of journalists) were not considered trustworthy. Participants agreed on how news needs to be cross-checked to conceive them as accurate. The work of individual mediators (not institutions) especially on social media was considered risky. The participants acknowledged that the received information is multiply filtered, which makes it more difficult to consider a communication channel trustworthy. In the same spirit, the participants expressed that in the digital era where social media govern communication, it seems that the defects from traditional means of communication have been or are being transferred to the newly developed digital means of communication.

But even in the case of institutions (like universities) communicating science, the content and the purpose defined the perception of the participants on its trustworthiness. For example, because they distinguish researchers from administrators, the role of administrators was characterized as saving the day in case a researcher was in trouble. This was a characteristic incident of how the trust in this type of channel was decreased because the intention behind this type of communication seems apologetic and intending to conceal a fault.

Concerning the characteristics that make communication channels trustworthy, the participants listed (1) references to other works that the public can access and check, (2) neutrality when presenting news or clarifying the position it takes, (3) preference for more official channels over individuals, (4) justified content presented with clarity and consistency, (5) content-based in factual evidence.

According to the participants, mediators share their part of the responsibility when communicating science. Taking as an example the mediators in COVID-19 (i.e., journalists, politicians, etc.) the participants claimed that the mediators have an impact on the formation of public opinion and have the means to critically affect social phenomena or as one participant expressed “It’s like it’s dynamiting this situation.” In such cases, the mediators tend to provoke and can be compared to the function of fake news or conspiracy theories that attempt to muddle the water, which has a direct negative effect on distrust in these channels.

3.6 Other themes

Other themes emerged only in the case of the discussion within Group 4 (ORANGE). Two other relevant themes arose: accountability and a framework for control. One participant mentioned that researchers should be held accountable when they present false data, in terms of legal repercussions and that a type of committee should be established to check and regulate the assumptions of the researchers. At the same time, the issue of the responsibility of the researcher's endeavour was risen by another participant who connected the lack of or minimum repercussions with the continuation of misconduct. The aforementioned were discussed within the context of the hazardousness from the backlashes of research misconduct.

Secondly, all participants agreed on viewing citizen science as voluntarism. Any activity related to citizen science was conceived as a type of voluntary contribution for helping researchers, entertainment or something to be combined with other hobbies (i.e., hiking).

3.7 Card sorting exercise

Group 1 (RED)

Even though the individual rankings were obviously not identical, there was a general consensus in the final rankings of Group 1. There was a difficulty for many of the participants to understand the ranking criteria (Impact of trust in science for each case) but after an extensive discussion we've managed to mostly overcome it.

Participant 1 (G1) was unanimously elected to represent Group 1 final ranking in the plenary discussion. The Group ranked Case 4 first, based on "its' positive, tangible, understandable arguments and well-founded thoughts which leads both the public and the researchers to have a contribution in the final result, that is, the public, as an observer on biodiversity issues, would help the researchers to come up with their findings and analyses". On the 2nd place was Case 1A having a negative impact on the participants both in terms of trust in science (mainly scientists to be exact) as well as in terms of how it was communicating (biases, subjectivity, imprecisions). Case 3B came up 3rd faced with indifference for most of the participants (some had also positive stance, as described above), mainly because a) the decision about the vaccines was already taken and b) many members of the Group felt that the Face book post was not providing them with enough information about the project. Case 2B was ranked 4th, illustrating the problems that we've previously mentioned (lack of understanding and inconsistency).

Table 3: Trust in science: Results of the group ranking.

Group 1 (RED)	Group 2 (GREEN)	Group 3 (YELLOW)	Group 4 (ORANGE)
Case 4	Case 3A	Case 4	Case 2A
Case 1A	Case 4	Case 3A	Case 4
Case 3B	Case 1A	Case 2A	Case 3B
Case 2B	Case 2B	Case 1B	Case 1B

Group 2 (GREEN)

Without much discussion during the ranking, the way participants made their personal ranking indicates that they consider public engagement in science as a significant factor that affect trust in science.

Group 3 (YELLOW)

The idea of active participation was the most popular among the participants of Group 3. For this reason Cases 4A and 3A were ranked as the most trustworthy, hence the participants seemed to give a priority to integration over integrity. There was only one participant (participant 5 (G3)) who ranked Case 3A as first and Case 4 as second, as this person considered public deliberation and collective thinking as the first step that we need to take in order to have proper public involvement in science (*“first discussion, then action”*). However, all participants agreed on the final ranking and its justification for the plenary discussion, so the group reached a consensus regarding the final ranking.

The main arguments had to do with the fact that active involvement can motivate lay people to trust science and scientists, as they become part of the scientific endeavour (Case 4). The expression of personal beliefs in public regarding science is, also, crucial and policymakers and politicians need to take them into consideration since their decisions affect people’s lives; this means that involving citizens (Case 3A). Furthermore, Cases 2A and 1B that were related with the discussions on integrity were ranked as third and fourth, respectively, not because the participants do not consider research integrity important, but, mostly, because they have a critical stance towards the chains of mediation involved in these cases (traditional and social media, press offices). In other words, the chains of mediation affect their trust in science, therefore they get more sceptical when this kind of mediation is used in science communication.

Group 4 (ORANGE)

The Orange group did not get a consensus, so the majority vote enabled the ranking. This was accepted by the members of the group since they thought that providing a space for a different opinion was more important.

The concept underlying the ranking process was a contemplation of the importance of the content and the character of the means of communication. The group ranked in the 1st position the Case 2A because of the importance and position of the channel of communication (the university’s communication office) and the significance of the content (whether there was an intention to conceal a scandal). Case 4 was ranked in the 2nd position because of two different reasons: the importance of public integration and the heavy duty of the public participating in the important process of scientific research. Case 3B was ranked in the 3rd position because of the importance of the means of communication (the reach social media have) but at the same time the content was not as significant as some other issues the group discussed. Lastly, Case 1B was ranked by the majority in the 4th position, mainly because the group agreed that the mediator (journalist) didn’t have that much of an impact; but one participant ranked it in the 1st exactly because of the dissemination capacities of social media (the mean of communication in this case).

4 Attitudes towards science & technology

Responses to questions A4 and B4: Table 2 provides an overview of the attitudes towards S&T before and after the public deliberative WS in Greece. The % agreement column is the aggregated result of two positive responses, namely “Strongly agree” and “Agree”. Please note that the full results in % are presented in the Appendix. The % agreement reaches almost a consensus in the case of the 2 first items. Specifically almost all participants have an agreement when they respond to the questions on whether they believe S&T (a) makes their lives easier, healthier, and more comfortable and (b) makes their lives change too fast.

The first item has clearly positive connotations, i.e. it represents the participants’ positive perceptions on S&T. The second item, however, represents a non-positive perception on S&T that received an almost equally high percentage. In the second item, as shown at the Appendix, the “Strongly agree” responses were slightly higher than in the first item. In addition, the bar chart shows that in both items this % agreement was decreased by 3 and 6 percentage units. Despite this decrease the almost consensus agreement still holds also after the end of the public deliberative WS.

Items 3 and 5 that have non-positive connotations on the societies’ overly dependence on science and not enough on faith and on the “obligatory” nature of trust on those who govern S&T, gathered the agreement of approximately the one third of the participants. As in the items 1 and 2, after the public deliberative WS the % agreement was reduced by 7 percentage units for item 3 and by 2 percentage units for item 5.

Finally, item 4 represented the trust of the participants to scientists. In this case, almost half of the participants agreed. Also, that was the only item that showed a slightly higher level of agreement after the end of the public deliberative WS.

Table 4: Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics.

Item	Before			After			Difference in means
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	48	2	97	47	4	94	1 (decrease)
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	47	9	94	44	0	88	3 (decrease)
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	19	0	38	16	9	31	3 (decrease)
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	22	13	44	23	11	47	1 (increase)
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	17	0	33	16	4	31	1 (decrease)

Note. N range = 30-32

Note. N range = 30-32

Responses to question B9: The majority, specifically 27 out of the 32 participants (84.375%), of the participants was the first time that participated in this type of event.

Responses to question B11: The majority, specifically 27 out of the 32 participants (84.375%), of the participants declared that they will get involved in events like this in the future. A smaller majority declared that they will talk to friends and family about this issue. A bit less than half of the participants declared that they will follow news stories on this issue. No participant filled any comments or additional input at the “Other” category.

Table 5: Impacts of event on participants: Results (%).

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	84.375
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	59.375
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	43.75
4. Other	0

Conclusions about the survey data: According to the bar chart, there we no significant changes of attitudes towards S&T due to the participants’ involvement on the Greek public deliberative Workshop. Items 1, 4, and 5 showed only marginal change, of no more than 3%, while items 2 and 3 showed a higher change of 6% and 7%, respectively. The responses to items 1 and 2 could be considered somehow ambiguous, since item 1 has a clearly positive and item 2 a clearly negative connotation towards S&T.

5 Appendix

The photos of the rankings on the wall of the breakout rooms and at the initiation of the 2nd plenary session are depicted below:

Ranking from the Red breakout room.

Ranking from the Green breakout room.

Ranking from the Yellow breakout room.

Ranking from the Orange breakout room.

Ranking of all breakout rooms at the initiation of the 2nd plenary session.

Table 6: Questionnaire 1: Full results (%).

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	50%	47%	3%	0%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	53%	41%	6%	0%	0%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	19%	19%	31%	6%	25%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	13%	31%	31%	9%	16%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	17%	17%	10%	17%	37%	3%

Table 7: Questionnaire 2: Full results (%).

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	44%	50%	6%	0%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	44%	44%	13%	0%	0%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	9%	22%	28%	9%	31%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	16%	31%	22%	9%	19%	3%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	19%	13%	16%	19%	34%	0%

Annex E: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – Portugal

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *Portugal*

Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Iscte)*

Contributors: Inês Sousa, Marta Entradas

1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the event

The Public Deliberative Workshop (PDW) took place on the 3rd of June of 2023 (Saturday), between 14:00 and 18:00hrs, at Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Avenida das Forças Armadas, Lisbon). Twenty-four individuals participated in the PDW and were distributed by four groups. Group 1 – the Einstein’s group – had 5 participants, group 2 – the Marie Curie’s group – had 7 participants, group 3 – the Freud’s group – had 6 participants, and group 4 – the Katherine Johnson’s group – had 6 participants.

The PDW also included four moderators, one in each group, one facilitator, Professor Rita Monteiro Mourão, and two students who helped to display posters with directions on how to get to the room, to prepare the kit to offer to participants and to welcome them. The expert, PhD Carla Gomes, research fellow at the University of Lisbon - Institute of Social Sciences, did a 15-minute presentation on the topic “Confiança na ciência climática: perceções sociais, investigação, comunicação” (Trust in climate science: social perceptions, research, communication).

Recruitment of participants. We engaged in a three-step recruitment strategy: 1) sending e-mails to associations and displaying posters at Iscte, 2) disseminating the event via social media channels, and 3) sending individual e-mails to personal contacts and others with an interest in scientific related issues.

Firstly, on the 18th of April, one and a half months before the event, the event was disseminated through e-mails sent to about 65 associations. These included students’ associations of universities located in Lisbon (e.g., Nova University, Católica University, Lisbon University), climate associations (e.g., ZERO – Sustainable Earth System Association, Climáximo), public health associations (e.g., Portuguese Society for Health Literacy, Health in Dialogue Platform) and science-related associations (e.g., International Science Festival, Living Science Association). Invitations were sent also to other associations such as the Portuguese Association for Diversity and Inclusion (APPDI), the National Confederation of Pensioners and Older People and the Youth Foundation, aiming to obtain a sample as heterogeneous as possible in terms of age, gender and educational background. Information about the date, schedule and location of the event was provided, as well as a link for registering in the event and a request for disseminating the event among their members. Simultaneously, posters disseminating the event were displayed at Iscte, in five places authorized by the institution. The event was also announced in the Lisbon Cultural Agenda, developed by Lisbon City Council (available at https://www.agendalx.pt/content/uploads/2023/05/ACL_jun23.pdf - Page 21).

Next, the event was disseminated through social media channels including the POIESIS social media channels, the national team research center – CIES-Iscte –, and the School of Sociology and Public Policy of Iscte (ESPP-Iscte). CIES-Iscte disseminated the event through LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook. On LinkedIn, the post generated 608 impressions, 12 reactions and 6 reposts. On Twitter, information about the event was shared on the 4th of May and on the 26th of May. The first tweet included a poster of the event (image) having generated 506 impressions, 2 retweets, 6 engagements, 4 expansions for details and 1 click in the link. The second tweet (without image)

produced 184 impressions, 2 likes, 1 retweet, 4 engagements and 1 expansion for details. Finally, on Facebook, the publication generated 586 impressions and 9 likes, 3 clicks in links and 4 shares. ESPP-Iscte also disseminated the event through its social media, namely Facebook and Instagram, on the 16th of May. On Facebook, the publication reached 105 accounts and generated 2 likes. On Instagram, the publication reached 321 accounts, generated 12 likes and 1 share.

The reach, impressions and engagement of these publications was poor in relation to the number of followers of these two pages and seems to have contributed very little to the recruitment of participants to the event. Therefore, the recruitment of participants through Iscte's social media was not effective.

By the 15th of May, only 6 participants had registered to participate in the event, which required a boost in the recruitment strategy. A second email was sent to all the associations contacted in April as a reminder, and to some other institutions (e.g., Culture and Art Community, Pint of Science Portugal) and research centers. We further opted to send individual emails to personal contacts (e.g., friends, acquaintances) and professional contacts, such as colleagues from our institution, science-related networks and research centers. We sent about 110 individual e-mails.

These efforts lead to thirty-two participants having signed up for the event. These received an e-mail from our team with information about the project and the event – the Participant Information Sheet and the Information Kit. As an answer to our e-mail, three people reported being unable to attend the event, which resulted in 29 participants expected in PDW. However, only 24 participants showed up.

After the event, some participants requested a certificate of attendance that is available in Appendix A.

1.2 Participants in the event

The sample consisted of 24 participants. About 79% of the participants were female, 38% completed a Master degree and 38% a Doctoral degree. Half of the sample was aged between 18 and 34 years old, 33% were middle-aged people (35 to 49 years old), and 17% were 50 years old or more.

The majority of the participants (63%) was employed, 33% were students and 4% (n=1) were retired. Considering participants' relation with science, around 52% were scientists, 22% considered science part of their work, 13% were students (science) and only 4% had no connections with science.

2 Discursive summary of cases

2.1 Phase 1 – Expert talk

Carla Gomes, the invited speaker, discussed the topic “Trust in climate science”. The expert started by showing some statistics about social perceptions of climate change (national and international data), followed by a discussion on how information on climate change is communicated to the public.

Carla mentioned that in Portugal a major source of information about Climate Change are the media organisations and, more recently, social media, to which she called a “Pandora’s Box”. About 85% of the Portuguese population considers climate change a very or extremely serious problem. However, there is a gap between perception and action: 55.3% of the respondents think that it is unlikely that many people around the world will actually reduce their energy consumption to fight climate change.

In Portugal, the III Major Sustainability Survey, carried out between June and August 2022 among 1,520 respondents, showed that climate change is perceived as the second most serious problem in the world and in the country. However, despite this concern, as the expert shared, personal measures taken in defence of the environment are still scarce.

Regarding climate communication, in Portugal, news about climate change is heavily influenced by the European and global agenda, and national and local actors and events are less prominent. Considering how people access and think about climate change news, in a study conducted by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism 53% of Portuguese people show interest in information on climate change. Furthermore, 50% choose documentaries and 43% major news organisations as the main sources for climate change news. Finally, Carla Gomes shared some insights on the role of social media in climate communication, focusing on Twitter, its climate of hostility towards scientists and the proliferation of disinformation, fake news, and bots.

2.2 Phase 2 – Focus groups

There were four groups to discuss the hypothetical cases (with two versions each) on scientific integrity and integration in science based on the stimuli materials developed for the purpose. The channels of mediation brought to the cases changed from version A to B, which guided the discussion in different directions in each group. In case 1, which focused on lack of integrity in science, version A presented news published by Jornal Público, a newspaper with a good reputation in Portugal, and version B presented the issue in a Facebook post shared by a journalist from Jornal Público. In case 2, also with a focus on scientific integrity, version A presented the story as an official statement from the university’s Communication Office, and version B presented the story as a series of tweets shared by a researcher of the same university. Case 3, which looked at public involvement in science, presented a public consultation advertised on the TV channel RTP, the Portuguese public television station (version A) and on a Facebook post shared by a journalist from RTP (version B). For cases 1 and 3, journalists’ names were the same for the two versions. Finally, case 4, with a focus on citizen science, was presented in a single version.

2.2.1 Group 1 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3B, 4

The discussion was initially focused on how COVID-19 could be perceived as a politicised issue and one participant stated that the dominant narrative was to emphasise the dangers of the virus with lack of impartiality, with the remaining participants disagreeing with her. After this, participants revealed they were suspicious about Pablo Costa, the researcher who figured in the discussion case, due to the lack of transparency he showed (not showing/sharing the data) and the poor defence argument he used (“We would never make up a study because it’s not ethical”).

The group continued the discussion by commenting on how communication seems partial, particularly in case 1A, despite most participants considered the source (Jornal Público) as trustworthy. Participants consider that the news story in case 1A lacked a conclusion that would provide the reader with enough information for taking a position (i.e., Was there fraud or not?).

Case 2B focused on communication means for science. Twitter, and social media in general, were identified as not trustworthy for getting information on scientific issues, due to the difficulty in verifying the veracity and sources of the information. In this regard, participants were of the opinion that, as information can reach many people via social media, the content of these means of communication is even more important, and in this specific case, they found it harmful to science, and to the actors involved (scientist and university).

On the positive side, participants thought that both cases show the relevance of science communication: media inform people about “good and bad science” and there are peers, colleagues, institutions that monitor the quality of science and “don’t let scientific fraud pass them by”.

To sum up the first part of the discussion, the group showed concern of how the communication of scientific findings can particularly affect those who are less involved with research. Participants identified two groups of people, one that is more informed about science-related issues and other that is less informed. A more informed person has more critical sense, believes less in the news and more in the scientific process, trusts more in science, whereas a less informed person could be manipulated by what is said (i.e., the way science is communicated).

Participants showed some interest in participating in a public consultation (case 3B), but their lack of technical knowledge about vaccines was perceived as an obstacle to a significant contribution to the public consultation. The group recognized that public participation in science could contribute to increase people’s trust in science by creating opportunities for people to share their views and hear different opinions, including those contradicting their own. Also, citizen science (case 4) can generate a feeling of belonging to the group of those who contribute to science and educate people about important issues such as climate change. However, information about such events should be disseminated through several and broad communication channels to avoid discrimination (for example, discrimination of people who are not comfortable using technology such as e-mails).

The ranking exercise at the end of the discussion was almost consensual, with participants unanimously agreeing on the arguments justifying it (see section 3.7).

2.2.2 Group 2 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3A, 4

The discussion was essentially focused on communication of science and the channels used to communicate it. One participant, whose job was related to science management and communication, dominated the first part of the discussion, directing (probably unintentionally) the conversation to the role of journalists and other actors in communicating science. This participant was particularly annoyed by the form and content of the news story in case 1B, identifying several problems with it and concluding that “if the study had no credibility recognised by peers and the competent authorities, what went through the journalist’s head to write this news?” (Participant 1). One of the topics she highlighted was the source of the news. For her, the news was being shared in the Facebook personal page of the journalist (i.e., his profile), but citing *Jornal Público* as the source of the investigative work, which can be extremely confusing for people. Other participant commented that Facebook “is not the place to share about serious things like science” (Participant 2).

In case 1B, other participants considered the information clear and emphasised that this news was important to inform the public about the differences between “good” and “bad” science. These two participants pointed out that by presenting the signs of a suspected lack of integrity, such as no data sharing or no record of study approval, the journalist was showing that fraudulent science exists. Integrity issues were identified as being the scientist’s individual responsibility, not generally affecting participants’ trust in science.

In case 2A, the focus was again on means of communication for science. Participants found the university’s statement confusing and inconsistent, ending with the defence of the university’s research unit in what was characterised by one participant as a “public relations stunt” (Participant 3). According to participants, these inconsistencies in the discourse can lead to distrust in science on the part of general public.

The second part of the discussion was mostly dedicated to the desired level of public involvement in science, with the majority of participants expressing a favourable opinion about the participation of society in some phases of the scientific process. Only one participant declared that citizens should be considered stakeholders and fully involved in scientific projects, “from start to finish” (Participant 1). In her own words: “I have radical thoughts about this [topic]”.

Regarding case 3B, all participants agreed that public consultations have the benefit of making people feel their opinions heard and that these events should not be binding. This means that the opinion of the public must be taken into account by the working group that advises the government, but the final decision does not have to be in agreement with the opinion of the majority. In this sense, some participants were concerned about the public’s reaction to a possible inconsistency between the opinion of the majority and the decision of politicians, as expectations could be disappointed, and this would affect trust in the institutions.

Case 4 was seen as exciting and fun. Two participants revealed that they already had participated in similar citizen science projects, and one other participant showed interest in taking part too.

At last, in the ranking exercise there was a relative consensus, as well as in the criteria to define it (see section 3.7).

2.2.3 Group 3 – Cases 1A, 2B, 3A, 4

The group had a balanced participation of all participants during the two parts of the discussion. The first part of the discussion focused mainly on the communication means used in the cases. On the one hand, for case 1A, participants considered that there was a bias in the description of the case, showing only one side of the story and giving more importance to Dr. Scott, the researcher pictured in the case, way of dealing with the situation, which was thought to discredit the study and the drug. On the other hand, the absence of a link on the news to the original study increased distrust among participants towards the news means, especially considering that this newspaper (Jornal Público) has a history of presenting references and links to original sources.

Participants briefly mentioned the lack of transparency as one of their concerns regarding the study presented in case 1. Also, the role of the prestige of the university in framing the case was briefly discussed. Participants assumed that this case of lack of integrity is not an important factor because “people don’t make the spaces” (Participant 3).

In case 2B, participants first identified a problem of scientific fraud, but lately discussed that this was not proved and the information they had was not sufficient to decide if there was lack of integrity by Dr. Jones. The discussion was focused on communication means, particularly the communication channel used in this case (Twitter). Social media in general - especially Twitter - were considered unreliable for disseminating scientific information by most participants, and traditional means such as TV or traditional media such as newspapers were considered more trustworthy. According to participants, social media are not adequate to discuss science and science-related issues (such as scientists’ behaviours) since information can be easily manipulated and most of the times there is no information contradicting the narrative advocated by the author of the publications.

In case 3B, face-to-face participation was identified as the most relevant by the group as it allowed for listening to all ideas as well as confrontation of opinions. However, some participants were unhappy about the existence of a favourable opinion from a group of experts. On the one hand, this could lead to a bias in the public opinion. On the other hand, it could alienate the public if they thought that the decision was already made and participation would be “fake” (i.e., with no real impact on the decision).

For case 4, half of the group considered public participation in science as relevant and important to bring society closer to science, emphasising the importance of co-participation. The other half of the group, while recognising potential benefits of this public involvement, showed concern about the “validity” of the studies (e.g., lack of knowledge about the topic, lack of scientific literacy to conduct a study, etc).

According to the participants, the two cases presented in part 1 did not generate distrust towards science. They were seen as isolated cases that do not represent the behaviour of most scientists and would be a “huge generalization” to science (Participant 5). The two cases presented in part 2 allow the general public to come into contact with scientific methods, which can contribute to trust in science, but people probably have to be interested in the topics of citizen science projects to get involved.

Finally, the ranking exercise generated a fruitful discussion with the participants feeling the need to quantify their arguments that will be presented in section 3.7.

2.2.4 Group 4 – Cases 1B, 2A, 3B, 4

The first part of the discussion was focused on several aspects of communication (i.e., content/discourse, communication channel and actors). The second part of the discussion focused on the desired level of public involvement in science, generating a lively debate among the participants.

Case 1 took up most of the discussion in the first part. Some participants considered that the news tried to “manipulate public opinion” and that “there were undisclosed interests” (Participant 1). Also, because this news was shared on Facebook, the group showed great distrust in the information. Additionally, the group discussed the role of the journalist sharing the news – they were not certain if Manuel Dias was sharing this post on Facebook as his personal opinion or as his role as a journalist in the *Jornal Público*. This ambiguity can contribute, in the group’s opinion, to greater misinformation about science among publics.

In case 2A, participants showed great concern for how such online communication could generate lack of trust in science on the part of laypeople due to an enormous lack of clarity in the statement about how and why the situation described happened (e.g., why is Dr. Jones being accused? Who is Russel?). The lack of explanations about what happened led the group to mistrust the Communication Office of East Anglia, more than the researcher accused of fraud.

During the discussion of case 3B, participants were interested in debating the desired level of public involvement in science. The group concluded that the main goal of a public consultation should be to inform the population and explain the reasons behind a particular decision, but do not allow people to vote or decide about scientific-based issues, especially if it is health-related. The main argument for this position is the lack of technical knowledge of the general population. For case 3B, communication has taken on little relevance.

Regarding case 4, many participants lacked personal interest in the project due to disinterest in the biodiversity topic. Again, the desired level of public involvement in science was highly debated, with participants not agreeing on the extent to which public participation should be allowed. After a heated discussion, and guided by the moderator, the group agreed that public participation is beneficial to bring society closer to science if the project has a “didactic objective” (Participant 3), and people can learn about the researched topic, such as the abundance of birds in a particular region (case 4). All participants highlighted the need for data collection in such events to be validated by researchers.

For most participants, the major difference between cases 3 and 4 was the type of involvement of the public. In case 3, people are involved by sharing their opinions, which are subjective and can change over time; in case 4, people are involved by taking photographs, videos, which constitute objective data that cannot be changed.

Lastly, all participants were highly engaged in the ranking exercise, in lively discussions, bringing several arguments to rank the various cases, as it will be presented in section 3.7.

3 Integrity and integration & trust in science

3.1 General attitudes towards science

This topic was barely addressed during the group discussions, but in general the participants showed positive attitudes towards science, which was also seen in the questionnaires (further information is available on chapter 4 of this report).

“For me, it was an achievement of science to have managed to develop a vaccine.”
(Participant 3, Group 3)

“Science does have its mistakes (...) but there is a logic behind arriving at a result.”
(Participant 4, Group 3)

Few negative attitudes were revealed by participants, those being most related to the idea that political interests can influence the directions of science.

“The article shows how science can serve political interests (...) more than a scientific question, it was a political position.” (Participant 2, Group 4) (referring to the development of COVID-19 treatment).

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

Participants identified more reasons to distrust science than to trust, which can be related to the emphasis on the negative aspects of science in the first two cases. Participants stated that one of the reasons for them to distrust science and scientists was the idea that science is always accurate and infallible, which was particularly evident in case 1.

“It is very hard to get 100% in anything, isn't it? (...) This number calls our attention to the idea that something is wrong. It's a red flag.” (Participant 3, Group 1)

“It [the medication] prevented 100% of infections by COVID-19. Here we talk about 100% when in science we talk most of the times in probabilities.” (Participant 5, Group 4)

Also, reasons to distrust science and scientists included the lack of transparency when presenting scientific findings. Participants pointed out that *“In science, conveying a statement with good intentions is not enough.”* (Participant 5, Group 1) referring to case 1 and the scientist's argument that *“We would never make up a study because it's not ethical.”* In the participants' opinion, trust in science implies transparency and access to the data (e.g., open access data).

“When I started [to read], I wanted to see the results, so that I can talk about something, so that I can argue about something that is tangible, see-through numbers. I can't, so I'm hypothesising a lot of things here.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

“What we expect from science is to be transparent in terms of open access, data quantification, these things.” (Participant 3, Group 2)

Participants also emphasised the relevance of communication for trusting in science, a topic that will be further addressed in section 3.5. Most participants declared that it is important to be completely informed about the situation at stake, for example, to be exposed to the two sides of

the story. Also, participants considered important to have the original sources of scientific information when reading news: *“Not having the link [for the original article] is strange.”* (Participant 2, Group 3)

As science – and other topics – are often communicated with lack of clarity, participants showed concerns with trusting communication channels, that is, it is not so much the science, but the way science is communicated.

“Just one thing. I think que this [case] does not affect the robustness of science. Never. But I think that it affects our trust in everything that we read.” (Participant 6, Group 4)

Furthermore, the (accelerated) pace of scientific discoveries could also lead to distrust in people, which was mentioned by few participants in Group 3.

“Participant 4: The social and economic challenges are a little bit different from the timings of science, right? Science must have a path, and when social and economic challenges arise, they put pressure on science to give an immediate response, naturally this will lead people to feel some...”

Participant 2: Insecurity.

Participant 4: Much more insecurity.”

It is interesting to note that participants used the term “science” in the broad sense, but referred to the particular situations of science, described in the cases participants read and the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, when showing distrust on scientists, participants were not targeting the whole professional class of scientists, but only those scientists involved in the case studies. For example, when discussing case 1, participants seemed to make a clear distinction between the scientist who committed fraud and the class of scientists in general.

“We are talking about one person that has built a career, is recognized, right? And therefore, I would say that this is not a well-conducted study. (...) Being a retired person, professor of medicine and from the University of Buenos Aires – that is one of the most renowned in the country. So, I am assuming that we are talking about a well-respected person in the field.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

“I putted a cross [meaning rejecting him] on the scientist, regardless of who he is.” (Participant 2, Group 3)

“Participant 4: In general, I believe that people do not define entities.

Participant 2: The habit does not make the monk...” (Group 3)

However, participants raised suspicions about the past of these researchers doubting their credibility. In their words: *[It makes me doubt] the scientist’s behaviour in the past.”* (Participant 5, Group 3)

One possible explanation for participants not generalizing their distrust in one specific scientist/situation to the whole scientific community/science might be their trust in the actors who act as ‘vigilantes’ of science. This idea was particularly salient in this PDW due to participants’ close link to science and their knowledge of the scientific process, including peer reviews when publishing science.

“This [situation] will not pass because there are instances, peers, people who are vigilant and they will not allow these situations to pass, these scientific frauds (...). There are vigilantes. Peers, colleagues, institutions that monitor us.” (Participant 5, Group 1)

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

The discussion on research integrity practices was superficial, and particularly focused on the negative perspective, addressing mostly actions and characteristics of lack of integrity. The dichotomy transparency–lack of transparency was present in all of the group discussions, making it the most important characteristic mentioned for trusting in science. Despite this, participants recognized that these cases of lack of integrity are an exception within the scientific community.

Views on integrity and lack of integrity

In participants’ views of integrity, and reinforcing the factors that affect trust (discussed in section 3.2), the scientist’s credibility depends on transparency. For cases 1 and 2, this meant describing and explaining the methodology of the study, showing the data and making the data accessible to everyone.

“This gentleman, to be credible, he had to show the data right away. To show what he did, how he did it, the data...” (Participant 2, Group 1)

“It should have selection criteria [for the sample], data should be transparent, should be in open access. (...) This news gives the idea of what should be a scientific study. The majority of people don’t know, for example, that to conduct a study that tests a medicine it is required to have all the age groups represented, people who are sick and not sick, to have a control group.” (Participant 4, Group 2)

“Anyway, to increase people’s trust in his work he should have shown the empirical data that were collected. Because methodologically the study seems to be well conducted with the meteorological stations both in urban areas and cities, and... In that sense, I think he should have shared the data.” (Participant 3, Group 2)

Also, as stated in one of the previous quotes, research integrity practices include the description of selection criteria for the sample and its thorough characterization.

Views about lack of integrity received greater attention from participants. Again, the lack of transparency in sharing the data was the most mentioned idea by participants.

“If he received a request to share the data and he did not share... It gives the impression that he might be hiding something about how the study was done.” (Participant 1, Group 3)

Other problems identified by participants as lack of integrity were:

- Lack of official recognition of the study;
- Lack of responsibility from the researcher;
- Lack of scientific rigour;

- Possible conflict of interest;
- Lack of ethical approval, particularly important in health sciences;

“There are suspicions of lack of scientific rigor. “The numbers, genders, and ages were inconsistent”, “There is no record...” – This is very bad! “Health officials in the province of Buenos Aires have also said that they also have no record of the study receiving local approval.” In fact, this is not a valid study. “That it is, at best, unreliable”. I would say, yes, being very generous, because in the worst case scenario it is a terrible deception and pure propaganda.” (Participant 1, Group 2)

“Did this scientist have an economic interest in the sales of the medication?” (Participant 2, Group 4)

Together, these ideas suggest that, in participants’ opinion, the study could be fake, and the researcher can be accused of scientific fraud, which is one of the most serious incorrect behaviours that a scientist could have: *“For me, scientific fraud is extremely serious.” (Participant 3, Group 2)*

Integrity and trust in science

The focus of Case 1 on Covid-19 triggered a heated discussion on the relationship between society and trust in science. Participants demonstrated their concern with a possible decrease in trust in science by the general public after reading a case where lack of integrity is evident, particularly when it is related to people’s health.

“[This case shows that] Scientific work might lead to hasty conclusions that are not serious, that are not rigorous. That are dishonest in a moment of crisis for people’s health.” (Participant 1, Group 1)

In general, participants agreed that studies where suspicion of lack of integrity exist, can compromise the image of science and discredit it among the general public, but still for those who shared that opinion, their trust in science was not affected. Again, such opinions should be interpreted considering the characteristics of the sample.

“Participant 4: Someone who doesn’t know the process and who isn’t so involved in these processes, very quickly takes away the image that “ok, there’s a lot here that is a fraud”. And so, it can also be a bit damaging [to science] in that sense.

Participant 2: And that’s what discredits society’s belief in science.” (Group 1)

“M: When you read this, do you feel that it shakes your idea about science, in other words, do you see this is an isolated case and “it doesn’t shake my confidence at all...”

Participant 2: No, no. Not at all.

Participant 5: In science, in general, I think it’s a huge generalisation.” (Group 3)

“Because I think that a person, even someone who is not a researcher, a person that is minimally informed about science by reading newspapers, this, this doesn’t affect the public image of science.” (Participant 1, Group 4)

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

This topic assumed a central focus on most discussions and all participants shared their opinions regarding the desired level of public involvement in science, its advantages and disadvantages. Although the majority of participants did not have previous personal or professional experience with public participation in science, the groups were able to discuss how these events would influence trust in science.

Personal involvement in science

The majority of participants had never taken part in citizen science projects. Few participants declared that they had already participated in biodiversity-related projects (e.g., BioBlitz) and shared their positive experiences with the colleagues.

However, as many participants had a professional link to science, they had conducted their own studies (from conception and definition of objectives to the dissemination of results) or had been participants in other studies (e.g., answering questionnaires).

Participants considered that interest in the projects' topics is crucial for them to become personally involved (*"Whether we would participate, that would depend on our interests"* – Participant 3, Group 3). But they also perceived the public level of knowledge about the topic as relevant (*"The type of knowledge required is not compatible with public participation"* – Participant 1, Group 4). The idea of having the 'required expertise' to truly contribute to a scientific discussion took centre stage in case 3, which emphasised public health of young children. In participants' words, *"I really don't want this to be a discussion outside the realm of science. The technical side. I don't see any advantages."* (Participant 4, Group 2).

Desired level of public involvement in science and in policymaking

In general, results suggest that participants agreed on the idea that the public involvement in science should be only partial and always verified by researchers specialized in the topic. Most participants voiced that public involvement in science should be essentially for sharing their opinions, asking their questions and collect some types of data. Only one participant revealed that in her view, citizens are stakeholders and should be involved in every step of the scientific process, from identifying the goals to analysing the data: *"For me, this data collection is still (...) unpaid voluntary work. This is scientists putting citizens in charge of the only part that they, the scientists, think citizens can do."* (Participant 1, Group 2)

For many participants, events involving the public should have an education purpose: specialists can inform society about the topic under discussion and explain the reasons for decisions already made – in a kind of science communication, but with the opportunity for the public to manifest their opinions and clarify their doubts.

"The population has these doubts, let's make a format in which all the doubts are already answered in general so that the population has more confidence in going in that direction." (Participant 5, Group 3)

"I think that the public should be much more involved in the communication, in the explanation, in the dissemination of this data, and perhaps more in the explanation, more for their reality, to know how this impacts them, than during the process itself,

because there are methodological aspects and issues that are (...) complicated.”
(Participant 4, Group 1)

Some participants stated that public consultations are important events for gathering the perceptions of individuals on a subject, including opinions in favour or against a certain measure to be adopted or public policy. However, these opinions should only be marginally taken into account in the decision-making process that will be done by those who are experts in the field. Most participants agreed that the public should not be involved in policy-making due to the lack of technical knowledge about the scientific issues at stake.

“I can't ask someone who has no idea about epidemics or viruses or whatever what they think about making a vaccine available to children aged five, six months, one year.”(Participant 4, Group 4)

Only one participant stated that she believed that citizens should decide how public funding for science should be assigned to different scientific fields.

Benefits and problems of public involvement in science

Lack of scientific and technical knowledge

In general, participants identified and mentioned more benefits than problems of public involvement in science. Still, the biggest issue mentioned by participants – the lack of scientific and technical expertise of the general public – seems to represent a great concern and a huge barrier to public participation in science from participants' perspective.

In the opinion of most participants, the lack of technical knowledge and expertise from the general public prevents people to make a real contribution to the discussion. In this sense, there is a risk that participation will be based on wrong information.

“Sometimes health issues are very specific issues that require very specific knowledge, a lot of data that perhaps most people don't deal with, don't know, don't understand.”(Participant 4, Group 1)

“The point of this [case on vaccination] is that it's a subject on which there is already a lot of misinformation. So not only is there already misinformation, but we're still going to hear everyone's opinion on whether they should have vaccinations or not.”
(Participant 6, Group 4)

“What I'm about to pass on is not reliable information, is it? I would always question whether this information is valid or not. It could bias the team's results.” (Participant 3, Group 4)

Bring society and science closer together

The most important benefit mentioned by participants was bringing science and society closer together, showing the openness of scientists and science decision-makers to the public opinion.

“It's fundamental, I think so, it's involving people (...) it can help to reduce distances, so between the political power or the political decision-makers or the scientists and the

population. So, this, this consultation helps to blur those differences” (Participant 4, Group 3)

“I think it brings people closer to what science possibly is, how science is done.” (Participant 5, Group 3)

Other benefits mentioned by participants were:

- To inform, raise awareness and educate society, directly (i.e., by participating) or indirectly (i.e., by preparing their participation by searching for information), including people who can be perceived as denialists such as the anti-vaccine movement:

“There is the benefit that in a public consultation when, for example, in this specific case, in the case of the anti-vaxxers, the moment we marginalise a group (...) the moment we give up trying to call out that group, that group gains strength and followers. However, if we waste a little time and try to explain and even debate with that group, so that other people can watch that debate... [we can inform people].” (Participant 2, Group 2)

“When people see these groups and want to participate, people also start looking for more information on that subject, and that also aims at a more informed community that knows more about the subject.” (Participant 6, Group 2)

“Besides the scientific part, there’s a very important part, which is raising awareness. And, for example, in the case of bats (...) regardless of whether there’s any concrete data, if people just realise that there are bats around them, look up at the sky at night...” (Participant 2, Group 3)

- To clarify doubts about the topics under discussion, such as the vaccination of young children as discussed in case 3:

“So that people could be enlightened” (Participant 3, Group 1)

“Demystifying ideas associated with the vaccine.” (Participant 3, Group 3)

- To get the opportunity to hear different perspectives about the topic, including arguments that contradict own’s view:

“It’s important for people to participate, because sometimes hearing someone speaking brings up another idea that perhaps hadn’t crossed our minds.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

“In a debate where there is contradiction, I can dispel some of my doubts.” (Participant 2, Group 2)

- To allow new ideas to be considered by scientists in their research:

“A question may arise that hasn’t been thought of. “It’s true. That gentleman or lady said this, this and this...” Why not? We can consider this variable in whatever study we’re doing” (Participant 2, Group 1)

- To create a sense of belonging to science:

“It also conveys some sense of belonging to people. “I can participate, I have an important role in describing this...” A sense of belonging.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

Devaluing public opinion

Some participants also shared their concerns about the consequences of devaluing the opinions of members of the public that are shared in a public consultation, if this ‘devaluing’ of public opinion is perceived by society, and which may lead to frustration and feelings that public opinion was never wanted, and that a ‘real’ consultation did not happen: “*he problems can be that if the final government or political decision goes against what the majority of people have discussed, they can feel frustrated and their opinion is not valued.*” (Participant 4, Group 2)

(Lack of credibility) of the data collected by participants

Finally, participants also pointed out as a problem the possible lack of rigour in data collection and the need for data to be validated by scientists:

“The collection of data by the general population, I think it’s something that can even generate more doubts about the credibility of the data.” (Participant 3, Group 1)

“The only thing you need to do in order to carry out an initiative of this calibre is to make sure that you can check the veracity of what people send. Because otherwise, I could be saying that I took a photograph here in Entre Campos of an extraordinary species of beetle and then it was in Porto...” (Participant 3, Group 3)

Public involvement and trust in science

Partial involvement – not in decision-making

In general, results suggest that there was some mistrust of the reliability of science (studies or projects) that involve public participation, particularly in the collection of data. This is particularly interesting when considering the close relationship between the sample and science. It seems that most participants (researchers and science students) do not trust that laypeople would conduct a rigorous data collection. People’s lack of training and skills for collecting data in a methodical and rigorous way is perceived as an obstacle to trust in science:

“And the training involved in research? Because observation isn’t just about observing, and as we know, observing human behaviour has a lot of issues that we have to be trained to deal with.” (Participant 3, Group 4)

For most participants, researchers can never be totally replaced by laypeople.

Also, as discussed before, participants did not feel confident about letting the general public to be involved in the decision-making process about scientific issues, mainly if they are health related.

“The point that I find most problematic – since we’re discussing trust in science – is that I think this kind of thing here is what completely discredits a study. Because how can something that’s already been recommended, that there’s already a group working on it, be open to people’s opinions? (...) Now if it were, for example, a working group wants to ask for random opinions, but not because it’s going to advise the government on anything. It’s already done. It’s already been decided. The policy is ready, and they want to consult because they want to. That’s different.” (Participant 2, Group 4)

However, one of the concerns that emerged from some participants was the frustration of the expectations of those who take part in a public consultation, voice their opinion, share their concerns but have no power in the decision-making.

“Imagine that the [working] group’s decision is contrary to what the majority in the public consultation said. Won’t that increase distrust in the institutions? (...) If people feel that their ideas are not valued, distrust in institutions increases, because what the beneficiary wants is never the same as what the technocrats want.” (Participant 4, Group 2)

Some participants suggest that public involvement can be particularly important for trusting science in the implementation phase, after science-based decision-making.

“Participant 3: When we talk about implementing decisions that come from science and involve the population, then I think it’s really crucial, right?”

Participant 4: I think it also increases people’s trust, if they are properly informed...

Participant 3: And it increases people’s trust. Yeah, that’s it. I think it increases confidence, there should be more of it.” (Group 1)

Still, case 4 presented some interesting exceptions to this rationale. If the public presents photographs and videos of birds or insects that can be easily verified by researchers, this data can constitute an interesting contribution to scientific advancement, as well as bringing society closer to science. Also, the lack of technical knowledge about animals didn’t seem to be such a concern for most of the participants’ trust. Probably, public participation as planned in case 4 has a (apparently) smaller impact on people’s lives, since it is about biodiversity, with the monitoring of animal species. Some participants faced this project as a more “recreational” project than a scientific project: *“If this project is designed to be fun proof, and as long as the researchers verify the data collected, I have no problem trusting science.” (Participant 4, Group 4)*

Involvement in this project and event

For most participants, this was the first time participating in a public consultation. Participants said they enjoyed taking part in the event, found the cases interesting and be pleasantly surprised by how the discussions went.

“My first time, I confess, and it’s super interesting, I like discussing ideas because sometimes (...) we come with a preconceived idea and then at the beginning of the debate new ideas come up and maybe the idea we came with changes. So, I think it’s important. And that feeling of belonging [to science]”. (Participant 2, Group 1)

“I’ve never attended an event like this before. (...) And I think it’s interesting, not only because we’re actually helping people to do research, but also because we get to know other people’s opinions and it’s really interesting to know how divergent opinions are and how those divergences can culminate in a common point.” (Participant 6, Group 2)

“I thought it was great. (...) But I really like these things. I really like taking part.” (Participant 2, Group 3)

“With these small cases that have been presented to us... It motivates me more to wake people up to the need to pay attention to this kind of news. And to actually read between the lines and investigate (...) to alert people to the need to investigate, and not

to read the first piece of news that comes along, and take it as the only information available. (Participant 3, Group 4)

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

Communication channels: Who and what is trustworthy?

Traditional media: trustful sources

Jornal Público, a Portuguese daily and generalist newspaper, was considered by all participants as a trusted source of information. In case 1A, the news was disseminated in Jornal Público's website, which is equivalent to printed newspaper and has the advantage of having the direct links to the original sources of information, such as the original scientific paper published. On the contrary, Correio da Manhã, another Portuguese generalist daily newspaper, is perceived to be a not trustworthy source.

"M: Do you trust Público?"

Participant 3: Oh, no. Undoubtedly. In fact, I'll take it from another well-known newspaper. For example, I trust more in Público versus Correio da Manhã.

Participant 2: For me, Público is on par with Expresso and Diário de Notícias. (...) In fact, I, at Público, whenever something comes out that interests me, I go to see the link." (Group 3)

Social media: Inadequate means for science communication

Social media were considered by most participants in the four groups as not adequate to get information about science. In most discussions, after identifying the channel of communication as a social media channel (Facebook and Twitter), participants almost immediately revealed that they were not sure about the veracity of the information provided in these channels. Some participants showed a high level of distrust towards social media for disseminating many subjects (*"I don't think social media in general inspires much confidence."* – Participant 5, Group 3), including science, due to the possibility of information manipulation and the dissemination of misinformation (fake news) or only partial information, the one that supports our own opinion. Furthermore, the enormous reach of social networks could lead to more people having access to this negative information about science.

"Because the image that is associated with social media is precisely fake news and so I don't believe everything." (Participant 2, Group 1)

"In my opinion, it got off to a bad start when it started out as a Facebook post." (Participant 2, Group 2)

"I don't think Twitter is a channel for publicising science." (Participant 2, Group 3)

"The misinformative pieces, they kind of copy... There's a word that is perfect for that, that's kind of a true news' chameleon. So, it's very common for you to see something this news sent from WhatsApp, for example, or Telegram, which are these media – I think they are very associated with phenomena of this type – that is people making

these messages, which you really have no way of knowing who made them, but with a cute signature. The “director of the X investigation group”, with a text like that, but it has no reference, it’s just that text that people forward to others.” (Participant 2, Group 4)

One group (Group 4) discussed that there are few social media more credible and adequate to discuss science related issues such as ResearchGate or LinkedIn, where you can share posts and create discussion forums for S&T.

The role of mediators in science communication

Regarding science communication, participants mainly discussed the roles of newspapers and journalists. Less mentioned, was the role of scientists and institutions in such communication.

Inform people about how science works

The main role of newspapers and journalists is, in participants’ perspective, to inform people about how science works (e.g., that is a teamwork), what the characteristics of a rigorous scientific study are and tips to help people identifying bad research practices.

“Educating people on what to look for when... Before making a decision, or to check the merits or reliability of what they are consuming in any area. They could have said “it’s important for people to decide what medicine or health treatment they’re going to take, to be wary of this, that, the other...” Because that would give security, you know? He [the journalist] would say that there is research that is supported, he could have complemented with that.” (Participant 3, Group 1)

“Would it be relevant to pass on to the public, to society information about how science is done? Even to the point that science is done as a team? And it’s not a bad scientist who spoils the team’s work.” (Participant 1, Group 2)

Scientific institutions, namely universities and research centers, have also the duty to clearly communicate about how scientific knowledge is produced and to clarify or explain their scientists’ behaviour, if necessary. These arguments emerged during the discussion of case 2A, where there is an institutional statement from the University.

“The Institution must explain what happened, separate itself from the scientist, explaining why and end up maintaining, trying to maintain trust. In other words, this person does not make the entire Institution that we are, we continue to be doing rigorous research.” (Participant 1, Group 2)

“Participant 4: I think this should come next to the email and explain: “This is not true because, because, because”. A sort of dismantling of what is...

Participant 3: Or saying what is...

Participant 2: Like fact checking.” (Group 4)

Finally, scientists should also be responsible for communicating their scientific findings. This was briefly discussed in Group 1.

"I think we [researchers] don't communicate our data. We don't know how to communicate our data, or we are not close to institutions. (...) But we should."
(Participant 5, Group 1)

Identify and verify sources

Although these actors can have an important role informing society about science, they also have the obligation to verify and include their sources of information. Particularly, if the journalist is using a social media channel to disseminate the news.

"We can say that whoever publishes this news item, or the newspaper itself, also has a duty to go and find the sources, on one side and on the other, regardless of what opinion we may or may not have about it." (Participant 4, Group 4)

"I think that if journalists also want to somehow use these social media to send out information and news, they should also use bibliographical references, in this case, the reference of a study." (Participant 3, Group 4)

Again, when using social media, journalists should be clear about their role in the publication, specifying if they are sharing the news in personal or professional name.

"It's one thing to see a post made by Manuel Dias who I don't know who he is. It's another thing to be Manuel Dias whose profile says journalist for the Público newspaper. (...) I have to make this discussion very clear. We don't know that for sure."
(Participant 4, Group 4)

Informing society about scientific initiatives

Communication channels have a crucial importance in informing and capturing participants for such initiatives. Traditional means of communication such as television stations and daily newspapers were suggested as the first and most important to be used to inform people about events such as public consultations. In Portugal, participants identified the four national television channels (RTP1, RTP2, SIC and TVI) and the newspapers with high credibility in society, such as Jornal Público (used in this PDW) or Expresso.

"I think that in this case, in terms of getting people involved in this kind of public consultations and decisions, perhaps the more traditional media. For example, the RTP news is mentioned, a channel, a television station that perhaps reaches people more widely than the post." (Participant 4, Group 1)

"So, the media continue to be unavoidable. I'm talking about media organisations, not social media, OK? I'm talking about RTP, SIC, CNN, TVI, all of them. Firstly, Radios, not necessarily the ones I listen to, which are TSF and Antena 1, but the radios that reach the most people. Maybe Comercial. Local radio stations too." (Participant 1, Group 2)

Motives for trusting and distrusting channels

Participants identified and discussed much more motives to distrust communication channels than motives for trusting, highlighting once again a negative perspective on science communication that the case studies provoked in the discussion groups.

Investigative journalism

One of the main reasons to trust a science communication channel is its concern to listen to all the actors involved in the story, ensuring that everyone has a voice and can share their perspective. This means that the media should look for information that contradicts the main narrative of their news. Therefore, investigative journalism is very important for someone to trust information coming from a channel.

“They went to the researcher and asked. They tried to get more information, it was the researcher who didn’t give it (...) They confronted the researcher and didn’t get any data.” (Participant 3, Group 1)

“Actually, what I thought when I read it was that there was a contradictory.” (Participant 2, Group 3)

Related to this, one of the participants’ concerns is when only one side of the story is told to the public. This was mostly discussed in case 1 and the Covid-19 related topics, but this view was not shared by all participants.

“The data they showed us was always all on the negative side of Covid. (...) Everything that is positive, we are not told. So, in order to discuss a situation, I have to have both sides of the story.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

“The moment he starts with this sentence, he’s already showing a tendency. He’s showing what his tendency is. And if we want to reach everyone, our interest is to reach everyone, not just those who want to hear us, it’s these phrases that need to be eliminated from communications.” (Participant 2, Group 2)

Original Sources

Also identified as a role in the previous section, communication channels need to present links to the original sources for the sake of transparency, as well as identify the people by name and not only by job title or role.

“They talk about a coordinator who doesn’t identify who she is either. She may be a well-known person, but she’s not properly identified.” (Participant 2, Group 1)

Social media

Participants do not trust social media to get scientific information because anyone can quickly write whatever they want without confirming the information or verifying sources. Also, people can share information that support their ideas, but omit or discard contradicting information. Manipulation of the information and fake news were recurrent themes when discussing science communication on social media.

“M: So, you agree that the social media discredits what...”

Participant 5: Do you know why? Because it’s quick to write this, it’s quick to say anything without anyone having read it first.” (Group 1)

“Participant 5: I think that from the moment these social media exist, social media allow completely contradictory messages to be spread at the same time.

Participant 3: And fake...

Participant 5: And fake, exactly. They perpetuate an idea that has already been thought up by the person who is publishing it. (...) Assuming that this was something seen by several people, it's because several people were either engaged with the case, or were agreeing with what was said, which goes along with their narrative.” (Group 3)

This idea appears to challenge the concept of democracy in social media: if on the one hand, anyone has the freedom to use this channel, on opinions that are not informed might compromise public attitudes and level of scientific information; participants seemed to believe that social media might not be a good showcase for science as it is a space open to anyone who wants to comment and share opinions rather than ‘informed’ opinions.

Institutional image

Lastly, participants showed some mistrust towards the university’s statement (case 2A). The two groups discussing this case voiced that this declaration seems a Public Relations manoeuvre, in an attempt to demonstrate a good image of the university – hence putting image over scientific veracity might be problematic to the image of science. However, the university fails to provide clear and strong arguments to exonerate the scientist accused of scientific fraud.

“An attempt to clean up the university’s image.” (Participant 2, Group 2)

“They are trying to defend their researchers against the accusations (...) This office, which is a Communication Office, so it’s a general office, it’s not specialised, basically says that climate change is unquestionable. Based purely and simply on a study by the university itself which, for better or worse, is being contested. So no, I don’t think that’s the best reaction, a Communication Office should have another perception that the scientific process isn’t certain and secure.” (Participant 1, Group 4)

“For me this is almost an opinion piece by someone who is “pulling the strings”. I have zero scientific evidence of the accusation of anything and no defence of who is on the other side.” (Participant 4, Group 4)

Communication and trust in science

The way science is communicated clearly affects the public image of science and people’s trust in science. In participants’ views, the scientific content that is described in the news could cause several damages to science, especially if communication channels give relevance to “bad cases”. For example, cases 1 and 2, where there are doubts about the integrity of the scientific process, were recognised by the majority of participants as doing a “disfavour to science” (Participant 3, Group 1).

To overcome this, some participants suggested that it would be important to explain how science works to help people to analyse critically the information provided in communication.

“The importance of communicating not only science and a scientific discovery, but the scientific process. If we want non-specialists to understand and trust science, etc., etc., we have to explain it to people.” (Participant 1, Group 2)

Participants also referred the inconsistency in the content that is communicated to people, that is, the lack of a coherent and logical discourse where the reader can quickly understand the arguments being presented by the communicator. Otherwise, people feel confused, and confusion leads to distrust.

"I, watching from the outside, I was like, I can't trust this, I can't trust (...) In this case, I don't find any coherence between the beginning and the end, I think it's a bit detached." (Participant 6, Group 2)

"For me, case 2 has contradictions given by the very entity that produces science. The text [statement] of the entity that produces science has contradictions. So, for me it's a red flag." (Participant 4, Group 4)

As we saw before, social media – regardless of who the actor behind it is (e.g., journalists, researchers) – are seen as not trustworthy and therefore, all the scientific content shared on these channels are also seen as not reliable. It seems that there is a spill over effect from distrust in social media to distrust in science. This is probably related to people's previous experience with accessing scientific information in social media (e.g., reading information that was manipulated).

"I think it's us perpetuating messages that have a scientific weight behind them and can have this false connotation that is harmful to science, and how people trust science and how they approach it. However, on social media, this is more than what exists, which is using articles, but to compose a story in our own way." (Participant 5, Group 3)

3.6 Other themes

Scientific literacy

One of the themes that emerged in the four groups of the Portuguese PDW and was transversely discussed across all cases was the scientific literacy and general interest in science from the public. Participants acknowledged that the relationship between the society and science is very complex due to the existence of several groups with different levels of proximity to science. Groups that are more educated, more interested in science and more informed about S&T have the critical ability to analyse the information they receive. This means that their trust in science is not easily shaken by negative news such as lack of integrity. These people often consider these cases to be one-off and not representative of science in general. These groups have similar characteristics to the participants in this PDW. However, participants identified a second set of groups that are less scientifically literate, have little interest in S&T and little knowledge of the scientific process (i.e., how science is done). For these people, news about bad practices in science and poor science communication can have a great negative impact on their trust in science. It is this less science-literate group that the participants are particularly concerned about and who they think may be most affected by the way science is communicated.

"Someone who doesn't know the [scientific] process and who isn't so involved in these processes very quickly gets the picture that ok, there's a lot of fraud here." (Participant 4, Group 1)

"We can conclude that there are two parties, two groups – one more informed and one less. The more informed group believes less in the news and more in science, gives

more credibility to science, and the less informed group tends to be manipulated by what is said, is that it?” (Moderator, Group 1)

“There’s a very high probability that most of Manuel’s followers won’t understand that text as you’re saying, because they don’t have your skills.” (Participant 1, Group 2)

“I think it has to do with interest. In other words, if a person is interested, nowadays, given how science is based, and the fact that there is open science and all that, anyone can get any information, for example, with Google Scholar. You don’t even have to use more professional platforms. (...) For example, with the COVID issues, lots of people have read articles about it. I think it depends a lot on interest.” (Participant 5, Group 3)

3.7 Card sorting exercise

Group 1 – The group decided its final ranking unanimously. First, the most important criterion for the group was the scientific rigour of the information provided in the cases. Case 4 showed, in their opinion, high levels of rigour, positivity and the opportunity for public involvement in science. Despite this, the group highlighted that they did not question the source of this case, contrary to what they did for the other three cases. Second, the consistency of the discourse and the channels used to share the information were also significant criteria. As case 2 was presented in social media (i.e., Twitter), the group considered that this was not “valid” information. Also, the discourse in case 2 was considered inconsistent as the author started with a “sharp attack and ended up trying to appease the situation” (group spokesperson at the plenary session). The suspicion of data falsification in Case 1 revealed lack of methodological rigour and a negative perspective about science and/or scientists, which decreased participants’ trust in science.

Group 2 – The group chose the “consistency” of the information presented as the main criterion to define their ranking. By consistency, participants meant the transparency, simplicity and coherence of the information provided in each case. Cases 3 and 4 generated higher levels of trust in science due to the simplicity of information provided, but also to the opportunity for the general public to share its opinion, regardless of the topics being debated. In the group’s view, as long as public consultations are non-binding, they can be an asset in increasing trust in science. The inconsistency of the discourse in case 2 was seen as a generator of mistrust - “It seems that first the university exposes the researcher accused of fraud and in the end comes to his defence” (group spokesperson at the plenary session). Finally, case 1, shared on a personal Facebook page (which was considered by the group as a poor science communication channel), revealed a biased discourse that will influence people’s opinion on the news.

Group 3 – The group carried out two individual decision rounds since after the first discussion the participants felt the need to change their individual ranking. Also, the group decided to quantify their choices. The two main criteria used by this group were the study’s methodology, which included mainly the level of public involvement and participation in decision-making processes in cases 3 and 4 (7 mentions), and the sources (i.e., channels of communication) (4 mentions). Participants reported to trust more on science when there is the opportunity for the public to be involved in the discussion and decision-making process of science-related issues. However, participants emphasised the importance of scientists validating data collected by the public. Also, to have access to the original sources (e.g., study presented in case 1), it is important for participants’ trust in science as it allows them to read and critically analyse the information

available. Case 2 was disseminated through Twitter and the group considered it an inappropriate source for receiving information on science, which together resulted in low levels of trust in science.

Group 4 – The group was not unanimous and there was a long debate about the final group ranking. Public involvement, provided it is well guided by scientists, was considered a relevant way to build trust in science. Credible sources and references for communicating science were also mentioned as one of the most important criteria for generating trust in science. In case 4, public participation can benefit trust in science, if the study is designed to accommodate participants’ lack of knowledge. As case 3 was communicated through social media (Facebook), the group considered it less trustworthy than case 4. Cases 1 and 2 generated low levels of trust in science due to the way scientific information was communicated, mainly the lack of clarity and tendentious discourse. In case 1, the group considered the discourse as “inflammatory” with suspicions of falsification of data, but “no room for contradiction” (group spokesperson at the plenary session). It was also not clear whether the news shared on a Facebook’s personal page represented the personal opinion of the journalist or the newspaper for which he works. In case 2, communication was poorly written, incongruous, and unclear.

These were the group results for the card sorting exercise. The photos taken to the rankings posted on the wall are available in the Appendix B.

Table 1. Trust in science: Results of the group ranking

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
Case 4	Case 3A	Case 3A	Case 4
Case 3B	Case 4	Case 4	Case 3B
Case 2B	Case 2A	Case 1A	Case 1B
Case 1A	Case 1B	Case 2B	Case 2A

4 Attitudes towards science & technology

In this section, we briefly describe the results from the closed-ended questions from the questionnaires administered before and after the event. Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the Attitudes towards Science and Technology (S&T) before (questionnaire 1) and after (questionnaire 2) the PDW. The full results can be found in the Appendix C.

Table 2. Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

Item	Before			After			Difference in means
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.42	0.50	100.0%	4.39	0.50	100.0%	-0.03
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	2.08	1.06	70.8%	2.13	1.01	69.6%	0.05
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	3.91	1.11	13.0%	3.68	1.25	17.4%	-0.23
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	3.18	0.85	33.3%	3.22	1.00	43.5%	0.04
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2.41	0.80	8.7%	2.65	1.07	17.4%	0.24

Note. N range = 23-24. Items 1, 4 and 5 were inverted.

Item 1 ‘Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable’ showed the highest means in both before and after measures, and 100% of the participants agreed and tended to agree with the idea that S&T make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable. These results are not surprising considering the strong and close relationship to science of most of the participants. On the contrary, item 5 ‘We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology’ revealed the lowest percentage of agreement before the PDW and one of the lowest percentages in the “after” questionnaire. This indicates that participants consider that there is the option to not trust those governing S&T, i.e., there is no unconditional acceptance of the decisions of S&T institutions. Item 2 ‘Science and technology make our lives change too fast’ showed the lowest means in both measurement moments.

The difference in the means between before and after of the five items are minor. Also, the percentage of agreement for item 2 is the only one that slightly decreased from questionnaire 1 to questionnaire 2. For items 3, 4 and 5, there is a small increase in the percentage of agreement. Taken together, these results suggest that participating in this event did not affect participants’ general attitudes towards S&T.

Results of the percentage of agreement for the five items are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Agreement

Note. N range = 23-24

About 95.8% of the participants reported that this was the first time joining an event like this, meaning that only one individual (4.2%) had previously participated in such event.

Table 3. Impacts of event on participants: Results (%)

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	75.0%
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	75.0%
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	79.2%
4. Other	12.5%

Note. N = 24

As show in Table 3, most participants will follow news stories on this issue, but also intend to get involved in events like this in the future and talk to friends and family about scientific issues.

Other answers:

- "Colleagues' knowledge";
- "Contribution to more of my thoughts on the subject. It is more impetus to keep studying this".

Main conclusions:

- In general, participants revealed positive attitudes towards S&T, which can be easily understood considering the characteristics of the sample: high levels of education (around 38% had a Doctoral degree) and close relationship to science (around 74% worked in or with science).
- Participants' attitudes towards S&T did not change substantially between the beginning and the end of the event, after the group discussions. These results can probably be explained by the short time (approximately 4 hours) between the two measurement moments, but also by the relatively homogenous perspective of participants about science and its great importance for society.
- Twenty-three out of 24 participants reported that this was the first time joining an event like this, which might indicate the almost non-existent participation of society in public consultations, in Portugal. Also, in this perspective, the characteristics of the participants who attended the event draw attention to the difficulty in attracting laypeople to PDW. This suggests that individuals participate in these events when they feel confident to talk about the topic because it represents part of their professional life or they have a high personal interest in the topic.
- This event can also contribute to increase people's desire to participate in similar events in the future, as well as to follow news and talk to family and friends about S&T. Despite being only intentions, this indicates that the event can represent a positive contribution for raising awareness among society - including laypeople - of the importance of participating in public consultations.

5 Appendix

A - Certificate of Attendance

 Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science
Projeto *POIESIS*

CERTIFICADO DE PARTICIPAÇÃO

Este certificado é atribuído a

Participante

pela sua participação na consulta pública sobre
confiança na ciência, organizada pelo Iscte – Instituto
Universitário de Lisboa.

3 de junho de 2023

Marta Entradas
Coordenadora do projeto em Portugal

B - Trust in science: Results of the group ranking

Figure 1. Trust in science: General results of the groups' rankings

Figure 2. Trust in science ranking: Group 1

Figure 3. Trust in science ranking: Group 2

Figure 4. Trust in science ranking: Group 3

Figure 5. Trust in science ranking: Group 4

C - Attitudes towards S&T: Results from the questionnaires

Table 1. Questionnaire 1: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	41.7%	58.3%	0%	0%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	33.3%	37.5%	20.8%	4.2%	4.2%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	0%	13.0%	21.7%	21.7%	39.1%	4.3%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	4.2%	29.2%	37.5%	20.8%	0%	8.3%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	0%	8.7%	30.4%	47.8%	8.7%	4.3%

Note. N range = 23-24

Table 2. Questionnaire 2: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	39.1%	60.9%	0%	0%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	30.4%	39.1%	17.4%	13.0%	0%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	4.3%	13.0%	26.1%	17.4%	34.8%	4.3%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	8.7%	34.8%	26.1%	30.4%	0%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	4.3%	13.0%	43.5%	21.7%	17.4%	0%

Note. N = 23

Annex F: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – Spain

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops - *Spain*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Iscte)*

1 Introduction

The Public Deliberative Workshop of the POIESIS project in Valencia was organised following the methodology and using the tools proposed in Deliverable 2.1 "Protocol for the empirical case studies". The protocol ensure a similar methodological approach between the POIESIS consortium members. In Spain, the workshop was organised by INGENIO (CSIC-UPV). The promotion and recruitment activities and the workshop organisation were supported by the private consultancy EMPODERA.

1.1 Set up of the event

1.1.1 Overview of the event

The Public Deliberative Workshop was held In Valencia on the 22nd of June, 2023, from 9.30 to 13.30 hours. Twenty-seven people registered for the event, and twenty attended. The dropout rate, whilst somewhat expected was also greater than expected, given the strategy of recruiting participants relatively close to the date of the event. The event was run by a team of five people from INGENIO (CSIC-UPV) and Empodera.

The venue chosen was the "*Casa de la Ciencid*", the headquarters of the Spanish National Research Council (*Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (CSIC)) in the Valencian region. The venue was selected for a combination of factors. Firstly, it is located in the *Plaza de la Virgen*, in the historic centre of the city, which is a very well-known location and easy to reach by public transport. Secondly, as the building belongs to the CSIC, the use of the different rooms was partially free of charge, as only costs related to cleaning and maintenance were paid. Finally, the venue offered rooms with all the elements necessary to carry out the methodology proposed, including a large conference room and small rooms to work in groups.

The agenda of the event was structured in the following way:

9:30 Reception of the participants. The participants arrived at the venue and signed the attendance list.

Participants were given the informed consent information to read and sign. The *ex-ante* questionnaire about attitudes of citizens towards science was distributed. Both documents were explained and completed during the reception period.

09:55 – 10:15 Presentation of the event. A presentation of the event's purpose, the agenda and practical information was given to the participants. Irene Monsonís Payá gave this presentation representing the INGENIO team.

10:15 – 11:00 Presentation by experts in science communication and debate. The presentation by experts was given by two professionals working at the institutional level in the communication and dissemination strategies of a public university (University Polytechnic of Valencia) and the national research council (CSIC). Their presentations provided an overall view of science journalists' role as communication professionals at public research centres and universities. The experts were:

Luís Zurano, a scientific journalist at the University Polytechnic of Valencia (UPV).

Isidoro García Cano, responsible for scientific communication and dissemination of the CSIC delegation in the Comunitat Valenciana.

After the presentation, a lively debate commenced, and the participants asked questions about the tensions in the relationship between communication professionals at public research organisations and science journalists.

11:00 - 11:15 Coffee-break

11:15 - 12:30 Workshops in small groups. The participants were split into three groups to develop the activities foreseen in the methodology. Two groups used Spanish as a working language, while a third used Valencian, the region's local language.

12:30 - 13:15 Plenary session. The group joined together again to share the results of the small groups in a plenary session. A representative of each group presented the main conclusions reached by each group and the topics that generated more consensus and more dissent.

13:15 - 13:20 Closure and ex-post questionnaire. The event was closed by thanking the participants for their attendance and presenting the next steps in the research. The participants who stayed until the end were asked to fulfil the ex-post questionnaire. All the participants received a gift voucher of 15 euros value to be spent in a local bookshop.

1.1.2 Sampling and recruitment process

The recruitment process combined several strategies to reach people from the public. These strategies combined formal and informal channels and were supported by the communication professionals of the CSIC and UPV and the consultancy Empodera. The strategies and actions put in place can be summarized as follows:

Adaptation of the promotional material provided by WP2 leaders to the local context.

The materials proposed by the WP2 leaders were adapted to the communication strategy in Spain. We created three elements to support the recruitment process:

A landing page hosted at the INGENIO website to update the event information and allow participants to register themselves.

A flyer with the basic information of the event to be shared through formal and informal channels.

A hashtag: #PoiesisVLC

Dataset of different actors to be contacted

A dataset was created to identify the potential actors, both organisations and individuals, that could support the promotional campaign among people from the public. The dataset included actors representing universities and research centres, scientific communication and dissemination

offices, civic society organisations representing the public, companies, and labour parties, among others. Specific communication strategies were designed to reach the different actors in the dataset.

Figure 2 Flier with the basic information about the workshop

Figure 3 Promotional [tweet](#) in INGENIO account

Figure 4 Promotional WhatsApp message

Promotional campaign in social media and newsletters of the partner’s account

The institutional accounts of INGENIO on Twitter and LinkedIn was used to spread information about the event. Also, the [Innovation Newsletter](#) at the UPV was used to reach the attention of the university’s stakeholders.

Phone calls and email campaigns to institutions

Several institutions working in the Valencian region were reached via phone call or email to be informed about the event and ask for dissemination among their specific public.

WhatsApp and groups on online platforms

More than 150 people were personally reached via WhatsApp from informal channels, including the organizing team’s professional contacts and networks (including different civic organizations). The contacts were asked to share the message among potential interested participants.

As a result of the recruitment process, 27 people registered for the workshop, with 20 people attending on the day of the event. A description of the participants in the event is presented in the following sub-section.

1.2 Participants in the event

Of the 20 participants in the event, 17 agreed to complete the *ex-ante* questionnaire. The data provided regarding their gender, age, job, education and link to science is summarised in the following figures.

Figure 5 Gender of the participants

Figure 6 Age of the participants

Figure 7 Job of the participants

Figure 8 Education of the participants

Figure 9 Link to science of the participants

2 Discursive summary of cases

2.1 Phase 1 – Expert talk

The expert talk included the participation of two institutional professionals working in science communication. The talk was structured in two parts, with each of the experts doing their presentation in turn. However, the experts were asked to interact during their presentation, so both professionals also provided their opinion about the issues presented in both talks. After the experts' speeches, a discussion was opened with the participants.

The first presentation was given by Isidoro García, who introduced the differences between scientific communication and scientific dissemination. The introduction of the differences between these two terms allowed a reflection on the role of the actors and the aims and purposes of scientific communication and dissemination. He also reflected on the role of institutional professionals in communication and how they cooperate with researchers to support the communication of their research results. He also explained the criteria used to consider information relevant, such as the scientific relevance and social interest of the research results, and the tools institutions use to nurture the relationship with scientific media and journalists, such as press releases and press conferences. In conclusion, this first talk was a baseline to understand the basics of scientific communication and dissemination and for reflecting on the relation of media and society with the research institutions, such as universities and research centres.

The second part of the expert talk was introduced by Luis Zurano, who presented cases of success in scientific communication focused on Covid-19 and climate change. During the talk, the need for further material resources to professionalize and improve the attention to the needs of the researchers to improve the communication of their research results was commented on. In this regard, it was reflected how during the crisis of Covid-19, some specific needs became evident. Some examples were presented about the difficulties some researchers found in adapting their communication skills to the expectations of media journalists. The challenge for communication professionals to identify scientists that could quickly react to media demands was also discussed. In parallel, the opportunities that the crises offered to talk about science and increase the visibility of the work undertaken by the research institutions was also stressed.

During the debate, the attendees asked questions related to:

- How communication professionals manage the private interests of private media, and how the media and scientific journalists modulate messages?
- How the information and reactions of the public to the institutional media shared in social media is managed by research institutions?
- What are the benefits of adapting the scientific terminology to a level of understanding of the public? What is the best way to do it?
- Do experts typically count on the support of graphic designers or infographics professionals to support scientific communication, in order to make the information more attractive to the public.

2.2 Phase 2 – Focus groups

2.1.1 Group 1 – Cases 1A, 4

During the focus groups, Group 1 worked on Case 1A and Case 4. Case 1A presented a scientific news item in the digital press of an important and well-known international newspaper. The news item in Case 1A dealt with research on the development of a drug to prevent COVID-19. The study presented in the news had been questioned by the scientific community due to methodological inconsistencies. Case 4 presented an open science project in which citizens could participate in the collection of data on biodiversity in urban, rural and natural environments.

There was a consensus in Group 1 regarding addressing the different issues of the two cases worked on. It is perhaps necessary to assume as a bias the university education of all the participants and that most of them remain directly or indirectly linked to universities.

It is worth highlighting that Group 1 strongly supported the reliability of public media channels as a tool for the social dissemination of scientific content. This was especially when compared with the relatively low trust the Group saw offered by other tools such as social networks, a discussion that arose in the debate about Case 1. In this regard, the need to work specifically with younger audiences was highlighted, with the objective of bringing them closer to science and steering them away from pseudoscientific positions that are particularly prominent via social media.

The element that generated the most controversy in the group was citizen participation in science in Case 4. The central object of the debate was whether participation is an opportunity for science to dialogue with society or whether it is a tool for scientific dissemination and education. The timing or place of citizen participation was also debated, whether as part of the choice of lines of research or in the framework of research already underway. Finally, risks of citizen participation were identified, such as the introduction of bias in research processes. In this sense, some participants viewed citizen participation as potentially undermining the rigour of research processes.

2.1.2 Group 2 – Cases 1B, 4

Group 2 worked on Case 1B and Case 4. Case 1B presented the same news item as Case 1A, but instead of being a news item published in a recognized digital newspaper, it was information shared on the social network Facebook by a journalist of the newspaper. Case 4 consisted of the same citizen science project described in the previous section.

The workshop dynamics operated to generate considerable consensus. This may have also been accentuated by the relatively homogeneous socio-economic backgrounds of all members of this group.

In the discussion of Case 1B, Group 2 concluded that social networks are not a credible source of information about science or for disseminating science. Group 2 stressed the importance of ethics for researchers and journalists when reporting on scientific topics.

Regarding citizen participation in reference to case 4, the group believed that people must be prepared and informed sufficiently beforehand about their roles, so that consultations or other activities are helpful and citizens can contribute effectively.

Finally, a debate was generated on the scientific method and the need to adapt it to the contexts in which it operates because, as Unamuno said, "science is a very rigorous way of being wrong". This phrase expresses an approach close to a debate that ran as a kind of thread across the workshop.

2.1.3 Group 3 – Cases 2B, 3B

Group 3 worked on Cases 2B and 3B. Case 2B presented a Twitter thread in which a researcher from a well-known university summarised a scandal about falsification of data related to global warming. As the thread explained, the scandal was triggered by the leak of emails from a research centre, which made it appear that there may have been falsification in the taking of samples. The thread concluded with information about an independent investigation that defended the integrity of the research, concluding that there had been no falsification of data. Case 3B consisted of information shared on the social network Facebook, presenting a public consultation to review a COVID-19 vaccination protocol and provide comments. The public consultation consisted of gathering comments by citizens interested in providing input to the vaccination policy proposed by experts and technicians.

The two cases worked on in this group have in common that the information or dissemination tools are social networks, Twitter (Case 2B) and Facebook (Case 3B). These two networks generated a debate in the group that hinged on the tension between two pillars: the potential of both dissemination tools to reach large audiences versus the ease of manipulating and falsifying content on these networks.

Regarding Case 2B, the group highlighted the need for references (links to study papers, bibliography, universities, etc.) that support the positions or arguments people defend in social network debates. Otherwise it is very easy for 'false' arguments to undermine the credibility of what is being disseminated. There was consensus that the communication of scientific issues through social media might negatively affect how citizens perceive science.

While discussing Case 3B, citizen participation in science was also the subject of debate. When to integrate participation of citizens? What is the appropriate scope of participation? and What citizens profiles are more appropriate for participation in specific issues, among others, were the elements of the debate in the workshop. Around these questions a variety of positions were held by participants, again reflecting concerns about whether the quality of science could be impacted by citizens' participation, but also more strongly expressing a deal of uncertainty about what precisely the integration of citizens in science should aim to achieve.

3 Integrity and integration & trust in science

3.1 General attitudes towards science

As described above, the three focus groups included many people connected to universities and with high levels of formal education qualifications. The participants' backgrounds may well affect their general view of science, which was positive. In Groups 1 and 2, there were some debates about the general character of science and research, the relevance and importance of the scientific method, and what can be considered to be 'doing good science'.

In these discussions, no negative attitudes towards science were presented. Participants' main concerns towards science were related to the scientific system and how science communication is done. Specific cases in which a lack of integrity or accuracy occurs in the presentation of research was viewed as resulting in the generation of mistrust just in those specific cases. Confidence in science in general was not seen as threatened.

"I said it does not affect the way I see science because it is science. It is questioning hypotheses, data and, therefore, doubt. It is rational."

"I also said no, because science is one thing and how it is communicated is another, and it complements it by saying I believe in science, in people and all the effort involved in the process, right?"

However, there was a very critical statement made in the course of the initial intervention of a participant in Group 3. This statement represented mistrust in science as strongly related to conflicts of interest. The statement reflected a particularly strongly held perception on the part of this participant:

"We are used to malpractice as in the case of genetically engineered organisms in agriculture and food, which are designed to respond to those who pay for them, such as stopping glyphosate toxicity tests on day 40 because it has been shown that longer tests do show toxicity."

Other comments reflecting negative attitudes towards science were made during the debates regarding the cases. These comments did not amount to a profound or fundamental critique of the science system but were contextualised comments on perceptions in specific cases.

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

Across the three Groups, participants presented different reasons for trust and distrust in science. A summary of the factors that were mentioned and discussed are presented in Table 18.

Confidence in the scientific method was the main factor driving trust in science. In addition, some factors and strategies used to reinforce and contrast the veracity of scientific information were mentioned. Specifically, the reputation of the source of information and the perceived rigour of individual science communicators were mentioned as factors determining participants' trust in a particular piece of information. There were also several mentions of the use of strategies based on searching a variety of information sources to check the veracity of scientific information.

Given the generally positive view of the scientific method among participants, the mention of factors with a negative impact on their perception of science consistently referred to specific cases. Lack of scientific integrity was mentioned as a factor generating bad perception on the actors involved. The case presented regarding a possible case of falsification of data was considered to go against the very essence of science (objectivity and transparency) and creating suspicion towards experts (scientists). Similarly, the existence of conflicts of interest was mentioned as a factor of mistrust. In this sense, the funding of experiments by actors with economic interests was mentioned as a generator of mistrust.

There were also several references to the mistrust generated by the way science is communicated and the communication channels used. The presentation of isolated scientific results was presented as a possible factor of mistrust because they could go against the scientific consensus. The existence of opposing scientific opinions was defined as a reality that can generate public discomfort. The inevitable lack of information about the long-term consequences of science and uncertainty regarding the use of scientific results were also discussed as factor impacting on public trust. The use of inappropriate language in science communication was also mentioned in this context.

Finally, references to the distrust linked to the dissemination of scientific information through social networks were reiterated. In this regard, the impact of presenting information and arguments ‘superficially’ in social media formats was mentioned.

Table 18 Factors that affect trust in science

Affecting trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability of the scientific method • Track record and reliability of the source publishing scientific information • Perception of rigour in the communication style of scientists • Contrasting variety of sources, cross-checking information from various sources
Affecting mistrust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty and lack of information about the long-term consequences of scientific results. • Falsification of data • Lack of relevant data • Information on isolated research • Conflicts of interest • Conflicting scientific opinions. • Social networks as channel for scientific information • Superficiality of information and arguments on social media • Inappropriate language

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

In general, in all three groups there was a similar attitude towards research integrity as an issue connected with specific cases where scientists did not execute “good science”. Discussions regarding the lack of scientific integrity addressed this issue with respect to the type of information that would be necessary to assess the veracity and scientific rigour of the research. Throughout the discussion, limited concerns were referred to regarding research integrity. The major concern referred to conflicts of interest related to the actors who fund research, in which

science can be overly influenced by the objective of supporting the economic interests of these investors.

Participants' attitudes about scientific integrity were uniformly positive and the topic was not explored in any depth in discussions. No reflections on personal experiences or interests in mediatized cases emerged.

However, participants did explore the role of different actors in dealing with cases of lack of ethical integrity. On the one hand, the need to provide sufficient data to be able to determine the veracity and reliability of the method and analyses carried out was addressed. It was felt that these requirements should be extended to professional colleagues, i.e. to other scientists who, when faced with a case of a possible lack of integrity, would contribute to cross-checking the scientific information in question. The following quote exemplifies these shared concerns:

"It would be good if those who have done the study and the critics had a kind of confrontation, a discussion to clarify these doubts. That is to say, if there is a well-defined group of people who are against it, a debate can be held if the issue is very important. To see..."

With regard to institutional actors, the responsibility of both universities and research centres to communicate and provide information on the practices in question was mentioned on several occasions. The responsibility of the media with regard to the information they provide was also mentioned. In this sense, the need to avoid giving information space to pseudo-sciences was mentioned.

From the analysis of the participants' discussions, it appears that the majority's confidence in science is not affected by awareness of specific cases of lack of scientific integrity. The participants analytically tried to identify what elements would be necessary to be able to assess integrity in the cases presented, but the majority did not express a concern beyond the specific case. However, there was one participant who did express concern about the impact of these cases on their general perception of science (see section 3.1).

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

Participants did not share previous experiences of participating in science as citizens. and as can be seen from the analysis of the questionnaires completed by them, the level of experience of participation in these activities is low. However, there were debates reflecting a variety of arguments regarding citizen participation in science, reflecting different perceptions.

The cases presented on public integration in research were described as interesting and aroused the interest of the participants in this type of initiative. The participants expressed their willingness to participate in research through these types of citizen science activities as well as in events to foster research and scientific discussions with citizens. A general comment in one of the groups expressed the importance of promoting the results of the integration exercises. Willingness to participate would be significantly reduced if the outputs of the research did not include the results of the participative activities.

Despite the general interest in participation, there were some concerns raised regarding the way in which the research would be designed to include citizens, how the results would be used, and a desirable level of participation of citizens in science.

On the one hand, resistance to participation was expressed due to a lack of knowledge on the part of citizens in decision-making. The following comment reflect this opinion, although this opinion only emerged in one group and was advanced by a single participant:

"Let's say that participation in itself for me is not a disadvantage, it is a plus, an added value. The disadvantage I see is if the participants start to decide, because as we have said in science since Thomas Kuhn, and much earlier, science has a method and you have to understand the language of science to then propose a decision, so participation. [...] The dangerous thing is then to decide, that the participants have the possibility to decide because you need knowledge to do that. The disadvantage is that it is useful for people to think that they already know about vaccines, so it would be dangerous, it would be chaotic."

Different factors that support the idea that citizens should be involved in the science and research process were also discussed. The importance of non-expert knowledge, of opinions and contextual knowledge on the part of citizens, was described as important and appeared in all three groups.

Regarding the degree of participation in decision-making, there were two positions. On the one hand, a group of participants expressed concerns about the capacity of citizens to make decisions on issues that are considered technical and for which they do not have specific training or skills. In order to solve the possible lack of knowledge to take decisions, different strategies were proposed, such as linking the level of involvement to the level of knowledge:

"I think you have to involve at different levels, the most informed as leaders of citizens, maybe they can get more involved. The public that has little information, that they are not necessarily part of the decision, but just participate to receive information."

On the other hand, a second group advocated involving citizens, especially in the early stages of research, to decide on the societal acceptance and relevance of research.

"I believe that participation should be from the origin, from the degree of decision on what research is carried out. Science researches to solve problems, and I think that research orientations are very much influenced by economic or academic interests, and research is not done on problems that can transform people's lives. Do we want to go to Mars? "

"A public consultation on what to research? I don't get into how, but for example, in the Valencian huerta, research is done on things where neither the farmers, nor the neighbours, nor the town councils participate... I see that there is a gap. Science must respond to social needs, to the real needs of the people."

The benefits and problems identified by the participants regarding integration in science are linked to the concerns expressed about the difficulty in managing different degrees and types of knowledge and their related opportunities. The list of benefits and problems is summarized in Table 19.

Table 19 Perceived benefits and problems of public involvement in science

Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awakening interest in and recognition of science • Increased scientific literacy • Building stronger, context- and socially-based knowledge • Increased acceptance of policy • Better alignment of policies to the expectations of citizens
Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of bias (economic, political, religious) • Time demands in order to adapt language and methods • Selection of participants and design of processes to facilitate participation of diverse stakeholders • If participation includes decision-making, targeting to avoid the use of resources on topics that may be socially interesting but not scientifically interesting (e.g. chemtrails)

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

Throughout the discussions in the three groups, opinions and reflections were interspersed about the credibility of different communication channels with regard to scientific information.

A clear difference was perceived between the perception of traditional media and social media. For example, certain TV channels were mentioned as very reliable sources of information and were associated with a high expectation of responsibility for the scientific information they share. However, other TV broadcasters were named for sharing and promoting less scientifically rigorous debate. These two examples showed that the participants had a clear idea of how much trust or distrust they could have in the traditional media. This capacity to discern between trusted and less trusted outlets within traditional media was clearly expressed. Specific factors linked to trust in traditional media were their perceived legitimacy, the number of years they had dedicated to communicating scientific issues, and the ownership of the media channel. Publicly owned media consistently referred to as being more rigorous in dealing with scientific stories or information.

However, with social media, the perception of the reliability of information was not so strong. Participants reported different strategies to overcome this lack of confidence in social media sources. Firstly, participants expressed resistance to the communication dynamics of social media and the purposes for which they are used, such as generating controversy rather than constructive dialogue. In addition, there was reflection on the lower quality of the information shared (possible lack of sources and links) and, above all, the need to cross-check information received via social networks. Some participants described certain social networks as emotional and unprofessional, and confirmed their systematic distrust of the information shared by these networks. Finally, the lack of checks on the information that can be shared on social networks was mentioned as a factor fermenting distrust. In traditional media or in these organisations use of social media profiles, the existence of an institution that reviews the content and is expected to be responsive to it, provides an expectation that is not present in information shared on social media by other actors.

We can conclude that participants consider they have more references to evaluate the reliability of scientific information in traditional media. When information is disseminated through social networks they develop strategies to verify its reliability due to the evident distrust they have regarding information transmitted through social media channels.

3.6 Concluding remarks by the groups

Due to time pressure and the need to several participants to leave slightly before the end of the event, the collective discussion was prioritised over the formal card-sorting exercise. The event ended with the participants sharing the main conclusions of each group, perception about how they worked, and presenting the issues that had generated the most consensus and dissent.

Group 1 highlighted the debate on the degree of participation in science that is appropriate for citizens. In support of participation, they mentioned that it could make citizens feel involved in S&T decisions and improve their perception of science. They also highlighted the risk of possible biases that could be introduced into scientific methods through citizen participation.

Group 2 highlighted the diversity of participants' background opinions and areas of expertise with regard to the cases discussed. They described their discussion as synergetic and constructive, with all participants contributing to the debates. They emphasised that they came to common points of view after the arguments and that the session worked well and they enjoyed the process. Regarding the substantive results, they highlighted that they concluded that social networks are not the most relevant source of scientific communication due to the need for greater rigour in these channels. Regarding citizen integration, they mentioned that they considered the preparation phases to be important to ensure an appropriate level of preparation of citizens. Finally, they highlighted that during the discussion, there was a constant need to contextualise the answers and arguments being made. They considered that this indicates that there are no universal answers to the questions raised in the individual cases.

Finally, Group 3 highlighted debates about social media and whether it informs or misinforms users of these channels. Negative feelings and attitudes associated with the accessing of confusing information on social media was reiterated. Referring specifically to one of the cases worked on, this group highlighted that controversy on social networks negatively affects the perception of science because it generates negative emotions and feelings. They also reflected that in the cases they worked on, the lack of links to information sources was a barrier to building trust, but that this was not always how social networks were used and that there were other strategies for sourcing information that worked better. In reference to citizen participation, they highlighted that there was an intense debate on the appropriate degree of participation and that the combination of different means of participation can be an appropriate way to respond to citizens' needs.

4 Attitudes towards science & technology

This section presents the results of the questionnaire distributed to the participants before and after the session. The results include the responses of the seventeen *ex-ante* questionnaires and the thirteen *ex-post* questionnaires completed. One of the *ex-post* questionnaires was not fully completed and some items are reported regarding this questionnaire for twelve respondents.

Regarding the attitudes toward science before the event (see Table 20), there is a very positive majority attitude among the participants that science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable. At the same time, however, a large majority of respondents also say that science and technology make our lives change too fast. However, for the last three items, the percentage of agreement is in the minority. Only a limited number of participants confirmed their agreement with the statements that we depend too much on science and not enough on faith, that scientists know best what is good for people, and that there is no option but to trust those governing science and technology. The results before and after the event for the different items had little variation as can be seen in the table below and Figure 10.

Table 20 Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

Item	Before			After			Difference in means
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.29	1.05	94.12%	4.42	0.67	91.67%	0.12
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	2.06	0.75	82.35%	1.67	0.65	91.67%	-0.39
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	4.18	1.7	11.76%	3.42	1.38	25%	-0.76
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	2.76	1.03	11.76%	2.83	1.27	25%	0.07
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2.29	1.36	23.53%	2.5	1.24	25%	0.21

Note. N range = 17 (before); 12 (after)

Regarding participants' previous experiences in events similar to the one developed in the framework of the Poiesis project, only two people indicated that they had previously participated in events with these characteristics, while eleven people reported that they had participated in events similar to the one developed in the framework of the Poiesis project.

Figure 10 Attitudes towards S&T: Before and after

Note. N range = 17 (before); 12 (after)

Participants were asked about the impact of the event on themselves (see Table 21). A majority of participants stated that they would participate in similar events in the future and a high percentage would follow news about these issues. Half of the respondents indicated that they would talk to their friends and family about the topics of the event. Lastly, one participant indicated that she would use the event and its content as a resource to plan sessions on Responsible Research and Innovation.

Table 21 Impacts of event on participants: Results (%)

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	83%
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	50%
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	67%
4. Other	8%

In conclusion, the participants in the event showed positive attitudes towards science, possibly influenced by the fact that a large majority of them had higher education or were developing their professional careers in related areas. The event did not produce major changes in the participants' attitudes towards science, although it did have a positive impact on their willingness to participate in similar events and to stay informed and share information about the content of the event.

5 Appendix

Figure 11 Pictures of the session

Table 22 Questionnaire 1: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	53%	35%	0%	0%	6%	6%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	18%	65%	0%	6%	0%	12%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	0%	12%	35%	0%	47%	6%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	6%	6%	65%	6%	18%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	6%	18%	18%	18%	41%	0%

Table 23 Questionnaire 2: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	50%	42%	8%	0%	2%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	42%	50%	8%	0%	2%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	8%	17%	33%	8%	33%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	8%	17%	50%	0%	25%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	0%	25%	33%	8%	33%	0%

Annex G: National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – United Kingdom

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

National Report: Public Deliberative Workshops – *United Kingdom*

**Project title: Probing the impact of integrity and
integration on societal trust in science**

Project acronym: POIESIS

Grant Agreement no.: 101057253

Lead partner for this deliverable: *Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Iscte)*

UK report

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London, 21 August 2023*

1 Introduction

1.1 Set up of the event

Date and place of London events

The deliberative events in London took place over three evenings on 4, 5 and 6 July 2023 at the *Marchmont Community Centre* in Central London, which was a very convenient location to organise such events.

In total we had five groups of participants arriving to the sessions. On 4 and 5 July we had group A from 18.00 to 19.30 and group B from 20.00 to 21.30; on 6 July we had one group between 18.00 and 19.30. Thus, we had five sessions in total, each lasting 90 minutes.

The London team opted for a series of deliberative events over three days rather than a single 'deliberative event'. We anticipated that a single 'deliberation day' was unlikely to succeed in Central London for several reasons: there is too much urban distraction for people to join a time-extended event of half a day or more in splendid summer weather; there was also much talk of looming industrial strike action in public transport, so a larger event on a single day would have been risky to organise. Hence, the London team decided to spread the risk and to organise events over three evenings rather than one day. Our concerns were borne out and allowed us to be more focused on the specification of participants for the events, and invited people turned up as planned.

Recruitment of participants

We recruited participants for the events with the help of a professional recruitment service (Apogee London) on the basis of socio-demographic specification. We discussed the selection criteria with Apogee and provided a tabulated grid for each session (see Appendix 5.3).

The event was advertised by Apogee to their panel of social media contacts (N=6000), mainly based in Greater London and the Southeast: as '*a discussion of trust in science, the attitudes towards science and concerns one might carry*'.

This elicited 350 (6%) self-selected responses to the call-up. These were further reduced to 65 'relevant responses' (20%) defined by our specifications; these were invited to join the deliberations. Finally, 45 persons were committed for the sessions by phone, 42 turned up (93% / 65% of invites). Table 1 below lists these steps of the recruitment process.

Each group was to have 9 participants. In the end, we had a turn-up of 42 participants across all five groups. The entire recruitment process went smoothly and was successfully on target in terms of specifications. The professionalism of the service is reflected in this result. Participants also received a cash incentive of £45 + £15 travel expenses. The total cost of the five session was around £6000 (£1200 per group), including venue rental, recruitment, consultancy, and refreshments on the day.

Table 1: the recruitment process

Focus group recruitment process - July 2023		
	N	Response rate
Panel of addresses	6000	=1
Responses received	350	0.06
Selection on grid, phone contacts	65	0.19
Target 5 groups @ 9 persons	45	0.69
Turn up on the day	42	0.93

Moderation of deliberations

All sessions were moderated by the London team: the discussions were led by Dr Bankole Falade and Professor Martin W Bauer; Ms Hannah Bunt was sitting in the background taking notes, preparing the card sorting exercise, and writing observations on the discussions. Bankole Falade secured the recording from a microphone to a computer, and on a mobile phone as back-up. And indeed, for group 3, we encountered a problem with the microphone recording in the first 10 min, and we needed to merge the phone and the microphone recording to create the final recording file.

Martin Bauer also acted a ‘expert in residence’ to address any particular question of a technical nature that would arise. This turned out to be hardly necessary over these proceedings, except in the case of the Climategate of 2009, which nobody but one person (in group 3) in the groups remembered as living memory. So, Bauer gave a short introduction of the events in 2009 at the University of East Anglia.

1.2 Participants in the event

Who participated?

The London deliberations involved five groups of participants, specified as follows:

- Group 1 – parents with younger children: 25-40 years of age, ethnicity and gender mixed, with young children, socio-economic C1/C2, basic education.
- Group 2 – parents with older children: 40-60 years of age, ethnicity and gender mixed, C1/C2, older children at university or with aspirations to engage in further studies.
- Group 3 – climate action sympathisers: 30-50 years of age, sympathisers of climate activists but not themselves activists, ethnicity and gender mixed.
- Group 4 – NHS workers: 30-50 years of age, ethnicity and gender mixed, having worked in frontline NHS (National Health Service) during the COVID-19 pandemic 2020-2022; we recruited a medical doctor, several nurses, and ambulance drivers.
- Group 5 – (post-)doctoral researchers: 25-35 years of age, ethnicity and gender mixed, currently working in an active research environment. We had electrical engineers, a medical sociologist, an educational psychologist, a public health researcher, and a clinical trials technician.

All five groups reflected the diverse demographics of Greater London. Table 2 below presents a sociodemographic breakdown of our complete sample (for further details, including a sociodemographic breakdown per group, see Appendix 5.5).

Table 2: Sociodemographic data from the complete sample

Demographic	Category	Count	Percentage
Age	18 – 24	0	0%
	25 – 29	3	7.1%
	30 – 34	13	31%
	35 – 39	6	14.3%
	40 – 44	7	16.7%
	45 – 49	5	11.9%
	50 – 54	3	7.1%
	55 – 59	5	11.9%
	60 – 64	0	0%
	Over 65	0	0%
Gender	Male	19	45.2%
	Female	23	54.8%
Education	Primary education	0	0%
	GCSEs or equivalent	4	9.5%
	A-Levels, AS, NVQ Level 3 or equivalent	11	26.2%
	Bachelor’s degree or equivalent	13	31.0%
	Master’s degree or equivalent	10	23.8%
	Doctorate (PhD) or equivalent	4	9.5%
Do you consider yourself to be professionally involved with science?	Yes, I am a scientist/researcher	6	14.3%
	Yes, I am a student	2	4.8%
	Yes, it is part of my work	4	9.5%
	Indirectly or occasionally	6	14.3%
	No/Not really	22	52.4%

Note: Some questions contained missing values and therefore do not add up to 42

Data corpus

Table 3 below outlines the structure of the resulting data corpus: we secured 7.5 hours of recording in MP3 format; these were transcribed with help of the transcription software Otter.ai, resulting in 250+ pages of transcript (ca. 70,000 words). All transcripts were manually edited by a member of the team.

We also have results of the card sorting exercise for each group, where ‘factors of trust in science’ are grouped or ranked according to ‘importance’. Finally, we have written observations on the conversational dynamics of each of the groups.

Table 3: the structure of the London data corpus

Group	Demographic	Quest 1	Quest 2	Card sort	Observations HB	Recordings MP3
1	Parents with younger kids	X	X	X	X	X
2	Parents with older kids	X	X	X	X	X
3	Climate action sympathisers	X	X	X	X	X
4	NHS workers	X	X	X	X	X
5	(Post-)doc researchers	X	X	X	X	X

2 Discursive summary of cases

2.1 Expert input and group dynamics

We had no specific experts invited to talk to the group; we wanted the deliberations to be largely unprompted on the ‘circumstances and factors of trust in science’. One among the moderators acted as ‘expert’ if such input was required. This was only necessary to provide context for the two case studies on ivermectin as a potential COVID treatment and Climategate.

2.1.1 Notes on the group dynamics

Group 1 – parents with younger children: a very friendly group of people; two people know each other and one person chats at the start about finding this a really interesting topic; keen to join the discussion. A fair bit of vaccine scepticism in the room; the more sceptical people seem also more vocal and overshadow the others a bit.

Group 2 – parents with older children: quieter group, had to be probed more to speak in the beginning. In this group as well as previous group, the more sceptical wear smart watches, despite voicing strong opinions about the unknown impact of technology. There are two fairly dominant voices because they are very articulate, but they don’t shut others up.

Group 3 – climate action sympathisers: quite an eloquent group; there’s no dominant voice; people listen well to each other and respectfully disagree where applicable.

Group 4 – NHS workers: the participants being healthcare workers is reflected in their domain-specific ideas of science; seems a like-minded group, not too much disagreement – people add a lot on one another’s points; no super vocal voices, though some are quieter than others; the dynamic overall is respectful; maybe one person in the room dominates the conversation a bit; he spoke a lot, and his wife, also present, complimented and reinforced his contributions.

Group 5 – (post-)doc researchers: very polite group of people; there aren’t really any dominant voices, most people engage fairly equally; multidisciplinary group which provides a wide variety of insights which all come to the fore in the discussions. Differences and similarities in academic traditions are equally appreciated amongst the group.

2.2 Outline of protocol and descriptions of groups

We developed a standard protocol for the sessions, accommodating the comparative design of WP2. The London protocol has five phases (see Appendix 5.4). A summary:

- Phase 1: welcome, explaining the purpose of the event, filling in of questionnaire 1.
- Phase 2: discussion of image of science; discussing the responses to questionnaire 1 (in particular the statement ‘we have no option but to trust those governing science and technology’).

- Phase 3: discussion of case studies; starting with case study 1, moving onto case study 2 (We kept case study 2 as a reserve case study in case the discussion of case study 1 was very lively and rich.)
- Phase 4: discussion of factors that may affect trust in science (written on sticky notes by Hannah), and subsequent rank-ordering of said factors upon group deliberation. Discussion of the role of public integration in securing trust in science.
- Phase 5: wrapping up, filling in of questionnaire 2 and giving thanks for participating.

As mentioned above, we held in stock two case studies: one from BBC news on COVID medication (case 1A; a research integrity case study), the other one being an East Anglia University press release on Climategate (case 2A; a public integration case study). The two cases represent opposite situations: the Climategate case study tries to rectitude trust in science once that is in doubt in form of a press release; the BBC report on COVID medication seeks to cast doubt on or even debunk a false scientific claim. We examined how people read and responded to these news items.

Different groups had either the COVID medication case study or the Climategate case study first, depending on which case we deemed should have priority of discussion. In case the discussion was very rich or lively, we would stick to the discussion of only one case study. However, all five groups ended up discussion both case studies.

Table 4: the ordering of case studies for each group

Group	Case study 1	Case study 2
1. Parents with young kids	Climategate	COVID medication
2. Parents with older kids	COVID medication	Climategate
3. Climate action sympathisers	Climategate	COVID medication
4. NHS workers	COVID medication	Climategate
5. (Post)-doc researchers	Climategate	COVID medication

In groups 3, 4 and 5 we also presented a trend for percentage agreement to the question ‘we have no option but to trust those who govern science and technology’ which was asked to several samples of the UK population from 2005 to 2022 (in BAS surveys and others). In 2005 to 2019 the agreement increased; post-COVID it sharply decreased. Participants were asked about their thoughts as to why they think the trend has developed like this.

Figure 1: ‘We have no option but to trust’ graph presented in some focus groups

2.2.1 Group 1 - parents with younger children / Group 2 – parents with older children

Groups 1 and 2 display a rather similar approach to the topics of deliberation. They put forward a somewhat idealised image of science, suggesting that science is good and well-intended and works for the betterment of society, as captured by the sentiment “*trying to make the world a better place*” (P13 FG2, 9:57). However, they also believe that its objectives are ‘polluted’ by external influences of politics, corporate profit, or bad technology (e.g., scary robots). This perspective is illustrated in the statement “*the problem starts the moment politicians get involved*” (P6 FG1, 17:47), a view that resonated with other group members.

While spontaneous associations do not clearly differentiate between science and technology, further discussions reveal a dual image: science is good; technology is good and bad, depending on the actors. This is exemplified by the remark “*the A bomb ... creating a monster*” (P12 FG2, 12:42). Recent developments and challenges in AI and healthcare loom large in this imagination.

Family health events in general, or recently the COVID-19 pandemic, have served as wake-up calls, highlighting the importance of science and the role of pharmaceutical companies. Science comes in various ‘levels of depth’, ranging from school-level teachings to advanced PhD research. Access to science can be limited, compelling people to rely on trust. However, this can inadvertently lead to the suppression of dissenting views, being branded as ‘conspiracy theories’. One such belief is that vaccines do not cure, they only prevent. There are concerns about the ‘hidden secrets’ of science, where people are being experimented on without knowing and corporations control the results (P18 FG2, 16:53).

In relation to threats to trust in science, the corrupting influences of politics and corporate interests loom large. Issues arise when science trickles down. For instance, the introduction of ULEZ (Ultra-Low Emission Zone) for automobiles throughout Greater London is seen as a political move beyond the scientific merits of pollution control and mitigating global warming. People feel like one has no option but to trust professionals: one depends on competent medical advice when

suffering from a condition or relies on the pilot during a flight. Trust in science is equated with trust in your doctor, with personal experiences anchoring opinions. However, here people believe they have alternative options, modelled on fighting your corner with doctors, and particularly so, if you have enough money.

The topic of 'climate change' has little stickiness as conversations revert quickly back to vaccine issues and whether governments are following scientific advice or not. There are worries about shutting up controversy, patronising elites, and participants demonstrate general distrust of mainstream media such as the BBC. In contrast, social media garner more trust "*Yeah, questioning everything anyway, especially what the BBC says*" (P7 G1, 1:05:01). The pace of scientific developments is also a source of mistrust. To some, science is like a "new religion" (P18 FG2, 07:05); there is no alternative, science is "*the best option we have*" (P12 FG2, 28:45); we are born into a religion, but nevertheless we chose our faith with more information (indicating deep ambivalence in G2).

In terms of public integration of science, participants talked about expected transparency, mass mediation of science news exposing the secrets and spreading misinformation, and even the possibility of public voting on science in referenda. However, mass media's credibility faces scepticism: mainstream media are dismissed (notably the BBC), while platforms like TikTok have credibility because of their 'immediacy of the images'.

Throughout the discussions, several core metaphors emerged: science is likened to the 'pilot of an airplane' (with command being in the inaccessible cockpit); science is perceived as a double-edged sword (indicating both potential benefits and harms when used as a weapon) and is sometimes referred to as the 'new religion'.

2.2.2 Group 3 - climate action sympathisers

The image of science is focused on outcomes, in pursuit of practical solutions. This still predisposes people to distinguish science from technology viewing science as good and technology as ambivalent (both good and bad). However, this group struggles with a clear distinction as they recognise the interrelations between the two.

In relation to trust, this group elaborates a critical attitude modelled on their image of 'scientists' themselves. They believe we should all be 'citizen scientists', embodying the sense of questioning and be careful with whom we trust.

The group's discussions on science highlight several perceived key components to science:

- Science refers to collecting something, i.e., data.
- It tries to make life easier, more accessible. Particularly biology and chemistry are used to understand diseases,
- Curiosity is central, just to make sense of things.
- Creativity, developing technology and science.
- Creating opportunities.

Importantly, science is distinctly different from technology (though they do go hand in hand):

- Science is chemistry and biology; technology mainly refers to the internet, AI etc.

- Science is methodology, the way to understand things; technology represents the tools and mechanisms we use.
- It is very difficult to distinguish the two. AI is a hot topic. Technology is associated with more consumerism.
- Technology is in science; putting technology inside, then probably one is serving the other.
- People are generally with scientists *“trying to progress”* (P21 FG3, 20:52). It might be naïve, but they are perceived as working for the greater good.
- When it comes to technology, the picture is more complex. Technologies like cars, the internet, and airplanes are integral to modern life. Concerns arise from unintended effects of both of science and technology, with technology being the primary concern. Notable examples include developments like the gas Nazis ended up using in the gas chambers, as well as controversies surrounding Facebook.
- We also need to consider the motives for investing in technology, or a piece of scientific research. The MMR jab controversy in the late 1990s, particularly in the Wakefield incident, is a case in point.
- Overall, it is difficult to separate science from technology as they are interrelated and bear on each other.

Understanding of methodology includes:

- Peer review, experiments, doing a series of experiments, hypothesis testing, quantification, being objective and rigorous.
- Criticising each other in collaboration; competing with each other.

Building safeguards is necessary because some people have too much power. Some concerns:

- Ethical review boards play a critical role, for example for embryonic stem cell research and emerging technologies. We don't have the international laws and regulations yet for areas like AI algorithms. Navigating these unknown territories requires ethical guidance.
- There is a dilemma: an experiment hurts somebody, but it is still producing true knowledge. Should we stop seeking the truth if the results are harmful? What about the development of weapons for the army to protect us?
- Here come in utilitarian arguments: should you kill five people to save one hundred? Psychological experiments in the 1960s are mentioned (e.g., the Stanford Prison experiment), which lacked ethics supervision.
- When do we shut down an experiment? What about those scientists who developed gas to enhance crops which later was used by Nazis for gas chambers? This example underscores the potential unintended consequences of well-intentioned research.
- With the advent of platforms like Facebook and social media, new challenges like scams and computer viruses have emerged.
- Experiments must not be done on children, not with people who cannot consent. The experiment itself should also be useful/beneficial, and when reporting and publishing the findings. Ethics should be there at every step of the process.

- But ultimately “*distrust comes with the press and how it reports science, rather than the scientists themselves.*”

In the realm of trust, blind faith is discouraged. Just as scientists question, test, and investigate, the public should do the same. Paradoxically, we expect from the public what we wouldn't expect from scientists. Citizens should become 'citizen scientists' and practise the same diligence. They should read from various sources, attempting to connect the dots. Yet, there's this sentiment: “*we have no option but to trust... but we shouldn't*” (P22 FG, 28:58). “*Scientists are fantastic at what they do... but they may not necessarily know how to draw the right conclusions*” (P24 FG, 32:31).

Upon being presented with the graph representing agreement percentages of the statement 'We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology' over time in the UK, participants attributed the trend change post-COVID to increased information. There are echoes of the MMR debate when public scepticism surged. Additionally, participants raise the point that many have begun to rely more on social media rather than traditional media. Also, trust might reside in science, but not necessarily in government.

Regarding the Climategate case study, the risk arises from relying on partners for data.

- The critical focus is on the hackers, who are they and what are their motivations? Their actions risk putting science into disrepute.
- The case study plays with 'questioning everything' which can be weaponised by vested interests (as seen with figures like Trump) to destabilise civil society. There are always tactics to undermine either the research or the individual, even when it comes to 'woke' issues (as mentioned by a middle-aged, middle-class man, P21 FG2, 44:14).
- There is lots of motivation to scare people about climate change. How do we ever truly know the intentions of Dr Jones?
- Simply reading about Climategate is already sowing seeds of doubt. As stated, “*we have lost a bit of trust by reading these first paragraphs*” (P25 FG, 47:31). How independent is the so-called 'independent' inquiry?
- There is an inherent trust in leaks and whistle-blowers. Although they might not conclusively prove anything, they can change public perceptions. Innocent mistakes can be blown out of proportion by vested interests.
- News today is driven by profitability, leading some to make up stories.
- The media landscape is not limited to the newspapers anymore, but has become much wider (P22 FG2, 55:47). There is a lot of chatter on social media that masquerades as news (e.g., Steve Bannon; GB news, Nige Farage). As one participant shared, “*My mother has been radicalised by YouTube ... she is refusing vaccines*” (P22 FG2, 1;21;08). According to the participant, she trusts science, but not from credible sources where she applies self-professed 'critical thinking'. This represents a case of misplaced trust.
- Statistics can be a slippery territory. Participants are aware that one can lie with statistics. Misrepresenting data can lead to exaggerations, such as overhyping health risks associated with cancer (like apple seeds leading to cyanide poisoning, P24 FG2, 58:57).
- Traditional media have a system of accountability, which social media lacks.

- Ironically, it is new technology (AI, social media) that enables this confusion and fosters distrust, causing it to spread and generalise.
- The age factor: young people have different news habits; they don't spend 20 minutes on a news item anymore. People read the headline, but don't click for the detail anymore. This idea extends to science.
- The COVID story underscored the idea that the public needs to be prepared. Emphasising a good scientific grounding from early education is important.

Core metaphors include: *"drilling in rather than looking at"* to describe the effect of social media (P22 FG2, 1:23:18). Additionally, YouTube works like 'club membership', able to deliver sales messages (P21 FG2 1:26:30).

2.2.3 Group 4 - NHS health workers

This group's image of science is dominated by notions of *"health service development and improvement"* (P31 FG4, 6:35). This represents a very managerial idea of science: gather data, provide feedback, improve, change the workplace, ensure the welfare of staff, and service for users, described as 'quality improvements'. It's about figuring out a question, forming a proposal, testing a hypothesis, and applying the results (P33 FG4, 09:34). One participant argues that there is not enough such research (P28, FG4, 1:14:55). There is no separation between science and technology, nor between science and its applications. The emphasis is on utilitarian outcome orientation.

Some further observations:

- There might be good intentions, but that is not sufficient to warrant trust. We need to consider real outcomes: consider 'nuclear fusion' (participant meant nuclear fission, i.e., the bomb, P29 FG4, 24:04).
- It is important that research is done in an ethical manner, whether quantitative or qualitative (P34 FG4, 11:56). Overcoming barriers to dissemination is important. Research has to sound in scientific and medical reasoning and also be ethical (P33 FG4, 13:07).
- People clearly recognise that in the context of treatment plans, patients have a choice and need to give their consent.
- Consent is key. It's about representing patients in the research process. The benefits should be all-encompassing. Data should be collected in a timely manner, without rush, and correctly. Practices should be evidence-based. The cost-benefit ratio of research is also crucial. Research should be safe, leading to positive outcomes, and there should be proper treatments to compare against.
- Ethics demands full information disclosure. Research animals also need to be treated well.
- Trust in doctors varies across generations. Older generations tend to trust doctors more readily, while the younger generation verifies information and consults social media about side effects. People have become more resourceful, seeking out additional information. This might enable them to eventually place more trust in science (P34 FG4, 30:36). However, controversies like the MMR vaccine situation can lead to vaccine scepticism and

reluctance (P32 FG4, 53:06). The perspective is that medical researchers do not know best: *"they don't know the frontline stuff"* (P34 FG4, 23:18).

Misinformation proliferates on sponsored websites. There are discussions about drugs before they are approved by NHS (P28 FG4, 30:06). This places undue pressures on medical services when patients arrive well-prepared with information, even if it is false.

Memories of COVID-19 in 2020/21 loom large among NHS staff. They recall being unprepared, underequipped, and unappreciated. They had incomplete information, felt personally unsafe, and lived through a major failure of a 'Great Nation'. They were scared, even at home, due to the risk of bringing the virus home, resulting in emotional drain.

Climate change is less elaborated on in the discussions. It did not capture their imagination. The primary focus is on distrust in media and seeing institutions deflect criticism from themselves. There are doubts regarding the true independence of institutional review processes.

Core metaphors used include science as "making better medical 'intervention processes'" (management), COVID described as a "movie set" (film), a news story likened to a "near miss", meaning an attempt that failed (ballistic), and "frontline knowledge" contrasted with textbook or theoretical knowledge (military).

2.2.4 Group 5 – (post-)doctoral researchers

This group's perception of how to conduct science is, expectedly, very elaborate and comprises the following notions:

- Following a method, being consistent, proving things, ensuring they are replicable, and identifying associations. *"We don't really do prove things very often"* (P39 FG5, 9:09), pointing towards disproving in a Popperian manner. There's a focus on designing, conducting and improving clinical trials, tracking patients, using statistics and hypothesis testing with numbers.
- Sticking to advanced plans and avoiding practices like p-hacking post-hoc.
- Medical education is different from medical science. However, both are systematic, with a structured approach and integrity.
- Finding a solution to a problem which others have not solved yet. Robotics, for example, is predominantly concerned with finding solutions to problems.
- Starting with the collection of vast amounts of data and refining it. Then apply mathematical modelling, all geared towards improving efficiency of a power system, which culminates in publishing findings and going to conferences.
- Supporting assertions with technical knowledge, theories, and methods. Considering variable assumptions. Focusing on practical impact and significance. Developing and testing for practical application (such as machine learning for power systems).
- Drug adherence is crucial; lives matter more than problems. Questions revolve around how to increase adherence; qualitative methods are used to find out more about these issues in the field of medical sociology.

- Using inductive, inferential approaches for qualitative data and deductive methods for quantitative data in psychology.

Discussions then shifted towards the tension between 'being scientific' and the drive to 'publish results'. Sometimes the structure of research isn't always to advance science but merely to get a paper written and published. In the subsequent paraphrasing of participants' views, a distinction between industry and academia emerges:

- Academics don't seem concerned about finding anything as long as they can get a grant and a paper published. Industry worries about practical applications.
- Context matters: in low-income countries, policy pressures are larger. Research there has a more industrial feel, aiming for tangible improvements.
- 'Publish or perish' pressures on young researchers are awful; The publishing process, where everyone incurs costs (taxpayers, readers, authors, libraries), seems skewed, with publishers' profit margin being a topic of frustration. Publishing becomes a primary driver of academic careers, overshadowing the importance of producing valid or useful findings.
- Trust among peers is key. We trust those whom we know. Reviewing other people's papers shows there is a lot of 'wacky' stuff from unknown sources.
- Journal reputation is another key cue, e.g., for engineers the journal AEEE is the main reference. Crucial variables include how research is published, whether it has undergone rigorous peer review, and who is funding the research.
- Government regulation, especially on technologies like ChatGPT, is not trustworthy. The political realm seems terribly ignorant of emerging technologies.
- Reading the methodology reveals a lot: was the study protocol published in advance? Is the actual study different from the protocol?
- When people are recycling material from other sources, one starts reading more closely: are they referring back to recognised authorities, known authors?
- The Stapel scandal is a case in point: he fabricated data, invited PhDs to use fake data. Retractions followed. This issue of data fabrication wasn't isolated to this case but was also observed during the Covid pandemic.

Public distrust is not the same as researcher distrust. The mediation of research is problematic. As findings leave the lab, sweeping statements are being made by politicians and corporate businesses, while scientists are generally more modest and reserved in their claims.

- Explaining complex science to the general public requires a different language. Most people don't have the prerequisite knowledge. One participant noted: "*the single mother, or mother of four does not have the bandwidth to think about things that don't directly affect her life*" (P39 FG5, 37:40).
- Thoughts as to why the percentage agreement on the 'no option trust' statement declined in the UK post-COVID: the vaccine process is in doubt. Important people are breaking the rules. It is those who govern science.
- There is a difference between 'trust in scientists' and 'trust in governance'. One participant shared: "*we are looking over a year since COVID and this is the winter lockdown, everyone*

actually hated it because it's just miserable ... I did not trust government governing science" (P37 FG5, 40:48).

- Government is generally not listening to science, and especially not during COVID. One participant expressed this sentiment as “*cool, sound good, but we are not going to do that*” (P39 FG5, 41:27). This also applies to other cases, such as medical views on abortion.
- Sensational news can distort risk perceptions. People move quickly from a single case to a general rule. Necessary actions are not taken as a result.

The discussion surrounding the East Anglia 'Climategate' press release highlights the challenges of maintaining credibility in research. Doubt is easily sowed on research with nefarious insinuations, and once cast, it is very difficult to recover from it. This particular case is illustrative of this difficulty.

- Nefarious actors seek to discredit the research; this calls for a defence. Yet, the actual allegations and details of the case remain unclear. What was the allegation?
- It says, 'independent investigation', yet, we know too little about it. Attackers play on stereotypes such as associating China with bad data. We recognise the attempt to discredit climate research, but this news item seems insufficient to convince of 'good research at work' or a 'sound investigation'. Such items get also easily lost in the general noise of other news.
- A lot of effort goes into immunising young people against misinformation.
- The BMA's (British Medical Association) strategy is to advise doctors not to talk to the media at all, but to refer directly to the BMA to avoid accidentally creating false news that discredits the entire profession (P39, FG5, 55:00).
- Nefarious social media logic: echo chambers on the example of Brexit. For example, nothing pro-Brexit ever reached one participant's social media feed, so she did not worry about the vote at all. The same logic applies to vaccine scepticism: they never see the other side. It is very frustrating to work with vaccine hesitancy in these circumstances. It constitutes a mass media breakdown for which no responsibility is taken.

Regarding the BBC's report on ivermectin as COVID medicine:

- The BBC's narrative attracts attention. The participants followed the BBC's arguments that a claim of a drug being 100% effective is not plausible, and that the fact that the trial location was unknown, the data was not public, was highly problematic.
- However, it is not clear what 'inconsistency' really means here. The article is set up to lead toward a 'bad trial', framing that the suspicion lies with Argentina. It is leading article.
- This piece provides incomplete evidence against Carvalho, nor is it in favour of Sheldrick. The BBC is a famously trusted, at least outside the UK. Maybe it requires some requisite knowledge to really appreciate this piece.
- In the case of vaccines, the public have no option but to trust those who give us the vaccine. That is the only one available. They tell us it is safe. We have to trust the governance of the process.

- Solutions include listening to peers and having proficient communication teams. Initiatives like those from the Wellcome Trust promote constructive discussions in communities.
- Though there is a risk of 'Twitter wars' which are not debates but show the public that we are not having confidence in each other. Why should the public have any trust?
- Public involvement is important, but we have to be careful how we engage. As one participant noted: "a *Twitter war*, where people start insulting each other and say, you are ... using swear words etc. out in the open sphere to criticize a scientific paper is obviously not going to build trust" (P39 FG5, 1:13:38). In contrast, involving people and asking for their opinions, gathering focus groups for health or about climate change, that is involving the public. It shows that things are done rigorously, and that we care. Conversely, social media or Twitter wars will have perverse consequences.

Core metaphors used include 'Twitter war', drawing from military parlance.

General comments on all five groups; the notable absences

- No participants actively recalled the 'Climategate' affair at East Anglia University in 2009.
- COVID-19 and related vaccination issues are dominant life experiences.
- Very few misconduct scandals are looming large, and details are hazy: MMR, Wakefield, Stanford Prison Experiment, and vaccine hesitancy (G3); Stapel and data falsification (G5).
- There is no mention of 'moral turpitude' that often hits the headlines as scandals of particular Institutions (e.g., sexual misbehaviour, career bias, financial impropriety).
- The idea of science potentially heading in an undesirable direction, such as prioritising war research over peace initiatives — a significant topic in the 1970s — wasn't raised in discussions about trust.
- Nor is the 'teaching quality' of a university part of this framework of trust in science, which is likely to be a major concern for parents with children in education.
- In our summary graphic (below in Figure 2), we initially specified our hypothetical expectations of factors which through mediation affect trust/distrust in science: in addition to epistemic integrity and public integration, there were elite distance, conflicts of interest and 'nefarious interferences' (i.e., politics and corporate profits, though not foreign influences) present in the discussions.
- However, absent from the discussions were the factors of teaching quality at the institutions (a concern for parents and students, a major feature of rankings), moral turpitude of researchers (scandals) and the overall profile of research (military vs. civil). The 'public discourse of trust in science' is likely to have some missing elements.

Figure 2: Summary illustration

3 Integrity and integration & trust in science

3.1 General image/attitudes towards science

Responses to the question “*What comes to mind when you think about science; when you think of doing something scientifically,*” varied in depth across the groups. Focus group 1 and 2, the families’ group, responded with narratives of experiences, compared with the post docs (focus group 5) on the highest end of the spectrum, which answered with technical terms and the climate change sympathisers (focus group 3) and NHS workers (focus group 4) in between. (Participants are numbered P1 to P42, FG1 to FG5 represents the focus group a participant belongs to, and we add the time stamp in the recording when citing a quote as UTC, 00:00).

A participant from focus group 1 said, when I hear science, “*I think about vaccines, laboratory tests, blood tests, medicine, the pharmaceutical industry ...*” (P7 FG1, 01:37). Her thoughts probably influenced by recent experiences with the COVID-19 pandemic while another from focus group 2 referred to science as the “*new religion*” (P18 FG2, 07:05), explaining later: “*you choose to put your faith in the science, you choose to put your faith in God, you choose to put your faith in government ... I have to pay rent to live, I have to pay for food, I have to work ... It's not a choice. I'm not a free man*” (26:11). The participant argues that he has no choice but to accept science in all its ramifications as we are all governed (more on the no choice debate in next section). For P13, (FG2, 09:26) science “*is just like trying to make the world a better place and just make it all easier*”. To study something scientifically is “*to observe and test and record and analyse factual verifiable data in a way that is objective and dispassionate*” (P12 FG2, 11:33) or to “*understand the makeup and components of something*” (P15 FG2, 12:07).

P22, from the climate action sympathisers group, separated science and technology, a distinction adopted by almost all participants across the groups: “*science is a methodology to the way we try and understand the world and how it works, and technology is a word for the tools that we use ...*” (FG3, 07:38). P19 based his distinction on use and occurrence, arguing “*technology is probably used more for consumerism ... whereas with science, just like vaccines*” (FG3, 21:58). Participants however argued that the distinction is not a perfect separation, “*they do go hand in hand*” (P20 FG3, 06:17) and “*they're interrelated ... so I think that you can't have one without the other*” (P23 FG3, 22:27).

The NHS workers had a unique perspective, focusing more on service development and improvement, rather than the expected, medications and outcomes. P31 said, “*when I think of science, I just relate it to ... having a positive effect on service we can provide for patients*” (FG4, 06:35). P20 described science as “*the process of how things work and also helping to improve quality of life safely*” (FG3, 07:37). To study something scientifically for an NHS worker, then, is “*to get data, and also feedback, and also where we are, where we can improve*” (P20 FG3, 08:18) and as P25 said, to “*start with a question and we try to figure out the answers to that question and then you can develop like a research proposal and then test your hypothesis*” (FG3, 09:34).

The scientists in (focus) group 5 were more detailed and discipline-specific in their definitions of science. P38 said “*it's mostly about finding a solution to a certain problem that other people haven't solved yet ... then try to find every possible problem that may arise with your sort of*

approach ...” (FG5, 12:30). P41 stressed the importance of replicability: “you need to follow a method up and then replicate and yeah, like, be consistent” (FG5, 08:33), stressing later (FG5 08:57) that “you need to prove or not ... associations”. P39 (FG5 09:09) cut in at this point arguing, “you don’t really prove things very often, do you”, adding that (P39 FG5 09:16) “as in a lot of research here trying to find statistical significance. But that doesn’t really mean you’ve proven anything; it just means you’ve rejected the null hypothesis”.

The discussions reflected the diversity of research approaches in the various scientific fields represented within the post doc group. Using his work in the medical field as case study, P42 (FG5, 10:04) said it depends, *“because in the world of medicine, it’s very much about the traditional empirical, quantitative, clinical trial research, which is very much based in statistics ... whereas in medical education ... it’s still about doing things systematically ... because your data is qualitative, that doesn’t mean that its less valuable.”* P38 (FG5, 12:30) noted that while in the medical field, a lot are interested in the statistics, *“if you are in robotics, you want to find the solution and prove your solution. So, it mostly depends on the sort of field that you’re working on.”* P36 (FG5, 14:04), who works in machine learning, argues that in her field, it’s about *“data modelling and mathematical modelling”* of perceived problems to derive more efficient systems, to prove the new is more efficient than the old. P40 (FG5, 15:28) said the focus in systems engineering is whether the new design will make an impact in practice or not, *“sometimes we can develop like machine learning algorithms ... but the problem is when you’re going to apply them in real time.”*

The definition of science (and what it means to study something scientifically) thus depends on your experience with science and particular fields of expertise. While members of the public tend to use lay epistemologies with a participant going as far as to relate it to the “new religion,” health workers focused more on service improvement than medicines, while the scientists in the doctorate category emphasised the differences in what research methodology entails in their different fields of expertise.

The participants also emphasized a distinction between science and technology, while also recognising the bonds that make them inseparable. While for some groups, the focus is on utility, for the doctorates, the distinction is in fields and methodologies.

3.1.1 What does it mean to ‘have no option but to trust science’?

This statement sparked an exciting debate among all participants regardless of group. While some argued that we have no option in several contexts or are too far down the road to control the momentum, others urged caution and discretion by the public. One of the participants argued that *“it is not a simple yes or no!”* (P12 FG2, 31:24) while another (P22 FG3, 28:58) said, *“I tend to disagree”* pointing out however that he did not ‘strongly disagree’ and he chose to read the statement as ‘should we?’ P18 (FG2, 31:27) modified the ‘option’ in the statement to ‘accept’ science, arguing *“not to trust, I don’t know, to accept it, perhaps, yes.”* The debates are best highlighted by both the pilot in flight metaphor and the idiom, look before you leap. P12 (FG2, 19:23) said,

my attitude to it is similar to when I get on a plane, I, you know, I don’t think about the pilot, I assume the pilot is there to get me to my destination and isn’t going to, you know, fly us into the side of a mountain. You know, I just kind of hand it over.

P23’s (FG3, 27:08) argued that trust should not be blind:

I never believed you should just blindly trust. I think you should [do], as scientists do, they question, don't they? They test and they investigate ... I think us as citizens should do the same ... as best as we can gather knowledge and information.

Many of the arguments here were informed by personal experiences with either science or technology. P6 (FG1, 15:34) said, *"I personally don't think we have an option ... If there is diagnosis of stage three cancer, I just don't know who else to go to ... what would be the barometer to select."* P12 (FG2, 27:33) compared scientific and religious alternatives, *"if there's a choice between religion and science, I'll choose science, because at least with scientific process, you know, things are verifiable ... tested and analysed in an objective way."* P12 (FG2, 28:45) noted however, that while he may have no option, he has reservations, *"I have misgivings about AI. I have misgivings about science being misused by bad actors, of course, but I think it's maybe the best we've got."* P18 (FG2, 31:46) was of the opinion humanity will survive transhumanism, *"we'll be part robotic; limbs will get better ... you can lose an eye and still see (with) both eyes because of technology. It's progressive and it's constant but to trust it implicitly, man? No."* Using the COVID-19 pandemic as an example, P20 (FG3, 27:55) argued that it's up to the individual to choose whom to trust, *"so COVID ... there was a massive debate whether the vaccine actually worked. So, it was up to us to make that decision looking at the research and figuring it out ourselves then we think yes, I trust this."*

Do scientists always know what is best for the public to guarantee absolute trust? A participant's response was, *"No, I don't think so"* (P33 FG4, 22:34). Another (P29 FG4, 24:04) said, *"I would say they have good intent. It's coming from a positive space ... nuclear fusion was to benefit the world; other people use it as a bomb."*

3.2 Diversity of factors that affect trust in science

A variety of issues emerged in the group discussions that could have both positive and negative effects on trust in science and scientists. These include perceptions by the public of double-edged consequences, untoward experiences, unmet expectations and perceived benefits and dangers. Others focus on the activities of scientists and science systems such as perceived elitism, unethical practices, mistakes and misconducts, representativeness, secrecy, and the notion of publish or perish.

A major issue for trust in science is the double-edged nature of innovations. Participants referred to gas (hydrogen cyanide) that was discovered to improve agricultural output (as pesticide) but converted to use in gas chambers during World War II, and Facebook, which was launched to connect friends but is now used by scammers and hackers. P7 (FG1, 35:18), said offshore wind farms, as alternative energy sources, are having unintended effect on tides, the weather and electrical storms while P12 (FG2, 12:42) noted that AI (artificial intelligence) can also become a monster, *"... the use of [the] atomic bomb ended the Second World War, but you know, it's become a dangerous thing in the world, I think that could potentially end life on this planet."* Science is a tool, P18 (FG2, 18:01) argued, it's neither good nor evil, it's how it's used that answers that question:

it's a double-edged sword, isn't it? Yes, of course, this technology has made our lives considerably easier in many ways. But there is also you know, there's a flip side to that, you know ... the government wants to track you, they know exactly where you are at all times, and Facebook has all your metadata and everything, you know, knows you better than you know, yourself ... (P18 FG2, 29:49)

On the other side, P3 (FG1, 02:07) noted that aircrafts which were used in wars are now used to travel all over the world.

Other areas of concern originated from experience, unmet expectations, perceived benefits and dangers. While there was commendation for innovations like artificial limbs and cancer treatments, P5 (FG1, 13:21) expressed concern that despite taking HPV vaccine, she still contracted the disease while P7 (FG1, 1:04:01) argued that there is a link between the current scale of autism and allergies in children and vaccines. P7 said, *“the ingredients in the vaccines, you have bovine, which is cow, so, you get babies allergic to dairy after they’ve been vaccinated, and you get eggs in the vaccines, and you get kids allergic to eggs.”* P8 (FG1, 14:37) was however appreciative of the expected benefits as her sister, who had breast cancer and was put on a trial medication, projected to control the cancer for two years, actually controlled it for five years.

Other factors that could promote or downgrade trust were hinged on the activities of scientists and science systems. P6 (FG1, 07:48) argues that elementary science is accessible to everyone while more advanced science seems out of reach of the public, reducing trust, adding later (18:20) however, that if the message comes directly from scientists in a lay man’s language it would be more accepting. P30, in the scientists group agrees with the need to address this gap, arguing that *“there is this kind of missing link between what we do, what we research, and how to spell it to a public, which doesn’t have the same sort of knowledge ... like, for example, if I would talk to my parents about machine learning, they wouldn’t understand anything. So, you need to change the sort of language”* (P38 FG5, 35:48). P7 warned about treating those with lesser knowledge as inferior arguing that it would be better to be explained to and not told:

I don't think everybody, everybody without a degree should be treated like they're a moron. And I do think that ... just because you went to university and got a degree or a PhD ... don't get me wrong, it's commendable ... but people are still able to understand and to, to take on that information and to process it, you know, all right, they might not go as in depth as you know ... but I'm still able to process information. And, you know, and if I don't get it, I'll ask a question about it. You know, I just think that yeah, you get told rather than explained (P7 FG1, 55:23).

P7 (FG1, 19:36) observed the disregard of the medical profession for any alternative outside clinical practice. Narrating her experience with psoriasis, she said the medicine prescribed by the doctor worked for about a month only for the condition to return worse, but she found a more lasting solution in a natural biotic which her GP and dermatologist dismissed. Another participant noted that most medical research and ultimately treatment guidelines are based on data which does not include people of colour who may have different responses to treatment. *“As a woman of colour, I expect that when they do medical research, it's usually on someone yourself (white) ... it's not based on a black body or black person or Afro Caribbean person”* (P9 FG1, 11:59).

Documented cases of secret and improper experiments by scientists were also raised as an issue that affects trust in science. P42 (FG5, 26:03) said he has reviewed trials from scientists across the globe that are best described as *“wacky stuff”* and P18 (FG2, 16:53) found disturbing *“secretive scientific experiments, that includes splitting up twins or infecting a whole community with syphilis ... that we found out 60 years later ... that continues, particularly in poor communities.”*

3.3 Attitudes towards research integrity practices and trust

The deliberations here focused largely on data integrity, scientists, scientific institutions, and the research process. Lack of transparency of the research process, data fabrication, subsequent investigations, and possible cover ups by institutions were highlighted by the participants as factors that may lower trust in science.

Regarding the research process, concerns were expressed over the speed of development of the COVID-19 vaccine. P2 (FG1, 1:08:51) said, *“the vaccines were created so quickly, and we know how much studying needs to go into a vaccine.”* P7 (FG1, 1:09:08) argued that the pandemic provided the opportunity for the pharmaceutical industry to introduce mRNA technology to the market and expedite its approval. P12 (FG2, 39:11) however countered that though it was approved rather quickly, people worked around the clock, *“pulling out all the stops in order to get a vaccine out there.”* P7 (FG1, 52:41) said she would have preferred to see the whole process from start to finish, *“I want to see video of the process, the whole process ... I want to be told how you got there ... how you came to this conclusion.”*

On the controversy over the integrity of the climate change data, one of the two case studies, P19 (FG3, 42:22) said the controversy was bound to happen, as it was a partnership and *“this is where one person has a genuine interest to do something right ... but then the manipulation comes from another sort of partner or another organization, which then affects the credibility of the work, unfortunately.”* P37 (FG5 48:22) said the researcher may have acted in good faith arguing that *“the culprits are the Chinese weather stations that are incorrect.”* P38 (FG5, 51:35) observed a bias because the data originated from China and if it had been *“US or UK data, then maybe there will be more trust.”*

P7 (FG1, 31:55) emphasised the importance of the data collection site and the range over which the results apply, citing her experience with the Department of Work and Pensions which used temperature levels collected from Heathrow weather station to process cold weather payments for residents of Islington. Heathrow, she argued, with a different topography and airport traffic, will be warmer than more residential Islington, *“I had to show them that the temperature was below zero in my area, because they took the data from a weather station, which said higher.”* P23 (FG3, 50:55) said it could be due to different interpretations of the same data set and the controversy may have been hijacked by vested interests, *“they just looked at the data, and they interpret it in a certain way. And then when somebody else looked at it, and went, oh, well, that’s not how I interpret it ... the media gets hold of that ... oh, well, this proves that climate change isn’t happening, it’s all vested interest.”* P25 (FG3, 49:09) however argued that *“we do tend to trust the integrity of the whistle blower or leak.”*

The post doc group was more critical of the scientists and the institution arguing that other scientists have, in the past, fabricated datasets. A case was cited of a psychologist who has a tenure position in the United States but fabricated datasets, *“... it got published and there was a TED talk on it. And then they had to retract it”* (P35 FG5, 32:04). The impartiality of the independent investigation in climate data controversy was also queried for lack of information on its composition. P40 (FG5, 45:10) said the statement issued by the institution on the issue indicates *“that they tried to cover it up.”*

Can we trust scientists who may have put in the wrong information to support a supposedly noble goal? P20 (FG3, 46:43) said, *“how can we trust you regardless of what the intention was?”* but P28 (FG4, 1:09:01) argued otherwise that *“if the larger goal is the outcome, (it) is desirable and more important ... what is going to improve the benefit (will) reduce the risk.”*

3.4 Public integration in science and trust

Discussions about public integration and trust in science covered how science is communicated by scientists, public disagreements among scientists, accessibility to scientific information, perceptions of the appropriate level of involvement, referenda on topical scientific issues, and the labelling and suppression of dissenting voices.

Accessibility to science was discussed in terms of language use by scientists in public communication, access to journal publications and availability of scientific innovations at point of use. A post doc participant (P38 FG5, 35:48) raised the issue of money required to access scientific articles and how to communicate scientific findings given the specialised language used by scientists. Pay to view, P38 argues, creates *“a sort of wall”* between research and the public and *“there is this kind of missing link between what we do, what we research, and how to spell it to a public.”*

Participants from the post doc group spoke on the effect that public disagreement among scientists may have on public engagement and trust in science. P39 (FG5, 1:11:54) argued that while it is important to criticise each other’s work, *“having it openly on Twitter shows the public that we don’t have confidence in each other”* and this is not the best way to promote trust in science. She noted however, that *“the public should also be aware that things aren’t as black and white as the government likes to make it look sometimes”* and getting the balance right is a difficult job for scientists. A Twitter war, P39 (FG5, 1:13:38) argued, is not going to build any trust, *“whereas involving people and asking them for their opinions, getting them involved in things like focus groups ... that is involving the general public, but in a way that does create trust and shows that things are done rigorously and that we care, whereas doing it on social media without thinking about the consequences that may have is what’s problematic.”*

On perceptions of the level of public involvement in issues like climate or medical research, P12 (FG2, 1:08:04) said *“I wouldn’t feel too confident about my ability to be very helpful ... I mean, if someone were to present me their findings and asked me to look over them, I’d be very confused.”* Acknowledging that it would be interesting to know about the process for transparency, P12 still insisted that *“unless you’re qualified, unless you know what you’re talking about, then I struggle to see the use of it”* (FG2, 1:08:46). Thus, while he will favour a transparent process, he was not sure how meaningful his contribution will be to a technical process he is not familiar with.

Some cases discussed by the participants however highlight ongoing involvement in personal issues, often medical. P3 (FG1, 21:24) narrated his experience with a General Practitioner who prescribed a drug, he later found to be an anti-depressant, for a backache, when all he needed was to change his chair, as he was working from home at the time, a move which eventually worked, *“So like I solved it, they didn’t solve it.”* P5 (FG1, 23:01) insisted on the need for a second opinion with medical issues, narrating an experience with her child, *“sometimes they’ll be like, oh, it’s just a viral infection ... and then I had to take my son back the next day, only for them to say, oh, he’s got tonsillitis, when they checked the tonsils with a different doctor and that’s what every time I go to hospital, I’m like can I have a second opinion, please”*, (see also P7’s experience with Department of Work and pensions earlier in section 4 on research integrity practices and trust).

The NHS group had an interesting take on public involvement. When asked if their definition of public involvement would be at the research stage or the acceptance stage, the group almost unanimously said both. P20 (FG4, 1:24:30) explained that some of the NHS workers who

participated in the trials volunteered to tell others about the vaccine. P31 (FG4, 1:25:21) argued in support that participating at the trial stage is more about its acceptance or transparency, once the research is done and is just as important.

Participants expressed concerns about being labelled as conspiracy theorists when posing questions outside the official narrative. P6 (FG1, 07:48) said *"... my issue is, if there's any opposing view, you get labelled quite easily as a conspiracy theorist. The opposing voices get shut down quite easily."* Shutting down other voices, he argued, *"creates more mistrust and people are gravitated towards such opinions"* (P6 FG1, 48:31).

The older family group deliberated on the prospect of a referendum on science issues, if this will increase trust. *"I am for that"* said P17 (FG2, 1.09.56), *"you'll really find out what the people want, instead of the government just steering it their way"*. P12 (FG2, 1:11:08) referred to the case of abortion in Ireland, which the public voted overwhelmingly in favour, noting however, that apart from being a scientific issue, it is also a *"moral, ethical, emotional issue"*. Asked if he will vote on climate change, P12 (FG2, 1:12:03) said *"I don't know ... that's very difficult ... it's very unlikely that a consensus would emerge, it would be very polarising."* On the current debate over the Ultra-Low Emission Zone in London, P12 (FG2, 1:12:59) argued that most Londoners will vote against it as *"people like their cars."* Meanwhile, P15 (FG2, 1:13:21) noted that being an issue that causes financial strain, *"it becomes personal."*

3.5 Communication channels and trust in science

Declining trust in the media - which no doubt has been influenced by media practices, advances in technology and wider social and political issues - has had its effect on the channel as a source of science news. Social media, and its association with citizen journalism, has led to new avenues for debates about science, both good and bad. Here, we examine public perceptions of the mass media (mainstream and social), concerns over how the media report science and how these affect trust in science.

The media, P5 (FG1, 39:54) argues, *"tells you a bag of lies every single time ... it's jargon, and I'm reading jargon now."* P3 (FG1, 40:49) argues that *"the media push their own agenda. So don't believe that BBC is impartial anymore ... It pushes the BBC's agenda."* The BBC, to P7 (FG1, 58:52), is an instrument for propaganda. The participants said they have now resorted to fact checking the media using other sources of information. P5 said *"I want to look and do my own little research"* (FG1, 39:54), a position elaborated by P2: *"If it interests me, I'll go have a look-up and I would see what other things are out there to say, and I'll see what resonates with me"* (FG1, 43:36). P2's statement was followed by sounds of agreement. Another participant (P7 FG1, 1:04:01) said, *"I use my eyes and my ears and my brain and my experience of my job and, you know, meeting people and talking to people and seeing patterns in stuff because science is patterns, isn't it? You look for patterns and stuff, don't you?"*

Some participants were of the view that the mainstream media is losing its voice to social media while others urged caution with social media usage arguing that it can also be a source of disinformation. P6 (FG1, 41:28) observed that *"the counternarrative on social media is much louder, much bigger, with massive exposure, which mainstream media doesn't have anymore ... I think that's influencing people more than what mainstream is saying."* P12 (FG2, 56:59), however, observed that social media is not a source of infallible information, distinguishing between a TikTok user who has *"gone somewhere and filmed something"* compared with *"someone sitting*

in his bedroom telling the world that something is a hoax". P22 (FG3, 1:21:08) narrated the experience of his mother who had become radicalised by YouTube and is now refusing vaccines after getting "bored of seeing the BBC news cycle over and over ... she found YouTube and now she is into all of the conspiracy (theories) because she won't take any of the recommended vaccines ... so it's been very much more important on her in terms of an influence."

A participant argued that while he might trust the social media, having faith in the news they broadcast represents a much higher level of acceptance. P12 (FG2, 56:59) argued that trusting *"some bloke on TikTok doesn't mean I put my faith on some bloke on YouTube."* P20 (FG3, 1:00:05) argued that advances in technology encourage more distrust *"because anybody nowadays can stick a green screen up and fill it with something and ... making something look so real."* A post doc participant (P41 FG5, 56:07) made a very insightful comment how social media reinforces certain worldviews rather than maximise viewpoints:

"I don't know how many of you were here around Brexit time, I was never presented anything on social media that was ... (anti EU) ... my entire social media was just populated with pro EU stuff. And I think it's similar if you're like an anti-vaxxer you don't see the other side ... because you click on the anti-vaccine things you get promoted more and more anti vaccine articles ... it's the same if you're looking at the climate change argument ... the algorithms work to maximise clicks rather than maximise viewpoints."

Distrust in media sources, however, has led to a broadening of information sources by the public to academic journals. P17 (FG2, 52:58) said while he won't trust the BBC or ITV or any other main news sources, *"if it was the Lancet, I believe it."* Apart from The Lancet, participants said they will look for other academic results. One of the participants (P24 FG3, 1:01:48) however argued that while these journal sources will be less biased, they are shielded by academic language and paywalls, making it *"really difficult to find, what I'm looking for."*

3.6 Political and corporate interference and trust in science

An issue raised during deliberations was different voices, and how trust (or distrust) in science should be distinguished from distrust in the voices with vested interests, namely those who fund and govern science. Trusting science in the case of (COVID) vaccines, P39 (FG5, 40:06) argued, was not so much about the vaccine but about the politicians governing science, who broke the rules which they claimed to have put in place on scientific advice. P41 cited 'Partygate' (partying in British Prime Minister's office) and the controversial visit to a second home by a Chief Medical Officer when everyone else was under lockdown rules. Another incident cited as affecting trust happened in the United States congress where a member, while questioning TikTok CEO over potential national security threats, displayed poor knowledge about how Wi-Fi networks work. P38 (FG5, 28:55), who expressed shock at the congressman's questioning, said, *"I wouldn't trust the government"* arguing that it shows people who are deciding on the law are *"completely ignorant"* of how the technology they are governing works. P37 (FG5, 40:48) argued that the response to the question do you trust scientists would be a bit better if it's about who is governing science, separating the work of scientists from those who govern the processes and products.

P7 (FG1, 04:20) said during the pandemic, she observed that a lot of the research is funded by the pharmaceutical companies and *"yeah, you can't be impartial if you're getting funded ... do you see what I mean"*, she asked? The profit motive of these companies was also raised as a cause

for concern. P14 (FG2, 43:38) argued that those who won the vaccine contracts made billions out of it because *“everyone’s [going to] get injections, that’s a lot of injections ...”*

Another participant said he doubts the data provided by people who are funded as *“it is in their interest to present it in a certain way to help their cause”* (P17 FG2, 1:02:47). When asked to explain further, P17 (FG2, 1:04:27) said, *“The people doing the research, ... they need another million pounds in funding to keep it going, to keep their jobs going, they can’t say yeah, we failed, I think is a waste of time, let’s close. So, if they can twist it a bit, but not too dishonestly ...”* P41 (FG5, 28:15) also voiced concerns regarding the influence of funders, *“because they are like driving more the results, rather than the person, you know, like if a big company hired me ... they want to relate or correlate something ... (they) say like, yeah, go with this, or no, no, no, it’s better just don’t show this.”* The research by Andrew Wakefield on the Measles Mumps and Rubella vaccine was cited by a participant (P23 FG3, 23:13), as a case of a research which was funded by vested interests and found to be *“flawed.”*

Science is a tool, argued P18 (FG2, 18:01), *“it’s neither good not evil and it’s how it is used ... so, scientists may be trying to find what’s good for us, but they are not in control of the outcomes of their work if they’re working at a university or if they’re working for a large corporation that is owned by a company or is owned by a billionaire.”* P12 (FG2, 19:23) also argued that while scientists may not necessarily know what’s best for us, on balance, *“they’re probably well intentioned for the most part, but again, this, this can be misused and manipulated, abused by corporate interests or government.”* Vested interests, P6 (FG1, 17:47) argued, don’t promote trust in science, and *“the moment the politician gets involved ... I think the trust level even drops for me.”*

These findings on trust and political and corporate interests in science can be summarised by answers to the question *“we have no option but to trust those who govern science?”* P40 (FG5, 1:08:57) remarked, *“No, we are not trusting, we are forced to trust ... There’s no option.”* P41 (FG5, 1:09:08) expressed, *“sometimes it’s not even what to believe or not, but it’s what you wouldn’t have access to. So, you know, if the only vaccine that’s available is AstraZeneca, even if Pfizer is shown to be better, but you don’t have access to it, you have no choice ... (it’s) the same thing in what gets funded by the NHS and what doesn’t ... you don’t have any other choice unless you’re a billionaire to fund your own health.”*

3.7 Card sorting exercise

The case studies were prompted in a different order for each deliberation session; in all events both cases were introduced to prompt the discussions as shown below in Table 5.

Table 5: The ordering of case studies for each group

Group	Case study 1	Case study 2
1. Parents with younger children	Climategate	COVID medication
2. Parents with older children	COVID medication	Climategate
3. Climate action sympathisers	Climategate	COVID medication
4. NHS workers	COVID medication	Climategate
5. (Post)-doc researchers	Climategate	COVID medication

According to the deliberations in London, four groups of factors make or break trust in science: public involvement and its modalities; mass mediation and the complications arising from social media; interfering political and business interests and finally the conduct of science (see Table 6).

The ranking of these factors of trust in science varied across groups as shown below in Table 7 (the pictures of the re-constructed ordering of cards are in Appendix 5.1).

Table 6: The four sets of factors that make or break trust in science

Public involvement	Mass mediation	Nefarious interferences	Conduct of science
Who is the voice, what ethos?	Social media a dubious news source	Funding sources of scientific research	Not enough research
Poor interpretation of scientific info	Social media increasing the visibility of sceptical voices	(Mis)use of science by politicians	Publish or perish incentives
Public disagreements among scientists	Misinformation on the internet	Poor governance of science	Journal reputation/peer review
Suppressing opposing views		Corporate influence on science	Secrecy of research
Constantly changing information			Representativeness of populations
Communication by scientists/institutions			Elitism of science
Practitioners (doctors) interpreting science			Untested/unknown risks
			Fallible scientists; faulty science
			Misconduct (falsification, plagiarism)
			Biased research
			Methodology
			Unethical research, lack of consent

Table 7: Card sorting exercise results

G1 young family	G2 older family	G3 climate change	G4 NHS workers	G5 (Post-)doc researchers
<i>Group ended up putting up the sticky notes in a circle to represent the idea that all factors are equally important. When probed further emerged two groups of factors emerged.</i>	<i>The group sorted the cards from the most important factor to distrust science to least important factor.</i>	<i>The group sorted the cards from the most important factor to trust science to least important factor.</i>	<i>This group less clearly distinguishes between trust and distrust in their ordering of the cards.</i>	<i>This group was probed to think about the most important factor to create trust amongst the public.</i>
<p>A) more important: the suppression of opposing viewpoints / corporate and political influence / media communicating science</p> <p>B) less important: elitism in science / representativeness of research / practitioners (e.g., doctors) interpreting science / funding of scientific research / science being “open” (or not)</p>	<p>Political and corporate influence / Who is the voice</p> <p>Money behind research/vested interests /</p> <p>Media communicating science / Secrecy /</p> <p>Untested potential dangers (e.g., mobile phones)</p> <p>Illicit, unethical research / Faulty science/fallibility of scientists</p>	<p>Methodology / Biased research / Unethical research (e.g., causing harm)</p> <p>Media communicating science / Funding of the research (and the funders’ vested interests) / Conducting research on ulterior, malign motives / (Mis)use of science by politicians / Online realm increasing visibility of science sceptic voices</p> <p>Social media as news source</p>	<p>(Mis)information from the internet / Unethical research (e.g., no patient awareness or consent)</p> <p>Funding behind research (vested interests) / Unsound research (e.g., rushed, incorrect data processing) / Representativeness of different people in research /</p> <p>Malign intent behind research / Poor interpretation of scientific information / Public involvement</p> <p>Poor governance of science / social media as a source of information</p> <p>Constant changing of information / Not enough research</p>	<p>Media communicating science /</p> <p>Governance of science / Public disagreement amongst science /</p> <p>Social media increasing visibility of science sceptical voices / Science communication by scientists or institutions /</p> <p>Scientific misconduct (e.g., fabricating data)</p> <p>Funding behind research (vested interests) /</p> <p>Journal reputation and peer review process /</p> <p>Incentives to publish (publish or perish) / Methodology</p>

Notes on how the groups rank-ordered the factors:

- Group 1: one participant kept driving her point home about how all factors are all equally important. There didn't seem to be a lot of input from others. Nonetheless, when probed, the other participants gave different factors as being important, so it's not an unfair conclusion to have them put in a circle.
- Group 2: we have two 'results' here. One is a way of grouping the factors together (which happened in two groups); the other is ranking them from most important to least important. In the box we only put the latter as this is what we're most interested in here. Important: Martin asks here what is important for **distrust**: *"Now if you think about... order them in terms of what really makes you doubt or really makes you think that we can't trust science... which one is the top one?"*
- Group 3: the group seems to pick up on the instruction what they should order the factors as to what is important to **trust** science. This is what Martin says: *"What is the most important of these factors, if you think, what drives you to be trusting or trust for science? Or yeah. Or causes mistrust? Which is the most important thing. Let's the most important up here."* After clarification from one participant (at 1:17:09) the group indeed goes with factors that are important for trust in science; another participant (at 1:23:24) also asks for clarification about whether the ordering concerns trust or distrust. This seems to suggest that the participants treat the trust/distrust questions separately.
- Group 4: Martin initially asks how the group would order the factors according to which is *"most important or having to do with your trust in science"* (at 1:10:22), but shortly after says it could also be related to distrust. The group therefore seems less concerned with considering trust and distrust separately.
- Group 5: Martin initiates the discussion by asking *"So if we wanted to make a diagonal, up here is the most important factor to create trust, which one do I put up there?"* (1:14:32), and a participant immediately asks, *"For the public or for us?"* (1:15:39) to which Martin replies, *"For the public."* The discussion mostly seems to evolve in an ordering of factors which affect the image of science, since some participants talk about 'the public not caring about journal reputation' for example.

The card sorting discussions in all the different groups seemed to have run quite different courses, depending on which interpretation of Martin's question was prevalent in the group. Arguably, there are subtle differences in how this task was interpreted, potentially ranging from "what drives distrust in science" to "what are important factors that are or should be there which make us trust science" to "what affects the image of science."

Importantly, the way we framed the discussion at the beginning of the focus group as revolving around "what concerns do you have in relation to science and technology" probably gave rise to a discussion on the problems that could affect trust in science, instead of a discussion on what the most important pillars building up to trust are or should be. Group 3 seemingly interpreted Martin's card sorting instruction as the latter question; the other groups seemed to consider the former question.

4 Evaluative attitudes towards science & technology (scales)

In all five deliberative events, participants were presented with a short questionnaire ahead of the group discussions and at the end of the group discussions. The first three open-ended questions (A1, A2 and A3) were discussed in plenary as warm-up questions, providing a shared understanding of what comes to mind when thinking about science and technology, what it means to study something scientifically, and whether participants had any concerns related to science and technology. Next, five questions measuring attitudes regarding science and technology were asked in both the pre- and post-questionnaire (henceforth Q1 and Q2). Descriptive results are provided below in Table 8. The answers to statement 1, 4 and 5 were reverse coded, such that higher scores on all items reflect a more positive attitude towards science and technology.

Starting with the first statement, *Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable*, participants tended to respond very positively to this question (with 90.5% in Q1 and 85.7% in Q2 being in agreement with this statement). The (recoded) mean for this statement (4.21 for Q1 and 4.02 for Q2) was the only one amongst all five statements which had a significant mean difference score across the two questionnaires, as measured by a paired sample t-test ($t=2.24$, $p=0.03$). Moreover, the variation in responses was also smallest for this first statement (SD = 0.75 and 0.87 for Q1 and Q2 respectively). Whilst the sample size is small (N=42), and the results should therefore be approached with caution, this only significant difference between Q1 and Q2 is worth noting.

Second, participants demonstrated considerable variance on the statement *Science and technology make our lives change too fast*, with a consistent mean of 2.55 and standard deviation of 1.11 in both questionnaires. Whilst several participants in various groups noted on the fast and ever-changing flow of information regarding science and technology issues, touching on technological progress and COVID-19 in particular, this sentiment is clearly not shared across the board (seemingly reflected in the agreement percentage of 50.0% and 54.8% in Q1 and Q2 respectively).

Third, participants tended to feel ambivalent about or disagreed with the statement *We depend too much on science and not enough on faith*, with a mean of 3.43 in Q1 (SD=1.23) and 3.45 in Q2 (SD=1.23). Again, participants were fairly consistent in their response to this statement pre- and post-group discussions. The topic of religion also hardly arose during the discussions, and therefore no noticeable change of mind regarding society's dependency on science and religion was expected to be flowing from the discussion.

Fourth, the statement *Scientists know best what is good for people* had a (recoded) mean of 3.07 in Q1 (SD=1.00) and 2.98 in Q2 (SD=0.95), demonstrating a general ambivalence amongst the group. This was also reflected in the group discussions. Whilst the mean decreased slightly from pre- to post group discussions, the difference is not significant in a paired sample t-test ($p=0.53$).

Finally, perhaps one of the most interesting statements (considering it was discussed at relative length in the deliberative event's warm-up section), *We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology* had a (recoded) mean of 2.95 in Q1 (SD=1.15) and 3.17 in Q2 (SD=1.09). Discussions during the warm-up section of the event revealed that participants initially interpreted this question, as posed to them in Q1, in varying ways: some perceived *governance* to lie at the heart of the question here, whereas others asked themselves whether we have no option

but to trust those working in science and technology themselves. It is possible that this discussion consolidated participants' answers to this statement in Q2. Whilst no consensus tended to be reached during the group discussion, a mean increase of 0.22 (albeit non-significant with a p-value of 0.095) and a general agreement increase of 8.2%, suggests a slight move towards agreement with this statement.

Table 8: Attitudes towards S&T before and after: Descriptive statistics

Item	Before N=42			After N=42			Mean difference score & difference in percentage agreement
	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	M	SD	% agreement (strongly agree/agree)	
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	4.21	0.75	90.5	4.02	0.87	85.7	-0.19 (-4.8%)
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	2.55	1.11	50.0	2.55	1.11	54.8	0 (4.8%)
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	.43	1.23	26.2	3.45	1.23	28.6	0.02 (+2.4%)
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	3.07	1.00	31.0	2.98	0.95	26.2	-0.10 (-4.8%)
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2.95	1.15	35.7	3.17	1.09	43.9	0.22 (+8.2%)

Note. N = 41 or 42 (one participant did not answer B4_5)

Figure 3: Results from questions A4 and B4

For 40 out of 42 participants (95.2%), this was the first time they participated in a public deliberation event about science (question B9). 2 out of the 42 participants (4.8%), therefore, had already had a comparable experience. As for impact of the event on participants (question B11, see Table 9), and most participants (88.1%) said they will get involved in similar events in the future. A further 64.3% felt spurred to talk to family and friends about related issues to the ones discussed during the deliberative events, and another 40.5% said they will follow related news stories going forward.

Three participants (7.1% of the sample) gave additional comments, although not highly meaningful for our current analytical purposes: “I will apply more critical thinking to these issues”, “Thanks”, and “Makes me really think!”.

That said, the first and last comment reflect our general perception that most participants engaged actively with and felt mobilised and stimulated by the discussions. The high number of participants responding positively to “I will get involved in events like this in the future” indeed suggests this is the case.

Table 9: Impacts of event on participants: Results (%)

Options	%
1. I will get involved in events like this in future.	88.1
2. I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	64.3
3. I will follow news stories on this issue.	40.5
4. Other	7.1

5 Appendix

5.1 Full questionnaire results question 4A and 4B

Table 10: Questionnaire 1: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	35.7%	54.8%	4.8%	4.8%	0%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	19%	31%	31%	14.3%	4.8%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	7.1%	19%	19%	33.3%	21.4%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	7.1%	23.8%	45.2%	16.7%	7.1%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	7.1%	28.6%	28.6%	23.8%	11.9%	0%

Table 11: Questionnaire 2: Full results (%)

Item	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
1. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	26.2%	59.5%	7.1%	4.8%	2.4%	0%
2. Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	16.7%	38.1%	23.8%	16.7%	4.8%	0%
3. We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	2.4%	26.2%	23.8%	19%	28.6%	0%
4. Scientists know best what is good for people.	4.8%	21.4%	47.6%	19%	7.1%	0%
5. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	2.4%	41.5%	22%	26.8%	4.9%	2.4%

5.2 Card sorting exercise

Group 1 – Parents with younger children; ordering of factors

Group 2 - Parents with older children; ordering of factors

Group 3 - Climate action sympathisers; ordering of factors

Group 4 - NHS workers; ordering of factors

Group 5 - (Post)-doc researchers; ordering of factors

5.3 Selection of participants

POIESES UK Focus group grid

- Group 1: Young families with and without preschool children
- Group 2: Older families with and without A levels and undergraduate students
- Group 3: Climate Change sympathizers' group
- Group 4: Health workers with over 10 years work experience
- Group 5: [Post] docs and early career academics in research institutions

Group 3 Climate Change				
		BAME	White	Total
Age	25 to 45	2	7	9
Gender	Mixed			
Qualification	Any			
Group 4 Health Workers				
Age	30 to 50	2	7	9
Experience	10 years plus			
Qualification	Professional			
Gender	Mixed			
Group 1 Young families				
Age	30 to 40	2	7	9
Children's education	Half preschool			
Social Grade	B1, B2			
Gender	Mixed			
Qualification	BSc (and lower)			
Group 2 Older families				
Age	40 to 55	2	7	9
Children's education	Half A-level to undergraduate			
Social grade	B1, B2			
Gender	Mixed			
Qualification	GCSE			
	Professional			

	BSc			
Group 5 post-doctoral researchers/early career academics				
Age	25-35	2	7	9
Gender	Mixed			
Qualification	PhD			
Field of research		2	7	9
	Natural Sci (4)			
	Social Sci (3)			
	Humanities (2)			

Questions for screening:

Group 3: Climate Change sympathizers' group

1. Do you belong to any climate change activists' group? (YES/NO)
2. Do you sympathize with disruptive action by climate change activists such as blocking traffic and other public spaces? (YES/NO)
3. I am very sympathetic to groups like 'HS2 Rebellion', 'Extinction Rebellion' and 'Ocean Rebellion' engaged in climate change activism. (YES/NO)
4. I support climate change activists' groups such as 'The Climate Action', 'Stop Climate Chaos' 'Campaign Against Climate Change', 'Just Stop Oil', 'Fridays for Future', 'Choked Up', etc. (YES/NO)
5. I won't join in any protest, but I agree climate change protesters a fighting a good cause. (YES/NO)

Group 4: Health workers with over 10 years work experience

1. Did you work with the NHS during the Covid-19 pandemic? (YES/NO)
2. Are you a frontline worker (nurse, ambulance workers, other health care professionals not doctor)? (YES/NO)

Group 5 - post-doc researchers [professionals] - YY

1. Did you complete your doctorate within the last 3 years? [YES/NO]
2. Are you working as a post-doc researcher or a Teaching Fellow [YES, NO]

5.4 Standard protocol for the sessions

POIESIS Deliberative Events London, Tue 4th to Thu 6th July 2023 Standard Protocol for the day

Time	What?	who	comment
17.30 / 19.30	Arrival, showing venue	HB BAF	
	Recording set-up	HB	Test recording set-up / back-up
	Consent form on table	All	Clear refreshments of old; place name cards
Phase 1 ... 30 min			
18.00 / 20.00	Arrival, take a seat,	MB, BAF	Welcome, Introduce project team, recording, consent sheet
18.05 / 20.05	Quest1 collect and ID	HB	Give every person a number on the quest; create a seating map
<p>Objectives of the study: what we are here to do. The study aims to explore public trust in science and whether and how this is affected by research integrity values and how integration of the public in research affects public trust in science.</p> <p>Your participation in the study is highly valued as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science.</p>			
118.15 / 20.15	MB BAF		<p>Referring back to questionnaire you just filled in, how do you understand the questions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What comes to your mind when thinking about science and technology? 2. What does it mean to you to study something scientifically? 3. What is your main concern about scientific research? 4. Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable 5. Science and technology make our lives change too fast 6. Scientists know best what's good for people 7. We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology
Phase 2 ... 30 min			
18.30 / 20.30	CASE 1	BAF MB	We are alternating case studies [see table below]
	Give copy to read	HB	One case study
<p>Stimuli questions [CASES of Research and Innovation]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think about this case? How does it make you feel? (e.g., sad, happy, angry, suspicious, betrayed) • What do you think about the actions of the scientists involved in this case? • Do situations as these (and specifically this one) affect the way you see science? your trust in science; image of scientists, institutions? Why? 			

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think about the actions of the journalists involved in this case? How much do you trust the information you receive from various news sources (social media and mainstream media) • What do you see as benefits – and as problems – of involving members of the public in decisions about science? And in policy-making more specifically? • What level of involvement do you think is appropriate for members of the public when it comes to decisions about science? • Are there other issues to consider in this case? 		
	mistrust of science	BAF MB	Steer discussion away from ‘trust in media’ to trust in the science/research
18.45 / 20.45	CASE 2 [in reserve]	BAF MB	We might reserve the decision to keep it to one case study, if the discussion is vivid and heating up; this in order not to curtail interesting discussions ...
	Give copy to read	HB	One case study
	Discuss case: mistrust of science	FAF MB	Steer discussion away from ‘trust in media’ to trust in the science/research
<p>Stimuli questions [CASES of Research and Innovation]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think about this case? How does it make you feel? (e.g., sad, happy, angry, suspicious, betrayed) • What do you think about the actions of the scientists involved in this case? • Do situations as these (and specifically this one) affect the way you see science? your trust in science; image of scientists, institutions? Why? • What do you see as benefits – and as problems – of involving members of the public in decisions about science? And in policy-making more specifically? • What level of involvement do you think is appropriate for members of the public when it comes to decisions about science? • Are there other issues to consider in this case? 			
Phase 3 ... 20 min			
19.00 / 21.00	Factors of mistrust [RI]	MB BAF	
	What to do about it [PE]	MB BAF	
	Card sort	HB	Order or rank order cards; discuss cards, order them; Take photograph
Phase 4 ... 10 min			
19.20 / 21.20	Quest2 collect and ID	HB	Make sure you identify the quest by number of round 1
19.25 /21.25	Thanks and last comments	BAF MB	
19.30 / 21.30	End, until another time ...		
	Debriefing in the group	All	Anything to keep in mind for next group? Do we have all the consent forms?

5.5 Participant profiles per group

Demo-graphic	Category	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	Total count	Total %
Age	18 – 24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
	25 – 29	0	0	0	0	3	3	7.1%
	30 – 34	3	0	6	1	3	13	31%
	35 – 39	3	0	0	1	2	6	14.3%
	40 – 44	3	2	1	1	0	7	16.7%
	45 – 49	0	2	1	2	0	5	11.9%
	50 – 54	0	1	1	1	0	3	7.1%
	55 – 59	0	4	0	1	0	5	11.9%
	60 – 64	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
	Over 65	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Gender	Male	4	4	4	3	4	19	45.2%
	Female	5	5	5	4	4	23	54.8%
Education	Primary education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
	GCSEs or equivalent	1	1	0	2	0	4	9.5%
	A-Levels, AS, NVQ Level 3 or equivalent	3	6	0	2	0	11	26.2%
	Bachelor's degree or equivalent	3	2	6	1	1	13	31.0%
	Master's degree or equivalent	2	0	3	2	3	10	23.8%
	Doctorate (PhD) or equivalent	0	0	0	0	4	4	9.5%
Do you consider yourself to be professionally involved with science?	Yes, I am a scientist/researcher	0	0	1	1	4	6	14.3%
	Yes, I am a student	0	0	0	0	2	2	4.8%
	Yes, it is part of my work	0	3	0	1	0	4	9.5%
	Indirectly or occasionally	2	0	1	3	0	6	14.3%
	No/Not really	7	6	7	2	0	22	52.4%
Is this the first time you have participated (...)?	Yes	9	9	7	7	8	40	95.2%
	No	0	0	2	0	0	2	4.8%
	Don't know	0	0	0	0	0	0	0%
Why did you choose to	To have the opportunity to discuss science and	9	3	6	4	6	28	66.7%

attend this event?	technology with others							
	To find out more about science and technology and research practices	2	3	4	4	4	17	40.5%
	To have my say on science and technology issues	2	3	2	2	2	11	26.2%
	Other	0	2	0	1	0	3	7.1%
What impacts do you anticipate this event will have on you?	I will get involved in events like this in future.	8	8	9	5	7	37	88.1%
	I will talk to friends and family about this issue.	6	6	6	5	4	27	64.3%
	I will follow news stories on this issue.	1	4	4	4	4	17	40.5%
	Other	0	2	0	0	1	3	7.1%

Note: some questions contained missing values and therefore do not add up to 42

Annex H: Guidelines for the PDW

Guidelines for running the public deliberative workshops

This is a guideline to assist in running the public workshops

It should be used in combination with the Deliverable 2.1. where general guides for preparing the event have been provided (Dec 2022)

2 May 2023

About this document

This document is a guide to help partners run the public deliberative workshops. It focuses on the agenda for the day, schedule, and how to use the materials. Please note that while there is some flexibility in the schedule, the case studies discussed will be the same in all partner countries.

This is a complement to Deliverable 2.1 (December 2022), which you used to organize the event, and where you find more detailed information on goals, objectives, plan, format and setting of the event.

Keep in mind the objectives and expected outcomes of the PW:

The public deliberative workshops will aim to explore public trust in science and whether and how it is affected by research integrity values and societal integration in science. These aims can be translated into the following questions that will guide the workshops:

- What are participants' attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices?
- What are participants' main concerns, hopes and expectations concerning research integrity?
- Do these affect public trust in science?
- What communication channels do people use and trust to get scientific information?
- What manifestations of integrity and integration in research affect public trust in science, and how?

Specifically, the data from the workshops will allow us to investigate:

- public attitudes, awareness, knowledge about research integrity practices
- public concerns, hopes and expectations towards research integrity practices
- whether attitudes and concerns about a lack of scientific integrity and societal integration affect public trust
- how people choose media and messages concerning aspects related to science and technology
- how people use and see traditional and new media as means of scientific authority
- desirable ways to integrate citizens and other stakeholders in the research process.

Before the event

- Participants will be sent a small **information kit before the event (within the previous week)**. The information kit is the following:
 - Information letter to participants with general info about the project and their participation (basic info on the project, participation privacy, confidentiality, etc.)
 - Info sheet: short summaries on the event itself (venue, date, etc.); short description of public trust & deliberative events; and participant's role in it.
 - Consent form (To be sent prior to the event and/or distributed on the day of the event).
- Participants will be asked to arrive 30 minutes before the start of the event.

Note: The 'participant information kit' is available in the subfolder 'Participant information kit' in Teams folder 'Deliberative Workshops'.

Overview of the event

We envisage a three-phase event with an initial expert presentation/Q&A session, small group discussions, and a plenary session, with the suggested agenda presented in Box 1.

Box 1. NEW suggested agenda

1.30 pm: Arrival of participants. Informed consent.

2.00 – 2.15 pm: Introduction by facilitator (purpose, domestic issues and timetable). Short questionnaire on public attitudes (1)

2.15 – 3.15 pm: Presentation by 'topical' experts and Q&A session

3.15 – 4.00 pm: Small group discussions (on integrity) (1st part)

4.00 – 4.30 pm: Coffee Break

4.30 – 5.15 pm: Small group discussions (on integration) (2nd part)

5.15 – 6.00 pm: Plenary session
Short questionnaire on changes in attitudes (2). Debriefing.

6.00 – 7.00 pm: Drink reception and departure

On the day of the event

1.30 pm: Arrival of participants

Participants will be distributed in four groups of about ten people. The participants will be assigned keeping gender balance and age. At this point, the consent forms should be distributed to each participant, even if they have been sent by email as part of the participant kit. The consent forms should be signed and delivered to someone from the organizing team.

If you prefer, you can assign an identification code (e.g., symbol, historical figure, etc.) to each group and give participants a sticker or a card with that identification. For example, you have Marie Curie group, Albert Einstein group, Charles Darwin group, and Stephen Hawking group, and you deliver a sticker with their faces and names to participants. Each group will have a moderator. This can be members of the project team or moderators assigned for the task, but not the topical expert who can join one of the groups as a participant.

2.00 – 2.15 pm: Introduction by facilitator

The facilitator will welcome participants and talk briefly about the purpose of the event, domestic issues, timetable and what is expected from participants in this event. After this introduction, the facilitator will invite the participants to complete the small questionnaire 1.

Short questionnaire to survey attitudes. Copies of the questionnaires will be already on the tables for participants to fill once the facilitator finishes the introduction. After completion, the moderator at each table keeps the questionnaires.

Note: This first part of the event might take a bit longer than 15 minutes (as some participants might need longer to complete the questionnaire), but the facilitator should try not to leave this to extend beyond much longer.

2.15-3.15 pm: Presentation by ‘topical’ expert(s) & initial debate/Q&A session

A 45-minute presentation and Q&A session by an expert will initiate the PW discussions. The goal of this first part of the event is to introduce the topic and prepare participants for the discussions to come. This initial talk will provide participants with concepts on research integrity and societal integration, which will be needed to inform the following discussions.

Participants will listen to the talk by a ‘topical’ researcher (Covid-19 or climate change) for about 10/15 minutes, who will expose his/her ideas and experiences on communicating responsibly about scientific information in his/her specific topic to initiate the round of discussions.

The talk will be followed by a Q&A session in which participants will have the opportunity to ask/clarify any issues with the expert. The facilitator can also help this phase of the discussion (if questions are not many) by using the open questions of the questionnaire and explore what participants wrote in the questionnaire (what does it mean to study something scientifically... and other broad questions as well such as ‘Where do you inform yourself about scientific issues? How do you keep informed? What means do you trust more?’)

The idea is to start a broad discussion about S&T issues and go down to integrity and public participation.

3.15-5.15pm: small group discussions

This second phase will follow a discussion format where participants, after reading the specific cases presented to them, will discuss among themselves their main impressions about the cases they were confronted with. In the first part of the group discussions participants will discuss cases on integrity, and in the second part of the small group discussions, participants will discuss cases of integration. There will be a coffee break between the two-part discussion.

Small group discussions

- **There are four cases available for the public discussions:** 2 cases on scientific integrity, and 2 cases on issues of integration and public participation practices related to the topical areas under discussion (Covid-19 or climate change). The two cases on integrity and one case on integration have two versions to address the chains of mediation (i.e., how research practices are communicated). The cases should be assigned to the groups as presented in table 1 in the cases document.
- **Cases per group.** Each group should be confronted with at least one case of integrity and one case of integration (mandatory). Ideally, each group should discuss two cases of integrity and two cases of integration as they will be required to the ranking exercise. For each case, the moderator should direct the discussions using a number of questions suggested for each case; the cases are available in the folder ‘stimuli materials’ in Teams. If time allows, partners might want to discuss an extra case - national case of interest (prepared by each national team).
- **What to discuss.** While discussions will unfold differently depending on the stimuli and the topical case, all groups are expected to (1) discuss the cases proposed by the moderators with a focus on a few questions related to the case; (2) to rank

issues of trust from the cases discussed; (3) share ideas among the group and with other participants by nominating a ‘speaker’ to bring those to the plenary session (if there are no volunteers to act as speakers, the moderator can take this part).

- **Ranking.** The ranking exercise will be conducted at the end of the small group discussions. This exercise has an individual phase, where people answer alone, and a group phase, where the group should come to a consensus about the final ranking (4 cases). These exercises should start with the question: *Do these cases make you trust science more or less?*
- You should prepare a set of cards (or post-its) where people will write and deliver them to participants at the time of the exercise. Participants will write their individual answers on the cards and then share them with the group. Then, the moderator should ask the group to define their collective ranking. Before or during the plenary session, one member of the group (or the moderator of the group) should put the cards on the wall.

Please keep in mind that you should prepare cards for the individual and the group phases, for the two parts of the small group discussions.

Each group will put up their rankings, side by side, on the same wall. These ideas will be brought to the plenary session by the facilitator or the spokesperson from each group.

5.15-6.00 pm: Plenary session

This third phase of the event will feed back information from the group discussions into the plenary session. This is also intended to be a reflecting period where participants review the main issues discussed, whether their most important questions and/or concerns have been discussed, and whether there have been changes in the way they see and think about research integrity and societal integration and about the role of the chains of mediation as sources of scientific information. The main point of this final session deals with participants recognising and prioritising which issues are most important to them about the topics at stake.

Examples of questions that can be asked:

- What were the reasons for the group to define this “ranking of trust”?
- If the cases your group discussed were slightly different – for example, disseminated through a different source (give examples from the other groups) – would this affect your trust?
- What are now your concerns about science?

Each group’s spokesperson/moderator will make a summary of the group discussion and ranking priorities identified. Then, the facilitator will bring these points and the

rankings put on the wall from the previous sessions and summarize the main points brought up by participants. Participants will then fill in a second short questionnaire.

After participants deliver their second questionnaire, the organizing team should also deliver the debriefing to participants – in the debriefing, a proforma (needed) presents information about the main goals of this study and an explanation about the made-up information for each case. It is a requirement from Iscte Ethics Council.

After the event, all participants will enjoy a drinks reception before they depart from the venue.

Recording the event

The discussions will be recorded through different materials to capture the main points of the discussions. These are:

- Audio-records of the small group discussions and plenary session (transcribed and translated into English by the national teams)
- Post-its or cards (kept by national teams, used for analysis)

What you will need:

- Recorders (one per table)
- Microphones (in needed, depending on your venue, one per table)
- One facilitator (up to the teams to choose)
- 4 moderators/facilitators (one per table)
- 4 note takers/observers (if possible, students)
- Case studies (printed in hard paper and larger font) (10 copies of each case per table)
- Post its; pens, etc.

Practicalities for the facilitation

Box 2 provides some notes on practicalities of the workshops, mainly for project researchers helping to facilitate the discussions.

Box 2. Note on practicalities of the workshops and facilitating discussions

- The workshops will include a short introduction by the facilitator who will introduce him/herself and anyone involved in facilitating the event; cover domestic issues (emergency exits, toilets...); and present the timetable for the event to help orientate the participants.

- In the introduction it will also be briefly explained what the purpose of the workshop is and how it will take place throughout the afternoon, what is expected from participants and the dialogue discussions, and how participants will work in groups. It should also be explained to the participants that all collected views, opinions and concerns of participants will be anonymized.
- The facilitator and the moderator at each table will make sure that the participants are clear about both the overall process they are involved in and the specific tasks they are being asked to undertake. The facilitator should indicate how long each exercise is intended to last, indicate how the time is passing, and give clear indications to participants about what needs to be done.
- After any explanation or instructions, it is important to check that participants understand instructions and tasks by asking ‘are there any questions?’. However, this does not guarantee that participants will ask for clarification, and it is therefore good practice to visit each group, once a task has begun, to check that they are ‘OK with what they are doing’.

Annex I: Information kit

Example with information about the Portuguese PDW

Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

POIESIS project

POIESIS examines research integrity and the integration of society in research as vehicles for responsible knowledge creation.

As society depends more and more on sound and responsible scientific research, concerns about **public trust** and mistrust **in science** have simultaneously been mounting.

Our goal is to contribute to increased public trust in science and increased development of research that addresses societal needs.

Public trust in science

To trust implies an accepted vulnerability: people must be willing to trust others. But this only happens when we believe that the other part is trustworthy.

Trust in science involves a large constellation of positive and negative attitudes towards science: respect, skepticism, lack of interest, admiration, etc. Research has also investigated trust in scientists.

In POIESIS, we explore **how public trust** might be **related to perceptions and evaluations of how science is conducted**.

Public Deliberative Workshops

A public deliberative workshop is a face to face event where people sit together to exchange ideas and opinions about a topic of common interest.

In this workshop, we aim to examine how the image of researchers and scientific institutions and the participation of members of the public in research affect the way they see science.

Your role

You will **share your opinions and views about science**, trust in science and scientists, and the ways science is communicated, as well as what you think citizens' participation in research should be.

Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

POIESIS project

POIESIS examines research integrity and the integration of society in research as vehicles for responsible knowledge creation.

Agenda for the event

 14:00 – 18:00

14:00 Presentation by Carla Gomes and Q&A session

15:00 Give your voice! (Small group discussions) – Part 1

16:00 Coffee break

16:30 Give your voice! (Small group discussions) – Part 2

17:15 Plenary session

18:00 Drink reception and departure

Carla Gomes
(ICS-ULisboa)

Venue information

Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa

Avenida das Forças Armadas, 1649-026 Lisboa
Room C103 (Building II)

How to arrive: <https://www.iscte-iul.pt/campus>

If you have questions, please contact:

Inês Sousa

ines_carneiro_sousa@iscte-iul.pt

We hope to see you soon!

Annex J: Participant Information Sheet

Example with information about the Portuguese PDW

Participant Information Sheet

Project Title: Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science

POIESIS Project in Portugal

This project is conducted in Portugal by Marta Entradas, Professor at Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa and researcher at CIES – Centro de Investigação e Estudos de Sociologia; and Member of the Public Value of Science Expert Advisory group, International Science Council/ISC; and Inês C. Sousa, Postdoctoral researcher at CIES-Iscte and Invited Assistant Professor at Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa.

POIESIS consortium. POIESIS is a consortium of seven partners: Aarhus University (Denmark), London School of Economics and Political Science (United Kingdom), Wissenschaft im Dialog (Germany), National Technical University of Athens (Greece), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (France), Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa (Portugal), Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (Spain)

General Outline of the Project:

- **Description:** The POIESIS project aims to study the relationship between trust, science and research integrity and integration practices in a world where there is increasing need for clear and open scientific information. We aim to run a series of events involving different actors including scientific experts and members of the public. One of those events is a public workshop to discuss and collect public views on scientific integrity, trust in science and scientific institutions, and public communication of science.
- **Use of Data:** Data collection will take place during the event in the form of audio recording and short questionnaires and, importantly, it will be used for research purposes only. All events will take place between May and June 2023 in the seven POIESIS partner countries. We intend to share the findings of the project with all participants in the workshops in October 2023.

- **Project Funding:** The POIESIS project is funded with a grant from the European Commission (EC) coordinated by the Aarhus University with a grant agreement number: 101057253

Participant Involvement:

- **Participants:** The participants in the public workshop were self-selected and not based on prior knowledge or connection to science. You do NOT need any prior knowledge on the topics that will be discussed; only an interest to discuss science with others and to share concerns and views on how it might benefit your life and future. Approximately 40 participants will be participating in the public workshop.
- **Voluntary Participation:** Your participation in the event is voluntary. The discussions will be audio recorded for exclusive use by the researchers. They will not be placed on a public platform. You can end your participation at any moment during the event. You may at any time demand removal of your data by a simple request to the coordinator of the study (Marta Entradas – marta.entradas@iscte-iul.pt). However, data that have already been published, cannot be removed.
- **What does your participation in this research entail?** Your participation will contribute to the discussions jointly with the other participants in the event and the experts. You will work in smaller groups (of about 10 participants) to facilitate the group discussions and will be guided by a moderator and a facilitator that will help conduct the discussions.
- **Risks and inconveniences:** We envisage little risk to participants in this research as the issues to be discussed will focus on opinions on science and trust. Yet, there is a small risk of discovering sensitive information related to institutional handling and management of particular ethical matters concerning the POIESIS topical areas – Covid-19 and climate change.
- **Confidentiality:** We will keep your information confidential, but other members of the workshop will hear what you say. Please try not to mention any confidential or defamatory information during the discussions.
- **Informed consent:** The informed consent form follows the guidelines of Iscte (as the main coordinator of this empirical study). You can find the consent form as part of this package.

Privacy Notice:

- In collecting your personal information within this research, Iscte complies with the legislation on data protection for scientific and historical research, in particular the framework arising from the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Law 59/2019 of 08/08 – Implementing Law, in the Portuguese legal system, of the GDPR. The Iscte Privacy Policy is available at <https://www.iscte-iul.pt/privacy>.

Data Storage:

- **Where:** Data management procedures will be in compliance with the GDPR and the Code of Ethical Conduct in Research – ISCTE. Iscte implements appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a way as to ensure that processing complies with the requirements of the GDPR and ensures the protection of the data subject's rights.
- **How long:** Data will be electronically stored for five years after any publication from the research.

Queries and Concerns:

Contact Details for More Information: If you require further information about the project or your participation in the study, you can contact the coordinator of the study in Portugal: Marta Entradas (marta.entradas@iscte-iul.pt) or the researcher Inês Sousa (ines_carneiro_sousa@iscte-iul.pt)

If you have any concerns or complaints about how this research has been conducted, please contact:

Secretary of the Ethics Council
Carlos Braceiro
conselho.etica@iscte-iul.pt
+ 351 210 464 287
or
Data Protection Officer (DPO)
dpo@iscte-iul.pt

Ethical Approval: The ethical aspects of this research have been approved by the Iscte Ethics Council (Protocol 45/2023).

Remuneration/compensation: The participants will be reimbursed for any travel costs associated with taking part in the deliberative workshops. All workshop expenses, including catering etc. will be covered by the project. The coffee break includes coffee, fruit and cake, and the drink reception will include some refreshments. You will receive a small gift as a thank you for your participation.

Project website: More information about this project is available in the project website: www.poiesis.eu

Annex K: Informed consent

Example with information about the Portuguese PDW

INFORMED CONSENT

This study is part of a research project taking place at Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, funded by European Commission under the programme Horizon Europe (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01, grant number 101057253).

The study aims to examine how integrity of researchers and scientific institutions and integration of the public in research affect public trust in science. Your participation in the study is highly valued as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science. You will participate in a four-hour event. In this event, you will be invited to answer to two anonymous short questionnaires, one at the beginning and one at the end of the session. You will also be invited to read some documents and share your views and opinions in a group discussion. The discussions will be audio recorded. Your answers to the questionnaires will not be associated to the audio recordings.

The partners in the POIESIS consortium share the responsibility for the processing of your personal data that are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, legally based on Article 6(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). A joint Data Controller Agreement was signed by all partners.

The study is conducted by Professor Marta Entradas (marta.entradas@iscte-iul.pt), who you may contact to clear up any doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You may use the contact indicated above to request access, rectification, erasure or limitation of the processing of your personal data.

Your participation in this study is **strictly confidential**. Your personal data will always be processed by authorised personnel bound to the duty of secrecy and confidentiality. Iscte assures the use of appropriate techniques, organisational and security measures to protect personal information. All investigators are required to keep all personal data confidential.

In addition to being confidential, participation in the study is **voluntary**. If you have decided to participate, you can stop your participation and withdraw your consent to the processing of your personal data at any time, without having to provide any justification. The withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

Your personal data will be kept for one year after this event, after which they will be destroyed, with their anonymity being assured in the study's results, being disclosed only for purposes of statistics, teaching, communication in scientific meetings, books or articles.

There are no expected significant risks associated with participation in the study. Iscte does not disclose, or share with third parties, information related to its personal data.

The aggregated results of the questionnaires and the transcripts will be shared with the partners within the POIESIS consortium, one of which is located in the United Kingdom, where there is an adequacy decision by the European Commission, and as such implements protective measures and guarantees your rights just like the European Union.

Institution has a Data Protection Officer who may be contacted by e-mail: dpo@iscte-iul.pt. If you consider this necessary, you also have the right to submit a complaint to the Portuguese National Authority (Comissão Nacional de Proteção de Dados).

I declare that I have understood the aims of what was proposed to me, as explained by the investigator, that I was given the opportunity to ask any questions about this study and received a clarifying reply to all such questions. **I accept** participating in the study and consent to my personal data being used in accordance with the information that was given to me.

Yes No

Lisbon, 03/06/2023

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Annex L: Debriefing

Example with information about the Portuguese PDW

DEBRIEFING/EXPLANATION OF THE RESEARCH

Thank you for having participated in this study. As indicated at the onset of your participation, the study is about trust in science and aims to investigate how integrity of researchers and scientific institutions and integration of the public in research affect public trust in science. More specifically, the main goals of this study are:

- Identify public attitudes, awareness, and knowledge about research integrity practices;
- Describe public concerns, hopes and expectations towards research integrity practices;
- Analyse how lack of scientific integrity and societal integration affect public trust;
- Determine how people choose and use media to be informed about science and technology;
- Identify desirable ways to integrate citizens and other stakeholders in the research process.

In the context of your participation, we would like to inform you that the cases presented to you are real, but that they have been slightly modified regarding the information about media channels to accomplish the goals identified above. These cases were not disseminated in the journals and social media that we present in the study, and the names of the authors of the cases (e.g., journalists) are not real.

We also would like to clarify that there are mechanisms to ensure integrity in science, such as institutional Ethical Committees or Offices, the double-blind peer review process in scientific publications or publicly accessible datasets.

We remind that the following contact details can be used for any questions that you may have, comments that you wish to share, or to indicate your interest in receiving information about the main outcomes and conclusions of the study: Marta Entradas (marta.entradas@iscte-iul.pt) e Inês Sousa (ines_carneiro_sousa@iscte-iul.pt).

If you wish to access further information about the study topic, the following sources can also be consulted: <https://poiesis-project.eu/>.

Once again, thank you for your participation.

Annex M: Case package

Stimuli Materials for the small group discussions in the PDW

Topics – Research integrity, Societal integration, Chains of mediation, Trust, Climate change, COVID-19

The main goal of Public Deliberative Workshops is to explore whether and how “lack of scientific integrity and societal integration affect public trust, how people choose media and messages, and how they use and see traditional and new media as means of scientific authority” (Technical Report).

Part of the workshop will be dedicated to group discussions based on case studies. In the first part of the discussion, the focus will be on research integrity cases (from group 1 below); in the second part, cases will focus on integration. Each group should discuss four cases. We suggest the following cases:

Block 1 – Cases about research integrity (two cases)

Block 2 – Cases about public integration in science (two cases)

“Boundary conditions” – Chains of mediation (i.e., information that varies for the same case – traditional vs new media)

The estimate is that each case takes about 20 minutes of discussion (including reading the case). Please consider that each group is composed of 10 participants, which represents about 2 minutes for person for each case.

- Case 1 is presented in two versions (1A and 1B), changing the chains of mediation only. Each group reads only one version; two groups will read the first (newspaper), two groups will read the second (social media).
- Cases 2 is presented in two versions (2A and 2B), changing the chains of mediation only. Each group reads only one version; two groups will read the first (communication office of university), two groups will read the second (social media).
- Case 3 is presented in two versions (3A and 3B), changing the chains of mediation only. Each group reads only one version; two groups will read the first (TV report), two groups will read the second (social media).
- Case 4 is presented in a single version.

For case 1A please choose a newspaper and a common name in your country. For case 1B use the same person. Also, please choose a design of a Facebook page that is suitable to your country (e.g., language, aesthetics) and to the person you “created”.

For case 2B please choose a common name in your country for the climate scientist and personalise the Twitter posts with that name/photo.

For case 3A please choose a TV channel and a common name in your country. For case 3B use the same person. Also, please choose a design of a Facebook page that is suitable to your country (e.g., language, aesthetics) and to the person you “created”.

For each case there are stimuli questions to help stimulate the discussion.

Example of how you can distribute the cases so that every group discuss all the topics:

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
1A	1B	1A	1B
2B	2A	2B	2A
3B	3A	3A	3B
4	4	4	4

Block 1 - Research integrity

Case 1A

A Prominent Study Said Ivermectin Prevents COVID, But The Data Is Suspect

A new study from Argentina has reported to have found a medicine (ivermectin) that prevents COVID-19 100% of the time — but its inconsistencies have led experts to question if it could have actually happened as advertised.

Mary Smith (BBC Reporter)

September 2, 2021

For anti-vaccine activists, the clinical trial results couldn't have been better. A group of scientists in Argentina has announced a drug that prevented 100% of COVID-19 infections.

"If you take it, you will not get sick," a physician told a Senate committee in December, describing it as a "wonder drug" and citing in part the trial "from Argentina".

However, there is a suspicion that some of the experiments were not conducted with the scientific rigour and as advertised by the physician.

The BBC News interviewed Kyle Sheldrick, the doctor and researcher who raised questions about how the study's data was collected and analysed. "The numbers, genders, and ages of the study's participants were inconsistent", he argued. A hospital named in the paper as taking part in the experiments said it has no record of the study happening. Health officials in the province of Buenos Aires have also said that they also have no record of the study receiving local approval.

The researcher supervising the project, Carvalho, a retired endocrinologist and professor of internal medicine at the University of Buenos Aires, one of the most reputable in the country, has declined to put the data open access and even share it with his own collaborators.

In short, independent experts told the BBC News, the study has so many red flags that it is, at best, unreliable. "There is no way in which I could see a trial that actually occurred producing a pattern like this," said Sheldrick.

Carvalho, the research supervisor, said the study was real. "We would never make up a study because it's not ethical."

Sheldrick says that at a time of a global crisis, when vaccination rates are slumping in the face of a relentless virus, Carvalho's research is being used to give desperate people false, and potentially dangerous, hope about the miraculous properties of a drug proven only to help kill parasites.

Case 1B

Mary Smith, a BBC reporter, shared the following post on her Facebook page.

A Prominent Study Said Ivermectin Prevents COVID, But The Data Is Suspect

A new study from Argentina has reported to have found a medicine (ivermectin) that prevents COVID-19 100% of the time — but its inconsistencies have led experts to question if it could have actually happened as advertised.

For anti-vaccine activists, the clinical trial results couldn't have been better. A group of scientists in Argentina has announced a drug that prevented 100% of COVID-19 infections.

"If you take it, you will not get sick," a physician told a Senate committee in December, describing it as a "wonder drug" and citing in part the trial "from Argentina".

However, there is a suspicion that some of the experiments were not conducted with the scientific rigour and as advertised by the physician.

Kyle Sheldrick, the doctor and researcher who raised questions about how the study's data was collected and analysed, was interviewed last week by us and said: "The numbers, genders, and ages of the study's participants were inconsistent". A hospital named in the paper as taking part in the experiments said it has no record of the study happening. Health officials in the province of Buenos Aires have also said that they also have no record of the study receiving local approval.

The researcher supervising the project, Carvalho, a retired endocrinologist and professor of internal medicine at the University of Buenos Aires, one of the most reputable in the country, has declined to put the data open access and even share it with his own collaborators.

In short, independent experts told us in the BBC News, the study has so many red flags that it is, at best, unreliable. "There is no way in which I could see a trial that actually occurred producing a pattern like this," said Sheldrick.

Carvalho, the research supervisor, said the study was real. "We would never make up a study because it's not ethical."

Sheldrick says that at a time of a global crisis, when vaccination rates are slumping in the face of a relentless virus, Carvalho's research is being used to give desperate people false, and potentially dangerous, hope about the miraculous properties of a drug proven only to help kill parasites.

 987

300 shares

The goal of this case – which we present in two version varying the means of communication – is to explore how lack of research integrity affects public trust in science, as well as to examine how chains of mediation influence this relation. The chains of mediation and the actors to be considered are the ones described in the POIESIS proposal.

Stimuli questions:

- What do you think about this case?
- How does this case make you feel? (e.g., sad, happy, angry, suspicious, betrayed)
- What do you think about the actions of the actors involved in this case?
 - Explore both the mediators and scientific actors in this case (e.g., the researchers, the university, the journalist, the BBC News, the person who shared the information on social media, the doctor who reported the “problems” in the study)
- What do you think about the mean of communication used to share this news? How much do you trust the information you receive from this source? (BBC News vs. Facebook)
- Do situations as these (and specifically this one) affect the way you see science? (your trust in science; image of scientists, institutions, or the way science is communicated?). Why?
- Are there other issues to consider in this case?

Case 2A

The Communication Office of the University of East Anglia issued a statement after more than 1,000 emails hacked from its Climate Research Unit were released online, which is known as the “Climategate” scandal. Here is the statement:

Official statement by the Communications Office of the University

Dr. Jones, a climate scientist and previous director of the Climatic Research Unit, faced claims that he sought to hide information about the temperature data on which some of his work on studying the pace of climate change was based. The emails and documents suggested that a series of measurements from Chinese weather stations were seriously flawed.

Jones was accused of scientific fraud for attempting to suppress data that could cast doubt on a study on the effect of cities on warming. The accusation is that there is an apparent attempt to manipulate temperature data from the Chinese weather stations. The university was asked about the location for the 84 weather stations in eastern China where data were collected, half of which were urban regions and half rural regions. The location of the weather stations was crucial to Jones’ study, as it allowed temperatures to be compared between regions and conclude that the rising temperatures recorded in China were the result of global climate changes rather the warming effects of expanding cities.

Despite all the accusations, the last independent investigation into the emails, led by Muir Russell, defended the integrity of the university’s Climatic Research Unit – the scientists involved had not manipulated data or subverted the peer review process.

This office would like to clarify that the integrity of the fundamental science of climate change is unquestioned – our climate is changing and the Climatic Research Unit has shown beyond reasonable doubt that humans are in part responsible.

The Director of the Communications Office

Case 2B

John Doe, a climate scientist working at the University of East Anglia, shared the following thread on his Twitter account.

The image shows a screenshot of a Twitter thread with four tweets. Each tweet features a profile picture of a man in a lab coat, the name 'JoDoe,PhD', a verified account icon, and the handle '@johndoe'. The tweets are separated by horizontal lines and each has a small blue Twitter bird icon to its right.

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

Old enough to remember the Univ of East Anglia ClimateGate emails scandal. More than 1000 emails hacked from its Climate Research Unit were released online

A thread (1/9)

15:30 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

Dr. Jones, my colleague, a climate scientist and previous director of the Climatic Research Unit, faced claims that he sought to hide information about the temperature data on which some of his work was based. (2/9)

15:31 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

The emails and documents suggested that a series of measurements from Chinese weather stations were seriously flawed.

(3/9)

15:32 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

Jones was accused of scientific fraud for attempting to suppress data that could cast doubt on a study on the effect of cities on warming.

(4/9)

15:34 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

The accusation is that there is an apparent attempt to manipulate temperature data from the Chinese weather stations.

(5/9)

15:35 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

The university was asked about the location for the 84 weather stations in eastern China where data were collected, half of which were urban regions and half rural regions.

(6/9)

15:37 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

The location of the weather stations was crucial to Jones' study, as it allowed temperatures to be compared between regions and conclude that the rising temperatures recorded in China were the result of global climate changes rather the warming effects of expanding cities.

(7/9)

15:39 • 12/10/20

JoDoe,PhD ✓ @johndoe

The last independent investigation into the emails, led by Muir Russell, defended the integrity of the CRU – the scientists involved had not manipulated data or subverted the peer review process.

(8/9)

15:41 • 12/10/20

JoDoe, PhD ✓ @johndoe

The integrity of the fundamental science of climate change is unquestioned – our climate is changing and the CRU has shown beyond reasonable doubt that humans are in part responsible.

(9/9)

15:42 • 12/10/20

The goal of this case is to explore how claims of research misconduct affect public trust in science, as well as examine how the chains of mediation influence this relation.

Stimuli questions:

- What do you think about this case?
- How does this case make you feel? (e.g., sad, happy, angry, suspicious, betrayed)
- What do you think about the actions of the actors involved in this case?
 - Explore both the mediators and scientific actors in this case (e.g., the researchers, the university, the journalist, the BBC News, the person who shared the information on social media, the doctor who reported the “problems” in the study)
- What do you think about the mean of communication used to share this news? How much do you trust the information you receive from this source? (BBC News vs. Facebook)
- Do situations as these (and specifically this one) affect the way you see science? (your trust in science; image of scientists, institutions, or the way science is communicated?). Why?
- Are there other issues to consider in this case?

Block 2 – Public integration in science

Case 3A

The reporter Mike Smith, from Channel 5, did a TV report about the following news:

The technical working group that advises the government on Covid-19 immunization will organize a public consultation on the provision of the Pfizer vaccine for the immunization of children from 6 months to 5 years old against Covid-19. To participate in the public consultation, people can choose to attend the meetings in their city council, take an online survey or submit feedback via email.

This technical working group had already issued a favourable opinion on the vaccination of children from 6 months to 5 years old, which was reiterated by several experts in the medical community.

The team leader encouraged the community to review the draft policy and provide their feedback: “Public participation is an essential element of inclusive, equitable policy development and I encourage everyone in our community to review the draft policy, attend the planned public meetings and provide your feedback”.

“This virus is a real and pressing threat to our way of life and we have to take urgent action to reduce children’s vulnerabilities”, she added.

Case 3B

Mike Smith, a reporter from Channel 5, published the following news on his Facebook page:

The image shows a screenshot of a Facebook post by Mike Smith, dated 15/12/2021. The post content is as follows:

The technical working group that advises the government on Covid-19 immunization will organize a public consultation on the provision of the Pfizer vaccine for the immunization of children from 6 months to 5 years old against Covid-19. To participate in the public consultation, people can choose to attend the meetings in their city council, take an online survey or submit feedback via email.

This technical working group had already issued a favourable opinion on the vaccination of children from 6 months to 5 years old, which was reiterated by several experts in the medical community.

The team leader encouraged the community to review the draft policy and provide their feedback: “Public participation is an essential element of inclusive, equitable policy development and I encourage everyone in our community to review the draft policy, attend the planned public meetings and provide your feedback”.

“This virus is a real and pressing threat to our way of life and we have to take urgent action to reduce children’s vulnerabilities”, she added.

The post shows 800 likes and 150 shares.

The goal of this case is to explore how people think about integration of society in research; what levels of participation do people think are appropriate; how societal integration in science (through public consultation events) affects public trust in science.

Stimuli questions:

- Would you like to participate in this public consultation? Why?
- If you wanted to participate in this public consultation, what method would you choose? (i.e., attend the meetings, take the survey, submit feedback via email)
- How does this case make you feel about science?
- After reading this case, do you think that the public should be involved in decisions about science? Why?
- What do you see as benefits – and as problems – of involving members of the public in decisions about science? And in policy-making more specifically?)
- What level of involvement do you think is appropriate for members of the public when it comes to decisions about science?
- What do you think about the means used to recruit people to this public consultation? (e.g., TV report vs. Facebook)
- Does public participation in science make you feel more confident about science?

Case 4

Vigie-Nature is a participatory science programme open to all those who are curious about nature, from beginners to the most experienced. Based on simple and rigorous protocols, it offers everyone the opportunity to contribute to research by discovering the biodiversity that surrounds us. People can go into the field, in the city or in the countryside, to become a biodiversity observer.

The observation of common species makes it possible to answer essential questions on ordinary biodiversity. For example:

- What is the quantitative evolution of our common fauna and flora? Which species are increasing in frequency or, on the contrary, tending to decrease?
- How do common species react to the various pressures of human origin (increasing fragmentation of environments, intensification or abandonment of agriculture, urbanisation)?

To achieve these goals, we offer you protocols that allow you to monitor several groups of living beings. All the observations you make can then be sent to researchers at the National Museum of Natural History so that they can use them in their research.

Your participation can include pictures, recordings, dictionaries, weather conditions, etc. Researchers will use your data to promote, think about and evaluate biodiversity conservation actions.

For example, for the program “Garden Birds” you can sit in a local garden and watch the birds for 15 minutes. Then, you should take notes on how many birds of each species land on the site at the same time. This protocol provides researchers the data on the presence and abundance of birds, which will allow them to study the effects of climate, urbanization, and agricultural practices on the diversity of common birds.

“Wild on my street” is a useful program that allows researchers to learn more about plant distribution in the city. You choose an area, such as street, and search for different species of wild plants and the type of environment where you found it (crack, lawn). These plants bring many benefits to the environment (e.g., source of food for animals, their roots protect the soil from erosion), so researchers aim to know their diversity in the city.

Currently, there is a great collection of photos of pollinating insects produced by volunteer participants and these photos that will be carefully analysed by researchers.

Gallery of insect photographs taken by volunteers

The goal of this case is to explore how people think about integration of society in research; what levels of participation do people think are appropriate; how societal integration in science (through citizen science) affects public trust in science.

Stimuli questions:

- Would you like to participate in this project? Why?
- If you wanted to participate, how would you contribute to the project? (e.g., taking pictures, recording information about weather conditions, etc.)
- How does this case make you feel about science?
- After reading this case, do you think that the public should be involved in decisions about science? Why?
- What do you see as benefits – and as problems – of involving members of the public in decisions about science? And in policy-making more specifically? (e.g., involving people in projects where they provide data like this)
- What level of involvement do you think is appropriate for members of the public when it comes to decisions about science?
- Does public participation in science make you feel more confident about science?
- Would you trust results from this research project more than results from the same project carried out entirely by scientists? Why?

Final question: What do you think about your participation in this project and event? How does that make you feel about science and your role in it?

Annex N: Questionnaires

Questionnaire 1

Welcome!

Your participation in this event is very important to the POIESIS team and will help us to understand more about public trust in science and public participation in science.

Please complete this questionnaire and leave it with the organizing team. Thank you for participating in the event!

Please tell us in your own words...

What comes to your mind when thinking about science and technology...

What does it mean to you to study something scientifically....

What is your main concern about scientific research...

For each statement below could you please let us know your level of agreement with each of them?

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Scientists know best what is good for people.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

About you

Gender: Male Female Other Prefer not to say

What is your job? _____ (If you are student/retired please indicate so)

Age:

- 18-24 35-39 50-54 Over 65
 25-29 40-44 55-59
 30-34 45-49 60-64

What is the highest level of qualifications you have obtained?

- Primary education (2nd cycle) Bachelor's or equivalent level
 Low secondary education (Middle school) Master's or equivalent level
 Upper secondary education (High school) Doctoral or equivalent level

Do you consider yourself to be professionally involved with science?

- Yes, I'm a scientist/researcher Indirectly or occasionally
 Yes, I'm a science student No/Not really
 Yes, it is part of my work

Thank you for your participation!

Questionnaire 2

Please tell us in your own words...

What is your main concern when thinking about bad practices in scientific research...

Thinking about the way scientific findings are communicated to the public your main view is...

Thinking about participation of members of the public in science discussions and developments, your main view is...

For each statement below could you please let us know your level of agreement with each of them?

	Strongly agree	Tend to agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Tend to disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
Science and technology make our lives easier, healthier and more comfortable.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Science and technology make our lives change too fast.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We depend too much on science and not enough on faith.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Scientists know best what is good for people.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We have no option but to trust those governing science and technology.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

About the Event

Is this the first time you have participated in an event of this type where the public are invited to discuss science?

Yes No Don't know

Why did you choose to attend this event? Please choose one option.

- To have the chance to discuss with others about science and technology
- To find out more about science and technology and research practices
- To have my say on science and technology issues
- Other (please specify):

Which of the following impacts will this event have on you? Put a cross in as many boxes as are relevant to you.

- I will get involved in events like this in future.
- I will talk to friends and family about this issue.
- I will follow news stories on this issue.

Other (please specify):

About you

Gender: Male Female Other Prefer not to say

What is your job? _____ (If you are student/retired please indicate so)

Age:

18-24 35-39 50-54 Over 65
25-29 40-44 55-59
30-34 45-49 60-64

What is the highest level of qualifications you have obtained?

Primary education (2nd cycle) Bachelor's or equivalent level
Low secondary education (Middle school) Master's or equivalent level
Upper secondary education (High school) Doctoral or equivalent level

**Thank you for participating in the
event and answering the
questionnaire!**

Annex O: Codebook

Dimension of analysis	Suggested code	Definition	Examples
Attitudes towards science	Positive/neutral attitudes	Positive feelings, beliefs, values about science and its positive impact on society/people's lives	Science is good; it helps people's lives; science is safe and respects people's freedom
	Negative attitudes	Negative feelings (including being worried/concerned), beliefs, values about science and its positive impact on society/people's lives	Science harms people; worthless; dishonest; manipulate people
General factors for trust/distrust	Factors for trust/distrust	Factors that contribute to trust/distrust in science (as an abstract entity)	Rigorous methods, financial influence
Trust in science (rationales, trusted groups...)	Trust in actors (which actors?)	What groups do people trust to talk/present science	Scientists, scientific institutions, journalists, etc.
	Rationales/reasons to trust (what motives?)	Rationales that contribute to trust in science/ scientists/ scientific institutions/ mediators (...)	Authority, people with high integrity, expertise; Prestige, reputation of the institution
	Rationales/reasons to distrust (what motives?)	Rationales that contribute to distrust in science/ scientists/ scientific institutions/ mediators (...)	Conflicts of interest, data falsification; Lack of rigorous methods; Lobbies, source of funding
Research integrity practices	Views on integrity	Good research practices are based on fundamental principles of integrity	Transparency, responsibility, honesty, reliability
	Views on lack of integrity	Research misconduct is generally defined as fabrication, falsification or plagiarism (FFP) when proposing, conducting or reporting research. Questionable research practices also undermine the integrity of the research process	FFP, self-plagiarism, copyright violation, misrepresent the information, not disclaiming conflicts of interests
Public integration in science	Personal involvement	Opinion about own involvement in research and scientific discussions	"I didn't participate in this kind of programmes in the past"; "I participated by taking photos and uploading them to an app"
	Desired level of public involvement	No involvement: Factors that support the idea that people should not be involved in science (at all)	Laypeople don't have knowledge/ expertise
Partial involvement: Factors that support the idea that people should be involved in part of the research process (e.g., collecting data, discussing findings)		The general public don't have knowledge to define goals, but they can help researchers collecting data	

		Full involvement: Factors that support the idea that people should be involved in the whole research process (from defining research goals to disseminate research)	Public is a stakeholder, and their opinions should be considered in the entire research process
	Benefits of public involvement	Benefits/advantages of involving the public in science	Shared responsibility, greater impact from research
	Problems of public involvement	Problems/disadvantages of involving the public in science	Lack of total control over the research process
Chains of mediation	Types of channels that are trustworthy	Communication channels identified as trustworthy to get information about science and technology	Institutional websites (e.g., universities), Twitter, podcasts, Facebook, newspaper
	Types of channels that are not trustworthy	Communication channels identified as not trustworthy to get information about science and technology	Institutional websites (e.g., universities), Twitter, podcasts, Facebook, newspaper
	Roles/responsibilities of channels	What different actors are supposed to do in relation to research and its communication	"Journalists should not engage in..." "It is not the task of researchers to ..."
	Motives for trusting channels	Characteristics/motives/reasons that make those communication channels or their communication trustworthy (e.g. transparency, consistency, impartiality)	Transparent communication from the Communication Office of the university
	Motives for distrusting channels	Characteristics/motives/reasons that make those communication channels or their communication not trustworthy (e.g., present info in a biased way)	"Public relations maneuver" from the university, lacking important information
Influence of bad practices/integration/communication of it on trust *	Influence of bad research practices on trust	Influence of bad research practices on people's trust in science (increased/decreased/did not affect)	
	Influence of public involvement on trust	Influence of public involvement on people's trust in science (increased/decreased/did not affect)	
	Influence of communication on trust	Influence of communication on people's trust in science (increased/decreased/did not affect)	

*Note: These (direct) relationships could be understood from the general analysis as a conclusion or we could look for evidence in the data as some groups might have directly explored these questions in the discussion (e.g., "Do situations as these (and specifically this one) affect the way you see science? (your trust in science) Why?"; the criteria/arguments used to make the final ranking, etc.)